

Bridging multiscale modeling of biomolecules and experiments through a user-friendly computational platform

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*A mis padres, por traerme hasta aquí.
A Berta, por estar siempre presente.*

Esta tesis es más vuestra que propia.

Resumen

En la presente tesis, la física teórica y computacional se combinan con disciplinas experimentales para estudiar fenómenos no solo propios de la física, sino también de otras ciencias como la biología o la química.

Cualquier técnica experimental puede entenderse como un proceso del cual se extrae información limitada de un sistema complejo. Esta información, que integra contribuciones de muchos grados de libertad, se encuentra encriptada en unas pocas señales experimentales. Esta tesis ofrece herramientas computacionales y teóricas para reproducir experimentos, que permiten incluir los grados de libertad del sistema en escalas mesoscópicas de modo que se pueda descriptar esta información y relacionar la señal experimental con los detalles y propiedades “microscópicas” del sistema. En particular la tesis se centra en fenómenos que involucran estructuras biológicas como proteínas, ADN o virus. Además se aplican estas herramientas al análisis del microscopio de fuerzas atómicas (AFM) y de forma secundaria otras técnicas como las pinzas ópticas (OT) o la microbalanza de cuarzo (QCM).

La tesis está dividida en cuatro partes. En la primera, se realiza una introducción a las diferentes herramientas teóricas empleadas; específicamente, discutiremos una lista de modelos que permiten diversas representaciones simplificadas de procesos y estructuras complejas. En la segunda parte, presentaremos un conjunto de herramientas computacionales diseñadas para describir diversos tipos de interacciones entre entidades mesoscópicas (de grano grueso) con diferentes grados de resolución. Esta parte de la tesis se ordena con una jerarquía de complejidad decreciente para el usuario, de modo que i) se muestra como implementar de manera eficiente nuevos tipos de interacciones en arquitecturas GPU, ii) como usar las herramientas con un entorno Python y iii) como usar las herramientas desde una interfaz web, introduciendo la información esencial de cada sistema experimental. A continuación, mostramos mediante una serie de proyectos aplicados, cómo combinar las herramientas computacionales y teóricas con experimentos para aumentar nuestra comprensión y realizar medidas de propiedades microscópicas de ciertas estructuras biológicas. En particular, nos centraremos en cómo estos sistemas logran comportamientos complejos modificando sus propiedades mecánicas. Finalmente, enumeramos cómo estas herramientas están siendo actualmente empleadas en nuevos proyectos por varios grupos de investigación y presentamos las conclusiones.

Abstract

In this thesis, theoretical and computational physics are combined with experimental disciplines to study phenomena not only pertaining to physics but also to other sciences such as biology or chemistry.

Any experimental technique can be understood as a process from which limited information is extracted from a complex system. This information, that integrates contributions from many degrees of freedom, is encrypted in a few experimental signals. This thesis offers computational and theoretical tools to reproduce experiments, which allow the inclusion of the degrees of freedom of the system at mesoscopic scales so that this information can be decrypted and the experimental signal can be related to the "microscopic" details and properties of the system. In particular, the thesis focuses on phenomena involving biological structures such as proteins, DNA, or viruses. Additionally, these tools are applied to the analysis of the atomic force microscope (AFM) and secondarily to other techniques such as optical tweezers (OT) or quartz crystal microbalance (QCM).

The thesis is divided into four parts. In the first part, an introduction to the different theoretical tools employed is provided; specifically, we will discuss a list of models that allow various simplified representations of complex processes and structures. In the second part, we will introduce a set of computational tools designed to describe various types of interactions between mesoscopic (coarse-grained) entities with different degrees of resolution. This part of the thesis is organized with a hierarchy of decreasing complexity for the user, so that it shows i) how to efficiently implement new types of interactions on GPU architectures, ii) how to use the tools with a `Python` environment, and iii) how to use the tools from a web interface, introducing the essential information of each experimental system. Next, we show through a series of applied projects how to combine computational and theoretical tools with experiments to enhance our understanding and perform measurements of microscopic properties of certain biological structures. In particular, we will focus on how these systems achieve complex behaviors by modifying their mechanical properties. Finally, we list how these tools are currently being used in new projects by various research groups and present the conclusions.

List of publications

- **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Natalia Martín-González, Álvaro Ortega-Esteban, Mara Laguna-Castro, Carmen San Martín, Alejandro Valbuena, Rafael Delgado-Buscalioni, and Pedro J. de Pablo. *Long-Range Cooperative Disassembly and Aging During Adenovirus Uncoating*, **Phys. Rev. X** 11, 021025. DOI:10.1103/PhysRevX.11.021025
- Klara Strobl, Ekaterina Selivanovitch, **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Francisco MorenoMadrid, Iwan AT Schaap, Rafael Delgado-Buscalioni, Trevor Douglas, Pedro J de Pablo. *Electromechanical Photophysics of GFP Packed Inside Viral Protein Cages Probed by ForceFluorescence Hybrid SingleMolecule Microscopy*, **Small** 18 (28), 2200059. DOI:10.1002/smll.202200059
- **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Aritz B. García-Arribas, Diego Carlero, P. Palacios-Alonso, Miguel Cantero-Reviejo, Pablo Ares, Guillermo López-Polín, Han Yan, Yan Wang, Soumya Sarkar, Manish Chhowalla, Hanna M. Oksanen, Jaime Martín-Benito, Pedro J. de Pablo, Rafael Delgado-Buscalioni *Broad adaptability of coronavirus adhesion revealed from the complementary surface affinity of membrane and spike*, **Accepted at Advanced Science**

Other research articles are nearing submission and are expected to be published soon:

- Nerea Alcazar-Cano, **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Rafael Delgado-Buscalioni, Ruben Pérez and Salvatore Assenza. *Mechanical response of phased A-tracts through coarsegrained MD simulations*, **To be submitted**.
- **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Alejandro Díez-Martínez, Alexander M. Bittner and Pedro J de Pablo. *The tubular hollow cavity screens mechanical stress and regulates disassembly of tobacco mosaic virus.*, **To be submitted**.

Software related publications:

- Raúl P Peláez, **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Pablo Palacios Alonso, Aleksandar Donev, Rafael Delgado-Buscalioni. *Universally Adaptable Multiscale Molecular Dynamics (UAMMD). A Native-GPU Software Ecosystem for Complex Fluids, Soft Matter, and Beyond*, Accepted at **Computer Physics Communications**. DOI:10.2139/ssrn.4705582

Other programs and algorithms presented in this thesis are also expected to result in publications. Currently, documentation describing the usage and development of the computational tools is available online:

- **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Pablo Palacios-Alonso, Raúl P Peláez, Salvatore Assenza, Rafael Delgado-Buscalioni. **UAMMD-structured** : uammd-structured.readthedocs.io
- **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Pablo Palacios-Alonso, Rafael Delgado-Buscalioni, Salvatore Assenza. **VLMP** : vlmp.readthedocs.io

Book chapters:

- María Jesús Rodríguez-Espinosa, Miguel Cantero, Klara Strobl, **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Alejandro Díez-Martínez, Natalia Martín-González, Manuel Jiménez-Zaragoza, Alvaro Ortega-Esteban, Pedro José de Pablo *Physical Virology with Atomic Force and Fluorescence Microscopies: Stability, Disassembly and Genome Release*, Physical Virology: From the State-of-the-Art Research to the Future of Applied Virology, 215-236, Springer International Publishing. DOI:doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-36815-8_10
- María Jesús Rodríguez-Espinosa, Miguel Cantero, Klara Strobl, **Pablo Ibáñez-Freire**, Alejandro Díez-Martínez, Natalia Martín-González, Manuel Jiménez-Zaragoza, Alvaro Ortega-Esteban, Pedro José de Pablo *Atomic Force Microscopy of Viruses: Stability, Disassembly, and Genome Release*, Single Molecule Analysis: Methods and Protocols, 317-338, Springer US. DOI:doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-3377-9_15

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Introduction

The objective of physics is to find a set of general principles to predict and control the different phenomena occurring in the Universe [1, 2].

In doing so, physics has build up theoretical frameworks which (at least, so far) allow to infer causal relations, i.e. explanations. However, the existence of a unifying set of principles does not seem evident at a first glance, as different phenomena are often described by seemly different frameworks [1]. For example, the framework describing molecular processes clearly differs from that used to understand the behavior of a cell, which in turn, have little in common with what it is used to describe the structure of a galaxy. Indeed, these phenomena are said to occur at different **scales**, simply because the relevant *elementary entities* we use to build their respective theoretical frameworks (atoms, organelles and stars) evolve in very different regions of the space-time chart [1]. In physics, the phenomena occurring at a particular scale are described by specifying the set of interaction rules governing the evolution of the elementary units [3]. These rules provide the “theoretical framework” of each particular “scale”. Importantly, although we cannot prove the existence (or non-existence) of a set of universal laws, physics is based on the hypothesis that the set of theoretical frameworks should exhibit a layered or **hierarchical structure** [2]. In other words, it should be possible to connect different frameworks by deriving the rules of the larger entities from the laws for the smaller entities composing the larger ones. While this search for the “fundamental laws” at ever-descendant scales drives the scientific endeavor, it is clear that the laws for the “finest” grains are not always a practical tool to explain phenomena at large scales [4]. In fact, following Occan’s razor argument, a satisfactory explanation of some phenomena should use a minimal set of elements, i.e. it should be based on the largest and slowest “elementary entities” required. In Occan’s words “entities should not be unnecessarily multiplied”. This is a very old methodological principle; Aristotle (384 BC) stated: “we may assume the superiority of the demonstration which derives from fewer postulates or hypotheses”. Also, Ptolemy (100 AD), “we consider it a good principle to explain the phenomena by the simplest hypothesis possible”. These arguments are actually the strongest methodological reason for the need of models and tools adapted to each specific scale. An argument which is even stronger than the much more frequently used one, based on “computational limitations”.

Essential to the birth of new conceptually different scales, with their own “elementary entities” and “rules”, is the concept of **emergent behavior** [5]. The emergence of new unforeseen patterns in the spatio-temporal chart, arise from non-linear interactions between the smaller entities (and noise or more generally chaos, help in the process). Non-linearity are already present at quantum level, and then transferred to inter-atomic, inter-molecular interactions and so on and so forth, up to the very existence of thermodynamic phase transitions. Nonlinear interactions create larger and slower structures with distinct properties and behaviors which are neither evident nor predictable from the sole knowledge of the fundamental rules for the elementary entities [5]. But then, emergent structures can be seen as elementary units of even larger scales, and this demands the specification of new interacting rules for the coarser entities [4].

As we shall discuss later, these “coarser models” can be obtained from at least two routes: “**bottom-up**” or “**top-down**” approaches. The “bottom-up” strategy, which can be posed in rigorous physico-mathematical ways [6], derives coarser models by averaging the details of the smaller and faster scales [7]. The “top-down” approach is based on the opposite idea: creating (and “tuning”) coarse-grained models that reproduce experimental facts observed at even more coarse levels and ultimately at macroscopic scales.

But, in any case, most phenomena involve multiple scales. Even the phenomena of “opening a door” requires a small key composed by even tinier grooves. And usually each scale demands a different theoretical framework and computational method [8]. This is particularly true in biological processes whose complexity and specificity involves the coordinated action of many different “scales” reaching down to the atomic one. For instance, a virus infection starts by atomic scale interactions at nanometer active pockets of proteins, then trigger motions of dozens of nanometers of complex viscoelastic structures (including the cell membrane) and eventually the transport of a suspension of many viruses over hundreds of microns of liquids.

This hierarchical view of problems (and the Universe) is the ultimate origin of the different scientific disciplines which deploy quite diverse theoretical and methodological frameworks [7, 8]. In this sense, **multiscale** problems often leads to **multidisciplinary** collaborations [9]; and this is, again, quite common in biophysics. Multidisciplinary research inherently presents the challenge of establishing a common “framework” for researchers with different backgrounds to exchange information efficiently. Despite these and other complications, multidisciplinary research should blossom in this century mixing people from biology, chemistry, physics and computer science [9]. Clearly, the central element should be the experiment as it represents the direct connection with “nature” [10].

In general, we can understand an experiment as a process in which information from a certain physical phenomenon is transported through different scales [11]. When information travels between scales it becomes **compressed and encrypted** due to the aggregated effect of many processes which, generally, also involve a complex interaction between the object of study and the environment (e.g. noise and propagation of external fields, such hydrodynamics, electric or magnetic fields). The aim of the research endeavor is to **decipher** and provide some relation between the experimental signal (the coarsest level of information) and its microscopic origin (higher resolution levels).

The ultimate goal of the theoretical and computational tools and methodologies provided in this thesis is precisely to help deciphering the experimental signals obtained in certain types of experimental devices. Although many of the tools developed are of general application, in this thesis we focus on biological macromolecules (proteins) to larger structures (e.g. virus), up to hundreds of nanometers size. In particular we will apply these tools to study their mechanical properties and functioning [12].

The first objective of this thesis is to implement a hierarchy of **computational models** with different levels of resolution, adapted to the various scales encountered in biophysics, notably covering structures up to hundreds of nanometers in size. The second contribution of this thesis targets the “Tower of Babel” challenge in multidisciplinary research. To this end, we provide a series of “computational frameworks” with a hierarchical level of complexity, where the computational models can be designed, implemented, modified and tested:

First, the **UAMMD-structured** framework, (built on top of the UAMMD library [13]), contains the highest level of complexity and the largest number of degrees of freedom. It is a program for the simulation of coarse-grained models, fully implemented on GPU, allowing the simulation of a large type of interactions. **UAMMD-structured** stands out for its modularity, with several interfaces to add new components, and its efficiency, enabling parallelization of both particular simulations or sets of simulations.

Second, the **Virtual Lab Modeling Platform (VLMP)** allows for a unified approach with **Python** scripting. It permits the combination of different elements to simulate various physical systems. Using **VLMP**, it is easy to build simulations involving viruses, proteins, colloidal systems, as well as to simulate nanoindentation experiments, pulling, and more.

Third, **Vexperiments**, a web application, is designed to create digital twins of selected experimental devices (and any other problem, in general) and is intended to be usable by non-experts in computational models. We expect **Vexperiments** to become a useful tool to communicate ideas, results, and new interpretations of experimental signals. Through its web interface, inexperienced users can carry out complex simu-

lations by setting a small number of parameters required to perform a digital twin of the selected experimental device.

This set of tools is distinguished by their degree of complexity. **UAMMD-structured** is the most flexible but requires advanced programming knowledge. **VLMP** provides a smaller amount of customizable elements but is simpler to use. **Vexperiments** allows setting a very small number of parameters, which can be configured and executed through a simple user interface.

Undoubtedly, the evolution in the design of new **Vexperiments** applications will benefit from the different points of view and knowledge of the various expertise involved in multidisciplinary collaboration. The development of these tools is not only intended to tackle new problems but also to democratize access to this type of technique by successively reducing the level of technical knowledge required to execute a calculation.

Finally, these computational frameworks and models are applied to study a set of problems, focusing on how mechanical properties condition the behavior of certain biological systems. Different experimental techniques are used, such as the atomic force microscope (AFM) or optical tweezers. The systems studied include the disassembly process of Adenovirus, the adhesion process of coronavirus to different surfaces, the confinement of proteins, and the mechanical behavior of specific DNA sequences.

Part I

Biomolecular Coarse-Graining modeling

Coarse grained (CG) models are an essential tool in the study of complex molecular systems, widely used in the study of biological systems [14]. CG modeling is able to provide fundamental insights on the behavior of biomolecular systems and also, when used properly, *quantitative predictions* [15]. The main idea behind CG is to simplify complex molecular interactions into simpler forms, for instance by representing groups of atoms by single interaction unit “bead”. This simplification process is carried out by integrating the effect of many atoms to derive a coarse interaction between the CG beads, hopefully capturing the most relevant features of the lower resolution scale. This abstraction allows for a significant *reduction in computational complexity* compared to fully atomistic models (Fig. 1 A), enabling the study of larger systems or longer timescales while keeping fundamental information about the behavior of the system [16–19]. **This approach is not just convenient for computational performance but is also about conceptual clarity.** Following Occams’s razor argument one should use the minimal model (resolution) able to respond the question posed in each specific research endeavor.

Different strategies in CG modeling reflect the different approaches to a problem. The “**top-down**” approach involves building CG models by matching large-scale behavior observed in experiments, often using simplified interactions and focusing on macroscopic properties [15]. Still, “top-down” CG models contain more degrees of freedom than the experimental signal, allowing to infer some microscopic information from macroscopic responses (experiment). In contrast, the “**bottom-up**” approach constructs models based on detailed atomistic information to approximate how these details manifest at a coarser level [20]. This approach is needed when chemical or biological specificity at atomic level, is crucial to understand the problem at hand. The “**knowledge-based**” approach is yet another strategy in CG modeling: add information from experimentally determined structures into the model [21–24]. This approach considers experimentally measured biomolecular structures as a necessary guide to understand and predict the molecular behavior [5]. Although the different approaches differ in their “philosophy”, they all share the same goal: to create simplified models that balance the trade-off between detail and computational efficiency while providing insight into the underlying physical phenomena. Any of these ways and their combinations are generally required to advance in scientific research.

In summary, CG modeling is more than a set of techniques; *it is a conceptual approach and a methodology to understand complex molecular systems.* It emphasizes the importance of identifying and focusing the most crucial elements of a system to gain deeper insight into the issues raised at different scales [15].

Figure 1: Different levels of representation for a protein dimer (specifically two FtsZ proteins (PDB: 1W59), each of the proteins that make up the dimer is represented by a different color. A) the all-atom representation is shown, in this case all atoms are explicitly added. B) Alpha carbon resolution model, where each amino acid is represented by a bead, this means that each CG bead represents about 20 atoms (Chapter 1). C) A representation of the dimer using the "Shape Based coarse grained" (SBCG) model is shown below (Chapter 2). In this model the resolution is variable. In this case each CG bead corresponds to about 150 atoms. D) Representation using a patchy particle model (Chapter 3). In this case each protein is represented by a single CG bead. The interaction centers between the different proteins are represented by patches on the surface (in this case the patches are represented as spheres). The interaction between the two particles is the combination of the interactions between the beads and the different patches.

The cornerstone of the development of a coarse-grained model lies in the choice of the so-called **mapping function**, which defines the relationship between microscopic (atomistic) and mesoscopic (CG) variables. The mapping functions used are determined by the desired resolution of our model (level of description). Excessively decreasing the resolution, could be useful to examine larger spatio-temporal scales, but may lead us to remove important fine-level events that might be essential for reproducing the phenomena we are interested in. And vice versa, an excessive resolution (e.g. all-atom) simply becomes useless to analyze slow and large collective phenomena.

Our main goal is to accurately reproduce experimental results involving large biological structures, such as protein complexes, viruses or DNA sequences. We face the challenge of spatial and temporal scales, as these processes often involve relatively large structures and take place over long periods of time. For example, when studying the indentation of a virus by AFM, we work with spatial scales in the micrometer range and time scales spanning seconds. Several coarse-grained models for biological compounds have been developed in recent decades. Among them, the **MARTINI** force field probably stands out for its balance between computational efficiency and accuracy [24]. MARTINI has gained great popularity for its ability to model a wide variety of biomolecular systems, including lipids, proteins, and carbohydrate complexes. However, one of the main limitations of MARTINI is that, for most models, it uses explicit water, which considerably increases the computational cost, especially in large-scale simulations. Given the large spatial and temporal scales considered in this thesis, we focus on models which represent water implicitly and have a lower resolution than MARTINI. This approach substantially reduces computational costs. In these models, the mapping function explicitly removes water, yet essential solvent effects are integrated into the CG potentials, influencing both, interaction energy [25–28] and dynamics [29]. Our systems of study may be considered to be in equilibrium, which makes irrelevant an accurate resolution of their dynamics [29]. In particular, in most cases, *we can eliminate hydrodynamic interactions*.

We adopt different levels of detail for biological structures, depending on the specific problem we are dealing with. In the following sections of this chapter, we will explore the various models used in the study of biological structures, moving from relatively high resolution models to lower resolution models.

The first models we will use are called **alpha-carbon resolution models** [30–33], this family of models takes its name from the representation used for proteins, where each amino acid in a protein is represented by a single bead located at the position of the alpha carbon [30] (Fig. 1 B). Compatible with this “single amino acid” resolution we will also introduce models for DNA [32, 34] and lipid membranes [31], as well as for the interactions between these elements [35–37].

Next, we present the so-called **Shape-Based Coarse Grained** model (SBCG) [38, 39], in which each bead represents hundreds of amino acids. This method is especially useful for studying large protein complexes or multiprotein assemblies [40, 41] (Fig. 1 C). Subsequently, we will introduce a **lower resolution lipid membranes model** [42, 43]. Such structures can be relatively large (as for example in the case of certain families of viruses) and therefore alpha carbon-resolved lipid models are not appropriate for simulating certain types of phenomena.

We next turn to **patchy particles** models [44, 45], these models represent a further reduction in resolution, but an increase in the ability to simulate complex interactions and large assemblies, especially in the context of protein-protein interactions (Fig. 1 D). Finally, we present elements of transition state theory and the escape theory of **Kramer** [46–48], which represents the most abstract level of our discussion. This approach is used to describe the evolution of a CG variable (or reaction coordinate) based on its free energy profile.

Chapter 1

Alpha Carbon resolution models

In this section, we introduce the so called **alpha-carbon resolution models** and their applications in studying structured and intrinsically disordered proteins [49] (IDPs), lipids, and DNA. Our objective is to understand how structure and composition affect the mechanical properties of these biological structures [50–52]. For instance, we investigate how the structure of a viral capsid responds when indented with an AFM tip [53], or how the response of the QCM varies with the sequence of the FtsZ linker [54]. We also explore the mechanical properties of DNA and how these vary with sequence, a factor with significant biological implications [52, 55–57].

When we refer to alpha-carbon resolution models in protein simulations, we are discussing a specific type of coarse-grained modeling. In this approach, each amino acid in a protein is represented by a *single bead located at the position of its alpha carbon* [30]. This results in beads with an approximate diameter of 0.5nm. The concept of alpha-carbon resolution might initially seem irrelevant for lipid or DNA models, as these structures do not have alpha carbons (Fig. 1.1). However, we use this term to denote that the resulting mapping yields beads of a similar size, which is useful for model integration [35–37, 58]. When conducting simulations involving different types of models, it is advantageous to have a uniform resolution. This ensures that energy scales are similar, allowing for simpler potential functions. Otherwise, we would need to deal with potentials that combine different scales, leading to computational inefficiency (since we would always have to use the most restrictive scale) and increased theoretical complexity.

In our modeling approach, we have chosen the alpha-carbon resolution for its balance between detail and computational efficiency. Here, each bead, represents *roughly 20 atoms* [22]. This level of detail is sufficient to capture the complexities of large biomolecules such as proteins and DNA, while still keeping the computational workload manageable. This resolution enables us to incorporate a substantial amount of structural information into our models. For instance, in the case of proteins, this may

Figure 1.1: Different biological structures represented by an alpha carbon resolution (all are at the same scale). On the left there are two protein structures. In these structures each of the different chains is represented by a different color. In the first place (from top to bottom) the protein beta-glucosidase (PDB: 3APG) is represented. This protein is composed of four chains. It performs enzymatic functions, in particular related to the processing of sugars [59]. Below FtsZ dimer (PDB:1W59) can be found. This protein is essential in the bacterial division process. Right in the middle we find a DNA strand. This particular strand has 100 base pairs. The upper right figure shows an intrinsically disordered protein (IDP). In particular this is the microtubule associated protein tau (MAPT). This protein is expressed in large amounts in neurons and its aggregation is suspected to be related to disease of Alzheimer [60]. Finally, a section of a lipid membrane is shown at the bottom. In particular formed by POPC.

include the orientation and folding of the protein chains [30, 61], while for DNA, it allows us to represent the double helix structure and the varying configurations it can adopt [32]. In addition, this scale is particularly useful for capturing the effects of charge distribution [62], which in many cases is determinant in the interactions between different structures [63].

A common aspect of this type of models is that they treat the interactions between beads differently depending on whether the beads involved in the interaction belong to the same “entity” (macromolecule or portions of a macromolecule) or belong to different “entities”. Usually, this creates a dualism which refers to **intramolecular** interactions (between “beads” of the same molecular entity) and **intermolecular** interactions (between beads of different “molecular entities”). This dualism is a consequence of two facts, firstly certain **internal** interactions (**intramolecular**) such as bonds or angular potentials have a different nature than interactions between different entities (**intermolecular**), which are mainly governed by electrostatic or hydrophobic interactions [64]. Secondly, since in certain cases (such as structured proteins or in the case of DNA), we know the structure of the entity, we can add this information to the model in the form of effective interactions through bonds [30, 61, 65] (whether distance-dependent, angular or dihedral) the effect of other interactions that are more complicated to model, such as the aforementioned electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions.

With this dual approach (**inter** and **intramolecular** interactions), models are able to reproduce more accurately the different phenomena that take place in this type of complex systems. More precisely, parameterizing properly the intramolecular interactions, models are able to capture the stiffness and flexibility of the structures [65, 66], which is mainly driven by the covalent bonds and the intramolecular forces. By contrast intermolecular interactions (between different entities), permit to simulate the protein complexes [35], the binding of DNA with proteins [67], and other collective patterns.

This distinction between interactions of beads belonging to the same structure (**intra**), and those belonging to different entities (**inter**), determines the structure of the present section. We first discuss models that represent only internal interactions, in particular we will present models for structured proteins and unstructured proteins as well as for lipids and DNA. Subsequently, we will introduce the models of interactions between different entities, focusing on the case of protein-protein interactions and protein-DNA interactions. Finally we will discuss the different strategies we can follow to couple these models.

1.1 Intra Models

Models for *internal interactions* were the first to be developed and contain all the elements that appear in more complex models. We will discuss models for structured proteins, intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs) and finally for DNA, with a brief mention of models for lipids.

1.1.1 Structured proteins

Protein simulation is a field that has evolved remarkably over the years, marked by a significant shift from all-atom molecular dynamics (MD) to coarse-grained (CG) models. This transformation is a product of advancements in technology, theoretical insights, and the need for more effective interpretation of experimental data.

Initially, in the 1970s, the field was revolutionized by Martin Karplus and his team through all-atom simulations [68]. This work, which later contributed to a Nobel Prize [69], enabled a detailed atomic-level understanding of protein dynamics [70]. These advances were made possible due to the increase in the computational power and the availability of detailed structures of certain proteins obtained by methods such as X-ray crystallography [71].

However, the complexity and computational intensity of all-atom simulations soon became a limiting factor, making it unfeasible to study larger systems or time scales. By the late 1990s and early 2000s, the scientific community began to shift towards coarse-grained models. This change was motivated to *capture broader physical and biological phenomena* that were difficult to observe in all-atomic models.

Most proteins present an unique folded configuration which is related to their function. These structured proteins represents about 60% of the total protein ensemble [72].

Among the pioneering coarse-grained models was the **Gō model**, introduced by Teketomi, Ueda, and Gō (1975) [21]. This model marked a significant advancement in studying protein folding [73], being based on the unique 3D structure of the folded proteins, **native structure**.

In the model of Gō, the protein is ideally represented as a polymer, the different particles that compose the polymer are located at the points of a lattice (first these lattices were in 2D and were later generalized to the 3D case, Fig 1.2 A). The distance between two points of the lattice is taken as the unit of length. In this type of models two types of interactions are distinguished: local interactions, when the particles involved in the interaction are contiguous in the sequence, and non-local interactions, when the particles are not close in the sequence but the distance between them is one unit of length (i.e. they are contiguous in the lattice). The form of these interactions is

variable, in addition to the distance between consecutive particles (which is fixed) we can also fix the angles depending on the sequence for the case of local interactions. For non-local ones we can explore several options, such as making them all homogeneous or associating a type to each particle and make the interaction depend on this type.

The process for the simulation of these models is as follows. First an initial structure is generated, which is called the **native structure**. Then the polymer is initialized in a linear way and the objective is to see what kind of interactions should be added and what parameters should be used to recover the native structure.

The conclusion reached by Gō is that a large specified number of interactions, both local and non-local, is needed to recover the native structure. For example, when two particles interact non-locally in the native structure (i.e. they are not close in the sequence but in lattice) they must interact attractively with a sufficiently high energy to recover the native structure. These and other observations led Gō to propose the so-called **consistency principle**, which has been of great help in understanding protein folding. This principle states that both local and non-local interactions must be consistent, i.e., both must energetically favor the native structure.

The lattice-based approach of the Gō model was further developed by researchers like **Dill, Shakhnovich, Onuchic, and Wolynes** [74–77] (1990s), leading to a new results about the protein folding. In particular, they allowed the enunciation of two key principles of protein folding; the **principle of minimum frustration** [78, 79] and the concept of **protein folding funnel** [80] (Fig. 1.2 B). The *principle of minimum frustration* introduces the idea that proteins have evolved, are optimized, to fold into stable and functional structures as directly and rapidly as possible; the interactions between amino acids are mainly cooperative and favor the folded conformation, rather than competing with each other and giving rise to non-functional intermediate conformations. The concept of *protein folding funnel* on the other hand is an idea that complements the *principle of minimum frustration* and serves to explain how proteins reach their native structure. At the beginning of the folding process there are a large number of high-energy conformations, these high-energy conformations are folded and combined with each other simultaneously, reducing the energy and the number of available conformations, this illustrates how protein folding is a directed process and not a random one (Fig. 1.2 B). The goal is to reach a conformation of minimum energy, more stable and functional.

The evolution in coarse-grained modeling continued with the transition to **elastic network models** (ENMs) [81] and off-lattice Gō models. ENMs, have become widespread because of their simplicity and effectiveness in modeling large-scale motions in proteins and other biomolecules [82]. They represent biomolecules as networks of nodes (usually placed at alpha carbons for the case of proteins) connected by

Figure 1.2: A) Different versions (2D left and 3D right) of the Gō lattice model. Non-local interactions are represented by dotted lines. In this type of model a native structure is defined (as shown in the figure) and it is studied what kind of potentials must be added to the model so that from an extended configuration the polymer (protein) folds into the native structure. There are a great variety of models of this type. The models differ in the type of interactions that are added. In some cases, for example, angle-fixing potentials are added or different types of potentials are associated with the particles and the interaction energy depends on the type of particles involved. In the figure the color of each bead depends on its position in the polymer, starting with blue and ending in red. B) Representation of the folding funnel idea. At first the different parts of the protein do not have a defined structure (first line). They interact in a parallel way to give rise to intermediate folded structures that similarly combine to reach the final form of the folded protein. During this process the free energy of the system is reduced. A core idea of the folding funnel is that of the different parallel folding paths. Different parts can fold autonomously and these contribute to the final protein structure.

harmonic springs [83], simplifying the complex interactions in biomolecular systems to basic harmonic interactions. ENMs are particularly useful for computing *normal modes of proteins* [84], which can be used for understanding biological functions like enzyme catalysis and ligand binding [85]

While the $G\bar{o}$ models offered a realization of the protein folding process, they were not able to reproduce the fluctuations of the protein in the native state. In contrast, ENM could approximate low-frequency native fluctuations but did not have the ability to perform any folding process. This limitation of the models led to the development of the off-lattice $G\bar{o}$ model by **Clementi, Nymeyer, and Onuchic** [22] (2000). This model *combined the characteristics* of both the lattice $G\bar{o}$ and the ENM. The mapping of the atomic structure to the coarse grained representation is carried out by removing the solvent and positioning a bead at the alpha carbon position of each amino acid, i.e. the final number of beads is equal to the amino acid number of the protein (Fig 1.3). Each amino acid is commonly associated with a mass equal to the sum of its constituent atoms and with a radius equal to its van der Waals radius [86] (Table 1.1). Subsequently different potentials are added for local and non-local interactions, depending on whether the amino acids are close or not in the sequence.

At low temperatures, the behavior of the off-grid $G\bar{o}$ model, matches those of the ENM, *reproducing the native fluctuations*. On the contrary, at higher temperatures, the model shows a *cooperative unfolding*, a feature not captured by the ENM. This dual functionality reproduces the behavior of proteins in different states. Clementi and coworkers [30, 87] applied this **$C\alpha$ $G\bar{o}$ off-lattice** model to small, fast-folding proteins and found that the folding pathways closely matched experimental observations.

As mentioned above, the model includes both local and non-local interaction terms. In particular for the latter, the concept of **native contact** is central. Two amino acids are considered to form a native contact if they are far apart in the sequence (in particular if $i - j > 3$ being i and j the index of each amino acid in the sequence) and interact in a significant way in the native structure. The criterion for determining whether two distant amino acids in the sequence interact (and thus form a native contact) is not unique. For example, in some cases only distance is considered as a criterion [65], while in others the nature of the amino acids and their orientation are taken into account in addition to distance [88].

This emphasis on native structure contacts is why $G\bar{o}$ models are also called “**structure-based models**”. However, while all $G\bar{o}$ models are structure-based, not all structure-based models, like ENM, fall under the category of $G\bar{o}$ models. *Henceforth, when we mention the **$G\bar{o}$ model**, we are specifically referring to its off-lattice variant, the $C\alpha$ $G\bar{o}$ off-lattice model.*

Table 1.1: Amino acid mass and van der Waals diameter.

Type	Mass (amu)	Diameter (\AA)
ALA	71.08	5.04
ARG	156.20	6.56
ASN	114.10	5.68
ASP	115.10	5.58
CYS	103.10	5.48
GLN	128.10	6.02
GLU	129.10	5.92
GLY	57.05	4.50
HIS	137.10	6.08
ILE	113.20	6.18
LEU	113.20	6.18
LYS	128.20	6.36
MET	131.20	6.18
PHE	147.20	6.36
PRO	97.12	5.56
SER	87.08	5.18
THR	101.10	5.62
TRP	186.20	6.78
TYR	163.20	6.46
VAL	99.07	5.86

Figure 1.3: All-atom (left) and coarse grained (right) representations of the protein beta-glucosidase (PDB: 3APG). In the case of the all-atom representation, the color of each atom is taken according to the type of residue it belongs to. Similarly in the coarse grained representation each bead is represented in a different color depending on the type of amino acid to which it corresponds.

The potential energy function in Gō models is designed to favor the native conformation of proteins by assigning lower energy to that conformation (Fig 1.4). This function, denoted as U , is an aggregate of several terms representing the different types of protein interactions, local; represented by distance, angular and dihedral bonds and non-local; using Lennard-Jones type potentials to assign lower energy to native contacts and WCA potentials to handle steric interactions. The use of these types of potentials sometimes results in local interactions being referred to as bonded and non-local interactions as non-bonded. The total potential energy is thus expressed as:

$$U = U_{\text{bond}} + U_{\text{angle}} + U_{\text{dihedral}} + U_{\text{non-bonded}} \quad (1.1)$$

The bond potential, U_{bond} , is calculated by summing the energy of all bonds, where the energy of each bond is given by $k_b(l - l_0)^2$, where k_b is the bond stiffness constant, l is the current bond length, and l_0 is the equilibrium bond length, those in the native conformation. This term ensures that the distance between beads, representing consecutive amino acids in the structure of the protein, keeps unchanged (but fluctuations), with k_b set high enough to prevent significant deviations from l_0 .

$$U_{\text{bond}} = \sum_{\text{bonds}} k_b(l - l_0)^2 \quad (1.2)$$

The angle potential, U_{angle} , maintains the correct geometric configuration of bonded triads of beads. It is computed as the sum of all angle deviations from their equilibrium state (given by native conformation), each weighted by the angle stiffness constant k_a . The term $k_a(\theta - \theta_0)^2$ represents the energy contribution of each angle, where θ is the actual bond angle and θ_0 is the equilibrium bond angle.

$$U_{\text{angle}} = \sum_{\text{angles}} k_a(\theta - \theta_0)^2 \quad (1.3)$$

The dihedral potential, U_{dihedral} , involves four consecutive beads. It depends on the angle formed by two planes, the first plane given by the first three beads and the second by the last three. This term is needed for capturing the three dimensional structure of the protein and is expressed as a sum over all dihedral angles, each contributing an energy term of $k_d[1 + \cos(n(\phi - \phi_0))]$, where k_d is the dihedral stiffness constant, n is the multiplicity, ϕ is the actual dihedral angle, and ϕ_0 is the value of the dihedral angle at equilibrium.

$$U_{\text{dihedral}} = \sum_{\text{dihedrals}} k_d^{(n)}[1 + \cos(n(\phi - \phi_0 + \pi))] \quad (1.4)$$

Figure 1.4: The figure shows the protein Eglin C (PDB: 1EGL). The all atom representation (left) and the alpha carbon representation (right) are shown. In a G \bar{o} -type model, local potentials would be defined on nearby particles in the sequence. In this case the bonds connecting consecutive residues are indicated by gray lines. Non-local interactions are between distant particles in the sequence. In this example, native contacts (defined by a simple distance criterion) in a certain region of the protein are represented (the selected region is indicated by a dashed ellipse). The interactions of the native contacts are essential to reproduce the secondary and tertiary structure of the protein. In this case the native contacts illustrated stabilize a beta sheet.

All equilibrium values in the G \bar{o} model, including l_0 , θ_0 , and ϕ_0 , are obtained from experimental data of protein structures to accurately replicate real-world protein structures.

The non-bonded potential, $U_{\text{non-bonded}}$, differentiates between native and non-native interactions:

$$U_{\text{non-bonded}} = \sum_{\text{native contacts}} \epsilon_{i,j} \left[5 \left(\frac{r_{0ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - 6 \left(\frac{r_{0ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{10} \right] + \sum_{\text{non-native contacts}} \epsilon_{\text{nnc}} \left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} \quad (1.5)$$

it includes a term for native contacts that uses a Lennard-Jones-like potential, and a purely repulsive term for non-native contacts (Fig. 1.4). The native contact term is a sum over all native pairs, using an energy scale $\epsilon_{i,j}$ and a distance-dependent function of r_{0ij}/r_{ij} , where r_{ij} and r_{0ij} are the current and native distances (those measured in the native structure) between residues i and j . The non-native contact

term uses a similar distance-dependent function with a general energy scale ϵ_{nnc} and a characteristic length scale σ .

In this model, the parameters k_r , k_θ , $k_\phi^{(1)}$, and $k_\phi^{(3)}$ weigh the relative importance of each interaction type. The choices of $k_r = 100\epsilon$, $k_\theta = 20\epsilon$, $k_\phi^{(1)} = \epsilon$, and $k_\phi^{(3)} = 0.5\epsilon$ reproduce experimental data or all atom simulations. As we will see throughout this chapter, this is a common approach. We propose a series of interactions motivated by certain physical hypotheses, such as distinguishing between local and non-local interactions, and then the parameters of these interactions are determined in such a way that they reproduce some kind of phenomena, experiment or simulation (or all of them). For example we can try to reproduce the unfolding temperature measured in laboratory or the aminoacid fluctuations obtained from all-atom simulations. In other words, in the terms used in the introduction of this chapter, this type of model follows a **mixed approach**, both “bottom-up”, “top-down” and “knowledge-based”.

As mentioned previously, the definition of native contacts is not unique. In particular, the original **model of Clementi** [30] employs the definition of native contact given by Sobolev et al [89]. In this case the definition of native contact depends both on the distance and the arrangement of the atoms forming the two aminoacids and on the nature of these atoms (whether they are acceptors or donors, their hydrophobic or hydrophilic character...).

The model of Clementi captures the essential dynamics of protein folding using a minimal representation. Subsequent to the development of this model another series of similar models emerged with the intention of refining the one proposed by Clementi. These new models add types of interactions that the original model did not take into account or use more appropriate parameters to reproduce certain physical phenomena more accurately. The development of these models has transformed these tools from purely theoretical ones to others that can be used to predict the behavior of specific proteins.

One such extended model is that developed by **Karanicolas and Brooks** [61, 90] (2002). A key aspect of the Karanicolas-Brooks model is the addition of a specialized term to account for the hydration layer, the layer of water molecules that interacts with the amino acid surface of the protein. This hydration layer is crucial for protein folding and stability, as it influences several aspects of protein dynamics. The term used in the Karanicolas-Brooks model is a modified Lennard-Jones potential (Fig. 1.5):

$$V_{ij} = \epsilon_{ij} \left[13 \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - 18 \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{10} + 4 \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right] \quad (1.6)$$

Figure 1.5: The potential proposed by Karanicolas-Brooks [61] (right, Eq. 1.6) is similar to the classical Lennard-Jones like potential (left, Eq. 1.5). The major difference is that the latter has a potential barrier before the minimum. This potential barrier simulates the effect of hydrophilic interactions. It is the energetic cost of rearranging the water molecules surrounding the amino acid.

Another important aspect of the Karanicolas-Brooks model is the *use of experimental information for potential parametrization*. In particular, the Karanicolas-Brooks model uses experimental measurements of the unfolding temperature of certain proteins. These measurements are used to scale the energy associated with the native contacts so that the model reproduces the experimental results. Such strategies will be commonly used in many subsequent models [73]. As for the definition of native contacts, the Karanicolas-Brooks model proposes its own definition in which native contacts are defined on the basis of hydrogen bonds between backbone atoms and side chain-side chain interactions. The additional considerations made by the Karanicolas-Brooks model allow it to more accurately represent the behavior of the proteins. This model has been employed in other works where it has been used as a predictive element [15, 91].

At the same time the Karanicolas-Brooks model has been also extended in different ways, for example by adding interaction between different proteins (as we will see in Sec. 1.2) or by adding a model of interaction with different surfaces [92, 93]. In the latter case the model adds an interaction potential between the protein beads and a surface. The potential that is added also takes into account the hydration shell and the hydrophobic or hydrophilic nature of the amino acids and the surface. This allows the model to be used to carry out simulations on a large number of situations where the interaction between proteins and surfaces is studied [94, 95].

Parallel to the development of the Karanicolas-Brooks model, which focused on studying folding processes. Other groups focused on the study of pulling processes. By using AFM or OT we could pull the ends of the protein and force its unfolding [65, 96]. These types of experiments are known as **pulling experiments**. During this

process it is possible to record the displacement and the applied force and by using this information we can obtain information about the structure of the protein as well as about its folding process [96, 97].

Simulating this type of process using all-atom models is not appropriate. This type of experiments involve very large time scales (of the order of a second [98]) compared to the typical scales of the processes that can be observed by all-atom simulations (of the order of a nanosecond [99]).

Thirumalai and coworkers pioneered the use of alpha-carbon $G\bar{o}$ models for studying protein mechanics [65] (2006). Initially focusing on single protein unfolding, these simplified representations proved computationally efficient for simulating large deformations and force-related phenomena. Early studies established the value of these models in deciphering unfolding pathways [65], force-extension relationships, and the influence of force application on protein response.

The model developed by Thirumalai is called **Self-Organized-Polimer** (SOP) [65, 100], and belongs to the family of $G\bar{o}$ models. Its interactions are classified into two types, local and non-local, but it is significantly *simpler* than the model developed by Clementi and the Karanicolas-Brooks model. In this case, local interactions are represented by a single bond, a FENE type potential, that is applied on consecutive particles in the sequence:

$$U_{ij} = -\frac{kR_0}{2} \log \left(1 - \frac{(r_{ij} - r_{ij}^0)^2}{R_0^2} \right). \quad (1.7)$$

Where $k = 14 \text{ N/m}$ is the spring constant, $R_0 = 2 \text{ \AA}$ and r_{ij}^0 is distance between the beads in the native structure. For non-local interactions, the native contact interacts with a Lennard-Jones potential. The ϵ value for this potential is common to all pairs, and sets the energy scale of the native contacts. Particles that are not bonded and do not belong to the same native contact interact with a simple steric potential:

$$U_{ij} = \epsilon_l \left(\frac{\sigma_l}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \quad (1.8)$$

For the SOP model, the definition of native contacts is extremely simple. Two amino acids form a native contact if they are separated in the sequence by more than two amino acids and if the distance between their alpha carbons is less than 8 \AA .

The SOP model (and its extensions [101]) has been widely used to simulate pulling (Fig 1.6). This model has been able to reproduce the experimental stress-strain curves allowing to relate them to the different sections of the protein that are unfolded during the experiment [100, 102–104].

Figure 1.6: Using the SOP model we can obtain a simplified representation of the GFP protein (PDB: 1EMA). This type of model has been used to carry out pulling simulations [65]. The different ends of the protein are pulled with a constant or time-increasing force. This results in the protein unfolded. This forced unfolding process is depicted in the current figure. Where each of the snapshots represents a higher force (from top to bottom). As can be seen by this simple model, we obtain a process of unfolding of the different internal structures in a sequential way, similar to how it is observed experimentally. This simulation has been carried out using UAMMD-structured and VLMP (Chapter 6 and Chapter 7)

Different models have also been used to simulate other mechanical experiments, such as the indentation process of a virus using the AFM [105, 106]. In this case, the work carried out by **Cieplak** (2008) stands out [66, 107–109]. Cieplak and coworkers first compared a large number of potentials for local and non-local interactions and definitions of the native contacts to see which combination best reproduced the experimental determined folding temperature as well as the force-deformation profiles obtained in the pulling experiments [107]. Once the optimal combination was determined, it was used to simulate a large number of empty virus capsid indentation experiments, revealing that the Gō models are capable of capturing the behavior of this type of phenomena [109]. The experimental structures of the viral capsids are used to position the beads. Using this approach viral capsids composed of as few as 10^5 beads to as many as 10^6 have been simulated. Another example of the use of Gō models to simulate AFM virus indentation is the work of Valeri Bargesov [102, 103, 110, 111]. In this work the SOP model has been used for simulating this process, by setting the value of a single parameter, the energy scale of native contacts [102, 103], it is possible to reproduce both qualitatively and quantitatively the indentation profiles obtained in the laboratory.

The Clementi model and the later development of the Karanicolas-Brooks model as well as the SOP model are just a few examples of the use of Gō models [15, 73]. This type of model is still used in a large number of works due to its simplicity and efficiency, and is being further developed to cover an ever increasing number of systems [101, 112]. By alternative definitions of the native contacts or the selection of one potential or another we are able to tune the behavior of these models to reproduce different phenomena. The success of this type of models is an example of the power of coarse grained techniques, once we have captured the central phenomena (the importance of local and non-local interactions, the principle of consistency ...) *we can reduce the complexity of the system* (removing redundant degrees of freedom) *and still reproduce the general behavior.*

1.1.2 DNA

The ideas employed in the development of coarse-grained models for alpha carbon-resolved proteins (such as the Gō models) have been extended to other types of systems including DNA. Coarse-grained models of DNA at this scale use three beads to represent each nucleotide, these beads are located at the phosphate, sugar and base. Such models have been used extensively to study a number of phenomena such as the mechanical properties of DNA [32, 34, 113], how its properties vary with salt concentration [114], its interaction with proteins [36, 115], or even how it is distributed within viral capsids [116], among other examples.

The **3SPN (3-Site Per Nucleotide) model** (2007) [113, 114, 117, 118], developed the group led by de Pablo, is probably the most popular model of this resolution for DNA. The 3SPN model was originally developed to reproduce experimental results such as DNA melting or mechanical properties observed in pulling experiments [117–119]. This model *incorporates many ideas from Gō models*. Interactions between particles of the same strand and neighboring nucleotides are represented by distance-dependent, angular or dihedral bonds similar to local interactions in protein models. For interactions between different strands different non-bonded potentials are employed, in particular for interactions between bases a Lennard-Jones potential is used, the parameters of this potential, ϵ, σ depend on the types of bases involved. The 3SPN model has been extended and updated several times increasing its accuracy and the number of phenomena it can reproduce [34, 113, 114]

Despite the updates, 3SPN does not accurately reproduce certain mechanical properties, such as the persistence length or the force-deformation curves (obtained by pulling experiments) and how they vary with sequence [32].

To overcome these limitations, Assenza and co-workers developed the **MADna (Mechanically-Accurate DNA) model** [32] (2022). MADna employs the same representation as 3SPN, three beads per nucleotide and distances between the different types of bases (Fig. 1.7). The main difference between MADna and 3SPN is that in the former the two strands are covalently bonded, so that they cannot be separated, and therefore melting phenomena cannot be studied. This limitation is compensated by the accuracy of MADna in reproducing the persistence length, the strain-force curves and how they vary with sequence.

Table 1.2: DNA beads mass and van der Waals diameter.

Type	Mass (amu)	Diameter (Å)
Phosphate (P)	94.97	4.5
Sugar (S)	76.05	6.4
Adenine (A)	130.09	5.4
Cytosine (C)	106.06	6.4
Guanine (G)	146.09	4.9
Thymine (T)	120.07	7.1

The potential employed by MADna distinguishes between bonded and non-bonded interactions. For bonded interactions it employs distance-dependent harmonic bonds, angular bonds and dihedral bonds. These bonds connect nearby beads in the DNA and it is through the precise parametrization of their spring constants that MADna achieves its accuracy. These constants are parameterized to reproduce the results of all-atom simulations (i.e. it follows a “bottom-up” approach). In addition, MADna

Figure 1.7: Adapted from [32]. Representation of a DNA strand by an all-atom model (left) and at alpha carbon resolution (right, used by 3SPN and MADna). In the CG model the phosphate group and sugar are represented by a single CG bead. In the figure the phosphate group corresponds to the red bead (right) and the sugar to the black bead (right). The different bases are represented by beads of different colors, depending on their type. Adenine (green), Cytosine (cyan), Guanine (yellow), Thymine (orange).

adds two interactions for those beads that are close in space, but are separated in the DNA. When these particles are charged (as is the case for phosphates), the interaction is treated with a Debye-Huckel model [120], where the effect of salts is implicitly added. The interaction between nearby particles that are not bonded is modeled with a WCA potential.

Although MADna is parameterized using molecular dynamics simulations, it consistently reproduces the persistence length and elastic constants measured experimentally for specific DNA sequences [32]. Using MADna we can study how the mechanical properties vary with sequence, which has important biological implications (an example of the use of MADna is given in Chapter 12.1).

1.1.3 Intrinsically disordered proteins

Intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs) lack a fixed 3D structure, unlike typical structured proteins [49]. This fact makes them more challenging to model, since there is no native structure itself and therefore we cannot employ the strategies presented in the previous sections. IDPs are characterized by their flexibility that produces a *wide range of configurations* [121] (Fig 1.8 A). This flexibility is essential to carry out their functions, many of which involve interacting with multiple proteins [122]. IDPs play a key role in cell signaling and regulation [123]

The challenges in modeling these structures are not limited to the coarse grained domain alone. Simulation of such structures using all-atom models also involves difficulties. Traditional force fields for the simulation of all-atom proteins (e.g. Amber [124] or CHARMM [125]) are often calibrated with protein structures obtained by experimental techniques. The use of this type of experimental data implies that employed potentials are biased towards folded structures, thus failing to reproduce satisfactorily the behavior of the IDPs.

Regarding the coarse grained models with alpha carbon resolution, they are able to reproduce successfully many of the characteristics of the IDPs [33, 126, 127] (Fig 1.8 B). The protein representation for the IDPs is the same as for the globular proteins, i.e. each amino acid is represented by a bead (Table 1.1). It is in the potential used where the differences that particularize the behavior of IDPs are found. As IDPs lack a native structure, no potential involving native contacts is defined (since it is not possible to define them in this type of structures). In general the different interactions do not have any information of any particular structure.

Interactions are still classified as local, those between amino acids close in sequence and non-local for amino acids far away in sequence.

Figure 1.8: A) Although intrinsically disordered proteins do not have a defined structure. Certain areas of the proteins tend to form transient structures. It is this type of behavior that coarse-grained models seek to reproduce. These partially folded states are essential for their function and condition experimental observables such as the radius of gyration. The figure shows the MAPT IDP. Certain transient conformations are indicated in the figure by dotted ellipses. This simulation has been carried out using UAMMD-structured and VLMP (Chapter 6 and Chapter 7) Comparison between the experimental results and those obtained by the model of Tesei et al. [33, 126]. As can be seen, although these models are relatively simple, they are able to reproduce the results obtained experimentally for the gyration radius. The graph has been elaborated using the data available at [33]

In the case of local interactions one strategy is to add distance, angular and dihedral bonds functionally similar to those used for the case of globular proteins. But in this case the different bond parameters, spring constants and equilibrium values are given by a statistical study of the different configurations observed experimentally [128]. That is, by analyzing the experimental results we obtain a probability distribution for the distances, regular angles and dihedral angles and then by the **Boltzmann inversion method** we obtain an energy profile [127]. Finally the different parameters of the interactions are fitted to reproduce these energy profiles (this procedure corresponds with a “top down” approach) . Notably, some models developed in recent years, which have proved to be very successful [33, 126], only add bonds between consecutive amino acids in the sequence, with all other interactions present being of a non-local type.

Regarding non-local interactions between amino acids the key idea is to handle them using potentials originally developed for the interaction between different proteins. These types of interactions will be discussed in detail in the Sec. 1.2.

Once all interactions have been added, they are calibrated using experimental data [33, 127]. In particular, the radius of gyration [129] is a widely used measure since it provides information about the general shape of the protein, in particular its degree of compaction or expansion (Fig 1.8 B).

1.1.4 Lipid membranes

Biological membranes have been a common target of coarse grained models. Their relatively *large size and the characteristic timescales* of the processes that take place in them, make the simulation of these structures using all-atom models infeasible [130]. Biological membranes are mainly composed of **lipids** made of an hydrophilic head and a one or two hydrophobic tail [131]. In particular alpha carbon resolution models have been developed for two common lipid types, POPC and DPPC [31].

In this resolution the lipids are represented by five beads each, two for the polar head (H1 and H2) and three for the hydrophobic tail (T1,T2 and T3) (Fig. 1.9). Each bead is located at the center of mass of its constituent atoms and its mass is the sum of the masses of the atoms it is made of [31].

We consider a potential made of four interactions to model the behavior of the lipids, two local and two non-local (between distant beads within the same lipid or between beads of different lipids):

$$U = \underbrace{U_{\text{Bonds}} + U_{\text{Angles}}}_{\text{Local}} + \underbrace{U_{\text{Repulsion}} + U_{\text{Attraction}}}_{\text{Non-Local}} \quad (1.9)$$

Figure 1.9: A) Each type of lipid (POPC and DPPC) is represented by five beads. Three of them (T1, T2 and T3) represent the tail and the remaining two (H1 and H2) the head of the lipid. Each CG bead is located at the center of mass of the atoms it represents [37, 132] B) Section of a lipid membrane formed by POPC using a coarse grained model of alpha carbon resolution.

The two local interactions are a distance-dependent harmonic potential applied between consecutive beads,

$$U_{\text{Bonds}} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{Bonds}}} K_{\text{bond},i} (b_i - b_{0,i})^2 \quad (1.10)$$

and an angular potential applied between three consecutive beads of the lipid [31],

$$U_{\text{Angles}} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{Angles}}} K_{\text{angle},i} (\theta_i - \theta_{0,i})^2 \quad (1.11)$$

Both potentials add a constraint on the distance between beads b_i or on the angle formed by three consecutive beads θ_i . For this purpose, an equilibrium value is introduced, $b_{0,i}$ for the distance and $\theta_{0,i}$ for the angle, around which the values of b_i and θ_i fluctuate. The magnitude of these fluctuations is controlled by the constants K_{bond} and K_{angle} . The values of the different parameters for these interactions are calibrated so that the coarse-grained model reproduces the fluctuations and equilibrium values obtained by all-atom simulations. All the parameters $b_{0,i}, \theta_{0,i}, K_{\text{bond},i}$ and $K_{\text{angle},i}$ depend on the types of beads involved in the interaction.

For non-local interactions, those between beads of the same lipid that do not belong to the same bond (either distance or angular) and those beads of different lipids, two types of interactions are considered, one repulsive and the other attractive. The repulsive interaction is modelled as a WCA potential (Fig. 1.10):

Figure 1.10: Non-Local potential energy described in [31]. Repulsive potential (left) represented by the WCA potential. Attractive potential (right) for lipid tail beads, shown for different interaction widths.

$$V_{\text{Repulsion}} = \sum_{i < j}^{n_{nl\text{-pairs}}} \begin{cases} 4\varepsilon_{ij} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 + \frac{1}{4} \right], & r_{ij} \leq \sqrt[6]{2}\sigma_{ij} \\ 0, & r_{ij} > \sqrt[6]{2}\sigma_{ij} \end{cases} \quad (1.12)$$

defining $\sigma_{ij} = (\sigma_i + \sigma_j)/2$, where $\sigma_{i(j)}$ represents the van der Waals diameter of the $i(j)$ CG bead. The scaling factor ε_{ij} is given by the geometric mean, $\varepsilon_{ij} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j}$, being $\varepsilon_{i(j)}$ different for each type of particle. The repulsive interaction is applied on all non-locally interacting particles. By contrast the attractive interaction acts only between the beads representing the lipid tails, excluding those interactions which involve beads of type $T1$ and $T3$ (Fig. 1.9) [31]. The attractive interaction is a consequence of the hydrophobic nature of the tails, beads tend to cluster together to reduce solvent exposure. The potential used to model this interaction is given by (Fig. 1.10):

$$V_{\text{Attraction}} = \sum_{i < j}^{n_{nl\text{-pairs}}} \begin{cases} -\varepsilon_{ij}, & r_{ij} \leq \sqrt[6]{2}\sigma_{ij} \\ -\varepsilon_{ij} \cos^2 \left[\frac{\pi}{2\omega_{ij}} (r_{ij} - \sqrt[6]{2}\sigma_{ij}) \right], & \sqrt[6]{2}\sigma_{ij} < r_{ij} \leq \sqrt[6]{2}\sigma_{ij} + \omega_{ij} \\ 0, & \sqrt[6]{2}\sigma_{ij} + \omega_{ij} < r_{ij} \end{cases} \quad (1.13)$$

where $\sigma_{i,j}$ and $\varepsilon_{i,j}$ are those used for the repulsive potential 1.12.

The parameter $\omega_{i,j}$ represent the width of the potential well and is defined as the arithmetic mean of each bead type $\omega_{i,j} = (\omega_i + \omega_j)/2$. The parameters ε_i , ω_i and σ_i are tuned to reproduce the mechanical properties of the membranes, in particular the lipids diffusion across the membrane and their bending modulus. In particular the parameter ω_i can take two values only, one the the head beads σ_H and other one for

the tail beads σ_T . To avoid the formation of persistent holes in the membranes these values are related, $\sigma_H = 0.65\sigma_T$ [31].

By the above interactions we reproduce the amphiphilic nature of the lipids, and this is sufficient for membrane formation. This model has been subsequently extended to simulate different types of lipids [132].

1.2 Inter Models

Interactions between different entities (protein-protein, protein-DNA, lipids-protein, etc) in “alpha carbon resolution” models are classified into two types, **polar** and **non-polar**. Polar interactions are those of electrostatic origin, i.e. they involve the charge of the different particles. Non-polar interactions, on the other hand, involve a wide range of phenomena. They are intended to represent effective interactions between the different beads that arise from the interaction between the atoms that compose them (and that do not have an electrostatic origin) as well as from the interaction of the atoms with the solvent (hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions). The reduction of all present interactions to these two categories has been shown to be sufficient to reproduce a wide range of phenomena, such as the aggregation of proteins, globular [35] or IDPs [133], the recognition of DNA sequences by proteins [36], or the inclusion of proteins in membranes [37], among others [15]. This simplification also significantly increases computational performance, allowing the simulation of larger systems or larger time scales than those accessible by all-atom models [134]. In the following sections we will discuss the different models available for each of these categories.

1.2.1 Polar Interactions

In the study of protein-protein and protein-DNA interactions, *the electrostatic component plays a critical role* (Fig. 1.11), especially given the charged nature of many amino acids and certain areas of the DNA, such as the phosphate groups [32]. In “alpha carbon resolution models” for proteins specific amino acids are considered charged. The charge of these amino acids depends on the pH of the solvent and the isoelectric point of each amino acid type [135]. Under biological conditions, typically at a pH 7, amino acids such as ARG and LYS are assigned a charge of $Q = 1e$, GLU and ASP $Q = -1e$, and HIS, which is at its isoelectric point, is often assigned a charge of $Q = 0.5e$ [35, 58], where e is the elementary charge. DNA is characterized as a negatively charged structure, which is key for its biological functions [136]. In models like 3SPN or MADna, it is assumed that all the charge is placed in the phosphate group, assigned a charge of $Q = -1.0e$ [32, 34].

When the solvent is removed, it is important to understand how this affects electrostatic interactions. A straightforward approach might be to use a Coulomb interaction, taking into account the dielectric constant of water, $\epsilon = 80.0$. The electrostatic potential can be expressed as:

$$U_{\text{elec}}(r) = \frac{q_i q_j}{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon r} \quad (1.14)$$

Figure 1.11: Example of the value of the electric field on each residue of the GFP protein (PDB: 1EMA). The field value varies between $\pm 75\text{mV}$. To calculate the field, the pH and the salt concentration of the solute have been taken into account [137]. It can be seen how there are zones of very different nature. Due to the anisotropy of the electric field over the surface and the relatively strong electrostatic interaction, this type of effect is central to the interaction between the different biological structures. The alpha carbon resolution models take this anisotropy into account by assigning different charges to each residue.

However, typically, the solvent contains dissolved ions. These ions drive a large number of interactions between proteins [138], DNA [139] and IDPs [140]. One way to deal with these ions is to simulate them explicitly, treating them as beads and allowing them to interact via the Coulomb potential [34, 141]. However, this approach has several limitations. Mainly, the Coulomb interaction is long-range, requiring careful handling and specialized algorithms like **Particle Mesh Ewald** (PME), significantly increasing the computational cost of simulations [142, 143]. Therefore, models often consider a completely implicit solvent, where the effect of the ions is incorporated as an effective interaction between charged particles [144]. One common method employed in alpha carbon resolution models is the **Debye-Huckel** [145] model for point particles:

$$U_{\text{DH}}(r) = \frac{q_i q_j}{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon r} \exp\left(-\frac{r}{\lambda_D}\right) \quad (1.15)$$

Here, λ_D is the Debye length [145]. This model assumes that ions screen the charge. The size of this screening is determined by λ_D and it depends on the ion concentration in the solution:

$$\lambda_D = \left(\frac{\epsilon k_B T}{\sum_{j=1}^N n_j^0 q_j^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1.16)$$

In this equation, n_j^0 is the concentration of ions of type j , and q_j is their charge. Under normal conditions, with salt concentrations around 100 mM, the Debye length is approximately $\lambda_D \approx 10$ Å. While the Debye approximation works well at relatively long distances, it fails at short distances [145].

To address this, it has been proposed to work with reduced dielectric constants [26, 146] or add distance-dependent dielectric constants to simulate this effect [36, 147, 148]. One option is:

$$U_{\text{DH}}(r) = \frac{q_i q_j}{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon(r)r} \exp\left(-\frac{r}{\lambda_D}\right) \quad (1.17)$$

where $\epsilon(r) = A + \frac{B}{1 + ke^{-\lambda Br}}$

Here, $A = -8.5525$, $k = 7.7839$, $\lambda = 0.03627 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ and $B = \epsilon - A$, where $\epsilon = 78.4$ is the dielectric constant of water. The parameters of this model are calculated so that the binding energy between DNA and proteins reproduces the values measured in the laboratory [149]. This approach allows for a more accurate representation of electrostatic interactions in an ionic solution, considering both, short-range and long-range effects. Using this model it has been possible to reproduce phenomena of DNA-protein interactions, in particular processes related to DNA expression [36].

1.2.2 Non-polar Interactions

To model non-polar interactions, we will present the two most common methods. In both cases we will use the protein-protein interaction as an example, since this has traditionally been the most studied system. Later on we will show how these methods are used in other types of systems. The first approach focuses on the hydrophobicity of individual amino acids, while the second involves so-called statistical potentials.

The **hydrophobicity-center approach** is used to analyze the interactions in amino acids based on their hydrophobic and hydrophilic properties [150] (Fig. 1.14). In this method, every atom in the amino acids is assigned a hydrophobicity value. Polar atoms are given positive values, non-polar atoms negative values, and charged atoms,

Figure 1.12: Ashbaugh-Hatch potential (left) for different values of the parameter λ . Kim-Hummer potential (right) for different values of ϵ (in units of $k_B T$).

such as those in Arginine, Aspartic acid, Glutamic acid, and Lysine, are assigned specific positive values. The total hydrophobicity of an amino acid is determined by summing these values. This value reflects the different effects of polar, non-polar, and charged groups on solubility. This leads to a ranking of amino acids from the most hydrophobic to the most hydrophilic. These hydrophobicity values, denoted as λ_i (where i is the amino acid type), are normalized between 0.0 and 1.0 (Table 1.3). The model uses the **Ashbaugh-Hatch** [151] functional form:

$$u_{i,j}(r) = \begin{cases} \Phi_{LJ} + (1 - \lambda_{i,j})\epsilon, & \text{if } r \leq 2^{1/6}\sigma \\ \lambda_{i,j}\Phi_{LJ}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1.18)$$

For interaction between two amino acids, the values for $\lambda_{i,j}$ and $\sigma_{i,j}$ are given by the arithmetic average, e.g. $\lambda_{i,j} = (\lambda_i + \lambda_j)/2$ and $\sigma_{i,j} = (\sigma_i + \sigma_j)/2$ respectively. Being σ_i the radius of amino acid i (Table 1.1). Φ_{LJ} is the standard Lennard-Jones potential:

$$\Phi_{LJ} = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r}\right)^6 \right] \quad (1.19)$$

A single free parameter, ϵ , is included in the model, setting the energy scale for the interaction. This scaling factor is common when this type of interactions are added. The above potential (1.18) indicates the relative energies between amino acids for this specific type of interaction. The relative energy between this interaction and the rest of interactions present in the model is unknown, some scale factor is needed. For this reason the parameter ϵ is added, using this parameter this scale can be set. Experimental data are usually used to set this type of parameter. For example, we can explore this parameter until we recover the free energy values for different protein compounds [35, 146], or the radius of gyration for IDPs [33, 126, 133].

Table 1.3: Residue-level hydrophobicity values for each amino acid.

Rank	Residue Name	Hydrophobicity	Normalized Hydrop.
1	Phe	-4.0	1.000
2	Pro	-4.0	1.000
3	Ile	-3.5	0.973
4	Leu	-3.5	0.973
5	Trp	-3.0	0.946
6	Val	-2.0	0.892
7	Tyr	-1.5	0.865
8	Met	-1.0	0.838
9	Ala	1.0	0.730
10	Thr	2.0	0.676
11	Gly	2.5	0.649
12	Cys	3.5	0.595
13	Ser	3.5	0.595
14	Gln	5.0	0.514
15	His	5.0	0.514
16	Lys	5.0	0.514
17	Glu	6.0	0.459
18	Asn	6.5	0.432
19	Asp	7.5	0.378
20	Arg	14.5	0.000

The second method for modeling non-polar interactions between different amino acids takes the so-called **statistical potentials** (sometimes referred to as knowledge based potentials) [152] as a starting point. Although it was not the first work where this strategy was carried out, the study by Miyazawa and Jernigan in 1985 [153] led to the popularization of this strategy for understanding and modeling the interaction between amino acids. The central idea of the model proposed by Miyawa and Jernigan is that the probability of observing an amino acid pair is closely related to its interaction energy. This allows the construction of a relative scale of energies by analyzing the structures.

First we establish a certain cutoff distance, if two amino acids (which are not close in the sequence) are less than this cutoff distance, they are considered to interact. Then we write down all the occurrences of the different amino acid pairs over all the proteins in the database; ALA-ALA, ALA-ARG, ALA-ASN, ..., using these data and performing a statistical modeling we can calculate the relative probabilities of each pair, and therefore, as mentioned, their relative energy [153–155]. The statistical analysis performed is not immediate, it is necessary to take into account certain considerations, both purely technical and physical, to obtain appropriate values.

Once we have determined the energy differences between the different amino acid pairs we must enter this information into a potential. In the case of protein-protein interactions, the first work that used this information to carry out molecular dynamics simulations was published in 2008 by **Kim and Hummer** [35]. In this work we start from the energies obtained by Miyawa and Jernigan for each pair of amino acids, ϵ_{ij} is the interaction energy for the amino acid of type i with the amino acid of type j . Subsequently, a scaling of these energies is performed:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \lambda(\epsilon_{ij} - \epsilon_0) \quad (1.20)$$

In order to determine the values of λ and ϵ_0 , the simulation of certain protein dimers is carried out, and then, the free binding energy is calculated and compared with the experimental results [35].

The potential used is a potential similar to that of Lennard-Jones. We must consider that the resulting interaction energies can be negative (the interaction is considered to be attractive) or positive (the interaction is considered to be repulsive). If $\varepsilon_{ij} < 0$ then we consider the potential:

$$u_{ij}(r) = 4|\varepsilon_{ij}| \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r} \right)^6 \right] \quad (1.21)$$

in the opposite case, $\varepsilon_{ij} > 0$, the potential used is:

$$u_{ij}(r) = \begin{cases} 4\varepsilon_{ij} [(\sigma_{ij}/r)^{12} - (\sigma_{ij}/r)^6] + 2\varepsilon_{ij}, & \text{if } r < 2^{1/6}\sigma \\ -4\varepsilon_{ij} [(\sigma_{ij}/r)^{12} - (\sigma_{ij}/r)^6], & \text{if } r \geq 2^{1/6}\sigma \end{cases} \quad (1.22)$$

In both cases the value σ_{ij} is calculated using the van der Waals radii for the different amino acids (Table 1.1).

Subsequent to the work of Miyazawa Jernigan, other publications have appeared where the data set is improved or additional considerations are made [156–158]. The strategy of statistical potentials can also be extended to other systems beyond proteins. If instead of protein-containing structures we use structures composed of DNA and proteins, we can derive a statistical potential for the interaction between these types of entities [159]. This strategy, is followed in the work of **Zhang et al.** [36] where the statistical potential obtained by Skoinick et al. [159] is used. In the work of Zhang et al. instead of the Lennard-Jones type potential used for protein-protein interaction, the following expression is used for the interaction between DNA and proteins (Fig. 1.13):

$$V_{\text{contact}} = \epsilon \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \frac{W_{i,j}}{2} (1 + \tanh[\eta(r_0 - r_{ij})]) \quad (1.23)$$

Figure 1.13: $V_{contact}$ potential, Eq. 1.23 for $r_0 = 8 \text{ \AA}$, $\eta = 0.7 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, $\sigma = 6.0 \text{ \AA}$ and $\epsilon = 1.0 k_B T$.

In this equation, r_0 is set at 8 \AA , and η is 0.7 \AA^{-1} (these values best reproduce the experimental free binding energies of a set of protein-DNA complexes [36]). Energy pairs W_{ij} are derived from the statistical potential of Skoinick et al. The potential used in this case is not the result of a particular physical phenomenon but is used for technical reasons. The potential 1.23 allows the different aspects of the interaction such as well depth, well width and slope to be varied independently.

Statistical potentials have been widely used, but they have certain characteristics *that make them tricky to work with*. One of the problems these types of potentials can have arises when interactions of different natures are included in the same dataset. For example, in the case of interactions between amino acids, we must construct the dataset based on the type of phenomenon we want to model. Specifically, if we want to study interactions between proteins, we should only include amino acid pairs where each amino acid belongs to a different protein. If we consider only this type of pair, the resulting distribution will differ from what we would obtain if we also included pairs of amino acids from the same protein. Consequently, the energy scale obtained would be different. This is because the nature of the pairs created within a protein (which have a prevalence of hydrophobic residues) differs from that of the pairs formed between proteins, which involve residues found on the surface (mainly hydrophilic residues). When selecting elements for our dataset, we must choose them carefully based on the phenomenon we intend to study [36, 67].

Figure 1.14: Example of the hydrophobic (green) or hydrophilic (blue) nature of the different residues of the GFP protein (PDB: 1EMA) calculated by the method described in [137]. Although it would be expected that most of the residues on the surface of a protein (and therefore those that determine the interaction between different structures) would be essentially hydrophilic and that those at the protein interface would be mainly hydrophobic, this is not always the case. Sometimes there are amino acids of different nature at the protein surface. The type of amino acid (hydrophobic or hydrophilic) must be taken into account when we want to reproduce phenomena of interactions between different structures.

Another problem that appears in this type of potential is that of *double counting*. These potentials effectively account for a large number of interaction types, including electrostatic interactions. So if we include in addition to this term the interactions described in the previous section, polar interactions, we may be adding this effect twice. In this type of situation, corrections must be made to eliminate this effect [36].

In conclusion, to model non-polar interactions between different entities first an energy scale of the interaction is constructed, then these energies are introduced in some potential which have to be flexible enough to be able to modify its parameters independently. Finally, the different parameters are scaled. Using experimental result, as a metric.

In this section we have focused on the interaction between proteins and also between proteins and DNA. For other types of systems the approach is similar, for example in the case of lipid-protein interactions, methods such as umbrella sampling can be used to determine the effective potentials between the beads representing lipids and those representing proteins [37]. From these potentials we extract the energy differences which we then introduce in a Lennard-Jones potential and scale them to reproduce certain experimental measurements, in the case of lipid-protein interactions, the angle formed by the proteins and the membrane is employed as metric [37, 132].

1.3 Coupling model

At this point we have one set of models for **intra** and another set for **inter** molecular interactions. In turn the models for internal representation (intra) can also be separated into different contributions, *local and non-local interactions*. Similarly, intermolecular interactions are classified into *polar and non-polar*. In summary we have four different categories, *local, non-local, polar and non-polar* interactions. For each of these categories there are a variety of models (Fig. 1.15).

To study different phenomena we combine different interactions at different parts of the molecules allowing for model refinements. Each interaction collects some phenomena and it is assumed that the energy difference between the configurations driven by these phenomena is well represented by the selected model. One must fix the different scales of each interaction, usually by inspection. A phenomenological factor is added to each type of interaction then explored to reproduce all-atom simulation or experimental results.

One of the first general models to do this was the **Kim-Hummer model** for protein-protein interactions [35]. In this model, which does not consider the internal interactions, the protein is represented as a rigid solid composed of beads located at the alpha carbon positions. For the interactions between different proteins a Debye-Huckel type interaction is taken for the polar component and a parameterized interaction using the Miyazawa-Jernigan potential is considered for the non polar part:

$$U(r)_{inter} = U(r)_{DH} + U(r)_{MJ} \quad (1.24)$$

The model of Kim Hummer also adds additional information, in particular it considers how exposed the amino acids are. The interactions are weighted according to the solvent accessible surface area (SASA) [160] value of the amino acids involved:

$$U(r)_{eff} = f(s_i)f(s_j)U(r)_{inter} \quad (1.25)$$

In this equation, s_i and s_j are the normalized SASA values. These values are determined as $s = SASA_i/SASA_{random\ coil}$, where $SASA_i$ is the solvent accessible surface area of amino acid i in the native structure of the protein, and $SASA_{random\ coil}$ is the SASA of the corresponding amino acid in a random coil configuration. The function f is a smooth function ranging from 0 to 1.

Ravikumar et al. [146] expanded the Kim-Hummer this approach by incorporating the Clementi model [87] for internal protein representation. This development allows for the consideration of how protein deformations influence inter-protein interactions. Similar to Kim-Hummer, they also used a combination of Debye-Huckel and

Figure 1.15: Example of a system where two proteins interact. The system is the barnase/barstar complex (PDB: 2ZA4). Each of the interacting proteins is represented with different colors, blue (barnase) and red (barstar). The all atom representation is shown in section A) and in section B) the alpha carbon resolution coarse grained model is shown. To properly reproduce this type of interaction it is essential to have a good description of the electric and hydrophobic/hydrophilic nature of the different residues. It is also important to have a good representation of the internal mechanics of the protein. Using the different approaches presented in this chapter, it is shown how the alpha carbon resolution models are able to adequately reproduce such features of the different types of structures. By careful parameterization it is possible to simulate such phenomena with these models with proper accuracy [35, 36].

Miyazawa-Jernigan potentials and adjusted the scale parameters to match experimental data, additionally they also consider changes in the dielectric constant near the protein surface [147]. Furthermore, the Kim-Hummer model has been combined with the Karanicolas-Brooks model to study the folding process, particularly in the context of chaperons [58]. Recently, this method of combining internal representation models with interaction models has been applied to study protein-DNA interactions [67]. Notable in this area are the works of Zhang et al. [36], who employed models similar to the model of Clementi for proteins and 3SPN for DNA. These studies focused on the interaction between proteins and DNA in nucleosomes, using a combination of Debye-Huckel and statistical potentials for protein-DNA interactions. These models were fine-tuned to address double counting issues in statistical potentials and variations in the dielectric constant. In the case of IDPs, non-local interactions between amino acids of the same protein are considered as if they were different proteins. To model IDPs the models for local interactions are combined with a Debye-Huckel interaction and potentials that reproduce the non-polar interactions [127]. In particular the model developed by Tesai et. al. [33, 126] employs one bond for neighboring amino acids only and Debye-Huckel for interactions between charged amino acids and the hydrophobicity-hydrophilicity potential described in section 1.2.2. This model successfully reproduces the behavior of certain IDPs, in particular the radius of gyration, and has been used to study how different aggregates behave [133].

In summary, with this type of models we have a set of mutually compatible tools that can be combined to study a wide range of phenomena. In this chapter we have given some examples of models of this scale but the field is very wide and is in continuous development.

Chapter 2

Shape-Based

Alpha carbon models have been used for simulating large molecular assemblies, such as viruses [66]. For example this type of models have been used for the simulation of the HK97 capsid, which comprises around 120,000 residues. In an alpha carbon model, this translates to an equivalent number of beads.

This approach, however, encounters limitations when studying phenomena that involves large spatio-temporal scales, primarily due to its significant computational requirements. To address this, alternative models like the **Shape-Based Coarse-Grained** (SBCG) model have been developed [40, 141, 161]. The SBCG model stands out for its flexible resolution, allowing each CG bead to represent various numbers of atoms, ranging from 100 to over 1000 for example, depending on the specific phenomenon under investigation (Fig 2.1). While this model substantially improves computational efficiency, it is not able to capture detailed phenomena, such as the folding and unfolding of individual residues or specific protein regions.

The SBCG model is designed to retain the shape of the underlying structure in the distribution of coarse-grained (CG) beads. This is accomplished through the implementation of the “**neural gas**” algorithm [162]. Consider a protein structure made up of N_a atoms, each characterized by specific coordinates \mathbf{r}_n and individual masses m_n . The objective of this model is to replicate the shape of the protein by arranging N_{CG} beads in a particular manner. This arrangement is guided by the mass distribution function $p_n(\mathbf{r}) = m_n\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_n)/M$, where M denotes the total mass of the protein. The mass distribution function is employed as the target for the bead distribution. The algorithm is an iterative process executed over S steps, where $S = 200N$ is sufficient for achieving convergence. It involves updating parameters λ and γ , which modulate the magnitude of positional variations, this update is done at each step, using the formula $f_s = f_0(f_s/f_0)^{(s/S)}$, where f_s represents the value of $\lambda(\gamma)$ at the step s , f_0 is the initial value, $\lambda_0(\gamma_0)$ and f_S is the final value (at $s = S$), $\lambda_S(\gamma_S)$. Here, s represents the current step, and the initial and final values of λ and γ are defined as $\lambda_0 = 0.2N$, $\lambda_S = 0.01$, $\gamma_0 = 0.3$, and $\gamma_S = 0.05$. The procedure is described in Alg. 1.

Algorithm 1 Topology-Representing Network, 'Neural Gas'**Require:** Atoms with coordinates r_n and masses m_n , $n = 1, 2, \dots, N_a$ **Ensure:** Positions of Coarse-Grained (CG) beads

```

1: Initialize  $N$  CG beads with random positions
2: Set  $\lambda_0 = 0.2N$ ,  $\lambda_S = 0.01$ ,  $\gamma_0 = 0.3$ ,  $\gamma_S = 0.05$ 
3: Set  $S = 200N$ 
4: for step = 1 to  $S$  do
5:   Randomly select an atom  $n$  with probability  $p_n = \frac{m_n}{M}$ 
6:    $v \leftarrow r_n$  ▷ coordinates of atom  $n$ 
7:   for each CG bead  $i$  do
8:     Count  $k_i$ : number of CG beads  $j$  where  $\|v - R_j\| < \|v - R_i\|$ 
9:     Update  $R_i^{new} \leftarrow R_i^{old} + \gamma \exp\left(-\frac{k_i}{\lambda}\right) (v - R_i^{old})$ 
10:  end for
11:  Update  $\gamma$  using  $\gamma_s = \gamma_0 \left(\frac{\gamma_S}{\gamma_0}\right)^{\frac{s}{S}}$ 
12:  Update  $\lambda$  using  $\lambda_s = \lambda_0 \left(\frac{\lambda_S}{\lambda_0}\right)^{\frac{s}{S}}$ 
13: end for

```

After determining the positions of the beads, they can be reproduced to other identical simulated proteins through appropriate rotation and translation operations. Subsequently, a Voronoi decomposition [141] is employed to link each atom with a specific bead, each atom belongs to the nearest bead. This ensures a unique association and introduce a simple way for the assignment of mass and charge to each bead:

$$M_j = \sum_{i \in j} m_i, \quad Q_j = \sum_{i \in j} q_i \quad (2.1)$$

The radius of each bead is then calculated based on the radius of gyration of the particles it comprises:

$$R_{g,j} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M_j} \sum_{i \in j} m_i (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{R}_{CM,j})^2} \quad (2.2)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{CM,j}$ is the center of mass of the atoms forming bead j .

For the effective interactions in the SBCG model, both bonded and non-bonded interactions are considered:

$$\begin{aligned}
V = & \sum_{\text{bonds } i} \frac{1}{2} K_i (R_i - R_{0,i}) + \sum_{\text{angles } i} \frac{1}{2} L_i (\theta_i - \theta_{0,i}) + \\
& \sum_{m,n} \epsilon_{mn} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{mn}}{r_{mn}} \right)^{12} - 2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{mn}}{r_{mn}} \right)^6 \right] + \sum_{m,n} \frac{q_m q_n}{4\pi \epsilon \epsilon_0 r_{mn}}
\end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Figure 2.1: Example of how a virus like particle (VLP) is represented for different resolution levels using the SBCG. The VLP comes from the P22 bacteriophage (PDB: 5UU5) [163]. Each of the different proteins that make up the VLP capsid is colored differently, in particular the pentons are shown in red. In this example different resolutions are shown. The resolution is reduced successively (from left to right and from top to bottom). The number in the upper left corner of each VLP specifies the resolution used. For example, for the case 150:1 means that each CG bead represents 150 atoms.

In this framework, non-bonded interactions are modeled through Coulomb and Lennard-Jones (LJ) potentials. The Coulomb interactions are directly determined since each bead inherits the charge of the atoms it represents. However, LJ interactions require an additional specification. For a pair of beads i and j , the LJ parameter, ϵ_{ij} , is computed as $\epsilon_{ij} = \sqrt{\epsilon_i \epsilon_j}$. These values, ϵ_i and ϵ_j are derived from the solvent accessible surface area (SASA) of the protein domain represented by each bead:

$$\epsilon_i = \epsilon_{\max} \left(\frac{SASA_i^{\text{hphob}}}{SASA_i^{\text{tot}}} \right)^2 \quad (2.4)$$

Here, $SASA^{\text{hphob}}_i$ and $SASA^{\text{tot}}_i$ are computed as the sum of the corresponding SASA values for each atom in the bead, being the hydrophobic SASA and total SASA respectively. The idea behind using SASA to determine ϵ_i is to simulate the aggregation of hydrophobic beads and the dissolution of hydrophilic beads in an implicit solvent. ϵ_{ij} will be zero for completely hydrophilic beads, allowing them to dissociate freely unless bound by other particles. Conversely, for entirely hydrophobic beads, ϵ_{ij} is equal to ϵ_{\max} , which should be adjusted to realistically represent hydrophobic aggregation. The correct value of ϵ_{\max} depends on the resolution we are considering, for example, with a resolution of 150 atoms per CG bead is about 10 kcal/mol.

Bonded interactions in the SBCG model are based in the Elastic Network Model (ENM), employing harmonic springs to connect particles within a specific cutoff distance. An alternative option is to bond two beads if some of the atoms it is composed of are bonded. Furthermore, angular bonds are used at junctions of two bonded beads. The force constants for these bonds, K_i and L_i (2.3), are determined through **Boltzmann inversion** [164, 165], relating the variance in distances and angles to thermal energy in accordance with the equipartition theorem:

$$K_i = \frac{k_B T}{\sigma^2}, \quad L_i = \frac{k_B T}{\sigma_\theta^2} \quad (2.5)$$

However, this method can overestimate K due to the assumption of independent R_i variables. To verify accuracy, one can simulate the protein with the CG potential and compare the variances to those from high-resolution simulations. If discrepancies are observed, the force constants are uniformly scaled down by a factor $\alpha < 1$, and the simulation is repeated until the fluctuations in both the coarse-grained and all-atom models align closely [164, 165],

The SBCG model has been used to study a wide variety of phenomena. This includes the simulation of proteins in membranes [161], the stability of viruses [39], and modeling the AFM indentation of a virus among other applications [40]. The model has recently been updated to improve the simulation of interactions between beads, using xDLVO theory [166]. Machine learning techniques have also been applied to more accurately reproduce the behavior of the structures [41].

Chapter 3

Patchy particles

In the protein models described above, several beads are used to represent a protein. However, we could consider that since proteins often behave as independent units, we could employ a **single particle** to represent them. This representation would be very useful for studying the interaction between a large number of proteins and would be the minimum resolution we could employ using a particle model. While certain behaviors of proteins, such as their diffusion in the cytoplasm [167], can be studied using models that represent the protein as a single particle and interact with other proteins isotropically, these types of models are not able to reproduce more complex processes such as the self-assembly of structures or polymerization. This is due to the fact that the interaction between proteins has a strong **anisotropic component**. Proteins can accumulate charged residues in certain regions of the surface or others with a marked hydrophobic or hydrophilic character. This results in the *surface of proteins not having a homogeneous nature*, and therefore the interaction between them strongly depends on their relative orientation. In fact, in many cases, it is the specialization of the surface that *encodes the function of the protein*.

Several models have been developed to represent proteins using a single particle (bead) and taking into account non isotropic interactions. In these types of models, in addition to its position, the bead has other degrees of freedom that describe the orientation of the protein in space. These models have been very useful for understanding certain protein aggregation processes, such as the assembly process of viruses [168], and have even been used to simulate the indentation process of a virus using AFM [169]. In this section, we will present a general type of model for simulating the interaction between anisotropic particles and discuss its application for the simulation of biological structures. These types of models are known as **patchy particles**.

The term “**patchy particle**” generally refers to particles that have specific interaction zones, or patches, on their surface. That is, the interaction between these types of particles is given by an isotropic interaction between the particles themselves,

which can be repulsive or attractive, and in parallel, an interaction between the different specific zones (patches) of the surface. Patchy particles are not only a theoretical model; this type of particle has been widely developed experimentally and represents one of the main tools when it comes to building self-assembling systems [170]. The anisotropy of these types of particles gives rise to the creation of complex structures when they interact with each other [171].

From a theoretical and simulation point of view, the idea of patchy particles has been used, with varying popularity depending on the era, to model a large number of systems. Interestingly, the idea of patchy particles can be found in “Lectures on Gas Theory”¹ [172] by Ludwig Boltzmann, published in 1896, specifically as an idea for modeling the chemical bond. These types of models have been used to simulate a large number of systems, such as atoms and molecules, proteins, viral capsids, hard faceted bodies, or DNA [173].

In this chapter, we will only present models that use a single particle decorated with an arbitrary number of patches. In these types of models, the state of the particle is determined by its position \mathbf{r}_i and its orientation in space $\mathbf{\Omega}_i$. For the representation of the orientation in space, $\mathbf{\Omega}_i$, a rotation is used, referred to the laboratory reference system [142]. In this sense, $\mathbf{\Omega}_i$ is a reference system that moves with the particle, and it is on this reference system that we define the position of the patches on the surface. Then, the interaction between two patchy particles is given by the potential:

$$U_{ij} = U_{isotropic}(\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_j) + U_{patches}(\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_j, \mathbf{\Omega}_i, \mathbf{\Omega}_j) \quad (3.1)$$

where the second term is a sum of the contributions of the different pairs of patches:

$$U_{patches}(\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_j, \mathbf{\Omega}_i, \mathbf{\Omega}_j) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{M_i} \sum_{\beta=1}^{M_j} U_{pp}(\mathbf{r}_\alpha, \mathbf{r}_\beta, \mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_j, \mathbf{\Omega}_i, \mathbf{\Omega}_j) \quad (3.2)$$

being M_i and M_j are the number of patches of particle i and j respectively and $\mathbf{r}_{\alpha(\beta)}$ the position of the patches. Note that $\mathbf{r}_{\alpha(\beta)} = \mathbf{r}_{\alpha(\beta)}(\mathbf{r}_{i(j)}, \mathbf{\Omega}_{i(j)})$, i.e., the position of the patch is completely determined by the position and orientation of the particle to which it belongs. The interaction U_{pp} is the potential with which the pairs of patches interact. For the interaction $U_{isotropic}(\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_j)$, several options can be considered, from some type of steric or soft core interaction to an electrostatic interaction, depending on the system studied.

The development of patchy particle models has consisted in specifying these two potentials, $U_{isotropic}$ and U_{pp} , in such a way that they reflect the type of phenomena being studied.

¹Part II, Chapter 6: "Theory of Dissociation", Section 62

The first systems where these models were employed intensively were the so-called associative fluids in 1980. These models described the associative species as repulsive spherical particles decorated with a small number of attractive sites. Through the application of the perturbation theory of Wertheim [174], it was possible to describe the thermodynamics of these types of systems. These models simulate the behavior of hydrogen bonds at high densities and reproduce certain anomalies and phase transitions observed in fluids with these characteristics, such as water.

The next important application of this model was, in fact, the study of proteins [175]. The behavior of proteins in solution, even today, is not fully understood. Early work found that the high directionality (anisotropy of bonds) could explain how phase diagrams shifted relative to what would be expected for a set of colloids interacting isotropically. Higher concentrations are necessary for crystallization. In contrast, it was also observed that depending on the position of the patches, proteins can create small crystals that remain in solution. The first models used to carry out these simulations were discrete models, in particular the so-called **Kern-Frenkel model** [44] (Fig. 3.1 A). This model (based on earlier models used for the study of fluids) is a combination of a hard sphere potential with an attractive square well along with a potential that depends on the relative orientation of the two particles (Fig. 3.1 A):

$$U_{ij}(\mathbf{r}_{ij}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j) = u_{ij}^{\text{hssw}}(r) \cdot f(\mathbf{r}_{ij}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j), \quad (3.3)$$

where u_{ij}^{hssw} is the hard sphere square well potential:

$$u_{ij}^{\text{hssw}}(r) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{for } r < \sigma \\ -\epsilon & \text{for } \sigma \leq r < \lambda\sigma \\ 0 & \text{for } \lambda\sigma \leq r. \end{cases} \quad (3.4)$$

and $f(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j)$ is the orientation-dependent part:

$$f_{ij}(\mathbf{r}_{ij}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \begin{cases} (\hat{\mathbf{e}}_\alpha \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} \geq \cos \delta) & \text{for some patch } \alpha \text{ on } i \\ \text{and} \\ (\hat{\mathbf{e}}_\beta \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ji} \geq \cos \delta) & \text{for some patch } \beta \text{ on } j \end{cases} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

where \mathbf{r}_{ij} is the vector joining the centers of the two particles and \mathbf{e}_α and \mathbf{e}_β are the vectors describing the position of the patches belonging to particle i and j respectively. The potential will then be attractive when the angle between a patch and the vector joining the particle centers is smaller than δ , which is the size or extent of the patch.

The Kern-Frenkel model has been applied to study a large number of systems [176]. However, it has certain limitations, including that it is a discrete model and therefore not convenient for molecular dynamics simulations.

Doye et al.[45] extended the previous model by proposing a more flexible and continuous version of the Kern-Frenkel model (Fig. 3.1 B). The idea is similar to the Kern-Frenkel model, with the potential separated into two parts: an interaction representing the isotropic interaction between particles and an interaction that depends on the orientation of the particles, i.e., the position of the patches. The isotropic part is described by a Lennard-Jones type potential:

$$V_{LJ} = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{LJ}}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{LJ}}{r} \right)^6 \right] \quad (3.6)$$

The anisotropic part modulates the attractive interaction of the Lennard-Jones potential:

$$V(r_{ij})(\mathbf{r}_{ij}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j) = \begin{cases} V(r_{ij}) & r < \sigma_{LJ} \\ V(r_{ij})V_{\text{ang}}(\mathbf{r}_{ij}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j) & r \geq \sigma_{LJ} \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

where the orientation-dependent interaction is given by the following expression:

$$V_{\text{ang}}(\mathbf{r}_{ij}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j) = \exp\left(-\frac{\theta_{k_{\min}ij}^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\theta_{l_{\min}ji}^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (3.8)$$

where σ controls the size of the patch, θ is the angle between the vector of patch k on particle i and the interparticle vector \mathbf{r}_{ij} , and k_{\min} is the patch that minimizes this angle among all possible patches. Doye et al. first developed the model for the problem of protein crystallization. But the model has been used to study a wide variety of systems, such as the formation of structures and their stability [177] (Fig. 3.2). Notably, this model and its extensions [178, 179] have been widely used for the study of quasicrystals, structures that are ordered but not periodic.

Parallel to the Kern-Frenkel and Doye models, the so-called **sticky point models** have been developed, where the interaction between patches does not have the angular component and is modulated only by the attraction between patches (Fig. 3.1 C). With this type of model, the valence, i.e., the number of patches that can form a bond, can be more precisely controlled. A simple model of this type would be:

$$V_{\text{pp}}(\mathbf{r}_\alpha, \mathbf{r}_\beta) = \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r_{ij,\alpha\beta}}{\delta_{\alpha\beta}} \right)^{10}\right] \quad (3.9)$$

Figure 3.1: A) Kern-Frenkel model [44]. In the scheme of the figure \mathbf{e}_α and \mathbf{e}_β represent the position of the patches of particle i and j respectively. The two particles interact if the cosine of the angle formed by the vectors \mathbf{e}_α and \mathbf{e}_β with the vector \mathbf{r}_{ij} is less than a certain value (which indicates the size of the patch). B) Model of Doye [45]. It is a continuous version of the Kern-Frenkel model. In this case the angles θ_{ij} and θ_{ji} are computed, being $\theta_{ij(ji)} = \arccos(\mathbf{e}_{\alpha(\beta)} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ij(ji)}/r)$. Then the 3.8 potential is applied. In both cases the single example is shown for the case of a single patch per particle. In the case of the Kern-Frenkel model, if the particle had more patches, then all combinations would be tested to determine if the particles would interact. In case of the Doye model if the particle has more patches then the angles θ_{ij} and θ_{ji} are computed for all the patch combinations and the one for which these angles are smaller is chosen [45] B) Model of a patchy particle. In this case each patch is placed at $\pm\sigma\mathbf{i}$, $\pm\sigma\mathbf{j}$ and $\pm\sigma\mathbf{k}$, where \mathbf{i} , \mathbf{j} and \mathbf{k} are the unit vectors associated with the comoving reference frame of each particle and σ is the particle radius. The patches can interact with different potentials, such as the Kern-Frenkel model, Doye or a simple potential well like 3.9.

In this case, we only have an attractive interaction between the patches. This type of potential has been combined with others that depend on the orientation of the particles and fix it, but the patch remains a point on the surface.

Both the Kern-Frenkel and sticky point models are the two major families of patchy particle models. There are several strategies to extend these models to enable simulations of a larger number of physical systems. One such extension is to assign different types to the patches, allowing two patches to interact or not depending on their types. This class of models has been used to model biological structures such as DNA, RNA, and how they interact with proteins to study how these components separate into different phases [180–182] or even the formation of microtubules [183]. A current application of patchy particle models is the design of self-assembling structures. Through coarse-grained simulation and the use of machine learning techniques, patchy particles can be designed and then they can be experimentally developed and lead to the formation of predesigned structures [184].

Figure 3.2: Example of how to use a patchy particles model to simulate a crystal. In the model we consider particles that have six patches each. Each patch is located at $\pm\sigma\mathbf{i}$, $\pm\sigma\mathbf{j}$ and $\pm\sigma\mathbf{k}$, where \mathbf{i} , \mathbf{j} and \mathbf{k} are the unit vectors associated with the comoving reference frame of each particle and σ is the particle radius. The interaction potential between the particles is a simple WCA while the interaction between the patches is an attractive well similar to those described by the potential 3.9. In the initial configuration we place the particles in a cubic lattice. If the temperature increases and some time elapses the structure will begin to evaporate as shown in the figure. Patchy particle models are very useful to study phenomena involving crystalline structures. By carefully choosing the patches we can simulate a large number of structures.

Chapter 4

Vesicle

Lipid membranes are a central element in biology. They form structures that allow for the **separation and regulation** of different environments, facilitating vital processes such as signaling, substance transport, and the protection of essential biological components [131].

The models presented previously (Sec. 1.1.4), which employ around five beads to represent each lipid and treat the solvent implicitly, still have *too much resolution* to effectively simulate some systems. Using these models, we can carry out simulations of certain areas of the membrane or small structures and, notably, study how proteins interact with membranes [37]. Unfortunately, these types of models are not suitable for studying processes involving larger spatial or temporal scales. There are other popular models, such as the one developed by Cooke and Deserno [185–187], where each lipid is represented by three beads, and the solvent is also added implicitly. This model has been used to carry out mesoscopic simulations [187]. However, the computational requirements make it unfeasible to study larger systems, such as liposomes, or biological structures such as exosomes or certain types of viruses with lipidic envelope (e.g. coronavirus) [19, 188, 189].

To simulate phenomena at larger temporal and spatial scales, we must represent each lipid or set of lipids with a single particle (in addition to treating the solvent implicitly). The challenge with these types of models is to reproduce hydrophobic behavior in the absence of an explicit solvent [190, 191]. The first model that employed a single bead to represent a set of amphiphilic molecules and managed to reproduce certain phenomena (such as the formation of membranes or vesicles) was the model by Drouffe et al. [192]. The central idea of this model is to add rotational degrees of freedom to each particle. In addition to its position, we also define its orientation in space, thus allowing the inclusion of anisotropic interactions. Through this type of interaction, it is possible to recover the behavior of amphiphilic molecules. This model was later extended and refined by **Zhang** and his collaborators [42].

In this section, we will present the model development by Zhang et. al and briefly discuss some of its applications. It is worth noting that there are other options for simulating lipid membranes at scales larger than those accessible through alpha carbon resolution models or the Cooke and Deserno model. One can opt to use non-particle-based models, i.e., continuous models. There are several options of this type, such as the finite element method [193] or phase field approaches [194–196]. There are also particle-based options, such as triangulated membrane models [197] or the meshless method [198]. However, these methods have certain limitations. Those that do not employ particles are hardly compatible with other models, which restricts their utility. The major limitation of these models is i) they do not include membrane fluidity (2D viscosity) and ii) they can not describe self assembly (membrane formation and rupture) [42, 189, 199].

As mentioned, the model of Zhang represents a set of amphiphilic molecules with a single bead (Fig. 4.1 A). Each particle is associated with a position and an orientation in space, *similar to a “dipole”*. We represent the position of particle i by the vector \mathbf{r}_i and its axis of symmetry by the unit vector \mathbf{n}_i . For the part of the interaction that depends solely on the distance between the particles, r , the model employs a function inspired by the Lennard-Jones potential:

$$u(r) = \begin{cases} u_R(r) = \varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{r_{\min}}{r} \right)^4 - 2 \left(\frac{r_{\min}}{r} \right)^2 \right], & r < r_{\min} \\ u_A(r) = -\varepsilon \cos^2 \zeta \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \frac{(r - r_{\min})}{(r_c - r_{\min})} \right], & r_{\min} < r < r_c \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

In this equation, ε and σ are the units of energy and length, respectively. The potential has two parts: one repulsive and one attractive. The shape of the repulsive part resembles a Lennard-Jones potential, but instead of having the classic 12-6 exponents, the 4-2 combination is chosen. This combination is selected because the behavior is *smoother*, which is expected from the interaction between a bunch of lipids. The attractive part employs a cosine function, which is chosen with the same motivation as the choice of the previous exponents, to smooth the behavior of the function. The limits of the potentials are taken as $r_{\min} = 2\sigma^{(1/6)}$ (similar to that used in the Lennard-Jones potential) and $r_c = 2.6\sigma$, so that interactions between second neighbors are considered. The effect of anisotropic interactions is added through the function that depends on the relative orientations, ϕ , which regulates the energy associated with different orientations:

$$U(\mathbf{r}_{ij}, \mathbf{n}_i, \mathbf{n}_j) = \begin{cases} u_R(r) + [1 - \phi(\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}, \mathbf{n}_i, \mathbf{n}_j)] \varepsilon, & r < r_{\min} \\ u_A(r) \phi(\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}, \mathbf{n}_i, \mathbf{n}_j), & r_{\min} < r < r_c \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

The function ϕ scales the attractive interaction while shifting the repulsive part, thus ensuring that the potential is continuous. The function ϕ contains the information about the lipid amphiphilic nature and shape (spontaneous curvature) by introducing an orientational interaction between “dipoles” with a preferential angle (Fig 4.1 A):

$$\phi = 1 + \mu [a(\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}, \mathbf{n}_i, \mathbf{n}_j) - 1] \quad (4.3)$$

where

$$a = (\mathbf{n}_i \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}) \cdot (\mathbf{n}_j \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}) + \sin \theta_0 (\mathbf{n}_j - \mathbf{n}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} - \sin^2 \theta_0 \quad (4.4)$$

The function a introduces the parameter θ_0 , which indicates the spontaneous curvature of the membrane; a (and therefore ϕ) reaches its maximum when $\theta_i = \theta_j = \theta_0$. When the relative orientation of the particles differs from θ_0 , an energetic penalty weighted by μ is added. Thus, the parameter μ regulates the bending rigidity.

This potential does not come from a detailed analysis of the underlying interactions or from the inspection of all-atom simulations. *The model is chosen to qualitatively reproduce the expected behavior of a set of amphiphilic molecules. To reproduce a particular phenomenon, the model has a set of free parameters, which we can select according to the case we wish to study.*

The parameters of the model are ε and σ , which set the energy and length scales, while the properties of the membrane are determined by ζ , μ , and θ_0 . As mentioned, the parameter θ_0 regulates the spontaneous curvature of the membrane. The parameters ε , μ , and ζ regulate the state of the membrane. The membrane can be in different states - solid, gel, liquid, or gas - depending on the value of these parameters [42]. By modifying the parameter ζ , we can vary the diffusion of the particles in the membrane, while the state of the membrane barely changes.

Using this model, we can reproduce a large number of phenomena, such as the creation of vesicles (and their fusion) (Fig. 4.1 B), endocytosis, lipid phase separation [200], solid/fluid membrane transition [199, 200], budding (when we add two types of particles), and more [42, 189, 201–203]. In particular, we will focus on how we can use this model to simulate vesicles.

The model gives rise to the spontaneous formation of vesicles for the appropriate parameters (those that result in a fluid state of the membrane). Vesicles can be obtained even for values of $\theta_0 = 0$. If we start from a random situation at a certain concentration, the particles first tend to group into flakes that increase in size until they collapse into vesicles [42]. This phenomenon is energetically favorable due to the edge effect. Once the vesicles are formed, we can determine their physical properties through an analysis of their fluctuations.

Figure 4.1: A) Adapted from [199]. The different components of the interaction are represented. Each particle is located at \mathbf{r}_i and \mathbf{r}_j . \mathbf{r}_{ij} is the distance vector from i to j and \mathbf{n}_i and \mathbf{n}_j are the vectors that determine the orientation of the particles. θ_i and θ_j gives the in-plane angles. The interaction is described by the equation 4.2. As for the angular part, the function ϕ it has a minimum when $\theta_i = \theta_j = \theta_0$. B) Example of a vesicle (simulated using UAMMD-structured, Chapter 6) For this case we take the parameters $\zeta = 4$ and $\mu = 3$ which ensure that the vesicle is in a fluid state [42]. We take $\theta_0 = 0$, for this value the energetic tendency of the beads is to form a membrane. When the membrane is large enough, it is favorable to energetically close on itself to reduce the energy of the edges. A section of the vesicle is also shown. In this case the vectors representing the particle orientation would be parallel to the radial direction.

The free energy of the vesicles can be described by the Helfrich model [199, 204, 205]. The eigenfunctions of the Helfrich functional for a sphere (normal modes) are the spherical harmonics which can be used to decompose the vesicle fluctuations, and use the equipartition theorem to evaluate the bending rigidity k_c , from the normal modes amplitude [199, 200].

Using this model, we can simulate processes even on the scale of seconds. This model has been used to simulate endocytosis processes, both of nanoparticles [202, 206] and viruses [201], and to study how vesicles move through cavities [199]. The model has been extended to allow the addition of an equilibrium volume, which allows reproducing the shape of other biological elements such as red blood cells [207]

Chapter 5

Reaction coordinate models

The relatively recent development of experimental techniques that allow for the mechanical manipulation of biological structures, from simple proteins to cells, has been key to advancing our understanding of how these structures function and operate together [208].

The main experimental techniques that enable precise mechanical forces to be exerted on biological structures are optical tweezers and atomic force microscopy (AFM). By employing these tools, it is possible to conduct a wide variety of studies on the structural properties of proteins, DNA [209], viruses [53], cells [210], and more [208]. However, to interpret the meaning of the signals obtained, *it is necessary to use models that capture the internal behavior of these structures when subjected to mechanical stresses.*

In this section, we will use protein pulling experiments as a central example, although the models presented have more general applicability. To model these types of experiments, we could opt for direct simulation of the process using one of the models presented in previous sections. It is possible to simulate certain experiments, such as protein unfolding, using coarse-grained particle models like the “alpha carbon resolution models” introduced in Chapter 1 [65]. However, in most experiments performed using optical tweezers or AFM, *the time or spatial scales of the processes are so large that carrying out simulations is not feasible.*

An alternative to simulation using coarse-grained particle models is to understand the entire process as if it were a **chemical reaction**. By using optical tweezers or AFM, we can determine if the sample is in certain conformational states. Specifically, following this analogy, it is possible to define a **reaction coordinate**. For example, in the case of protein pulling, we can use the distance between the two ends of the protein (on which we apply a mechanical force) as the reaction coordinate to identify the state of the protein, whether in its native configuration or in some unfolded state.

Based on this assumption, **Bell** proposed the first theoretical model in 1978 to explain these phenomena [46]. Bell suggests that the reaction coordinate, which is a *collective variable* (a function of a large number of degrees of freedom), is sufficient to define a *free energy function*. That is, the free energy of the system can be represented by a function of the reaction coordinate. Then a multi-state model can be represented by a continuous free energy with different local minima, each minimum representing a state of the system. By observing these transition processes, we can obtain information about the energy profile of the sample. However, these transitions do not occur spontaneously because the difference between the states is generally large enough that the probability of observing such events is very low. We can use optical tweezers or AFM to force these transitions. By applying a force on the reaction coordinate (in the case of protein pulling, when we pull on both ends), we make these transitions more likely. Using phenological arguments, tools from solid state theory and inspired by previous works on transition state theory by Eyring and Polanyi [211] (or even Arrhenius at S.XIX) Bell proposes the following model to explain how the transition rate between states varies as a function of the applied force:

$$k(F) = k_0 \exp\left(\frac{Fx^\ddagger}{k_B T}\right) \quad (5.1)$$

where $k_B T$ is the Boltzmann constant times the temperature, F is the applied force, and x^\ddagger is an effective distance that provides information about the response of the system to the external force and must be determined experimentally. This approximation is widely used to calculate the equilibrium rate k_0 and x^\ddagger [46, 48]. The central idea of Bell is that the application of force “tilts” the free energy profile, making the transition more likely as the force increases (Fig. 5.1). This simple equation was used for years (and still is today) to analyze experimental results. Specifically, it is often used to calculate k_0 and compare this value when the sample is modified, for example, in protein pulling by mutation or changing environmental properties such as the ions concentration [210, 212, 213]. By comparing the different k_0 values, we can understand how various modifications affect the studied structure [48].

The above equation (5.1), being essentially phenomenological, does not allow a clear interpretation of k_0 and x^\ddagger . To resolve this, a precise derivation of the equation using **Kramers theory** can be performed [214, 215]. This derivation starts from the idea of Bell that the application of force modifies the energy profile. Then Kramers theory is applied, which serves to calculate the transition probability when a particle is immersed in a fluid viscous enough that there is no inertia (as is the case for water in systems the size of cells, viruses, and proteins) across a potential barrier [145]. In this case, the interpretation of the parameters is straightforward. We can estimate

the probability of spontaneous transition, the size of the barrier, and the parameter x^\ddagger , which corresponds to the distance (in terms of reaction coordinate) between the potential minimum and the barrier maximum.

This set of theoretical tools is widely used for interpreting pulling experiments. These experiments, along with model of Bell and its subsequent developments, have been employed to obtain crucial information about protein folding [210]. They can be used to determine the cascade of transitions that occur in unfolding processes [208, 216]. Currently, this technique is even used to study the transcription and translation of DNA into proteins by employing optical tweezers on a system consisting of a DNA sequence and a ribosome [217, 218]. The set of theoretical tools used is more general and can be applied not only to the optical tweezers and protein systems. They can be applied to any system that exerts a mechanical force on a structure that can deform or break. In Chapter 9, we use this type of theoretical analysis to study the disassembly process of a virus, where in our case, the mechanical stresses are applied by an AFM tip.

Figure 5.1: Effect of applying an external force on a potential barrier. In this case GFP protein is considered as example. In a situation where no external force is applied, the protein tends to remain in its native conformation. If we express the energy as a function of the distance between the two ends of the amino acid chain that make up the protein, we can say that the energy has a minimum in the native conformation (red line). When we apply a force on this reaction coordinate (the distance between the two ends of the amino acid chain) we reduce the height of the barrier (dashed lines). If we continue to increase the force we reach a point where the protein can cross the barrier, i.e. the protein is unfolded. On this type of modeling (proposed by Bell [46]) we can apply the theory of Kramer and derive an analytical expression [48].

Part II

Computational tools

The use of computational tools, in particular for simulations of physical systems, has become an integral part of scientific development. In the field of soft matter, especially in biology, these tools have been crucial in understanding a large number of systems, often difficult to access by experimental techniques. Just to name a few examples, these include the internal dynamics of proteins [125], quantum phenomena involved in enzymatic reactions [219], among many others. Furthermore, *computational techniques are essential in validating theories*. By simulating a system based on a set of hypotheses, we are able to check if the results of the simulation match with experimental findings [40, 110, 220]. These types of tools also stand out for their predictive capabilities [221], not only qualitative but also quantitative.

Different tools are required for different scales and description levels. Here, we focus on the **mesoscale**, where most biological phenomena take place [222, 223]. The mesoscale roughly ranges from a few nanometers to several hundred microns and includes timeframes from picoseconds extending to microseconds.

Once we have decided which phenomena our tool will deal with, we must attend to another important decision. This decision is of a technical and design nature. In software development we must find a *balance between accessibility and adaptability*. If our software has a high degree of customization it is likely that it will also require more advanced users. So, finding the balance between ease of use and level of customization is essential. This mainly depends on the type of user the software is aimed at and the complexity of the tasks it will perform. To deal with this task, we have developed a set of computational tools that differ from each other in their complexity:

- **UAMMD-structured**: This tool is an extension of **Universally Adaptable Multiscale Molecular Dynamics**, **UAMMD**, a C++/CUDA (GPU) library initially developed by Raul P. Pelaez within our research group, focusing on multiscale simulation algorithms [224, 225]. **UAMMD-structured** enhances the functionality of **UAMMD** by simplifying its usage and introducing new features. Primarily designed for the simulation of coarse-grained models, **UAMMD-structured** is distinct from **UAMMD** in that it eliminates the need for users to interact directly with the code, instead utilizing a general-purpose precompiled executable.
- **Virtual Lab Modeling Platform, VLMP**: Designed as a Python library, **VLMP** allows to carry out simulations of complex systems by specifying their basic components. **VLMP** understands simulations in a modular fashion, as if they were a set of blocks, these blocks can be combined in different ways and give rise to different simulations. In addition, **VLMP** has an interface to facilitate the parallel execution of these simulations both locally and in **High Performance Computing** (HPC) environments.

- **Virtual Experiments Web, Vexperiments:** Through `Vexperiments` we can create simple web interfaces to carry out complex simulations and share them with other users.

These tools, although designed to function independently, are equipped with interfaces to communicate with each other. This interoperability makes them a very useful software for collaboration between different users with different knowledge and capabilities. For example, advanced GPU algorithms can be implemented using the functions of `UAMMD-structured`. Users not familiar with GPU programming can take advantage of these tools with `VLMP` to build complex systems. These systems can then be made accessible through a simple web interface, allowing them to be used by people with no technical knowledge.

`UAMMD-structured` and `VLMP` are specially crafted for use them in high-performance environments. Both `UAMMD` and `UAMMD-structured` are fully GPU-implemented, this fact adds complexity to the algorithms but significantly enhance the performance. This enhanced performance allows for the study of more complicate phenomena and larger systems. `VLMP`, meanwhile, is adapted to work in HPC clusters, with features designed to distribute tasks efficiently within the cluster resources.

In the following sections the different tools are introduced. We will discuss their motivation, their most relevant technical aspects and how to use them.

Chapter 6

UAMMD-structured

At the **mesoscale** we have to deal with complex interactions between entities of diverse nature such as nanoparticles, colloids and viscoelastic structures among others. To study these types of interactions, we must use knowledge from very different fields, such as fluid mechanics, molecular biology and coarse-grained theory. From a technical point of view, computational methods with different spatial and dynamical resolutions and the ability to selectively eliminate non-essential fast modes for specific problems are also required. No single computational tool can effectively address the full range of mesoscale phenomena due to their complexity. An integrative approach combining different methods, such as MD and CFD, is needed. Standard software packages, such as GROMACS, LAMMPS and OpenFOAM, while excellent within their scope, often lack adaptability and flexibility [226–229]. *The ideal solution for the investigation of mesoscale phenomena is a flexible and modular platform adapted to the specific needs that arise at this scale.*

UAMMD is a native-GPU tool, designed to bridge gaps in mesoscale simulation. It integrates discrete particle models with continuum fluid dynamics, offering a set of algorithms for diverse dynamic regimes and timescales [225, 230].

- *Native GPU:* UAMMD stands out for its GPU-resident architecture. This means that all main calculations are performed on the GPU, significantly reducing the number of data transfers required between the CPU and GPU. This kind of operations are very slow compared to the other calculations performed and can significantly slow down the performance of a program [225].
- *Modular and Open:* UAMMD has a modular design which simplifies adding new features. In addition, its *open source* status allows these new features to be shared among other users [225, 231, 232].

- *Designed as a Library:* As a C++14 library, UAMMD easily integrates into various projects, extending its utility beyond mere standalone simulations.

This approach provides considerable freedom and responsibility to the user, who must configure these functions to tailor them to the specific problem they aim to face. UAMMD strives to be as generic as possible, reducing core assumptions to the minimum necessary. This methodology has its advantages and disadvantages. Its primary benefit is that it provides the code with remarkable flexibility. UAMMD supplies algorithms that are highly efficient and commonly used in various fields of physics (as well as in other disciplines), such as neighbor lists and spreading and interpolation algorithms. At a basic level, UAMMD specializes in algorithms related to hydrodynamics, but even here there is an important distinction. UAMMD implements various algorithms necessary for building these integrators in an agnostic way, making them available for implementation in other contexts if found useful. While this approach is extremely beneficial in many cases, it also has certain drawbacks. Firstly, it necessitates the rewriting of many codes. If two users are working in a similar field, they might need similar functions. This increases the complexity and the time required to implement an idea in UAMMD. Furthermore, the level of expertise required to use UAMMD must be considered. Being a C++/CUDA library, it is assumed that the user is proficient in these languages. Generally, the required proficiency significantly surpasses the average level attained by a physicist or a computation chemist (the primary target audience of UAMMD) during their academic training.

UAMMD-structured, built on top of UAMMD, specifically targets the complexities involved in coarse-grained model simulations. This development focuses on systems with diverse potentials across various parts, offering a structured framework for defining hierarchical levels like atoms within residues, residues within chains, and chains within larger models. The organized nature of this approach is encapsulated in its name.

UAMMD-structured marks an evolution in the original scope of UAMMD, shifting towards a more specialized role in the field of molecular dynamics and coarse-grained modeling. What began as a mere adaptation of UAMMD has matured into a highly generalized and structured tool. This evolution has been so significant that UAMMD-structured now serves as a versatile tool for a broad spectrum of simulations.

To better understand the positioning of UAMMD-structured in the field of molecular dynamics, it is useful to classify the software in this area into three main categories:

- **Gromacs, Amber, Charmm, etc.** [125, 226, 233]: These programs are designed for users with limited programming skills. They are compiled to a single binary and the user configures one or more input files to simulate a specific system. They focus on atomic simulations, surfaces, proteins, and inorganic compounds, but are not easily adaptable for the implementation of the new ideas of the users.
- **OpenMM, Hoomd** [229, 234]: These programs offer more flexibility than the previous ones and are distributed as Python packages. They allow, within certain limits, the implementation of custom models by users, although making significant changes can be complex.
- **LAMMPS** [227]: This software is designed to be customizable. It is compiled to a single binary and the different options are selected via an input file. LAMMPS is intended to be modified, its code is designed to add new features easily.

In this context, **UAMMD-structured** aligns more with the philosophy of LAMMPS. Like LAMMPS, it allows the implementation of a wide range of models, but it stands out in several key aspects.

Firstly, from the perspective of efficiency. LAMMPS, originally designed for CPUs and later adapted to include GPU functions, faces certain limitations. Integrating code on GPUs is more complex and the frequent need to transfer data between GPU and CPU adversely affects performance. Additionally, it is not implemented in modern C++, increasing the complexity of its development.

In contrast, **UAMMD-structured** stands out as it is not subject to these limitations. It is entirely implemented for GPU and developed in modern C++, significantly facilitating the integration of new elements. **UAMMD-structured** enhances the simulation process by introducing batch simulations, a method particularly beneficial for coarse-grained simulations on GPUs. The inherent challenge in these simulations lies in their inefficiency, mainly due to the small number of particles used in coarse-grained models. This leads to underutilization of the computational power of the GPU, sometimes making CPUs a faster alternative. To address this inefficiency, batching is employed, where multiple small simulations are combined into a larger one.

Unlike **UAMMD**, **UAMMD-structured** is designed to operate as a single executable, where the various components that are desired for use are selected through an input system. This system is intended to be manageable with high-level languages such as Python. This means that the use of **UAMMD-structured** is facilitated through the use of these input files. For adding new features, a C++/CUDA interface is integrated, following the logic of **UAMMD** but with a simplified process for incorporating

certain common components. Moreover, `UAMMD-structured` allows these new additions to be easily exposed to the input system, **enabling users who may not have C++/CUDA expertise to utilize them.**

In this chapter, we will introduce `UAMMD-structured`. After presenting the general functioning, we will focus on the different interactions available. Some of these interactions, such as certain pairwise interactions, the so-called many-body bonds, and patchy particle models, are unique to `UAMMD-structured`. We will examine their functioning by exposing their algorithms and discussing certain aspects of their implementation. Following this, we will explain how `UAMMD-structured` has a batching mechanism to parallelize a large number of small simulations, thus fully utilizing GPU potential. We will also present `pyUAMMD`, a Python library used not only as an auxiliary tool to facilitate work with simulation inputs but also to execute simulations. Finally, we will introduce `USCM`, an auxiliary program that manages different components and allows for the easy addition of new ones. Throughout this discussion, technical details have been omitted. For a complete exposition of the `UAMMD-structured` application, including these omitted technical details, instructions on obtaining the code, and guidance on compiling and installing it, please refer to the online documentation [235].

6.1 Execution

Initiating a simulation with `UAMMD-structured` begins with preparing the input, the details of which are covered in following sections. Once the input has been configured, there are mainly two methods to conduct simulations. The first involves compiling `UAMMD-structured` into a single executable and launching the simulation via the command line:

```
UAMMDlauncher simulation.json
```

Here, `UAMMDlauncher` is the compiled executable, and "simulation.json" is the selected input file.

Alternatively, `UAMMD-structured` can be used through Python, the `UAMMD-structured/Python` interface is provided by the `pyUAMMD` package. In this approach, the simulation input is specified using the `simulation` object from `pyUAMMD` (which works as a Python dictionary). The simulation is then executed by invoking the `run()` method:

```
import pyUAMMD
sim = pyUAMMD.simulation()

sim[...] = {...} # Set up simulation parameters
...

sim.run()
```

Both methods are functionally equivalent, giving users the flexibility to choose the one that best suits their workflow. The key here lies in setting up the input correctly to perform the desired simulation, contrasting with `UAMMD` where new code needs to be written and compiled for each new simulation type.

6.2 Design

`UAMMD-structured` is designed with the primary goal of simulating **generic physical systems**. This process is accomplished through the use of several entities, each responsible for managing and storing some of the information needed to run a simulation. Each of these entities is responsible for different aspects of the simulation, such as managing particle states, handling interactions and performing the integration process.

A key aspect of `UAMMD-structured` is its strong reliance on input. As highlighted earlier, there are two primary ways to operate `UAMMD-structured`. It can be compiled into a single, general-purpose binary that processes inputs in a specific format. Alternatively, it can be executed through a `Python` interface, where input is provided in the form of a dictionary. In both cases the format of the input is similar. The customization of the simulation is achieved by modifying the options available in the input file or dictionary. Through this input, the properties of the following basic entities are specified, determining the type of simulation being conducted:

- **System:** Specifies technical aspects of the simulation, like the name of the simulation, backup and restarting systems, or the seed for random number generation.
- **Integrator:** This `section` defines the integrators employed in the simulation. Integrators are algorithms responsible for updating the state of the simulation. `UAMMD-structured` provides a range of integrators, from the classical Verlet algorithm, to more complex ones used for simulating systems with fluid interactions.

Commonly, only one integrator is used; however, `UAMMD-structured` also offers the option to sequentially apply multiple integrators.

- **Global:** Adds elements to the simulation not related to individual particles, such as the units used, the type of particles, or the ensemble (temperature, volume ...) for the simulation.
- **State:** Specifies the properties of particles that may vary throughout the simulation or that are unique to each particle, like position or orientation.
- **Topology:** Encapsulates information typically found in topology files in other software (e.g., GROMACS). This facilitates entry for new users by using a common language in the field. Topology specifies:
 - **Structure:** Associates each particle with a type and specific structures, like the residue or the chain it belongs to.
 - **Force Field:** Defines the interactions to which the particles are subjected, such as bonds, short-range interactions, external fields ...
- **Simulation Steps:** Selects the type of information obtained from the simulation. These are operations performed at user-defined intervals, involving different measurements or writing information to a file, such as dumping the state of the simulation or measuring temperature and pressure.

Upon specifying these entities, `UAMMD-structured` processes, connects them, and initiates the simulation. **Therefore, understanding `UAMMD-structured` is equivalent to knowing the different options available for these entities.**

6.3 Input

`UAMMD-structured` is designed around the input system. This input system is flexible enough to be able to adjust the characteristics of the simulation without the need to recompile the entire program.

The central element of the input system is the `DataEntry`. A `DataEntry` is a data structure designed to initialize a specific entity of the simulation. The different `DataEntries` are organized hierarchically. They can be grouped in `sections`. These `sections` can contain several `DataEntries` or also other `sections`. Both `sections` and `DataEntries` are identified by a `name`, which has to be *unique*. For clarity, in the `Integrators` section, users will find different `DataEntries`, each uniquely identified by names like "langevin", "brownian" ... These entries are designed to initialize entities associated with the integration task. This includes not only the integrator

Figure 6.1: This figure illustrates the architecture of the UAMMD-structured simulation framework. It highlights the key components involved in simulating physical systems. The architecture is broken down into several main entities: *System*, *Integrator*, *Global*, *State*, *Topology*, and *Simulation Steps*.

itself but also other entities that have an impact on the integration process. The UAMMD-structured input system is designed with two key principles in mind: *consistency* (for ease of learning) and *modularity* (for extensibility). Each `DataEntry` contains a series of fields to store information in different formats:

- **Type:** Defined by two strings, the class and its subclass, this field identifies the specific entity type to be initialized. For instance, a Langevin integrator initialization would label its class as "integrator" and the subclass as "Langevin".
- **Parameters Entry:** This field contains a dictionary that allows the user to specify the parameters of the `DataEntry` in detail, using a standard key-value format. It is versatile enough to support a wide variety of data types, such as floats, strings, lists, and more. As an example, consider a `DataEntry` for a harmonic spring potential, where a typical parameter like "K", representing the spring constant, might be specified.
- **Matrix Format for Data-Intensive Entities:** Employed for entities requiring extensive data, this format uses a matrix structure. Organized using "labels" (keys) and "data" (values), it is flexible, supporting varied data formats such as numerical values, strings, or lists. For instance, in setting parameters for a Lennard-Jones interaction, pairs of particle types are related with their respective ϵ and σ parameters. Assuming that there are two types of particles, "A" and "B", the parameters of the interaction would be specified in the following format:

Labels	Name i	Name j	ϵ	σ
Data	A	A	ϵ_{AA}	σ_{AA}
	A	B	ϵ_{AB}	σ_{AB}
	B	B	ϵ_{BB}	σ_{BB}

Then to access a particular parameter we must specify its corresponding row (by its index) and label.

`Sections`, on the other hand, can have a `Type` field and contain a set of `DataEntry`s. The presence of *parameters*, *data* and *labels* fields in a `DataEntry` is optional, depending on the needs of the type of entity to be initialized. A `DataEntry` is still considered valid whether these components are included or not. By contrast, the `Type` field is compulsory as it defines the nature of the entry. While the name serves an identification purpose and can vary widely, the `Type` field is crucial for the program to understand what the `DataEntry` represents. The input format is sketched in the Fig. 6.2.

Figure 6.2: Diagram showing the input format in UAMMD-structured , highlighting the hierarchical organization of DataEntry within different sections .

There are important exceptions to this structure. The six principal elements: `system`, `global`, `state`, `integrators`, `topology`, and `simulation steps`, along with the two main elements within `topology` (`structure` and `forcefield`), are identified uniquely by their names. These elements are so central to the functioning of `UAMMD-structured` that they do not require a `Type` field; their names are enough to identify them.

`UAMMD-structured` employs both JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) [236] and YAML (YAML Ain't Markup Language) [237] for its input mechanism. These formats were selected due to their suitability for the aforementioned requirements:

- **Human-Readable and Write-Friendly:** Both formats are clear and accessible, simplifying user interaction and understanding.
- **Hierarchical Structure:** They support nested structures, aligning well with the hierarchical input of `UAMMD-structured`.
- **Flexibility in Data Types:** Efficient in managing various data types, crucial for different entries like "Type", "parameters", and matrix like format data.
- **Broad Support:** Due to their popularity, numerous tools across languages are available.

Although JSON and YAML were chosen, the design of `UAMMD-structured` permits integration with other formats, requiring careful implementation to maintain compatibility.

In this thesis, YAML is mainly used for its better readability. Yet, for the specific data structures used in `UAMMD-structured` input, both YAML and JSON formats are equivalent, and conversion from one file type to another can be done easily.

To illustrate the implementation of the input system of `UAMMD-structured` using YAML, some examples are shown below. These examples are provided to give a clear idea of how the structured input format, is translated into practical YAML templates. The first example (Code 6.1) shows a basic YAML structure for a simple `section` of the input file. The second example (Code 6.2) demonstrates how nested `sections` are represented in YAML.

Code 6.1: Simulation Template 1

```
Section1:
DataEntry1-1:
  type: ["class", "subclass"]
  parameters:
    param1: "value1"
    param2: "value2"
    "...": "..."
  labels: ["label1", "label2", "..."]
  data:
    - ["label1_data1", "label1_data2", "..."]
    - ["label2_data1", "label2_data2", "..."]
    - ["..."]
DataEntry1-2:
  type: ["class", "subclass"]
  parameters:
    param1: "value1"
    param2: "value2"
    "...": "..."
  labels: ["label1", "label2", "..."]
  data:
    - ["label1_data1", "label1_data2", "..."]
    - ["label2_data1", "label2_data2", "..."]
    - ["..."]
# ...
```

Code 6.2: Simulation Template 2

```
Section2:
DataEntry2-1:
  type: ["class", "subclass"]
  parameters:
    param1: "value1"
    param2: "value2"
    "...": "..."
  labels: ["label1", "label2", "..."]
  data:
    - ["label1_data1", "label1_data2", "..."]
    - ["label2_data1", "label2_data2", "..."]
    - ["..."]
# ...
SectionA:
DataEntryA-1:
  type: ["class", "subclass"]
  parameters:
    param1: "value1"
    param2: "value2"
    "...": "..."
  labels: ["label1", "label2", "..."]
  data:
    - ["label1_data1", "label1_data2", "..."]
    - ["label2_data1", "label2_data2", "..."]
    - ["..."]
# ...
# ...
```

6.4 Simulation

Once we have introduced the necessary elements to set up an execute a simulation, we now introduce a typical simulation example. Specifically, this example shows a system of four particles configured in a simple rod-like structure, where consecutive particles are bonded by harmonic springs. Additionally, a harmonic angular potential is added between the first three and the last three particles (Code 6.3).

Code 6.3: Simulation Example

```
system:
  info:
    type: ["Simulation", "Information"]
    parameters:
      name: "ROD"

global:
  units:
    type: ["Units", "None"]
  types:
    type: ["Types", "Basic"]
    labels: ["name", "mass", "radius", "charge"]
  data:
    - ["A", 1.0, 0.5, 0.0]
  ensemble:
    type: ["Ensemble", "NVT"]
    labels: ["box", "temperature"]
    data:
      - [[[10.0, 10.0, 10.0], 1.0]]

integrators:
  lang_bbk:
    type: ["Langevin", "BBK"]
    parameters:
      timeStep: 0.001
      frictionConstant: 1.0
  schedule:
    type: ["Schedule", "Integrator"]
    labels: ["order", "integrator", "steps"]
    data:
      - [1, "lang_bbk", 1000000]

state:
  labels: ["id", "position"]
  data:
    - [0, [0.0, 0.0, 0.0]]
    - [1, [0.0, 0.0, 1.0]]
    - [2, [0.0, 0.0, 2.0]]
    - [3, [0.0, 0.0, 3.0]]
```

Code 6.3: Simulation Example (Cont.)

```
topology:
  structure:
    labels: ["id", "type", "modelId"]
    data:
      - [0, "A", 0]
      - [1, "A", 0]
      - [2, "A", 0]
      - [3, "A", 0]
  forceField:
    bonds:
      type: ["Bond2", "HarmonicCommon_K_r0"]
      parameters:
        K: 100.0
        r0: 1.0
      labels: ["id_i", "id_j"]
      data:
        - [0, 1]
        - [1, 2]
        - [2, 3]
    angles:
      type: ["Bond3", "KratkyPorodCommon_K"]
      parameters:
        K: 50.0
      labels: ["id_i", "id_j", "id_k"]
      data:
        - [0, 1, 2]
        - [1, 2, 3]

simulationStep:
  info:
    type: ["UtilsStep", "InfoStep"]
    parameters:
      intervalStep: 10000
  saveState:
    type: ["WriteStep", "WriteStep"]
    parameters:
      outputFilePath: "test"
      outputFormat: "sp"
      intervalStep: 10000
```

Every `DataEntry` (excluding *state*) possesses a "type" field, which is compulsory and must always be present. However, in some entries, we have both parameters and data, while in others, we might only have parameters or just data.

Starting with the *system* section, it is primarily used to initialize basic simulation aspects. In our example, only the name of the simulation is present.

The *Global* section sets units, particle types used, and the ensemble for the simulation. Following that, the *integrators* section indicates the use of a Langevin integrator of the BBK type. In this section, the `DataEntry` "schedule" is also found. "schedule" is used to specify the order and number of steps for every integrator. For example, it indicates that the integrator named "lang_bbk" will execute first for 10^6 steps.

In the *state* section, particle IDs and positions are specified. Other information, such as velocity or particle orientation, can also be added here.

Then we come to the *topology* section, further divided into *structure* and *forceField* sub-sections. In *structure*, each particle is associated with a type and potentially a superior structure, like a model, chain, or residue.

The *forceField* lists the interactions present. In our example, we see two bond types: pair bonds and angular bonds.

Finally, the *simulationSteps* are a series of operations carried out at specific intervals. Here, we have two types: an *InfoStep* and a *WriteStep*. The former displays simulation process information, like elapsed time and the number of integration steps performed by second. The latter, *saveState*, is used to save the simulation state, here in the "dcd" format.

This example is representative of a general simulation in UAMMD-structured and encompasses all its elements. This file would be given to the UAMMD-structured executable (Section 6.1), which would start the simulation.

In the following sections, we will introduce the different components that can be employed in the input and discuss the implementation of some of the most important ones in detail.

6.5 System

To carry out a simulation, we must not only determine the purely physical variables of the system, but often it is also necessary to specify certain technical aspects. These options are indicated in the *System* section . The *System* section is the first segment of the input to be processed in a UAMMD-structured simulation. This section establishes some fundamental parameters of the simulation. Currently, within *System*, we can specify two types of `DataEntries` : one is mandatory ("Information"), and the other is optional ("Backup"). Both entries are categorized under the main type "Simulation" (Code 6.5).

Code 6.5: System Example

```

system:
  info:
    type: ["Simulation", "Information"]
    parameters:
      name: "example"
      seed: 123456
  backup:
    type: ["Simulation", "Backup"]
    parameters:
      backupFilePath: "backup"
      backupIntervalStep: 10000
# ...

```

The "Information" `DataEntry` is essential and must always be included in the input. This entry is employed to assign a name to the simulation, which is specified using the "name" parameter. Optionally, the "seed" parameter can be set to fix the seed for random number generation. Fixing a specific seed value is done for ensuring that simulations are reproducible, providing consistent outputs which are needed for validating results or for debugging purposes.

6.5.1 Handling Errors

The optional "Backup" `DataEntry` activates backup and restart mechanism of UAMMD-structured . This mechanism is used for maintaining simulation integrity, especially if an error occurs. If activated, the simulation can revert to a previously saved state and attempt to continue from there. While it might initially appear counterintuitive, presuming a repeated failure at the same simulation point, the utility of this feature depends on the nature of the failure. For instance, a simulation might fail due to a particle being subjected to an excessively large force, leading to instability

and senseless numerical values. In molecular dynamics, this situation often arises from an inappropriate setting of the time step integration parameter, "dt" [238]. Adjusting "dt" can mitigate the occurrence of these extreme events, although it cannot entirely prevent them [239]. This problem intensifies in coarse-grained simulations where a larger "dt" is usually employed [240] and particularly on GPUs, where work is often done with single precision [241]. To address this, `UAMMD-structured` modifies the random number seed upon a simulation failure, with the intention that this alteration will sufficiently diverge the simulation path to avoid the previously encountered low-probability failure event. The "Backup" entry allows specifying the file path for saving the simulation state ("backupFilePath") and the interval at which these backups occur ("backupIntervalStep").

In the C++/CUDA environment of `UAMMD-structured`, error handling is sophisticated. Standard CPU exceptions are captured and handled by regular C++ procedures, but CUDA presents a challenge with its “sticky” errors: *error flags set by the CUDA API that remain unless the process is restarted*. To counter this, `UAMMD-structured` employs the following strategy: at the initiation of a simulation with restart enabled, a system call creates two processes: a parent and a child. The child runs the simulation, while the parent supervises. If the child process ends due to an error, the parent detects this and can restart the child process using a backup file, thus bypassing the “sticky” error issue in CUDA and continuing the simulation from a previous save point. This procedure is shown in Fig. 6.3.

6.6 Global

The second section to be processed is *Global*. As its name suggests, the *Global* section sets certain overall aspects of the simulation. Unlike the *System* section, the properties here have a physical meaning. Within the global section, we can add four types of entries: **fundamental**, **units**, **types**, and **ensemble**. It only makes sense to add one entry of each type (for example, it does not make sense to indicate two different units systems); doing otherwise will result in an error and prevent the simulation from starting. The following code shows a typical configuration example for the *Global* section (Code 6.6).

Figure 6.3: Flowchart depicting the subprocess management in UAMMD-structured for handling errors in CUDA.

Code 6.6: Global Example

```

global:
  fundamental:
    type: ["Fundamental", "Time"]
  ensemble:
    type: ["Ensemble", "NVT"]
    labels: ["box", "temperature"]
    data:
      - [[100.0, 100.0, 100.0], 300.0]
  types:
    type: ["Types", "Basic"]
    labels: ["name", "mass", "radius", "charge"]
    data:
      - ["A", 1.0, 0.5, -1.0]
      - ["B", 1.0, 0.5, 0.0]
      - ["C", 1.0, 0.5, 1.0]
  units:
    type: ["Units", "KcalMol_A"]
# ...

```

6.6.1 Fundamental

Fundamental `DataEntry` is somewhat abstract. In fundamental, we can set the *main property governing the simulation*. A common example would be to have "Time" as the fundamental type, meaning time is the main controlling quantity, as is typical in molecular dynamics simulations. There are other options for specific cases, but generally, "Time" is used, and if this entry is not specified, "Time" is considered by default.

6.6.2 Units

UAMMD-structured provides a unit system featuring various options, including the **Kcal/mol Å** units, commonly known as AKMA in the literature. When some particular units is selected, all input data is interpreted according to it. For example in the case of AKMA (widely used in molecular dynamics simulations of proteins, DNA, RNA ...), specific units for physical quantities like length, mass, temperature, energy, and others are defined. The units within the AKMA system are listed in Table 6.1.

The AKMA Time Unit is a derived unit in this system, calculated from the primary units of mass, length, and energy. It is equivalent to 4.888821×10^{-14} seconds. For practical purposes, however, time in AKMA units is usually represented in picoseconds, with 20 AKMA time units being approximately 0.978 picoseconds. The input and

Table 6.1: Units in the AKMA System

Quantity	Unit	Symbol/Formula
Length	Angstrom	Å
Mass	Dalton (Atomic Mass Unit)	Da (amu)
Temperature	Kelvin	K
Charge	Electron Charge	e
Energy	Kilocalorie per mole	kcal/mol
Time	AKMA Time Unit	AKMA Time Unit
Force	Kilocalorie per mole per Angstrom	kcal/(mol·Å)
Pressure	Atmospheres	atm
Velocity	Angstroms per AKMA Time Unit	Å/(AKMA Time unit)

the output are unchanged, when this unit system is used then input and output are assumed to be in AKMA time units.

"None" units system can also be selected, in this case the interpretation of units is left entirely to the user. Internally, when we set a units system, what happens is that the value of certain physical constants are fixed, such as the Boltzmann constant or the vacuum permittivity, when "None" units system is select all physical constants are considered to be equal to one. Currently, only these two units systems ("KcalMol_A" and "None") are available, but new units systems can be added [235].

6.6.3 Types

In certain cases, particles can be **grouped** based on their mass, charge, etc. In this case, it is said that they belong to a certain **type** of particles. Therefore, instead of assigning certain properties to each particle, we can associate it with a *type* and have its properties inherent from it. The "Types" entry allows for the selection of particle types for use in the simulation. Choosing a specific type enables certain characteristics to be assigned to each particle. `UAMMD-structured` currently incorporates only one class of particle *type*, known as "Basic". When this type is selected, user can define particle types and specify their mass, radius, and charge. The example (Code 6.6) shows how three particle types, "A", "B", and "C", are defined, all of them with the same mass and radius but different charge. These values are interpreted according to the units system, with mass in Dalton, radius in Angstrom, and charge in multiples of the electron charge, for this example (AKMA units). Importantly, this section defines available types, but the association between types and particles is performed in other input sections, the "structure" section within *Topology*.

6.6.4 Ensemble

Many of the physical processes of interest do not occur in a vacuum but rather under specific conditions, such as a predetermined volume or temperature. The set of these global variables is commonly referred to as **ensemble**.

The *Ensemble DataEntry* in `UAMMD-structured` is where the ensemble for a simulation is selected. Defining the ensemble involves setting certain macroscopic variables of the system. For example, if we choose the NVT ensemble, we can then fix the temperature and volume (simulation box, which is periodic by default) of the simulation.

However, sometimes the options available under the ensemble category are stretched to include global variables that typically would not be categorized as ensembles in scientific literature. An example within `UAMMD-structured` is the `NVTλ` ensemble. In addition to defining the volume and temperature, this ensemble also specifies the parameter λ . This parameter is employed in techniques like **Thermodynamic Integration** (TI) [242].

6.7 State

In the *State section*, the simulation is initialized by adding particles. Particle properties, such as initial position or velocity, can also be specified independently for each particle. It is mandatory to assign each particle an **identifier** (`Id`) and a position. The `Id` serves as a unique tag for each particle, enabling their identification throughout the simulation for tracking purposes.

In defining the particles present in the simulation, specifying an *Id*, *position*, and possibly other properties is equivalent to creating a particle. In the following example of *State*, when defining a particle, we assign it a position and a velocity (Code 6.7).

Code 6.7: State Example

```
state:
  labels: ["id", "position", "velocity"]
  data:
    - [0, [1.6, 2.7, 3.3], [0.1, -1.8, 2.3]]
    - [1, [2.5, -3.7, -1.9], [-1.2, 3.7, 1.1]]
    - [2, [-3.3, 1.0, 2.1], [-3.2, 1.3, -2.6]]
    # ...
  # ...
```

An important available property is *direction*, which defines the orientation of a particle in space. UAMMD-structured incorporates various potentials, such as *patchy particles* (Chapter 3), which require the definition of this property. *Direction* is specified using quaternions, which can be understood as a set of four numbers equivalent to a rotation [142]. When a quaternion (direction) is assigned to a particle, it is represented as $q = [q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3]$, which corresponds to the rotation matrix:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - 2q_2^2 - 2q_3^2 & 2q_1q_2 - 2q_0q_3 & 2q_1q_3 + 2q_0q_2 \\ 2q_1q_2 + 2q_0q_3 & 1 - 2q_1^2 - 2q_3^2 & 2q_2q_3 - 2q_0q_1 \\ 2q_1q_3 - 2q_0q_2 & 2q_2q_3 + 2q_0q_1 & 1 - 2q_1^2 - 2q_2^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.1)$$

To employ this information in encapsulating the orientation of the particle, we assume the particle carries a co-moving reference frame. To express the orientation of this frame, the laboratory reference system is used. Thus, the co-moving reference system can be described as a rotation of the laboratory reference system, this rotation is given by 6.1.

Figure 6.4: Particle orientation is encapsulated as a quaternion

In some cases, properties like mass or charge may vary significantly between particles, making it impossible to express them uniformly through types. Hence, these properties can also be defined within the *State* section. If mass or charge are specified in both *State* and *Types*, the values in *State* take precedence. This flexibility allows us to specify the characteristics of individual particles.

6.8 Integrators

Once the initial state of the simulation has been established through *State*, the next step is to determine how this state evolves. This is accomplished using integrators. In `UAMMD-structured`, integrators are the elements responsible for updating the state of the particles. Although other algorithms, like Monte Carlo, can be implemented, our focus here is on molecular dynamics integrators. Generally, these integrators evolve the state of the system over time by computing properties such as forces or torques, which are then used to determine the position (and orientation) of the particles at subsequent simulation steps. The selection of the integrator(s) and the number of integration steps required, are specified by the type of input given in code 6.8.

Code 6.8: Integrator Example

```

integrators:
  bbk1:
    parameters:
      frictionConstant: 1.0
      timeStep: 0.00001
    type: ["Langevin", "BBK"]
  bbk2:
    parameters:
      frictionConstant: 1.0
      timeStep: 0.001
    type: ["Langevin", "BBK"]
  schedule:
    data:
      - [1, "bbk1", 10000]
      - [2, "bbk2", 1000000]
    labels: ["order", "integrator", "steps"]
    type: ["Schedule", "Integrator"]
# ...

```

The integrators section must include an additional `DataEntry` of type `["Schedule", "Integrator"]`. This entry sets the sequence and the number of steps for each integrator. The integrators of the simulation are first defined (e.g., two Langevin integrators of the BBK subtype in the current example), followed by specifying their execution order and the number of steps in the schedule.

This ordered execution is particularly beneficial for certain processes such as equilibration. For example, in thermalization, an integrator with a smaller "dt" might be used initially for a few steps, followed by a longer period using an integrator with a larger "dt". This approach is also advantageous in fluid dynamics scenarios, where a Langevin integrator can first equilibrate the system, followed by a fluid integrator for analyzing dynamic properties.

UAMMD-structured implements integrators commonly used in coarse-grained model simulations, including a Langevin dynamics integrator, specifically one that implements the BBK method [243–245]. It also includes Brownian dynamics integrators, including the Brownian dynamics integrator for rigid bodies [246]. This integrator is needed for simulations of oriented particles such as in lipid models [42] (Chapter 4) or patchy particles [247] (Chapter 3). Additionally, UAMMD-structured includes integrators not intended for molecular dynamics but used for generating initial positions. Sometimes when a system is generated, certain particles are placed in such a way that they cause a steric clash. To resolve this, we can employ certain algorithms that eliminate these clashes by slightly modifying the positions of the particles, particularly UAMMD-structured implements the *steepest descent* which places the system in a local energy minimum.

UAMMD stands out with its wide array of integrators, addressing various simulation levels from the microscopic to the hydrodynamic. At the microscopic level, the dynamics are governed by Newtonian equations of motion, with Molecular Dynamics simulations implemented using the velocity Verlet scheme [248]. This level deals with the positions and momenta of all particles, covering scales of up to hundreds of nanometers and nanoseconds. For Langevin dynamics, which represents the dynamics of solute particles in a thermal bath, UAMMD incorporates integrators like the Gronbech-Jensen integrator [249], Dissipative Particle Dynamics [250], and Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics [251]. The hydrodynamic level in UAMMD replaces individual solvent particles with fluctuating hydrodynamic fields, using the Immersed Boundary method [252] for fluctuating hydrodynamics, effective for minimal resolution particles (blobs) [230, 253]. UAMMD offers both compressible [230, 253, 254] and incompressible hydrodynamic schemes, the latter using pseudo-spectral schemes and GPU-adapted Fast Fourier Transforms. At the Brownian level, UAMMD deals with the dynamics of solute particles with small inertia, solving Brownian Dynamics with and without hydrodynamic interactions. It includes various tools for handling complex operations associated with these simulations, like the Cholesky [255] and Lanczos [256] methods for calculating the noise-related square mobility matrix. Finally, UAMMD also incorporates integrators for specific boundary conditions, such as Quasi2D [257] for doubly periodic slices of fluid and double periodic Stokes [225] for integrating hydrodynamic interactions in slabs. These integrators allow for efficient simulation of complex systems under varied boundary conditions.

All these integrators can be used through `UAMMD-structured`, which for these types of integrators acts merely as a wrapper to certain functions of `UAMMD`. They can be added in the integrators section, the types and parameters can be consulted in the online documentation [235]. Furthermore, the simplicity of using these integrators, combined with the extensive range of interactions that can be added, makes `UAMMD-structured` an immensely useful tool for research in soft matter, enabling researchers to conduct complex and detailed simulations with ease.

6.9 Topology

In the *Global section*, we establish the general conditions of the simulation, setting aspects like the units, particle types, and the ensemble. In the *State DataEntry*, we introduce particles and define some of their properties, such as position and orientation. The *Integrators section* is then used to determine the evolution of these particles over time. At this stage, the information input is quite generic, and without further detail, all systems would appear similar. The key to **differentiating and detailing a unique physical system** lies in the *Topology section*.

The *Topology section* is where we define the properties of particles that remain constant throughout the simulation, including their type or position within the structure, and the interactions that take place in the system. *Topology section* consists of a `DataEntry`, called *structure*, that specifies types and the structural information (this is where its name comes from), and a `section` named *force field* for detailing the interactions (Code 6.9).

Code 6.9: Topology Example

```
topology:
  structure:
    # ...
  forceField:
    # ...
# ...
```

6.9.1 Structure

In many simulations, particles are characterized by specific features, rather than being anonymous entities. As explained in Sec. 6.6.3, each particle is part of a broader category defined by its *type*. Additionally, in numerous systems, **each particle holds a specific position within the structure to which it belongs**.

Certain coarse grained models of proteins employ potentials for the interaction of two beads belonging to different proteins (inter) different from those used for the interaction between beads of the same protein (intra) (Chapter 1). In this type of system the particles need to be classified according to the structure or substructure they belong to. This categorization process is handled in the *structure* `DataEntry`. Here, every particle must be assigned a type, which fix the values of some particle properties such as mass, charge, and radius (depending on the selected type style, Sec. 6.6.3). Assigning a *type* is compulsory, in addition, additional structural details can also be provided (Code 6.10).

Code 6.10: Structure Example

```

topology:
  structure:
    labels: ["id", "type", "modelId"]
    data:
      - [0, "A", 0]
      - [1, "A", 0]
      - [2, "A", 1]
      - [3, "A", 1]
      # ...
  forceField:
    # ...
# ...

```

UAMMD-structured uses a hierarchical classification system inherited from protein notation. In this system, particles are organized into residues ("**resId**"), chains ("**chainId**") and models ("**modelId**"). These additional data do not modify the particles themselves, but can be used to define particular interactions at different structural levels, e.g., two particles may interact with one type of potential if they belong to the same model, but with a different one if they are located in distinct models. In this example, each particle is assigned not just a type, such as "A", but is also linked to a specific model. For instance, particles 0 and 1 are part of model 0, while particles 2 and 3 belong to model 1. This configuration enables the calculation of unique potentials between particles from different models. Assigning both type and structural information it is necessary to use the particle identifier, "id".

The ability of UAMMD-structured to define interactions on various hierarchical levels, based on the type and structural position of particles, makes it a highly effective tool for simulating coarse-grained models [258], some of them discussed in Chapter 1.

6.9.2 Force Field

To fully customize our system, we have to specify the types of interactions that take place. The *force field* section is where the interactions present in the simulation are defined. These interactions vary based on the number of particles involved, their nature, among other factors. In this section, different `DataEntries` are incorporated, each representing an interaction. We can also introduce certain `DataEntries` that activate not interactions per se, rather specific data structures used by the interactions (Code 6.11).

Code 6.11: Force field Example

```
topology:
  structure:
    # ...
  forceField:
    interaction1:
      # ...
    interaction2:
      # ...
    interaction3:
      # ...
    # ...
```

The wide variety of available interactions, along with the numerous different integration schemes, are the two cornerstones of `UAMMD/UAMMD-structured`. When we refer to "interaction," we are discussing a broad concept: an interaction is a specific way to group particles before evaluating a potential on them. For instance, in a bonding interaction, one might assess a harmonic potential or a Morse potential. For short-range non-bonded interactions, a potential like Lennard-Jones might be used. In the case of external interactions, a potential from an electric field or a surface could be applied. We will examine them in detail in the following sections (Sec 6.11,6.12,6.13, ...), offering examples of the available potentials when describing an interaction.

6.10 Simulation Steps

So far, we have shown several ways to configure the elements that make up the simulation. However, running such simulations in their current form would cause our calculations to produce no output. *Arguably, the most important aspect of conducting a simulation is the extraction and analysis of data from it.* To access this data, we utilize **simulation steps**. In essence, a *simulation step* is a function that is executed

periodically, granting access to the complete simulation information. This capability allows us to process and output specific data, either by saving it to a file or displaying it on screen. Importantly, simulation steps are not just passive data handlers. They can actively modify the variables of the simulation, enabling the implementation of various scenarios and dynamic adjustments during the simulation.

The following example illustrates the addition of three distinct simulation steps. The first step, labeled "info", serves to display key simulation data like velocity (steps per second) or remaining time. The second, "saveState", records the state of the simulation, particularly the position of the particles, into a binary DCD-format file. This format is widely recognized in simulation analysis software, facilitating further trajectory analysis. The third step, "thermodynamicMeasurement", tracks certain thermodynamic variables, such as energy or temperature. Each of these steps includes an "intervalStep" parameter, a standard feature across all *simulation steps* that dictates the frequency of which each step is executed (Code 6.12).

Code 6.12: Simulation Step Example

```
simulationStep:
  info:
    type: ["UtilsStep", "InfoStep"]
    parameters:
      intervalStep: 10000
  saveState:
    type: ["WriteStep", "WriteStep"]
    parameters:
      intervalStep: 100000
      outputPath: "output"
      outputFormat: "dcd"
  thermodynamicMeasurement:
    type: ["ThermodynamicMeasure", "ThermodynamicQuantityMeasure"]
    parameters:
      intervalStep: 10000
      outputPath: "thermo.dat"
# ...
```

There are numerous types of simulation steps available, catering to diverse needs. For instance, the "[WriteStep, WriteStep]" type, as exemplified above, is used for saving simulation states in various formats such as DCD, XYZ, PDB, LAMMPSTRJ, etc.

Using *simulation steps* we are able to not only to measure specific observables, like energy distributions or unique experiments such as AFM indentation curves, but also to implement a wide array of algorithms. These steps go beyond mere data collection, enabling modifications to the simulation state itself. This functionality is particularly needed for executing complex algorithms,

such as **Thermodynamic Integration** (TI) which is a fundamental tool for free energy evaluation [242]. We will illustrate how a *simulation step* can be used to provide a protocol for the TI scheme. In TI, the objective is to compute the average derivative of a potential energy function $U(\lambda)$ with respect to a parameter λ , as represented by:

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial U(\lambda)}{\partial \lambda} \right\rangle_{\lambda} \quad (6.2)$$

This calculation extends across various λ values within the $[0, 1]$ interval. The aim is to determine the free energy change, $\Delta F(A \rightarrow B)$, by integrating the above quantity over λ :

$$\Delta F(A \rightarrow B) = \int_0^1 \left\langle \frac{\partial U(\lambda)}{\partial \lambda} \right\rangle_{\lambda} d\lambda \quad (6.3)$$

To perform the TI, we must first select the suitable potentials, these potentials depend on the λ parameter, through this parameter (which takes values between 0 and 1) the potentials are turned on or off. `UAMMD-structured` provides these potentials for bonds and pairwise interactions [259]. The simulation uses the $NVT\lambda$ ensemble, defining a global λ parameter. By selecting the right simulation step, ["ThermodynamicMeasure", "ThermodynamicIntegration"], the process is set in motion. This *simulation step* takes as parameter the different values of λ interval $[1, \dots, 0]$. The algorithm then computes the derivative in equation 6.2 and records the results for subsequent integration, as show in Eq.6.3.

In addition, `UAMMD-structured` includes *simulation steps* for computing correlations or certain system properties, such as the moment of inertia or the position of the center of mass. Calculating pair-defined properties, like the pairwise force matrix (f_{ij} for potential-induced force), is particularly challenging on GPUs due to their parallel nature. Standard GPU functions tend to focus on computing the total force on a particle (f_i), since each GPU thread is usually linked to a specific particle. `UAMMD-structured` addresses this by implementing a feature that allows the computation of such pairwise matrices, needed for many coarse-grained parametrization algorithms [6], and the Hessian matrix, relevant for analyses like normal mode analysis [260]. Notably, a *simulation step* is available for calculating stress on each particle [261].

A complete list of all the simulation steps, as well as a detailed guide on how to add new ones, can be found in the online documentation [235].

6.11 Bonded Interactions

Bonded interactions are a specific type of interactions that are applied to a predefined set of particles, identified by their IDs, and remain constant throughout the simulation. These interactions are used to model a wide range of phenomena, the most paradigmatic being two particles connected by, for example, a harmonic bond. This means that two particles, which we identify using their IDs i and j , are interacting with a potential of the type $U(r) = \frac{1}{2}K(r - r_0)^2$, where $r = |\mathbf{r}_{ij}| = |\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|$ and K and r_0 are the spring constant and the equilibrium distance respectively, which are the characteristic parameters of the potential. `UAMMD-structured` offers a variety of these types of interactions, which are categorized based on the number of particles involved in the bond.

Often, we want to apply specific potentials to one particle only. In these cases, we indicate the ID of the particle. This type of bond is encompassed under the type "Bond1" (Code 6.13).

Code 6.13: Bonds Example 1

```

topology:
  forceField:
    # ...
    bond1_example:
      type: ["Bond1", "FixedHarmonic"]
      labels: ["id_i", "K", "r0", "position"]
      data:
        - [0, 1.5, 0.0, [0.1, 2.3, 5.8]]
        - [1, 2.5, 0.0, [2.2, 0.3, 0.6]]
        - [2, 1.3, 0.0, [1.1, 3.5, 0.9]]
        - [3, 2.1, 0.0, [0.5, 1.1, 1.7]]
    # ...
  # ...

```

In the example, certain particles identified by their IDs 0, 1, 2, 3 are subjected to a potential of the type:

$$U(\mathbf{r}_i) = \frac{1}{2}K(|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{pos}| - r_0)^2 \quad (6.4)$$

Where `pos` represents a specific position in space. This potential is commonly used to fix the position of particles in space. In addition to this potential, "Bond1" also allows us to apply forces or torques to specific particles. There is also a version of potential 6.4 where each term is multiplied by the parameter λ^2 of TI, enabling us to use these types of potentials to calculate free energy differences between different particle configurations.

Possibly the most common bonds within this category are those involving two particles. These types of interactions are frequently used in modeling systems (Code 6.14).

Code 6.14: Bonds Example 2

```

topology:
  forceField:
    # ...
    bond2_example1:
      type: ["Bond2", "Harmonic"]
      labels: ["id_i", "id_j", "K", "r0"]
      data:
        - [5, 6, 2.1, 0.2]
        - [6, 7, 2.6, 1.2]
        - [7, 8, 3.2, 3.8]
    bond2_example2:
      type: ["Bond2", "FeneCommon_K_R0"]
      parameters:
        K: 3.2
        R0: 4.0
      labels: ["id_i", "id_j", "r0"]
      data:
        - [8, 9, 11.3]
        - [9, 10, 1.5]
        - [10, 11, 2.8]
    # ...
  # ...
# ...

```

The example demonstrates the application of both a harmonic potential and a FENE potential [262]. In the latter case, the "FeneCommon_K_R0" version uses shared parameters K and R_0 for all bonds, specified in the "parameters" field. Such variations of potentials are common in UAMMD-structured, aiming to simplify the input. The list of available potentials under the "Bond2" category is extensive and can be consulted in the online documentation [235]. To name a few, Morse potentials [263] are available, as well as Lennard-Jones potentials used in coarse-grained models for proteins (1.1). This context also includes potentials for mimicking the effects of hydrophobic interactions [61]. Moreover, there are versions of the harmonic potential modified with the λ parameter, enabling their use in TI.

Finally, there are also the "Bond3" and "Bond4" categories, involving 3 and 4 particles, respectively. These categories implement potentials that involve certain angles. For "Bond3", if it consists of three particles i, j, k , with j being the central particle, then the potential depends on the angle formed by vectors $\mathbf{r}_{ji} = r_i - r_j$ and $\mathbf{r}_{jk} = r_j - r_k$, where $\cos \theta = \frac{\mathbf{r}_{ji} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{jk}}{|\mathbf{r}_{ji}| |\mathbf{r}_{jk}|}$.

Hence, we can define potentials such as $U(\theta) = \frac{1}{2}K(\theta - \theta_0)^2$, which we refer to as "HarmonicAngular" in the following example (Code 6.15).

Code 6.15: Bonds Example 3

```

topology:
  forceField:
    # ...
    bond3_example:
      type: ["Bond3", "HarmonicAngular"]
      labels: ["id_i", "id_j", "id_k", "K", "theta0"]
      data:
        - [12, 13, 14, 1.32, 1.15]
        - [13, 14, 15, 3.13, 0.53]
    bond4_example:
      type: ["Bond4", "Dihedral"]
      labels: ["id_i", "id_j", "id_k", "id_l", "n", "K", "phi0"]
      data:
        - [16, 17, 18, 19, 1, 43.2, 0.1]
    # ...

```

The example also adds a dihedral potential. This potential takes the form $U(\phi) = K(1 + \cos(\phi - \phi_0))$, where ϕ denotes the dihedral angle. This potential is categorized in "Bond4" interactions, which involve four particles labeled i, j, k, l . The dihedral angle in this context is defined by the angle between the planes formed by the particles i, j, k and j, k, l . UAMMD-structured has implemented a range of such potentials, commonly used in coarse-grained modeling [235]. These potentials, angular and dihedral, play a crucial role in coarse-grained models, aiding in the establishment of equilibrium configurations and accounting for fluctuations (Section 1.1.1). An application of these potentials, where parameters are tuned to accurately reflect structural and dynamic properties, can be seen in the MADna model for DNA [32] (section 1.1.2).

Although the types of interactions (and some of the potentials) mentioned were available in UAMMD, they have undergone a complete reimplementaion to ensure compatibility with the input system of UAMMD-structured, and to streamline the process of integrating new potentials. This is particularly pertinent for dihedral potentials, which require careful handling due to stability issues related to the definition of dihedral angles. The new implementation follows the methodologies outlined in [264], with the GPU algorithm implementation following the approach detailed in [225]. The framework now allows for the introduction of new categories involving more particles with relative ease. Additionally, the process for adding new potentials within each existing category has been simplified, with guidance for this process provided in Sec. 6.21.1.

6.12 Short Range Interactions

Short-range interactions are employed for modeling a wide range of physical phenomena. The Lennard-Jones potential, for example, is extensively used to simulate interactions between uncharged particles [120]. Moreover, the Debye-Hückel potential plays a critical role in modeling charged particles within saline solutions [120, 133]. These potentials, while grounded in physical concepts, are also employed as conceptual models. They are often used to hypothesize about the nature of the studied phenomena, particularly when the exact physical underpinnings are not well-defined. This approach is exemplified by the Lennard-Jones potential, which is employed to represent particles with steric interactions and short-range attractive forces [35]. Additionally, it serves as a foundational model, frequently modified to introduce other effects [61, 90], showcasing its versatility as a fundamental tool in physical system modeling (Chapter 1).

Figure 6.5: Lennard-Jones Potential (Left) and Debye-Hückel Potential (Right). These potentials are characterized by rapid decay, qualifying them as short-range potentials.

While multi-body short-range potentials are more general (naturally resulting from exact coarse graining theory [6]) and used in some applications [265], this discussion focuses on two-body (pairwise) potentials. The application of a truncation to these potentials leads to the definition of a cutoff radius r_{cut} , where $U(r) = 0$ for all $r > r_{\text{cut}}$. The choice of r_{cut} is potential-specific and often depends on the parameters within the model. For instance, with the Lennard-Jones potential, a typical cutoff radius is $r_{\text{cut}} = 2.5\sigma$, balancing computational efficiency with physical accuracy.

From a computational standpoint, short-range potentials offer several advantages. In contrast to long-range potentials, where the interaction of a particle with all others must be calculated, short-range interactions simplify computations significantly.

Generally, there are three main approaches to computing long-range interactions: *N-body* approaches [266], *Ewald summation* [267], and the *fast multipole method* [268], among others [269]. The first two are implemented in UAMMD [13] and in particular Ewald summation is used for computing electrostatic interactions that will be introduced later. However, a common trait among these methods is their relatively high computational cost, exceeding $\mathcal{O}(N)$. In contrast, for short-range interactions, it is possible to construct structures, commonly referred to as **neighbor lists**, which significantly reduce computational complexity to an $\mathcal{O}(N)$ level. These neighbor lists efficiently manage the interactions between particles by only considering those within a predetermined distance. This approach ensures that only the most relevant interactions are computed, thereby saving computational resources and time. This efficiency is particularly advantageous in simulations involving a large number of particles, where every reduction in computational load can lead to significantly faster and more efficient simulations.

In our context, we introduce **neighbor lists**, *neighbor lists are understood as structures that enable access to all neighbors of a given particle*. Specifically, for a particle i , these lists include particles j for which the condition $\text{distance}(i, j) < r_{\text{neighbors}}$ holds, with $r_{\text{neighbors}} \geq r_{\text{cut}}$. This criterion ensures that all the particles within the interaction range defined by the cutoff radius r_{cut} are included in this list.

Various algorithms exist for constructing neighbor lists in computational simulations. The straightforward approach would involve calculating the distances between all particle pairs and then, for each particle i , assembling a list of neighbors comprising those particles j that lie within a distance less than r_{cut} . However, this method is computationally expensive, characterized by a $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ complexity, akin to the traditional N-body approach.

To optimize this process, more efficient algorithms have been developed, one of which is the **cell list** method [266]. This method hinges on subdividing the simulation space into a grid of cells. The number of cells in each dimension α (where α includes x , y , and z dimensions) is determined by dividing the simulation volume length, L_α , by the cutoff radius, r_{cut} , and taking the floor value: $n_\alpha = \text{floor}(L_\alpha/r_{\text{cut}})$. Consequently, the total number of cells is given by $N_{\text{cells}} = n_x \cdot n_y \cdot n_z$.

Figure 6.6: Example of a two-dimensional cell list. In this example, the size of each cell is $w \approx r_{cut}$. When determining the neighboring particles of a certain target particle (the blue particle in the figure), we only check those particles that are located in the same cell as the evaluated particle and in the neighboring cells (within the dashed blue square in the figure). Particles that are not found in these cells (the red particles in the figure) are not considered as candidates, which greatly reduces the compilation time. Of the particles we check, only those that are located at a distance less than r_{cut} (the green particles in the figure) are considered neighbors, so the remainder particles in the neighbor cells (orange particles in the figure) are not considered when the potential is computed.

In this cell list approach, each particle is assigned to the cell it occupies in space. The neighbor list for a particle i is then constructed by examining particles j not only in the same cell as i but also in adjacent cells, respecting periodic boundary conditions. A particle j is added to the neighbor list of i if the distance $\text{distance}(i, j)$ is less than r_{cut} . This approach drastically reduces the number of distance computations. Assuming a uniform distribution of particles, the average number of particles per cell is $N_{ppc} = N/N_{cells}$. In a 3D space, each cell interacts with its own and the 26 adjacent cells, leading to an average of $N_{checks} = 27 \cdot N_{ppc} = 27 \cdot N/N_{cells}$ distance checks per particle, a significant reduction from the N^2 checks required by the direct pairwise comparison method.

Although the cell list method considerably lowers computational complexity, it does have limitations, particularly in GPU-based implementations [266]. While in CPU implementations, the linked cell approach allows for dynamic updating of cells as particles move [267], the GPU requires a complete reconstruction of the list at each integration step due to the simultaneous movement of all particles. This need for continual reconstruction introduces additional computational overhead.

To efficiently manage the need for frequent reconstruction of neighbor lists in simulations, the **Verlet list** approach is employed [13, 267]. The key principle of Verlet lists is to minimize the continuous rebuilding of these lists. This objective is achieved by creating a neighbor list with an enlarged radius, termed the Verlet radius, r_{Verlet} , which is larger than the cutoff radius, r_{cut} . As a result, the neighbor list constructed using r_{Verlet} remains valid for the interactions within the range of r_{cut} . In essence, for every particle i , all other particles j that satisfy the condition $\text{distance}(i, j) < r_{\text{cut}}$ are included in the neighbor list of i . This inclusion holds as long as no particle travels beyond a distance greater than r_{max} from its initial position when the list was generated. The distance r_{max} is defined as follows:

$$r_{\text{max}} = (r_{\text{Verlet}} - r_{\text{cut}})/2 \quad (6.5)$$

Figure 6.7: Initially, two particles lie outside the neighbor list of each other, separated by the Verlet distance r_{Verlet} , which is greater than the cutoff radius r_{cut} . Over time, if they move closer such that their separation is less than r_{cut} , they should be included in neighbor list of each other for interaction calculations. The maximum allowable movement without updating the Verlet list is $r_{\text{max}} = (r_{\text{Verlet}} - r_{\text{cut}})/2$, ensuring all potential interactions are accounted for within the simulation timeframe.

This particular distance is calculated based on the worst-case scenario, as illustrated in Fig 6.7. Here, two particles initially distanced at r_{Verlet} and therefore not in neighbor lists of each other, start moving towards one another in opposite directions. After some time, their distance diminishes to r_{cut} , at which point their interaction becomes relevant, necessitating their inclusion in the neighbor lists of each other. The total distance traversed by the particles in this scenario is $r_{\text{Verlet}} - r_{\text{cut}}$,

and consequently, each particle travels a distance given by equation 6.5. Since we cannot conclusively determine whether this situation will occur, the Verlet list must be reconstructed whenever a particle moves the distance defined by 6.5.

In summary, we generate the cell list for a radius larger than the cutoff radius, denoted as r_{Verlet} (note that we use cell lists, but other algorithms could be used for constructing the neighbor list; the Verlet list is an algorithm to trigger the list reconstruction, not for the construction itself). Each time we update the positions of the particles, we check if they have moved a distance greater than r_{max} compared to the position when the list was built. If so, we reconstruct the list.

The key parameter in Verlet lists is the Verlet radius, r_{Verlet} . As we increase the radius, we also increase the number of particles we need to check when evaluating an interaction. Conversely, we can perform more updates before needing to reconstruct the list. Therefore, the efficiency of this approach depends quite a bit on the specific system; its density, diffusion, etc.

Let us now consider how Verlet lists behave for certain types of potentials, specifically examining their behavior for certain coarse-grained models [35, 36, 112]. We will use a protein model as an example, but the principles can be generalized to many other cases. In these models, it is common to employ different types of interactions for particles within the same structure “*intra*” interactions and those involving interactions between particles from different structures, “*inter*” interactions,¹ (Chapter 1). This situation is depicted in Fig 6.8.

The approach combining cell lists and Verlet lists encounters challenges in handling these types of interactions. The feasible solution involves evaluating each interaction to determine the appropriate potential. This process, particularly on GPUs, faces difficulties due to the SIMD architecture [225, 241]. It causes significant divergence in the code, adversely affecting performance. Furthermore, this approach limits the reusability of interactions because it requires the implementation of distinct potentials for each specific scenario. For instance, consider a scenario where the *inter* interactions are modeled using a Lennard-Jones potential, and the *intra* interactions employ a WCA-type potential. In such a case, it becomes essential to define a unified potential capable of appropriately applying either the Lennard-Jones or WCA interaction, based on the particle pairs (*intra/inter*). Ideally, implementing a versatile potential system that allows for selective application to various particle pairs would be more efficient, reducing the need for extensive coding.

¹By a common misuse of language, the terms “intramolecular” and “intermolecular” are often employed, even when not dealing with molecules per se

Figure 6.8: Coarse-grained models with three copies of a protein (GFP), each colored differently. Interactions involving particles of the same color (same structure) engage with a different potential than those involving particles of different colors (different structures).

6.12.1 Conditional Verlet lists: definition

To address these challenges, we have developed **conditioned Verlet lists**. This algorithm allows us to generate a set of neighbor lists, ensuring that each pair within these lists meets certain predefined conditions. We will discuss the algorithm in detail in a dedicated section later, but for now, let us describe it in general terms and explain how to use the different lists. This approach enables us to create multiple Verlet lists from a single cell list. Let us consider the previous example: our goal is to generate two lists, one for *intra* conditions and another for *inter* conditions (noting that in this case, the conditions are mutually exclusive, although the algorithm is applicable to more general conditions). To determine which structure each particle belongs to, we must set the "modelId" variable for each particle. This is done in the *structure* section; if two particles have the same "modelId," they belong to the same structure; if they differ, they belong to different structures. In this example, we are working with "modelId", but other identifiers like "resId" or "chainId" could also be used. This allows us to define the use of one potential or another based on the hierarchy in the structure of the interacting particles.

The algorithm operates similarly to the Verlet list approach. In the Verlet list, we construct a cell list with a Verlet radius $r_{\text{Verlet}} > r_{\text{cut}}$ and reconstruct the list when particles move a distance greater than r_{max} from their position at the time of list construction. The construction of conditioned Verlet lists starts similarly by building the cell list. However, instead of creating a single list, we construct multiple lists depending on whether certain conditions are met. For example, for particle i , we iterate over particles in the same cell and neighboring cells, denoted as j . Then, for each pair (i, j) , we iterate over possible conditions, such as *intra* and *inter* in our case, and if any condition is satisfied, we add particle j to the neighbor list of particle i that fulfills that condition. At the end of the process, we obtain a Verlet list for each condition. The rest of the procedure remains the same. If a particle moves more than r_{max} , we repeat the process and reconstruct the lists.

Various sets of conditions are available for selection. As a first example of the input format, we will use the "all" condition, where all particles within the Verlet radius are considered for the list, with no additional conditions applied. This condition generates a result similar to the traditional Verlet list, i.e., it only generates a single neighbor list: the "all" list. In the following example, we demonstrate how to select this list and apply a Lennard-Jones potential and a Debye-Hückel potential (Code 6.16).

Code 6.16: Short range Example

```

topology:
  structure:
    # ...
  forceField:
    nl:
      type: ["VerletConditionalListSet", "all"]
      parameters:
        cutOffVerletFactor: 1.2
    LennardJones:
      type: ["NonBonded", "LennardJonesType2"]
      labels: ["name_i", "name_j", "epsilon", "sigma"]
      data:
        - ["A", "A", 1.4, 1.5]
      parameters:
        condition: "all"
        cutOffFactor: 2.5
    DebyeHuckel:
      type: ["NonBonded", "DebyeHuckel"]
      parameters:
        condition: "all"
        cutOffFactor: 1.2
        debyeLength: 2.3
        dielectricConstant: 80.0
    # ...

```

In our input configuration, it is important to note that the sequence of elements does not affect the outcome. We start by defining a conditioned Verlet list, which we label as "nl," and select the subtype "all." This action specifies our choice of the "all" condition. Following this, the "all" condition is consistently applied to the potentials, indicating that both the Lennard-Jones and Debye-Hückel potentials will be applicable to all neighbor pairs within their respective cutoff ranges.

Each potential has its unique way of determining its cutoff radius. For the Lennard-Jones potential, the cutoff is calculated using $r_{\text{cut}} = \sigma_{\text{max}} \times \text{cutOffFactor}$, where σ_{max} represents the highest sigma value in the potential, with a value of 1.5 in this example. On the other hand, the cutoff for the Debye-Hückel potential is determined as $r_{\text{cut}} = \lambda_D \times \text{cutOffFactor}$, with λ_D being the Debye length.

The selection of the Verlet radius for the "nl" list is based on the following formula:

$$r_{\text{Verlet}} = \max(r_{\text{cut}}) \times \text{cutOffVerletFactor} \quad (6.6)$$

This formula means that the Verlet radius is set to the maximum value among the cutoff radii of the potentials using the Verlet list, multiplied by a predefined factor specified in the parameters. This setup allows for the possibility of declaring multiple conditioned Verlet lists, each of which can be associated with different potentials.

In molecular dynamics, particularly in coarse-grained models, **exclusion lists** are a common feature. By using exclusion lists, we enumerate a set of particles j that can never be considered neighbors of particle i , regardless of their distance or any other conditions. This condition, the requirement of not being excluded, necessitates the specification of an exclusion list when selected.

In the following example (Code 6.17), we illustrate how to define two sets of conditioned Verlet lists, "vcl1" and "vcl2". The first set, "vcl1," is of the type "intra_inter." This means it generates two Verlet lists: one under the "intra" condition, where particles are assumed to have the same molecular index, and the other under the "inter" condition, where each pair of particles belongs to different models. The second set, "vcl2," is of the type "nonExclIntra_nonExclInter." This condition also creates two lists similar to the first (using the same names), but additionally considers the exclusion list indicated in the data section. In other words, the "inter" list will include pairs of particles that belong to different molecules and are not excluded from each other.

In this scenario, besides selecting the condition in the interactions, we must also specify which neighbor list we are referring to. This was not necessary in the previous example, as there was only one neighbor list, which by default was used for all "Short Range" interactions (Code 6.17).

Code 6.17: Conditional Verlet List Example

```
topology:
  structured:
    # ...
  forceField:
    # ...
  vcl1:
    type:["ConditionalVerletListSet","intra_inter"]
    parameters:
      cutOffVerletFactor: 1.5
  vcl2:
    type:["ConditionalVerletListSet","nonExclIntra_nonExclInter"]
    parameters:
      cutOffVerletFactor: 1.5
    labels: ["id", "id_list"]
    data:
      - [0, [1, 2, 3]]
      - [1, [0, 2, 3]]
      - [2, [0, 1, 3]]
      - [3, [0, 1, 2]]
      - # ...
    # ...
  interaction1:
    type:["NonBonded",...]
    parameters:
      neighbourList: "vcl1"
      condition: "inter"
    # ...
  interaction2:
    type:["NonBonded",...]
    parameters:
      neighbourList: "vcl2"
      condition: "intra"
    # ...
  # ...
  # ...
  # ...
  # ...
```

The complete list of available conditions for conditioned Verlet list sets, as well as the various lists they generate, can be found in the online documentation. Similarly, a list of the available potentials can also be located there. `UAMMD-structured` allows users to easily add more conditions and interactions [235].

Conditional Verlet Lists Set: implementation

In this section, we will explore how the set of conditioned Verlet lists is implemented. The algorithms discussed are designed for execution on a GPU. Each algorithm runs in a specific thread and is responsible for constructing the Verlet lists for a single particle. This approach follows the Thread Per Particle (TPP) scheme, where threads execute the algorithm concurrently. The design for GPU execution is crucial, as it aims to minimize divergent instructions across threads. This focus is essential because instruction divergence can significantly impact the performance of the GPU code. By ensuring more uniform execution across threads, these algorithms are optimized for the parallel processing capabilities of GPUs, enhancing computational efficiency and throughput.

To begin with, it is helpful to examine the algorithm for constructing a traditional Verlet list [13, 266]. The algorithm assumes the existence of a neighbor list, `NeigList`. This neighbor list is constructed using a cell list with the cell size set to the Verlet radius, the number of cells per dimension is $n_\alpha = \text{floor}(L_\alpha/r_{\text{Verlet}})$, where $\alpha = x, y, z$. Our goal is to build the Verlet list. To do this, we need to define two data structures: `VerletList` and `VerletListNgN`, in addition to the value `NgMax`.

The `VerletList` is a matrix (implemented as a continuous array [270, 271]). Its size is $N \times \text{NgMax}$, where `VerletList[i,k]` represents the k -th neighbor of particle i . `NgMax` is the maximum number of neighbors. The array `VerletListNgN` stores the number of neighbors for each particle. For instance, if `VerletListNgN[i] = n`, it means that particle i currently has n neighbors.

The algorithm to construct the Verlet list is given in Alg. 2. If an attempt to add a particle results in the list becoming saturated, exceeding the maximum allowed number of particles, the algorithm halts and sets the flag `tooManyNeigFlag = true`. This flag is checked on the CPU after the algorithm has finished processing for all particles. If the value of the flag is `true`, then `NgMax` is incremented by one, the necessary memory is allocated, and the algorithm is executed again. This iterative approach ensures that the Verlet list can dynamically adapt to accommodate the number of neighbors each particle has.

Algorithm 2 Construction of Verlet List

Require: VerletRadius.**Require:** $\text{dist}(i, j)$, returns the distance between particles i and j .**Require:** NeigList, NeigList[i] is a list containing all neighbors of i .**Require:** VerletList, the resulting Verlet List. VerletList[i, k], the k th neighbor of i .**Require:** VerletListNgN, VerletListNgN[i] is the number of neighbors of i .**Require:** NgMax, max. number of neighbour per particle the Verlet list can manage.**Require:** tooManyNeigFlag = false, if there is no space available in any of the lists this flag is set to true.

```

1:  $i \leftarrow$  Current particle index
2:  $n \leftarrow 0$  ▷ Particle  $i$  neighbor counter is initialized to 0
3: for  $j$  in NeigList[ $i$ ] do
4:   if  $j == i$  then
5:     continue ▷ Self interactions are not considered
6:   end if
7:   if  $n \geq \text{NgMax}$  then ▷ Check if current list is full
8:     tooManyNeigFlag  $\leftarrow$  true
9:     return
10:  end if
11:  if  $\text{dst}(i, j) < \text{VerletRadius}$  then
12:    VerletList[ $i, n$ ] =  $j$  ▷ Add new particle
13:    VerletListNgN[ $i$ ]  $\leftarrow n + 1$ 
14:     $n \leftarrow n + 1$ 
15:  end if
16: end for

```

To implement conditions, we need to modify the structure of the Verlet list, `VerletList`. This is replaced by a list of Verlet lists, known as the conditioned Verlet list set, `CondVerletListSet`. We also set the integer variable `nConditions`, which specifies the number of available conditioned lists, one for each condition. Therefore, `CondVerletListSet` is a list containing `nConditions` Verlet lists. Similarly, we define `CondVerletListNgN` as a list of size `nConditions`, where each element is a list of size N , storing the number of neighbors for each particle under different conditions. Each condition is associated with an integer starting from zero. Hence, `CondVerletListSet[c]` will be the neighbor list whose index is `c`, and similarly, `CondVerletListNgN[c][i]` will be the current number of neighbors for particle i that satisfy condition c . We also define a vector of booleans, `cond`, of size `nConditions`, where the result of the function `checkCondition(i, j, cond)` is stored. This function evaluates whether the conditions are met for particles i , j and stores the result in `cond`. The body of the function `checkCondition(i, j, cond)` is where we specify the conditions. This function has access to all the information of the simulation. For details on how it is defined and how it can be modified, we refer the reader to the online documentation [235]. Algorithm 3 shows how the conditioned Verlet lists for the conditions “intramolecular” and “intermolecular” would be constructed.

In this scenario, the function `conditionChecker(i, j, cond)` accesses the data from the `modelId` vector, where `modelId[i]` stores the model to which particle i belongs. Therefore, if `modelId[i] = modelId[j]`, then `cond[i] = true`; otherwise, `cond[i] = false`. This previous algorithm (Alg. 3) is easily generalized for an arbitrary `nConditions`, Alg. 4.

Finally, `UAMMD-structured` adds the option to use shared memory as a cache for conditioned Verlet lists [225, 241]. When we plan to reuse data, instead of accessing it through global memory, we can load it into shared memory for faster access. This is particularly beneficial when the data volume is relatively large. In cases where the data volume is not large, it is expected that the GPU itself will cache these data internally if it detects frequent access.

An application of this is seen in exclusion lists. Imagine we are evaluating the previous algorithm for particle i , and the condition involves checking whether particle j is on the exclusion list of i . Without going into details, the exclusion list is also a matrix where `exclusions[i][k]` represents the k -th particle excluded from i , and there is also an array `exclusionsN`, with `exclusionsN[i]` being the number of particles excluded for i . The function `conditionChecker(i, j, cond)` will access this array and iterate over it to determine if j is in `exclusions[i]`. This process is repeated for all particles j . Therefore, the array `exclusions[i]` is a prime candidate to be moved to shared memory, making data access more efficient.

Algorithm 3 Construction of “intramolecular” and “intermolecular” Verlet Lists

Require: VerletRadius.**Require:** $\text{dist}(i, j)$, returns the distance between particles i and j .**Require:** NeigList, NeigList[i] is a list containing all neighbors of i .**Require:** CondVerletListSet, CondVerletListNgN**Require:** nConditions = 2, number of conditions, 2, "intra" and "inter".**Require:** intraIdx = 0, index of “intramolecular” list in CondVerletListSet.

CondVerletListSet[intraIdx] = IntraVerletList

CondVerletListNgN[intraIdx] = IntraVerletNgN.

Require: interIdx = 1, index of “intermolecular” list in CondVerletListSet.

CondVerletListSet[intraIdx] = IntraVerletList

CondVerletListNgN[interIdx] = InterVerletNgN.

Require: cond, boolean array of size nConditions. If $\text{cond}[\text{intraIdx}] = \text{true}$ (false), "intra" condition is met (not met). If $\text{cond}[\text{interIdx}] = \text{true}$ (false), "inter" condition is met (not met).**Require:** checkCondition(i, j, cond), populates array cond according to whether i and j satisfy conditions intra or inter.**Require:** NgMax, maximum number of neighbour per particle any list can manage.**Require:** tooManyNeigFlag = false, if there is no space available in any of the lists this flag is set to true.

```

1:  $i \leftarrow$  Current particle index
2: for  $j$  in NeigList[ $i$ ] do
3:   if  $j == i$  then
4:     continue                                ▷ Self interactions are not considered
5:   end if
6:   if  $\text{dst}(i, j) < \text{VerletRadius}$  then
7:     conditionChecker( $i, j, \text{cond}$ )           ▷ Populate cond boolean array
8:     for condIdx = 0 to nConditions-1 do     ▷ Iterate over conditions
9:       if  $\text{cond}[\text{condIdx}]$  then
10:         $n \leftarrow \text{CondVerletListNgN}[\text{condIdx}][i]$ 
11:        if  $n \geq \text{NgMax}$  then                ▷ Check if current list is full
12:          tooManyNeigFlag  $\leftarrow$  true
13:          return
14:        end if
15:        CondVerletListSet[condIdx][ $i, n$ ] =  $j$     ▷ Add new particle
16:        CondVerletListNgN[condIdx][ $i$ ]  $\leftarrow n + 1$ 
17:      end if
18:    end for
19:  end if
20: end for

```

Algorithm 4 Generalized Construction of Verlet Lists for Multiple Conditions

Require: VerletRadius.

Require: $\text{dist}(i, j)$, returns the distance between particles i and j .

Require: NeigList, NeigList[i] is a list containing all neighbors of i .

Require: CondVerletListSet, CondVerletListNgN

Require: nConditions, number of conditions.

Require: Condition indices:

cond1Idx = 0

...

condNIdx = nConditions - 1

Then for CondVerletListSet we have:

CondVerletListSet[cond1Idx] = Cond1VerletList,

...

and for CondVerletListNgN:

CondVerletListNgN[cond1Idx] = Cond1VerletNgN,

...

Require: cond, boolean array of size nConditions.

If $\text{cond}[\text{cond1Idx}] = \text{true}$ (false), "cond1" is met (not met).

...

Require: checkCondition(i, j, cond), populates array **cond** according to whether i and j satisfy present conditions.

Require: NgMax, maximum number of neighbour per particle any list can manage.

Require: tooManyNeigFlag = false, if there is no space available in any of the lists this flag is set to true.

1: $i \leftarrow$ Current particle index

Execute similar steps as in Alg. 3

...

To facilitate this, the function `set(i, ...)` is added, which, like `conditionChecker(i, j, cond)`, can be customized as desired. This function is executed right after instruction 1: and allows access to a shared memory buffer to copy the desired data. This buffer is then accessible for `conditionChecker(i, j, cond)`. Note that this also requires configuring another function to inform the CUDA kernel of the amount of shared memory needed for the construction of the lists [225, 241]. In the case of exclusions, this function is tuned to copy the current particle exclusion list to shared memory.

6.13 Long range interactions

Long-range interactions are those that **do not diminish rapidly with distance**, unlike short-range interactions. Consequently, if we apply an arbitrary cutoff, ignoring these interactions beyond a certain distance, we risk neglecting significant contributions to the overall behavior of the system. This issue becomes more pronounced when using periodic boundary conditions (PBC), as we must consider the interactions of particles not only with others within the same simulation box but also with their images in the replicated boxes surrounding the original one.

In coarse-grained simulations of biological systems, the most important long-range interaction is the electrostatic interaction, described as:

$$U(r) = \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon r} \quad (6.7)$$

Here, q_i represents the charge of each particle, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, ϵ is the permittivity of the medium, and r is the distance between particles. In most coarse-grained models, this interaction is considered to be screened by the ions present in the solution, often employing the Debye-Huckel approximation. However, this approximation can significantly deviate from reality in certain regimes [120]. As a result, some models explicitly add ions and calculate the interaction between these ions and charged beads using 6.7 [34, 272]. To employ this interaction in `UAMMD-structured`, the following input is used (Code 6.18).

Code 6.18: Electrostatics interaction

```

topology:
  forceField:
    # ...
    electrostatics_example:
      type: ["LongRange", "Electrostatics"]
      parameters:
        epsilon: 80.0
    # ...
  # ...

```

In this setup, it is necessary to specify the value of ϵ (the value of ϵ_0 is set when selecting the unit system). The charges referred to are either those indicated by types or specified in *state*. The algorithm used here is the one implemented in `UAMMD` [13], described in [273, 274], and the function in `UAMMD-structured` acts as a wrapper to the implementation in `UAMMD`.

6.14 External interactions

In external interaction types, each particle is subjected to a potential. This approach allows for the modeling of a variety of scenarios (Code 6.19).

Code 6.19: External Example

```
topology:
  structure:
    # ...
  forceField:
    # ...
  external_example:
    type: ["External", "ConstantForce"]
    parameters:
      constantForce: [0.0, 0.0, 10.0]
  surface_example:
    type: ["Surface", "SurfaceWCAType2"]
    parameters:
      surfacePosition: 0.0
    labels: ["name", "epsilon", "sigma"]
    data:
      - ["A", 1.0, 2.5]
      - ["B", 1.5, 3.0]
    # ...
  # ...
# ...
```

As shown in the example, such interactions are effective for simulating external fields. The given example (Code 6.19) illustrates the application of a constant force, but options also exist for modeling external electric fields or oscillating magnetic fields. Additionally, these interactions can incorporate the effects of surfaces. UAMMD-structured offers a range of these interaction types [235].

The implementation process for these interactions is straightforward. In UAMMD-structured, the implementation is derived from the approach followed in UAMMD [13], tailored to align with input system of UAMMD-structured.

6.15 Many body bonded interactions

For many-body bonded interactions, we refer to a class of potentials that depend not on the individual variables of certain particles, **but on collective variables**. A typical example is a harmonic potential that depends on the distance between the centers of mass of two groups of particles:

$$U(R) = \frac{1}{2}K(R - R_0)^2 \quad (6.8)$$

Here, $R = |d\vec{R}_{12}| = |\vec{R}_2 - \vec{R}_1|$ is the distance between the centers of mass of particle groups 1 and 2. Such interactions are commonly used in two scenarios. Firstly, for algorithms that compute free energies along a reaction coordinate, like in umbrella sampling for calculating the Potential of Mean Force (PMF) [267] of two structures based on the distance between their centers of mass. This distance would be the reaction coordinate. Here, a potential like the above is applied at multiple points along the reaction coordinate, varying the R_0 parameter. Techniques like WHAM [275] can then be used to derive the PMF as a function of R . Another application of these potentials is in simulating processes like pulling, where a force is exerted on two groups of particles in opposite directions [65]. Additionally, these potentials can be used to apply torque on groups of particles, similar to the stresses applied by magnetic tweezers on proteins, DNA [32], etc. Adding such potentials to a UAMMD-structured simulation is done as presented in Code 6.20.

Code 6.20: Many Body Example

```

topology:
  structure:
    # ...
  forceField:
    # ...
  mbb1_example:
    type: ["ManyBodyBond1", "FixedHarmonicCenterOfMass"]
    labels: ["idSet_i", "K", "r0", "position"]
    data:
      - [[0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10], 20.0, 0.0, [0.0,0.0,50.0]]
      - ...
  mbb2_example:
    type: ["ManyBodyBond2", "HarmonicBondBetweenCentersOfMass"]
    labels: ["idSet_i", "idSet_j", "K", "r0"]
    data:
      - [[11,12,13,14,15], [16,17,18,19,20], 10.0, 15.0]
      - ...
    # ...
  # ...

```

These potentials fall under two categories: "ManyBodyBond1" and "ManyBodyBond2". The first category includes potentials applied to a single group of particles, while the second involves potentials applied to two groups of particles². In the first case, we specify that a potential, which fixes the position of the center of mass, is applied to the particles from indices 0 to 10. The second case corresponds to the equation 6.8, where we indicate that a harmonic potential is applied to the distance between the center of mass of the particle group from indices 11 to 15 and the center of mass of the group from indices 16 to 20. Although in the example only one entry is added under "data" for each potential, an indefinite number can be included. There is just one restriction: for the same potential, a particle can only be in one group. This is due to implementation details, which we will discuss next.

Currently, the following potentials are implemented:

- **ManyBodyBond1**, potentials involving collective variables of a single group:
 - *ConstantForceOverCenterOfMass*: A constant force is applied to the position of the center of mass, \vec{R} , of a group of particles, with the potential $U(\vec{R}) = \vec{F} \cdot \vec{R}$.
 - *ConstantTorqueOverCenterOfMass*: A force \vec{f}_i is applied to each particle in a group such that the total torque on the center of mass is \vec{T} . This is calculated as $\vec{T} = \sum_i (\vec{r}_i - \vec{R}) \times \vec{f}_i$, where \vec{R} is the position of the center of mass.
 - *FixedHarmonicCenterOfMass*: The position of the center of mass of a group of particles is fixed using a harmonic potential. For \vec{R} being the center of mass, the potential is $U(R) = (1/2)K(\vec{R} - \vec{R}_0)^2$.
- **ManyBodyBond2**, potentials involving collective variables of two groups:
 - *ConstantForceBetweenCentersOfMass*: For \vec{R}_1 and \vec{R}_2 as the positions of the centers of mass of the first and second particle groups, respectively, the distance vector between the two groups is defined as $d\vec{R}_{12} = \vec{R}_2 - \vec{R}_1$. The applied potential is $U(d\vec{R}_{12}) = \vec{F} \cdot d\vec{R}_{12}$.
 - *ConstantTorqueBetweenCentersOfMass*: For two groups of particles S_1 and S_2 , with centers of mass at \vec{R}_1 and \vec{R}_2 respectively, the connecting vector is $d\vec{R}_{12} = \vec{R}_2 - \vec{R}_1$. A torque of $\vec{T} = Td\vec{R}_{12}/|dR_{12}|$ is applied to S_1 and $\vec{T} = Td\vec{R}_{21}/|dR_{21}|$ to S_2 . This is achieved by applying specific forces \vec{f}_i to each particle to generate the aforementioned torque on each group.

²Currently, only these two categories exist, but the implementation can be easily generalized for potentials involving three or more groups of particles

- *HarmonicBondBetweenCentersOfMass*: A harmonic potential is applied to the distance between the centers of mass of both groups, with $R = |d\vec{R}_{12}| = |\vec{R}_2 - \vec{R}_1|$. The potential is $U(R) = (1/2)K(R - R_0)^2$.

These potential are defined over some set of collective variables (such as the center of mass of a particle set). After computing the effect of these potentials over these collective variables, its effect is distributed among the particles which conform the collective variables.

The parameters and specific configuration of each potential can be found in the online documentation [235]. The efficient implementation of these potentials for correct evaluation on the GPU is non-trivial and will be discussed in the following section.

6.15.1 Many-Body Bonded Interactions Implementation

In this section, we present an algorithm designed for calculating many-body bonded potentials. This algorithm is optimized for GPUs, focusing on maximizing parallelism and minimizing thread divergence to enhance performance. It is available in two versions, with the choice between them depending on the number and size of the many-body bonds in the simulation. One version is suited for scenarios with a large number of small bonds (a large number of bonds, > 100 , that involve a relative small number of particles, $\approx 10 - 100$ particles), while the other is better for fewer but larger bonds (a reduced number of bonds, $\approx 10 - 100$, that involve a large number of particles, > 1000 particles).

The algorithm works by computing the effects of these potentials on particles involved in many-body bonds. Consider, for example, a harmonic potential between two groups of particles, as described by the equation:

$$U(R) = \frac{1}{2}K(R - R_0)^2$$

In this case, a harmonic spring is applied between the centers of mass of two particle groups, denoted as S_1 and S_2 . To calculate the force on each particle, we proceed as follows. This potential depends on the distance between the centers of mass of these groups, represented by $R = |d\vec{R}_{12}| = |\vec{R}_2 - \vec{R}_1|$. So, the first step is to compute these quantities using the expression:

$$\vec{R}_1 = \frac{1}{M_1} \sum_{i \in S_1} m_i \vec{r}_i \quad \vec{R}_2 = \frac{1}{M_2} \sum_{i \in S_2} m_i \vec{r}_i \quad (6.9)$$

Where M_1 and M_2 are the total masses of each set. Consequently, the force on the center of mass of each set is:

$$\vec{F}_1(R) = K(R - R_0) \cdot d\vec{R}_{12} \quad \vec{F}_2(R) = K(R - R_0) \cdot d\vec{R}_{21} \quad (6.10)$$

where $d\vec{R}_{12} = -d\vec{R}_{21}$. After calculating the forces on each set, we can determine the force on each individual particle, with s being the set to which particle i belongs:

$$\vec{f}_i = \frac{m_i}{M_s} \vec{F}_s \quad (6.11)$$

The steps followed to calculate the forces on each particle can be generalized. We define N_S as the number of sets involved in each many-body bond of the potential we are calculating. Initially, we need to compute a set of global quantities for each set. In each set, we have to calculate N_Q quantities, denoted as $Q_1^{(s)}, Q_2^{(s)}, \dots, Q_{N_Q}^{(s)}$, where $s = 1, \dots, N_S$. For calculating these quantities, we access the information of each individual particle i and perform some operation on them, transforming them into other intermediate quantities, which are denoted by $q_{(1)i}, q_{(2)i}, \dots, q_{(N_Q)i}$. We then perform some reduction operation on these transformed quantities to obtain $Q_1^{(s)}, Q_2^{(s)}, \dots, Q_{N_Q}^{(s)}$. That is, we perform a reduction operation on $q_{(1)i}$ for all $i \in S_s$ to obtain $Q_1^{(s)}$, and in general, we reduce $q_{(n)i}$ to obtain $Q_n^{(s)}$. These quantities are used along with the parameters of the many-body bond, CP (compute parameters), to calculate a certain global property, denoted by P . This property does not depend on the set, it is at the bond level. Finally, using the quantities $Q^{(s)}$ and P , as well as properties of each particle, we calculate the energy, the force, etc., for each particle.

To illustrate the process, let us express the calculation of the harmonic potential in the terms defined. In this case, $N_S = 2$. In our example, we have two types of quantities, $Q_1^{(s)}$ and $Q_2^{(s)}$. The first is the total mass of the particles in the set, and the second is the sum of the products of the masses by their positions. For the first case, we access the information of each particle and calculate a transformed quantity, $q_{(1)i} = m_i$ (applying the identity transformation on the mass of the particle) and $q_{(2)i} = m_i \vec{r}_i$. Once we have calculated these quantities, we perform the reduction operation, in our case the sum, to calculate $Q_1^{(s)}$ and $Q_2^{(s)}$. For the first set, $Q_1^{(1)} = \sum_{i \in S_1} q_{(1)i} = \sum_{i \in S_1} m_i = M_1$, and for the second quantity, $Q_2^{(1)} = \sum_{i \in S_1} q_{(2)i} = \sum_{i \in S_1} m_i \cdot \vec{r}_i$, and similarly for $Q_1^{(2)}$ and $Q_2^{(2)}$. Then, we calculate $P = \vec{F} = K(\vec{R} - R_0) \cdot d\vec{R}_{12}$, using the $Q^{(s)}$ for the calculation of $d\vec{R}_{12}$ and $CP = [K, R_0]$. Finally, for each particle in each set, we calculate the force. For particles in set 1, $\vec{f}_i = (m_i/Q_1^{(1)})\vec{F} \quad \forall i \in S_1$ and for particles in set 2, $\vec{f}_i = -(m_i/Q_1^{(2)})\vec{F} \quad \forall i \in S_2$. Note that $Q_1^{(1)} = M_1$ and $Q_1^{(2)} = M_2$.

Let us now discuss the implementation of this algorithm, starting with an implementation for the case of the harmonic potential between the centers of mass of two sets and subsequently generalizing it.

To implement the previously described algorithm, we must define the auxiliary functions that calculate $q_{(1)i}$ and $q_{(2)i}$. We simply use $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t})$, assuming these functions can access the information of each particle. Therefore, when we apply $\mathbf{q}(1)(i)$, it applies the intermediate transformation $q_{(1)}$ to particle i . Similarly, considering $\mathbf{q}(2)(i)$ applies the transformation $q_{(2)}$ to particle i . That is, $\mathbf{q}(1)(i)$ returns $q_{(1)i}$, m_i , and $\mathbf{q}(2)(i)$ returns $q_{(2)i}$, $\vec{r}_i m_i$. To perform these summations, we also need to define the initial value, returned by the function $\text{ZeroQ}(\mathbf{t})$, where $\text{ZeroQ}(1)$ returns 0 and $\text{ZeroQ}(2)$ returns a zero vector $(0, 0, 0)$.

We now define a generic function $\text{Reduce}(\text{operation}, \text{zero}, \text{set}, \text{transform})$. This function applies the transform function to the elements of the set and then reduces them using the operation operation , initializing the reduction value with zero . We will discuss different versions of this function later.

Finally, we define the matrix $RSLT_Q$. The results of the summations are stored in this matrix-like data structure, where $RSLT_Q[t, s]$ stores the value of Q_t in the set S_s . In our case, $t = 1, 2$ and $s = 1, 2$.

To generalize the previous algorithm (Alg. 5) for any type of potential defined over an arbitrary number of particle sets, we need to define two more functions: **Property** and **Spreading**, which we will explain below. Additionally, in certain situations, such as when applying torques, the $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t})$ functions may require prior quantities, for instance, to calculate $\mathbf{q}(2)$ we might need to know Q_1 . To handle this type of scenario, we extend the definition of $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t})$ to $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t}, RSLT_Q)$. We can assume that when we evaluate $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t}, RSLT_Q)$, the values of $RSLT_Q[a, s]$ are correctly calculated for all $a < t$ and for all s .

In summary, to specify a particular potential, we need to define six functions. Here, \mathbf{s} is a variable that we will use to refer to the set we are evaluating, N_S is the number of sets for the current potential, and \mathbf{t} is the set quantity we are calculating. Therefore, the functions are:

- $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t}, RSLT_Q)$: Calculates transformed intermediate data for each quantity \mathbf{t} using the results stored in $RSLT_Q$.
- $\text{ZeroQ}(\mathbf{t})$: Provides the initial value for the sum of set quantity \mathbf{t} .
- $\text{Reduce}(\text{operation}, \text{zero}, \text{set}, \text{transform})$: Applies a transform function to the elements of a set and then reduces them using the operation operation , starting with the value zero .

Algorithm 5 Center of Mass Harmonic Bond Potential Algorithm

Require: S_1, S_2 arrays containing indices of set 1 and set 2, respectively.

Require: $q(t)$ function which returns the transformed intermediate data for the quantity t .

Require: $\text{ZeroQ}(t)$ initial value for the sum of set quantity t .

Require: $\text{Reduce}(\text{operation}, \text{zero}, \text{set}, \text{transform})$

Require: CP Compute parameters, a struct: CP.K is the bond constant and CP.R0 the equilibrium distance.

```

1: for t = 1 to 2 do                                ▷ Iterate over set quantities
2:   for s = 1 to 2 do                               ▷ Iterate over sets
3:      $RSLT_Q[t, s] \leftarrow \text{Reduce}(+, \text{ZeroQ}(t), s, q(t))$ 
4:   end for
5: end for                                           ▷ At this point  $RSLT_Q[a, b]$  is filled
6:  $R_1 \leftarrow RSLT_Q[2, 1]/RSLT_Q[1, 1]$          ▷  $R_1 = Q_2^{(1)}/Q_1^{(1)} = \sum_{i \in S_1} m_i \vec{r}_i / M_1$ 
7:  $R_2 \leftarrow RSLT_Q[2, 2]/RSLT_Q[1, 2]$          ▷  $R_2 = Q_2^{(2)}/Q_1^{(2)} = \sum_{i \in S_2} m_i \vec{r}_i / M_2$ 
8:  $\vec{dR} \leftarrow \vec{R}_2 - \vec{R}_1$ 
9:  $R \leftarrow |dR_{12}|$ 
10:  $P \leftarrow CP.K \cdot (R - CP.R0) \cdot \vec{dR}$ 
11: for s = 1 to 2 do                                ▷ Iterate over sets
12:   for i in  $S_s$  do                                 ▷ Iterate over particles in set s
13:     if s = 1 then
14:        $f_i \leftarrow (m_i/RSLT_Q[1, s]) \cdot P$     ▷  $\vec{f}_i = \frac{m_i}{M_1} \cdot \vec{F}$ 
15:     else
16:        $f_i \leftarrow -(m_i/RSLT_Q[1, s]) \cdot P$    ▷  $\vec{f}_i = -\frac{m_i}{M_2} \cdot \vec{F}$ 
17:     end if
18:   end for
19: end for

```

- $\text{Property}(RSLT_Q, \text{CP})$: Calculates a global property of the bond based on the results in $RSLT_Q$ and compute parameters CP.
- $\text{Spreading}(RSLT_Q, P, \mathbf{s})$: Distributes the calculated property P across the particles in set \mathbf{s} , using the results in $RSLT_Q$.
- CP (Compute Parameters): A structure containing parameters specific to the many-body bond.

In addition to the previously defined functions, to provide greater generality, we can choose an arbitrary reduction operation \odot . Consequently, the algorithm for generic many-body bond potentials is given in Alg. 6.

Algorithm 6 Many-Body Generic Potential Bond Algorithm

Require: N_S , number of particle sets involved in each bond.
Require: N_Q , number of quantities to be computed for each set.
Require: $RSLT_Q$, result matrix of size $N_S \times N_Q$ where the values of Q are stored.
Require: S_s , arrays containing the indices of the particles in set s .
Require: $\text{ZeroQ}(t)$, initial value for the sum of the set quantity t .
Require: $q(t, RSLT_Q)$, function that returns the transformed intermediate data for each quantity.
Require: \odot , reduction operation.
Require: $\text{Property}(RSLT_Q, \text{CP})$, function to compute the bond property.
Require: $\text{Spreading}(P, RSLT_Q, \mathbf{s})$, function to spread the bond property across particles in set s .
Require: $\text{Reduce}(\text{operation}, \text{zero}, \text{set}, \text{transform})$.
Require: CP, compute parameters, a structure.

```

1: for  $t = 1$  to  $N_Q$  do ▷ Iterate over set quantities
2:   for  $s = 1$  to  $N_S$  do ▷ Iterate over sets
3:      $RSLT_Q[t, s] \leftarrow \text{Reduce}(\odot, \text{ZeroQ}(t), s, q(t, RSLT_Q))$ 
4:   end for
5: end for ▷ At this point  $RSLT_Q[a, b]$  is filled
6:  $P \leftarrow \text{property}(RSLT_Q, \text{CP})$ 
7: for  $s = 1$  to  $N_S$  do ▷ Iterate over sets
8:    $\text{Spreading}(P, RSLT_Q, s)$ 
9: end for
```

There are two versions of the algorithm implementation: one where each bond is assigned a thread (Thread Per Bond or TPB), and another where each bond is processed by a block of threads (Block Per Bond or BPB). Let us first examine the TPB option.

“**One thread per bond**” (TPB) strategy performs best when the number of particles per bond is small, around a dozen. However, it can efficiently handle a large number of bonds, in the order of thousands. The difference between TPB and other implementations resides in the **Reduce** function and how the **Spread** function is evaluated. In the TPB version, each thread iterates over the elements of each set and applies the reduction operation sequentially. This implementation is represented in the diagram Fig. 6.9. The reduction operations are depicted within red boxes, and the spreading operations in blue. As observed, we fix the quantity Q to be calculated and proceed to iterate over the sets. In each set, we first initialize Q with the value returned by the **ZeroQ** function and then iterate over the elements of the set (represented by boxes with highlighted black borders), applying the transformation operation q and then the reduction operation (represented by a plus sign in the diagram). Once the reduction is complete, the value is stored in the $RSLT_Q$ matrix, and the same operation is then performed on the next set. We execute this procedure for all Q quantities. After completion, the thread calculates the global property and proceeds to spread (blue boxes), iterating over each particle in each set, from $s = 1$ to $S = N_S$, and evaluating the spread function that modifies the force/energy of the particle.

The TPB approach becomes less efficient as the number of particles increases. Each thread has to perform many operations, including write operations (in spreading) that are especially costly. To solve this problem, a “**Block Per Bond**” (BPB) version is also implemented, where each bond is processed by a block of threads concurrently. The **UAMMD-structured** implementation decides which algorithm to execute based on the number of particles in the largest bond; if this exceeds 32, the BPB version is used. How this implementation works is shown in Fig. 6.10.

In BPB, each bond is processed in parallel but now with a group of threads concurrently. The general algorithm remains the same, i.e., we first iterate over the Q quantities, and once these are set, we calculate their values in all sets. In this case, the different threads carry out the reduction operation in parallel. Once all operations on the sets are complete, each thread accesses the result saved in $RSLT_Q$ and calculates the bond property. Finally, the spread, which is also parallelized, is carried out. In this way, the more costly write operations are distributed among the different threads of the block. This implementation can efficiently handle many-body bonds where the number of particles per bond can be in the order of thousands.

Figure 6.9: Diagram of the Thread Per Bond (TPB) Implementation: Showing sequential processing of reduction (red boxes) and spreading (blue boxes) operations for each bond. Note that the dependency of the q function on $RSLT_Q$ is not indicated in the figure due to space constraints.

Figure 6.10: Parallel Processing in the Block Per Bond (BPB) Implementation: Depicting concurrent reduction (red boxes) and spreading (blue boxes) operations by a block of threads, suitable for bonds with a higher number of particles. The dependency of the q function on $RSLT_Q$ is not shown in the figure due to space limitations.

As mentioned, each algorithm executes bonds in parallel, either following a one-thread-per-bond scheme or a one-block-per-bond scheme. In both cases, particles from different bonds are evaluated concurrently. This is why it is not permitted for a particle to belong to more than one bond, as this could lead to a situation where multiple threads simultaneously attempt to update the same information of the particle. Such a scenario would create a race condition, where the value being modified becomes undefined.

A quick solution to this is to use atomic operations when writing to memory to modify the properties of the particle, ensuring that a race condition does not occur. However, these operations can impact performance. Therefore, we have chosen to impose the restriction that a particle cannot belong to more than one set. This is also a common situation when using these types of potentials.

6.16 Patchy Particles

As mentioned in Chapter 3 the term "patchy particles" refers to a group of models used in the study of particle interactions. These models define various interaction zones on the surface of a particle, each with distinct interaction properties. There are several notable models of patchy particles, among which the Kern-Frenkel [44] model and the **sticky points model** [173] are the most significant. The Kern-Frenkel model identifies specific regions on the particles (Chapter 3). Interactions occur only when these regions are correctly oriented relative to each other and are at an appropriate distance. On the other hand, the *sticky points model* conceptualizes patches as individual particles located on the surface of a larger parent particle. The interaction between these particles, the patches, is translated into forces and torques for parent particles.

Figure 6.11: Example of patched particles. In this example all particles are identical. Each parent particle (blue) has 6 patches (small red dots). The patches can interact attractively with each other, resulting in the cluster-like distribution shown in the figure.

In the sticky points model, patches are represented as particles located on the surface of a larger parent particle 6.11. These patches can interact with each other, and their interactions result in forces and torques applied to the parent particle. However, there is no direct interaction between the parent particle and the patches. In parallel, parent particles themselves can interact with each other, for instance, through Lennard-Jones potential or DLVO theory.

Another crucial aspect of the interaction between patches is the valence of the interaction. This refers to the number of patches a single patch can interact with simultaneously. There are two main types: infinite valence, where each patch can simultaneously interact with an unlimited number of other patches, and unitary valence 6.11. In the case of unitary valence, a patch can only interact with one other patch at a time. When this occurs, the two interacting patches are considered bonded. this unitary valence situation is known as the **single-bond-per-patch** (SBPP) condition. The SBPP condition is common and it is used to model processes like polymerization or specific interactions between structures. Consider, for example, two proteins that can interact specifically with each other. Each protein has a zone that interacts specifically with a certain zone of the other protein. Once this interaction occurs, these zones are blocked, preventing other proteins from interacting in the same specific manner. This type of phenomenon is what we model under the SBPP condition. Both options of interaction valence are available in `UAMMD-structured` .

As we will discuss in the implementation, when we add patchy particles to the system, they behave like a **simulation within the broader simulation**. They share with the main simulation, *system*, *ensemble* and *units*. However, other global elements, such as *types* or *fundamentals*, must be specified, along with the *state* and *topology*. An example of how to add these interactions to the simulation is given in Code 6.21.

Firstly, it should be noted that in this case, we should not add a simple `DataEntry` to define the patches; instead, we use a `section` . In this example, the type is ["Patchy-Particle", "DynamicallyBondedPatchyParticles"]. The subtype indicates that we are using a model applying the SBPP (single-bond-per-patch) condition. Let us now discuss the contents of the "patchesGlobal" `section` . When selecting this type of patchy particle model, which adheres to SBPP, we need to specify a threshold energy. If two patches interact with energy below this threshold, they are considered bonded and thus blocked for interaction with other patches. This threshold energy is specified in the "fundamental" entry, as seen in the example.

Additionally, in the "patchesGlobal" `section` , we will also define the types of patches, similar to how we do it in the *global section* . Continuing, we add the `DataEntry` named "patchesState". In this `section` , we define the patches by assigning each an ID and a position. *This position does not correspond to the global position of the patch in the simulation box. Rather, it refers to the position of the patch position relative to the parent reference system of the particle.* The association between a patch and its parent particle is made in the `DataEntry` named "structure", within the "patchesTopology" `section` .

Code 6.21: Patches Example

```

topology:
# ...
forceField:
  patches:
    type:["PatchyParticles","DynamicallyBondedPatchyParticles"]
  patchesGlobal:
    fundamental:
      type:["Fundamental","EnergyThreshold"]
      parameters:
        energyThreshold: 0.0
    types:
      type:["Types","Basic"]
      labels: ["name", "mass", "radius", "charge"]
      data:
        - ["P", 0.0, 0.1, 0.0]
  patchesState:
    labels: ["id", "position"]
    data:
      - [0, [0.5, 0.0, 0.0]]
      - [1, [-0.5, 0.0, 0.0]]
      - [2, [0.5, 0.0, 0.0]]
      - [3, [-0.5, 0.0, 0.0]]
      ...
  patchesTopology:
    structure:
      labels: ["id", "type", "parentId"]
      data:
        - [0, "P", 0]
        - [1, "P", 0]
        - [2, "P", 1]
        - [3, "P", 1]
      ...
    forceField:
      verletList:
        type:["VerletConditionalListSet","all"]
        parameters:
          cutOffVerletFactor: 3.0
      exponential:
        type:["NonBondedPatches","DistanceSwitchExponential"]
        labels: ["name_i", "name_j", "E", "K", "rc"]
        parameters:
          condition: all
        data:
          - ["P", "P", 10.0, 1.1, 0.5]

```

Here, similarly to the general setup, we associate each patch with its type. Additionally, we associate it with the parent particle by specifying the "id" of the parent. In this example, two patches are added to particle 0 and two to particle 1.

Finally, we enumerate the interactions between the patches. In this case, a "short-Range" interaction type is used, which establishes a Gaussian well between the patches. Additionally, we specify the corresponding set of conditioned Verlet lists, similar to what we would do for normal particles. This allows for the effective simulation of interactions between patches, taking into account their specific positions and associations within the system.

For the proper functioning of these types of interactions, the particles must have **orientation**. This means that "direction" should have been specified when defining the "state" of the particles. Additionally, an appropriate integrator for this kind of system, such as a rigid body integrator [276], must be employed.

Through these models, a wide range of scenarios can be simulated. Currently, there are various short-range potentials between pairs of patches, many of which involve the orientation of the two parent particles (Chapter 3). Additionally, there are external potentials for patches, such as interactions with a surface. Adding new potentials is very similar to the process used for other interactions. However, due to specific implementation details that we will discuss later, certain peculiarities need to be considered.

Parallel to this, interactions can always be added to the parent particles. Moreover, hydrodynamics interactions can also be incorporated, as UAMMD includes integrators that couple changes in the orientation of the particles with the fluid.

6.16.1 Patchy particles implementation

Let us discuss the implementation of patchy particles in parallel molecular dynamics simulations. We will begin by exploring a basic approach for simulating such systems. Consider a scenario where patches interact with each other through an attractive potential, while parent particles repel each other using some kind of steric interaction, like a WCA potential. This setup is commonly used to study aggregation processes.

Initially, we could implement this interaction as a pairwise interaction between particles. Assume a potential between the patches with a certain cutoff radius $r_{cut}^{patches}$. If the distance between two patches (not the parent particles, but the patches themselves) is such that $r < r_{cut}^{patches}$, then we should evaluate the potential.

To facilitate this, we need to construct a neighbor list for an interaction with a cutoff radius $r_{cut} = r_{cut}^{patches} + R_{max}$, where R_{max} is the largest radius among all parent particles involved in the simulation. Then, when two particles are within this distance,

we evaluate the distance between all pairs of patches. For those pairs whose distance is less than $r_{cut}^{patches}$, we assess the potential and calculate the force and torque on the parent particle.

However, this approach has several drawbacks. If N_1 and N_2 are the number of patches on particles 1 and 2, respectively, and considering a GPU algorithm where each thread is associated with a particle, this thread would have to evaluate $N_1 \times N_2$ possible combinations. Let $N = N_1 = N_2$ and N_{neig} be the number of neighboring particles. Then each thread would have to evaluate $N_{neig} \times N^2$ interactions.

Notably, as the cutoff radius is given by $r_{cut} = r_{cut}^{patches} + R_{max}$, N_{neig} would also be larger than usual in a particle system. Additionally, this approach is inefficient as the distance between patches often will not satisfy $r < r_{cut}^{patches}$, leading to unnecessary distance evaluations. This introduces inefficiencies in the code and, depending on the GPU implementation, potential divergence in the kernels [225, 241].

Considering these issues, a different approach was developed to handle the simulation of patchy particles more efficiently.

The central concept of our algorithm is to treat the patches as an **independent system within the molecular dynamics simulation**. Generally, any molecular dynamics simulation can be divided into two types of steps: integration steps and steps for calculating forces, torques, and other quantities necessary for integration. Based on this concept, we handle the patches as a separate simulation comprising three steps (Fig. 6.12):

1. Update the positions of the patches based on the positions of their parent particles.
2. Compute forces, torques, etc., for each patch.
3. Aggregate all calculated quantities from the patches back to the parent particles.

This method aims to address the previously mentioned challenges effectively. Essentially, we transform an interactor (the patches interactor) into a standalone simulation.

This reasoning explains the specific format of the input data. When specifying the positions of the patches, this information is not stored in the same manner as the positions of standard particles. Instead, it is stored in an array we will refer to as ‘patchesLocalCoord’, \mathbf{r}_{patch}^* . This array corresponds to the position of each patch relative to the co-moving reference system of its parent particle. Recall that this co-moving system is encoded as a quaternion (Sec. 6.7), denoted as \mathbf{q}_{parent} . Therefore, denoting \mathbf{r}_{parent} as the position of the parent in the laboratory reference system, the position of the patch in this reference system is given by a specific transformation

Figure 6.12: Example of how a system with interactions via bonds (section 6.11), short-range interactions (section 6.12), and patch interactions would be processed. Given a certain initial state, the procedure is similar to a system without patches. The different interactions (bonds and short-range interactions in this example) are calculated. When processing the interaction for the patches, the set of patches is treated as an autonomous system. First, their positions are calculated, then the different interactions (in this example, short-range interactions between the patches) are evaluated. Finally, the contribution of each patch to the parent particle is summed. After all forces and torques are computed the system state is updated.

involving $\mathbf{r}_{\text{patch}}^*$ and $\mathbf{q}_{\text{parent}}$. This allows for a dynamic and efficient simulation of patch interactions, taking into account the relative motion and orientation of each patch with respect to its parent particle:

$$\mathbf{r}_{\text{patch}} = \text{Rotate}(\mathbf{q}_{\text{parent}}, \mathbf{r}_{\text{patch}}^*) + \mathbf{r}_{\text{parent}} = \mathbf{q}_{\text{parent}} \mathbf{r}_{\text{patch}}^* \mathbf{q}_{\text{parent}}^{-1} + \mathbf{r}_{\text{parent}} \quad (6.12)$$

When calculating the interaction between patches, the first step is to update the positions of the patches. For this, we need to define the array `patchId2parentId`. This array associates the ID of a patch with the ID of its parent particle. The Alg. 7 takes care of this task. This algorithm is executed in parallel on the GPU, following the scheme of one thread per particle.

Algorithm 7 Patches Global Position Update

Require: `parentPositions`, an array containing the positions of the parent particles.

Require: `parentOrientations`, an array containing the quaternions that encapsulate the orientation of the parent particles.

Require: `patchesLocalCoord`, the position of the patch in the co-moving reference system of the parent.

Require: `patchesPositions`, the position of the patches in the laboratory reference system.

Require: `Rotate(q, r)`, a function that takes a quaternion and a vector as arguments and returns the vector after applying the rotation of the quaternion.

Require: `patchId2parentId`, an array that associates each patch with its parent.

```

1: i ← Current patch id
2: parentId ← patchId2parentId[i]
3: localCoord ← patchesLocalCoord[i]
4: pPos ← parentPositions[parentId]
5: pOri ← parentOrientations[parentId]
6: patchesPositions[i] ← Rotate(pOri, localCoord) + pPos

```

As seen, this algorithm is quite straightforward, involving only four read operations, one write operation, and a set of floating-point operations in the `Rotate` function. The impact on the overall performance of the program is minimal.

At this point, the positions of the patches are updated and function similarly to regular particles. This means, for example, that neighbor lists do not need new logic to determine whether they need to be updated or not. The potentials will evaluate forces on the patches. It is important to mention that for patches, we need *specific potentials*. For example, if a Lennard-Jones potential is applied to the patches, each patch, in addition to applying a force on the central particle, *would also apply a torque*. Particularly, if the force on the patch is denoted as \mathbf{f}_i , the torque that this force would

exert on the parent particle is given by:

$$\tau_i = \mathbf{f}_i \times \mathbf{r}_i^* \quad (6.13)$$

where \mathbf{r}_i^* is the local coordinate of the patch, similar to the format in 6.12. The forces, in contrast, are applied directly to the parent particle. In other words, the potentials for the patches must not only calculate the forces on the patches but also the torques that these forces would generate on the parent particle. In some cases, the potentials of the patches also determine the orientation of the parent particles, resulting in torques that do not directly arise from the forces of attraction/repulsion between the patches.

After evaluating the different interactions involving the patches, they store certain values of energy, force, and torque. The final step is a reduction operation. In this operation, we iterate over the different patches of each parent particle and sum these values to ultimately obtain the total value for the parent particle. For this purpose, we introduce the arrays `patchesParent`, and `patchesParentN`. The former is a matrix where the patches that make up each particle are stored. That is, `patchesParent[i]` is an array of size `patchesParentN[i]` where each element is an ID of the patches. The Alg. 8 is designed to be executed with each parent particle associated with a thread.

This algorithm is also relatively undemanding in terms of computational resources. In this way, we can perform the calculations of the effects of the patches on the particles, avoiding all the previously mentioned inconveniences, which translates into improved performance.

Several considerations remain to be made. What has been explained so far is correct for those systems in which we do not apply any type of restriction on the valence of the bonds. In the following section, we will discuss how the SBPP condition is implemented.

Single bond per patch condition

When we set the Single Bond Per Patch (SBPP) condition, we indicate that when two patches are bonded, they are in a way "locked" and cannot interact with other patches until the bond is broken. To implement this behavior, the first thing we need to develop is a definition of a bond. That is, when can we say that two patches are bonded. For this, we add the parameter `thresholdEnergy`. Through this parameter, we establish an energy threshold; if the interaction of two patches results in energy lower than this threshold, then the particles are considered bonded.

Algorithm 8 Patches energy/force/torque reduction

- Require:** `parentEnergy`, an array to store the total energy of each parent particle.
- Require:** `parentForce`, an array to store the total force acting on each parent particle.
- Require:** `parentTorque`, an array to store the total torque experienced by each parent particle.
- Require:** `patchEnergy`, an array containing the energy values of each patch.
- Require:** `patchForce`, an array containing the force values exerted by each patch.
- Require:** `patchTorque`, an array containing the torque values exerted by each patch.
- Require:** `patchesParent`, a matrix that maps each patch to its corresponding parent particle.
- Require:** `patchesParentN`, an array where each element represents the number of patches associated with a corresponding parent particle.
-

```

1:  $i \leftarrow$  Current parent id
2:  $\text{totalEnergy} \leftarrow 0$ 
3:  $\text{totalForce} \leftarrow (0,0,0)$ 
4:  $\text{totalTorque} \leftarrow (0,0,0)$ 
5: for  $\text{index}=0$  to  $\text{index}=\text{patchesParentN}[i]$  do
6:    $\text{patchId} \leftarrow \text{patchesParent}[i][\text{index}]$ 
7:    $\text{totalEnergy} \leftarrow \text{totalEnergy} + \text{patchEnergy}[\text{patchId}]$ 
8:    $\text{totalForce} \leftarrow \text{totalForce} + \text{patchForce}[\text{patchId}]$ 
9:    $\text{totalTorque} \leftarrow \text{totalTorque} + \text{patchTorque}[\text{patchId}]$ 
10:   $\text{patchEnergy}[\text{patchId}] \leftarrow 0$   $\triangleright$  Reset patch quantities for future calculations
11:   $\text{patchForce}[\text{patchId}] \leftarrow (0,0,0)$ 
12:   $\text{patchTorque}[\text{patchId}] \leftarrow (0,0,0)$ 
13: end for
14:  $\text{parentEnergy}[\text{parentId}] \leftarrow \text{parentEnergy}[\text{parentId}] + \text{energy}$ 
15:  $\text{parentForce}[\text{parentId}] \leftarrow \text{parentForce}[\text{parentId}] + \text{force}$ 
16:  $\text{parentTorque}[\text{parentId}] \leftarrow \text{parentTorque}[\text{parentId}] + \text{torque}$ 

```

The second thing to consider is that intuitively, we need some kind of data structure to store this condition, that is, to store whether the current patch is bonded to another or not. For this, each patch is associated with a variable, `bondedPatch`. This variable is an integer; if two patches, say with IDs i and j , are bonded, then `bondedPatch[i]=j` and `bondedPatch[j]=i`. In other words, `bondedPatch` is an array where each patch is associated with the patch to which it is bonded. If a patch is not bonded to any other patch, then this variable takes the value -1. `bondedPatch[i]=-1` if i is not bonded to any other patch. `bondedPatch` is an array of size N_{patches} .

The second component we need is another pair of variables, `tentativeBondedPatch` and `tentativeBondedPatchEnergy`. The former is an integer, and the latter is a real number, both are arrays of size N_{patches} . In the first, we store the patch with which we could establish a bond, and in the second, the energy of this bond. At the beginning of the simulation, these variables default to `tentativeBondedPatch=-1` and `tentativeBondedPatchEnergy=thresholdEnergy`. Similar to `bondedPatch`, when `tentativeBondedPatch` is equal to -1, this indicates that there is no patch with which it is possible to form a bond, and in this case, the energy is considered the threshold energy. We recall that to evaluate interactions between patches, there are three steps: first, update the position of the patches, second, calculate interactions between patches, and finally, accumulate the result in the parent particles. When applying the SBPP condition, we modify the first step. It now also manages not only the updating of the position of the patches but also the `bondedPatch` array. Therefore, after applying Alg. 7, we implement the Alg. 9:

With the Alg. 9, we determine whether a patch is bonded to another patch and ensure system consistency in such cases: `bondedPatch[i] = j` and `bondedPatch[j] = i`. The condition to check if the tentative bond of the tentative bond of patch i is indeed i is crucial, as this is not guaranteed in all situations. This algorithm ensures that a bond is only formed if both patches mutually recognize each other as their tentative bonding partner, which is a key aspect of the SBPP condition.

In Figure 6.13, the interaction among three patches is depicted. In the figure, numbers are placed over the larger particles, but we refer to each patch using these numbers. Let us assume that $E_{12} < E_{13}$, and both are less than $E_{\text{threshold}}$. In this scenario, a bond should form between patches 1 and 2. However, let us examine the situation from the perspective of each patch. For patch 1, the logical choice would be to form a bond with patch 2; for patch 2, it would be with patch 1, but patch 3 would also try to form a bond with patch 1.

Algorithm 9 Bonded patch updated under SBPP conditions

Require: `thresholdEnergy`, the energy threshold for bond formation.

Require: `bondedPatch`, an array to track the current bonded status of each patch.

Require: `tentativeBondedPatch`, an array for potential bonding partners of each patch.

Require: `tentativeBondedPatchEnergy`, an array holding the potential bond energy for each patch pairing.

```

1:  $i \leftarrow$  Current patch id
2: if tentativeBondedPatchEnergy[i] < thresholdEnergy then
3:   tentativeBondId  $\leftarrow$  tentativeBondedPatch[i]
4:   tentativeBondOfTentativeBond  $\leftarrow$  tentativeBondedPatch[tentativeBondId]
5:   if tentativeBondOfTentativeBond = i then
6:     bondedPatch[i]  $\leftarrow$  tentativeBondId
7:   else
8:     bondedPatch[i]  $\leftarrow$  -1
9:   end if
10: else
11:   bondedPatch[i]  $\leftarrow$  -1
12: end if

```

Figure 6.13: An illustration of SBPP condition handling. In this situation (assuming $E_{12} < E_{13}$), if not additional checking is performed, inconsistencies appear.

Without the condition that the tentative bond of the tentative bond of i should effectively be the patch i , an inconsistency arises. In such a situation, patch 3 would consider itself bonded to patch 1, but patch 1 would be bonded to patch 2. This scenario illustrates the necessity of the condition in the algorithm, ensuring consistent bonding relationships under the SBPP condition. By implementing this logic, the system prevents conflicting bonding states, maintaining a coherent bonding structure throughout the simulation.

At this point, two questions remain to be addressed: how to ensure that if a patch is bonded to another, it only interacts with that patch and not others, and how to update `tentativeBondedPatch` and `tentativeBondedPatchEnergy`. Both considerations are managed by modifying the potentials. Two parts must be added to the normal potential: one at the beginning and one at the end.

At the beginning of the energy or forces/torque computation, when evaluating the interaction between patches i and j , we apply the Alg. 10, which checks if patches i, j should interact. Patches interaction is only consider when: *both patches are free or when they are bonded together*.

Algorithm 10 Determine interaction condition in SBPP

Require: `bondedPatch`

```

1:  $i \leftarrow$  current patch id
2:  $j \leftarrow$  id of the patch current patch is interaction
3: bonded  $\leftarrow$  ((bondedPatch[ $i$ ] =  $j$ ) and (bondedPatch[ $j$ ] =  $i$ ))
4: free  $\leftarrow$  ((bondedPatch[ $i$ ] = -1) and (bondedPatch[ $j$ ] = -1))
5: interact  $\leftarrow$  bonded or free
6:
7: if interact then
8:   Evaluate potential ...
9:
10: end if

```

Finally, when applying the SBPP condition, the potentials need to perform an extra operation. After evaluating the energy, force, and torque, and before continuing with the next potential or beginning the reduction operation, the current potential performs the operation described in Alg. 11 to update the values of `tentativeBondedPatch` and `tentativeBondedPatchEnergy`.

Algorithm 11 Updating patch states during force and energy calculation

This code executes before concluding an interaction between pairs of patches.

Assumption: We are in a GPU environment with one thread per particle scheme.

Require: `currentPatchId`: ID of the current patch.

Require: `interactingPatchId`: ID of the patch interacting with `currentPatchId`.

Require: `currentInteractionEnergy`: Energy of the current interaction between `currentPatchId` and `interactingPatchId`.

Require: `tentativeBondedPatchEnergy`.

Require: `tentativeBondedPatch`.

```

1: if currentInteractionEnergy < tentativeBondedPatchEnergy[currentPatchesId]
   then
2:   tentativeBondedPatch[currentPatchesId] ← interactionPatchId
3:   tentativeBondedPatchEnergy[currentPatchesId] ←
     currentInteractionEnergy
4: end if

```

6.17 Special interactions

In some instances, the general interactions previously discussed may not suffice to accurately model the system under investigation. In such scenarios, it becomes necessary to develop a specific interactor tailored for particular types of problems. These specialized interactions fall under the "special" category. Next, we will detail one such interaction, which is used to conduct simulations of Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM).

6.17.1 Atomic Force Microscopy

To simulate Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), we follow the scheme used by previous studies [277, 278]. In this model, the AFM tip is represented as a sphere connected to a virtual point, referred to as the chip, through an anisotropic spring:

$$U_{\text{tip-chip}} = \frac{1}{2}K(z_{\text{tip}} - z_{\text{chip}})^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{xy} [(x_{\text{tip}} - x_{\text{chip}})^2 + (y_{\text{tip}} - y_{\text{chip}})^2] \quad (6.14)$$

Adjusting the position of the chip allows us to manipulate the location of the tip. Typically, K_{xy} is significantly larger than K to restrict lateral movement. To simulate indentation, we decrease the position of the chip, dragging the AFM tip primarily along the z axis due to the large value of K_{xy} . The deflection force of the tip can be measured by calculating the magnitude $K(z_{\text{tip}} - z_{\text{chip}})$. Figure 6.14 illustrates this setup. AFM potential does not include the surface interaction, which must be added separately using an external potential.

Once we have added the tip particle and the sample we can add the AFM potential using the interaction of type ["AFM", "SphericalTip"] (Code 6.22).

Figure 6.14: The figure shows a model of the tobacco mosaic virus [279]. Also included are the AFM tip and the chip, represented by a blue dot. The particle representing the tip is connected to the chip through the potential described by 6.14. As the position of the chip is lowered, the AFM tip indents the sample. A surface is also added, which is not defined by the AFM interaction and must be included separately.

Code 6.22: AFM Example

```

topology:
  structure:
    # ...
  forceField:
    AFM:
      type: ["AFM", "SphericalTip"]
      labels: ["idSet_i", "idSet_j",
              "epsilon", "sigma",
              "K", "Kxy",
              "tipVelocity", "startChipPosition",
              "indentationStartStep"]
      data:
        - [[0], [1, 2, 3, "..."],
          -1.0, 1.0,
          1.0, 10.0,
          -0.5, [0.0, 0.0, 50.0], 0]
    # ...
  # ...
  # ...

```

Initially, we must identify which particle represents the AFM tip and which group constitutes the sample. The AFM tip is a normal particle, requiring definition in `sections` like "state" and "structure" within the `DataEntry` using specific labels/data fields. "idSet_i" indicates the particle for the tip (particle 0 in our example), while "idSet_j" designates the particle group of the sample. Parameters such as "epsilon," "sigma," "K," and "Kxy" define the characteristics of the tip. The interaction between the tip and the sample is modeled using a modified Lennard-Jones potential for larger, non-point-like particles:

$$U_{\text{tip-sample}} = \sum_{i \in \text{sample}} \varepsilon_{\text{tip}} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{tip}}}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_{\text{tip}}| - R_{\text{tip}}} \right)^{12} - 2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{tip}}}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_{\text{tip}}| - R_{\text{tip}}} \right)^6 \right] \quad (6.15)$$

Here, ε_{tip} and σ_{tip} are the predefined values, and R_{tip} is the radius of the particle representing the tip. The position of this particle is denoted by \vec{r}_{tip} .

Finally, we define the velocity of the chip ("tipVelocity") along the z-axis, its initial position ("startChipPosition"), and the moment indentation begins ("indentationStartStep"). The position of the chip at simulation step $n > nStart$ (where $nStart$ is the step when indentation starts) is given by:

$$z_{\text{chip}} = z_{\text{chip0}} + v_{\text{chip}} \cdot (n - nStart) \cdot dt. \quad (6.16)$$

The position of the chip in the xy plane remains fixed. Consequently, the chip will progressively lower (for $v_{\text{chip}} < 0$), dragging the tip due to the potential 6.14. If the tip encounters an obstacle, such as the particles of the sample, it will exert increasing force upon them. This configuration allows us to simulate the AFM indentation process on a sample. Additional AFMs can be included as rows in the `DataEntry`, operating in a similar manner.

Atomic Force Microscopy implementation

The interaction potential described by Eq. 6.15 is peculiar. With N_{sample} being the number of particles comprising the sample being indented, we need to calculate both the energy and the interaction force that one particle, the tip, exerts on each of the sample particles. Simultaneously, we must compute the total force that the particles and the bond with the chip exert on the tip. This disparity, where one *particle is treated differently from the rest*, the tip and the sample, *contrasts with the philosophy of the GPU*, where each particle is associated with a processing unit (thread), and the high performance is achieved when a similar set of instructions is executed for each thread.

To address this difficulty, the problem is divided into two steps. In the first step, we calculate the force that the tip exerts on each of the particles. Subsequently, we calculate the force that the particles exert on the tip.

Figure 6.15: Schematic of how the interaction between the AFM and the sample is calculated. In the first part, the effect of the AFM on each particle is calculated, and the effect of the particles on the AFM is stored in a buffer (additionally, the first thread calculates the effect of the bond on the AFM and stores it along with the remaining previous interactions). Subsequently, a synchronization operation is performed to ensure that all threads have finished. Finally, the buffer is reduced, and its result is stored.

In order to execute this process, we follow these steps. The core idea is that when calculating the force exerted by the AFM on each particle, we **process and store** this result, which is then used to compute the total force on the AFM.

First, we declare a GPU array of size $N_{sample} + 1$. This array will store information about the interaction. Then we execute a kernel following the approach of one thread per particle [225, 241]. Each thread will calculate the energy/force exerted by the tip on the particle associated with the thread. In addition to storing this result in the particle properties array, we also save it in the buffer. Specifically, if e_i is the interaction energy between the tip and the sample and f_i (as given by 6.15) is the force exerted by the sample on the particle, then in this array we store e and $-f_i$, the force that the particle exerts on the tip. Furthermore, the first thread also calculates the force that

the bond exerts on the tip 6.14 and stores this information in the additional position of the array, along with the energy/force that might be acting on the tip due to other previously calculated interactions (such as the interaction between the tip and the substrate). This process is depicted in Fig. 6.15. Afterwards, we wait for all threads to finish, i.e., perform a synchronization, and then carry out a *reduction* of the buffer, storing the result in the memory associated with the energy/force properties of the tip particle.

This approach maximizes parallelization of the equations, minimizes divergence, and ensures the entire process is carried out on the GPU, avoiding costly CPU/GPU communications. With this algorithm, efficient AFM simulations with samples of hundreds of thousands of particles can be conducted.

6.18 Groups

In certain situations, we want a specific interaction or a particular simulation step to apply only to a subset of particles. For such scenarios, groups are defined. We define a group by specifying its name, the type of selection to be made, and the selection itself (Code 6.23).

Code 6.23: Groups Force Field Example

```

topology:
  structure:
    # ...
  forceField:
    groups_example:
      type: ["Groups", "GroupsList"]
      labels: ["name", "type", "selection"]
      data:
        - ["ids_group_1", "Ids", [0, 1, 2, 3, 4]]
        - ["ids_group_2", "Ids", [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]]
    interaction1:
      parameters:
        group: "ids_group_1"
    interaction2:
      parameters:
        group: "ids_group_2"
    # ...
  # ...

```

In Code 6.23 we define two groups, "ids_groups_1" and "ids_groups_2". The definition of these groups is made through IDs, followed by indicating the selection. Subsequently, we specify in each interaction the group it acts upon using the "group" parameter. Similarly, we can define selections for simulation steps (Code 6.24).

Code 6.24: Groups Simulation Step Example

```

simulationStep:
  groups_example:
    type: ["Groups", "GroupsList"]
    labels: ["name", "type", "selection"]
    data:
      - ["types_group_1", "Types", ["A"]]
      - ["types_group_2", "notTypes", ["A"]]
  simStep1:
    parameters:
      group: "types_group_1"
  simStep2:
    parameters:
      group: "types_group_2"
  # ...
  # ...

```

In Code 6.24, group definitions are made using "Types". In the first selection "types_group_1", we specify that it comprises particles of type "A". The second defined group is "types_group_2", which consists of particles that are not of type "A".

Finally, we can also declare groups similarly in integrators. This can be useful for constructing complex boundaries that cannot be expressed well through a potential. We can create a system formed by two groups, "particles" and "boundaries", where only the first is integrated, but potentials apply to both (no group defined in the force field). Thus, only "particles" will advance in time but will feel the interactions of the "boundaries" particles.

6.19 Simulation Batching

In scenarios where numerous small simulations are required, for instance, for statistical analysis or parameter exploration, running these simulations sequentially might not be the most efficient approach. Let us assume a single simulation takes a time T to complete. If we need to perform N simulations sequentially, the total time required would be TN . However, since GPUs are not fully utilized during each small simulation, this presents an opportunity to **execute multiple simulations simultaneously on the same GPU**.

We want to group simulations into batches, where each batch, of size N_S , contains enough simulations to **fully utilize the capacity of the GPU**. Ideally, the execution time for a batch of N_S simulations should be approximately equal to the time for a single simulation (T). Therefore, the total number of batches needed would be approximately $N_B \approx N/N_S$, and the overall execution time becomes $\approx TN_B \simeq TN/N_S < TN$.

In certain systems, batch sizes could be as large as $N_S \approx 100$, leading to significant efficiency gains.

However, the actual implementation of this batching on GPUs can be challenging due to their inherent hardware design. When different simulations are executed on the same GPU, *their instructions tend to become serialized rather than parallelized*. This effect is illustrated in Fig. 6.16. In Panel A, two simulations are executed sequentially, with each running its instructions in order. In contrast, Panel B shows what happens when two simulations are run simultaneously on the GPU: instructions from each simulation are executed in an alternating pattern³. Unfortunately, this interleaving of instructions disrupts the potential benefits of simultaneous execution, as it does not lead to a significant reduction in total computational time.

Figure 6.16: Illustration of default multitasking on GPU. A) Two different programs are executed sequentially. First, the instruction set of the first program is evaluated and once it is finished, the instructions of the second program are evaluated. B) Both programs are executed at the same time. The instructions that compose both programs are evaluated alternately, the time needed to execute the two programs in this way is similar to that required in A.

To overcome the challenges of multitasking inefficiencies on GPUs, NVIDIA introduced the Multi-Process Service (MPS) [280]. MPS facilitates the concurrent execution of multiple programs on the GPU, but it comes with certain limitations. Each simulation running on the GPU requires execution by a CPU core, thus making CPU cores a bottleneck in scenarios with numerous simulations. There is also a cap on the number of processes that can run simultaneously on the GPU. Memory usage scales linearly with the number of simulations; each new simulation added demands a similar amount of memory. Another constraint is that different instances within MPS do

³This explanation is a simplification; the process involves more complexities and details. A more technical description can be found in [280]

not easily exchange information between them. This restriction leads to problems for algorithms that require inter-batch communication. One of the major complications with MPS is its requirement for prior configuration through software, as it is not available by default. In high-performance computing environments like computing clusters, configuring MPS can be quite complex. Consequently, it is not widely used in such environments due to the complexity of its configuration.

Figure 6.17: CUDA MPS illustration. When using CUDA MPS, each program is associated with a different process and can run concurrently sharing GPU resources.

UAMMD-structured addresses the challenges of GPU multitasking by introducing an efficient batching system. This system enables simultaneous execution of any number of simulations, maximizing the capacity of the GPU without being limited by the number of CPU cores, as it functions as a single process. One of the key advantages of the batching system of UAMMD-structured is its minimal memory usage. This efficiency is achieved by sharing large data structures, like neighbor lists, across multiple simulations. Such an approach is particularly beneficial for simulations involving memory-intensive potentials, including tabulated potentials and increasingly popular neural network-based potentials [281]. The latter, already implemented in programs like LAMMPS, could potentially be extended to UAMMD-structured. The system design also enables easy exchange of information between different batches, which can be used to implement algorithms that require multiple independent simulations, such as parallel tempering [282]. To employ the batching system in UAMMD-structured, we need to choose which particles belong to different batches. This categorization is done in the structure `section` (Code 6.25).

Code 6.25: Batching Example

```
state:
  labels: ["id", "position"]
  data:
    - [0, [1.6, 2.7, 3.3]]
    - [1, [2.5, -3.7, -1.9]]
    - [2, [-3.3, 1.0, 2.1]]
    - [3, [1.5, -1.1, 0.2]]
    - [4, [2.3, 1.5, 2.8]]
    - [5, [-1.5, 1.7, -2.1]]
    - [6, [-2.8, 1.3, 1.7]]
    - [7, [4.5, 1.3, 1.2]]
    # ...

topology:
  structure:
    labels: ["id", "type", "batchId"]
    data:
      - [0, "A", 0]
      - [1, "A", 0]
      - [2, "A", 0]
      - [3, "A", 0]
      - [4, "A", 1]
      - [5, "A", 1]
      - [6, "A", 1]
      - [7, "A", 1]
      # ...
  forceField:
    # ...
# ...
```

In this example (Code 6.25), alongside the type in the structure, an additional column named "batchId" is included. This "batchId" indicates the batch of each particle, integrating it into the hierarchical structure: particle \subset residue \subset chain \subset model \subset batch. When two particles have different IDs in this column (i.e., different "batchId"), UAMMD-structured handles them as belonging to separate batches. This **ensures that these particles do not interact with each other during simulations**. For some types of potentials, interaction parameters can be tailored based on the "batchId" (Code 6.26).

Code 6.26: Force Field Batching Example

```

topology:
  structure:
    labels: ["id", "type", "batchId"]
    data:
      - [0, "A", 0]
      - [1, "A", 0]
      - [2, "A", 1]
      - [3, "A", 1]
      # ...
  forceField:
    # ...
  nl:
    type: ["VerletConditionalListSet", "all"]
    parameters:
      cutOffVerletFactor: 1.2
  batched_LennardJones:
    type: ["NonBonded", "LennardJonesType2"]
    labels: ["name_i", "name_j", "epsilon", "sigma", "batchId"]
    data:
      - ["A", "A", 1.0, 1.5, 0]
      - ["A", "A", 3.0, 3.5, 1]
    parameters:
      condition: "all"
      cutOffFactor: 2.5
  # ...

```

Such a structure enables encapsulating a broad range of situations within a single batch. For interactions where parameters are associated with particle IDs, like bonds, setting different parameters for batches effectively means assigning different parameters for each listed interaction.

The implementation of batches in UAMMD-structured is software-based. Specifically, each component of UAMMD-structured, including interactions, simulation steps, and others, must handle different batches. This requirement is the primary limitation of the batching system of UAMMD-structured compared to hardware-based batching methods like MPS.

To effectively utilize batching, `UAMMD-structured` not only implements it at the code level but also integrates it into the `pyUAMMD` Python library. As we will discuss in the following section, `pyUAMMD` includes a mechanism to automatically combine different simulations into a single simulation.

Figure 6.18: `UAMMD-structured` batching is done by combining the different inputs from different simulations into a single input, i.e. into a single simulation. To ensure that particles belonging to different simulations do not interact with each other, a different `batchId` is associated with them.

The batching implementation in `UAMMD-structured` is composed of two integral parts: the primary functionality within `UAMMD-structured` itself, which ensures that particles from *different batches do not interact during simulation*, and the `pyUAMMD` library, which provides an easy combined input generation.

As mentioned previously, batching in `UAMMD-structured` operates through software, requiring each component to recognize and handle particles with distinct "batchId" values. However, this software-based approach limits the applicability of batching with certain interaction types and integrators. Particularly, batching is incompatible with components that involve hydrodynamic interactions and electrostatic interactions. This is because, for these particular features, `UAMMD-structured` mainly serves as a wrapper for `UAMMD`, which does not inherently support batching. Therefore, using batching with these incompatible components results in an error and consequent termination of the simulation.

Regarding interactions of `UAMMD-structured`, handling batching is relatively straightforward for bonds, many-body bonds and AFM, as long as two particles from different batches are not part of the same bond or belong to the same AFM. This condition is verified prior to the simulation start, and an error is issued if the condition is violated. For external interactions is similar, no additional considerations are needed, since this kind of interaction involves one particle only. *For short-range interactions, batching is implemented effectively due to conditioned Verlet lists.* This is done adding a simple check: if particles i and j belong to different batches then *they can not become neighbors*.

The approach to simulation steps in the presence of batches is slightly different. Since these steps are not crucial to the core simulation (being executed periodically), they are implemented by modifying the input. This task is handled by the `pyUAMMD` library, which organizes simulation steps by creating groups (Sec. 6.18) for each batch and applying the steps to different batches. While this method does not run simulation steps in parallel, it allows them to function effectively in simulations with multiple batches.

Through these procedures, a large number of simulations can be run simultaneously in `UAMMD-structured`. When smaller simulations are combined into batches, the total execution time remains essentially unchanged. This holds true until the combined simulation reaches a size that fully utilizes the resources of the GPU. Even at this point, a modest improvement in performance is achieved because certain operations, like kernel preparation [225, 241], occur concurrently for all simulations.

In scenarios where there are numerous small simulations to be executed, the most effective strategy involves distributing these simulations across available GPUs. This is done by dividing the total number of simulations by the number of GPUs, forming batches accordingly. Each batch is then assigned to a different GPU for parallel processing. This batching approach is especially beneficial when dealing with a large number of simulations, each of which is relatively small in size. This concept of batching is central to the **VLMP framework**, which will be explored in the subsequent chapter.

It is also worth noting that this approach fills a gap often overlooked by current simulation environments like GROMACS, LAMMPS, and OPENMM. These platforms tend to focus on simulating increasingly larger systems, sometimes neglecting the frequent need for multiple smaller simulations. Furthermore, as GPU technology continues to advance, so the definition of what constitutes a 'small' simulation is constantly expanding.

6.20 pyUAMMD

Manually writing input files can be tedious. To facilitate this task, pyUAMMD has been developed. It is a Python library that adds tools for easily working with UAMMD-structured input files. pyUAMMD includes a single class, `simulation`, which behaves like a dictionary where different sections and DataEntries of UAMMD-structured can be specified (Code 6.27).

Code 6.27: pyUAMMD Example

```
import pyUAMMD
sim = pyUAMMD.simulation()

sim["system"] = {}
...
sim["global"] = {}
...
sim["integrator"] = {}
...
sim["state"] = {}
sim["state"]["labels"] = ["id", "position", "direction"]
sim["state"]["data"] = []
for i in range(N):
    sim["state"]["data"].append([i, [0,0,0], [0,0,0,1.0]])

sim["topology"] = {}
sim["topology"]["structure"] = {}
sim["topology"]["structure"]["labels"] = ["id", "type"]
sim["topology"]["structure"]["data"] = []
for i in range(N):
    sim["topology"]["structure"]["data"].append([i, "A"])

sim["topology"]["forceField"] = {}
...
sim["simulationStep"] = {}
...

sim.write("simulation.json")
```

The `simulation` class has the `write(...)` method to write the dictionary content to a JSON file. Writing a dictionary to a JSON file is trivial in Python using the `json` library, but this is extremely slow. To address these restrictions, we have developed the **JFIO** (JSON Fast Input Output) library [283]. It uses `pybind11` [284] to create a wrapper with C++ functions of `nlohmann::json` [285], enabling rapid writing and reading of JSON files where simulation parameters are set.

`simulation` also includes the `append` method, which allows different simulations to be merged into one. This method is central to the implementation of batching. With `append`, we add the content of another simulation (the added simulation) to the current one (reference simulation). The `append` method has two modes:

- "modelId": In this mode, the added simulation is considered part of the same simulation. The result is configured so the number of batches does not increase. Contents of the added simulation (like particle IDs, group definitions, interaction parameters) are adjusted to make the resultant simulation viable. This method is useful for building complex simulations from simpler ones. For example, suppose we have two simulation files, `sim1.json` and `sim2.json`, each containing a different protein using the same model. We could create two `simulation` objects with `pyUAMMD` and then add them together. The resultant simulation would contain both proteins, and by adding an interaction potential between the them, it could be used to study their interaction.
- "batchId": Using this mode, the two simulations are joined into one, but each is associated with a different `batchId` (in addition to configuring the rest of the parameters to make the simulation viable). This is the simplest way to use `UAMMD-structured` batching and allows for incorporating a large number of simulations into a single large simulation to execute the sub-simulations concurrently.

So far, we have shown how to use `pyUAMMD` to create simulations with the intention of finalizing this procedure by executing the `write` method, which writes a `.json` file containing the simulation input. This file is then used to run the `UAMMDlauncher` binary, initiating the simulation. But `pyUAMMD` also allows direct execution of the simulation from Python with the `run` method (Code 6.28).

Code 6.28: `pyUAMMD` Run Example

```
import pyUAMMD
sim = pyUAMMD.simulation()

sim["system"] = {}
...

sim.run()
```

This method starts the simulation, yielding a result analogous to using the binary. This approach is intended to make `UAMMD-structured` more accessible for less advanced users who may not be comfortable using a **command line interface** CLI. This implementation is straightforward with `pybind11` [284]. Launching the simulation is fully functional and can be executed. It also serves to showcase the potential for integrating `UAMMD-structured` with `Python`. Future work aims to extend interoperability with `Python`, with the first objective being the ability to program simulation steps entirely in `Python`. This would allow users with basic `Python` knowledge to access simulation information in real-time to extract or process variables they consider to be relevant.

6.21 Extending UAMMD-structured

`UAMMD-structured` inherits its modular design from `UAMMD` [13, 232], which focuses on extensibility. In `UAMMD`, interfaces for *integrators*, *interactors*, and *particle data* allow users to implement new component types, ensuring these new elements work seamlessly with the existing code [13]. `UAMMD-structured`, as an extension of `UAMMD`, retains this capability for implementing extensions. However, `UAMMD-structured` further simplifies this process by integrating a set of tools that aid in adding specific components. These tools are consolidated within the `UAMMD-structured` Components Manager (USCM).

6.21.1 USCM

The `UAMMD-structured` Components Manager (USCM) is a key component of the system. One of its main roles is to automate the creation of files necessary for interoperability between the code and the input system. In a C++/CUDA program like `UAMMD-structured`, where input is directly linked to the initialization of certain objects, *it is essential to establish a relationship between specific input values and object types at compilation time*. This requirement often needs editing the code to add new features like potentials or simulation steps. USCM simplifies this process by generating the required files automatically:

```
USCM --generate
```

In addition to file generation, USCM serves as a management tool for all integrated components. It assists in organizing and monitoring all data and components within the system:

```
USCM --list data/components
```

A significant function of USCM is facilitating the addition of new components. It offers templates for specific component types to ease the integration of new elements. For instance, when adding a new bond type between two particles, a template can be created using:

```
USCM --create Interactor Bonds Bond2 BndTst
```

This command generates a file named "BndTst.cuh", indicating customizable aspects of the new bond. After modifying the template, it can be integrated into UAMMD-structured using USCM as follows:

```
USCM --add component Interactor Bonds Bond2 BndTst --file BndTst
.cuh
```

Consequently, after recompiling, the bond can be used by selecting the `DataEntry` of type ["Bond2","BndTst"]. This mechanism for adding new components to UAMMD-structured is applicable to most components, including the addition of new *units*, *types*, *fundamental* and ensembles for *global*, new types of *integrators*, potentials (like in the example) and *simulation steps*, and even new conditions for Verlet lists. USCM also provides an interface for adding new data types to particles and those that can be set via "State". This greatly simplifies the addition of new components to UAMMD-structured. Once added, these components are immediately usable from the input system. The detailed process and more examples for adding different component types can be found in the online documentation [235].

Chapter 7

VLMP: Virtual Lab Modeling Platform

An essential aspect of any simulation is the **construction of the input**. For instance, when simulating a protein, we need to incorporate information such as the protein structure (which could be contained into a PDB file we have to analyze), or in the case of DNA, the specific sequence of interest. From this initial information, a series of processes are applied to finally obtain a representation of the structure to be simulated along with the interactions that occur within it. *This process can often be complex.* Consider, for example, protein models discussed in Chapter 1, where determining native contacts requires an in-depth analysis of the structure of the protein [61], or DNA models like MADna, where parameters for different bonds (pairwise, angular, or dihedral) vary based on the sequence [32].

To simulate these systems, we need to implement algorithms for generating the input or use tools usually developed by authors for this purpose. However, imagine wanting to combine these models to study interactions between proteins and DNA. This task is not straightforward, it involves merging inputs (which may be in different formats) and adding interactions between them. This final step might even require modifying the code. In the case of `UAMMD-structured`, this would likely require programming in C/C++ CUDA, adding considerable complexity to the process and requiring increasingly specialized skills from the user.

To deal with such situations, we have developed the **Virtual Lab Modeling Platform** (VLMP), a tool that simplifies carrying out complex simulations and is specially designed for High-Performance Computing (**HPC**) environments. VLMP is implemented in `Python` which simplifies its use, especially when compared to the combination of C/C++ and CUDA that `UAMMD-structured` requires. A guide on how to obtain and install the code can be found in the online documentation [286].

VLMP understands a simulation as a **collection of blocks**, as if it were a **building game**. *These different blocks can be used to build various simulations.* Adding a new feature is akin to introducing a new block to the existing stack of available blocks.

In this chapter we will introduce VLMP, how it is designed and how to use its capabilities. But as an illustrative example we show how a set of simulations would be carried out using VLMP. In this simplified example (Code 7.1) we show how to set up a collection of VLMP simulations for a worm-like chain (WLC), a basic polymer model composed of interconnected beads [287].

This example (Code 7.1) shows the key features of VLMP. In the example, our aim is to perform a set of simulations, in particular we want to simulate the WLC for different values of the constant K_a , this constant regulates the stiffness of the angular bond between the different beads of the model. In VLMP we must build a list of simulations called **simulation pool**. *Each element of the simulation pool constitutes a single independent simulation.* Each simulation is represented by a dictionary, where each *component* fixes a different aspect of the simulation, the used units, the ensemble where the simulation take place, the model we use ... In this case, we add a "WLC" type model, where we set the number of particles and the constants of the bonds as parameters, in particular of the angular bond K_a . We also add an external force, which will stretch polymer. Finally we indicate that we want to save the trajectory every certain number of steps.

As can be seen we add to the *simulation pool* several simulations all of them similar but with different values varying for the parameter K_a . This *simulation pool* is then loaded into VLMP which splits it into different chunks, in this case each chunk contains two simulations. Finally the files are generated by calling the method `setUpSimulation`. At this point VLMP would have generated all the files to carry out the simulations, which would have been grouped in sets of two that can be executed concurrently. VLMP offers several choices for conducting the simulation, including the ability to execute simulations on HPC clusters.

7.1 Design

The central element of VLMP is the **component**. *These components are akin to the building blocks of a construction set.* By combining these blocks, various types of simulations can be configured. These simulations are then added to a *simulation pool*, which is ultimately processed and prepared for execution.

Code 7.1: VLMP example

```

import VLMP

L = 100 # Number of beads
Kb = 100.0 # Worm like chain bonds spring constant
Ka = [10.0,20.0,30.0,40.0,50.0,60.0] # Worm like chain angular
    bonds spring constants

simulationPool = []
for ka in Ka:
    simulationPool.append(
        {"system":[
            {"type":"simulationName","parameters":{
                "simulationName":"wlc_Ka_"+str(ka)}},
            {"type":"backup","parameters":{
                "backupIntervalStep":10000}}],
        "units":[{"type":"none"}],
        "types":[{"type":"basic"}],
        "ensemble":[
            {"type":"NVT","parameters":{
                "box":[200.0,200.0,200.0],"temperature":1.0}}],
        "integrators":[
            {"type":"BBK","parameters":{
                "timeStep":0.001,
                "frictionConstant":1.0,
                "integrationSteps":1000000}}],
        "models":[{"type":"WLC","parameters":{
            "N":L,"b":1.0,"Kb":Kb,"Ka":ka}}],
        "modelExtensions":[
            {"type":"constantForceBetweenCentersOfMass","parameters":{
                "force":1.0,
                "selection1":"WLC polymerIndex 1",
                "selection2":"WLC polymerIndex -1"}}],
        "simulationSteps":[
            {"type":"saveState","parameters":{
                "intervalStep":10000,
                "outputFilePath":"output",
                "outputFormat":"dcd"}}]}
    )

vlmp = VLMP.VLMP()
vlmp.loadSimulationPool(simulationPool)
vlmp.distributeSimulationPool("size",2)
vlmp.setUpSimulation("WLC")

```

7.1.1 Components

VLMP exploits the idea that any simulation, no matter how complex, can be broken down into a series of small interacting components. These *components* form the basis of the simulation and range from purely computational aspects like backup management to strictly physical elements such as the employed potentials. These *components* are versatile, capable of constructing more than one type of simulation. For example, if blocks add a model for a protein, one can construct a simulation for pulling experiments or create a pair of these proteins to study protein-protein interaction phenomena. VLMP provides a set of blocks that can be combined in numerous ways to create a wide variety of simulations.

Developing these blocks can be relatively complex, but once created, they can be reused in other scenarios. This makes the modular design of these *components* extremely beneficial for sharing and collaboration. The fact that VLMP is programmed in a high-level language like Python significantly reduces the cost of developing new *components*. For instance, one can use libraries such as NumPy [288] for system initialization or tools like BioPython [289] and MDAnalysis [290] for constructing coarse-grained models for proteins. The implementation of *components* in VLMP is structured using dictionaries. Each component is defined with up to three entries: two mandatory fields, "type" and "name", and an optional "parameters" field. The "type" field is essential as it specifies the nature of the component (Code 7.2).

Code 7.2: Component Example 1

```
{
  "name": "componentName"
  "type": "componentType",
  "parameters":{
    "param1": "...",
    "param2": 1234,
    "param3": {"A": [1,2,3], "B": [4,5,6]},
    ...
  }
}
```

Although the "name" field is mandatory, it can be omitted. *In such cases, the component assumes the "type" as its name.* This simplifies scenarios where the distinction between types and names is not critical. For example, in Code 7.3, the name of the component would be "componentType".

Code 7.3: Component Example 2

```
{
  "type": "componentType",
  "parameters": {
    "param1": "...",
    "param2": 1234,
    "param3": {"A": [1, 2, 3], "B": [4, 5, 6]},
    ...
  }
}
```

Each component added to a simulation must have an *unique* name to ensure proper identification and handling within VLMP . The "parameters" field, also structured as a dictionary, allows specification of the required data by the component to work properly (Code 7.4).

Code 7.4: Component Example 3

```
models: [{
  "type": "SOP",
  "parameters": {
    "PDB": "2CV5"
  }
}, {
  "type": "MADna",
  "parameters": {
    "sequence": "ATCAACGGCTGTCTAGCAGT"
  }
}]
```

7.1.2 Simulation

A simulation in VLMP is composed of various *components*. To specify a simulation, we list all the *components* we wish to use, categorized by their functions. VLMP has *nine* possible categories, each related to a different aspect of the simulation. Some categories are mandatory, while others are optional depending on the needs of the simulation. The available categories and the types of information they add to the simulation are the following:

- **System** (Mandatory): *Components* in the System category are used to set elements somewhat external to the simulation itself, like technical aspects including backup management or behavior in case of errors. *System* is the only category that contains a mandatory component for the simulation, known as "simulation-Name", which provides a unique alias for each simulation.
- **Units** (Mandatory): In the *Units* category, we select the unit system to be used. Choosing a unit system sets the value of certain physical constants like the Coulomb and Boltzmann constants. These constants are also accessible to other *components*, allowing them to be aware of the unit system and the value of physical constants. *Units* is unique in that it accepts only one component, as working with more than one unit system has no sense. An example of a *Units* type component is "none", where all relevant physical constants take a unit value.
- **Types** (Mandatory): The *Types* category indicates what information will be available for the particles. For example, using the "basic" component implies that particles have defined properties like mass, radius, and charge. This category also accepts only one component and is accessible to other *components*.
- **Ensembles** (Mandatory): The *Ensembles* category accepts a single component that sets the ensemble for the simulation, such as "NVT", indicating a constant number of particles, volume, and temperature. The chosen ensemble component is available to other *components*, informing them of the simulation box size, for example.
- **Models** (Mandatory): The *Models* category is central to VLMP . It specifies the different physical systems to be simulated, such as coarse-grained models of proteins, DNA, viruses, patchy particles, etc. Models are responsible for adding particles and interactions to the simulation. There is no maximum number of *components* in this category, the different models added will be combined together by VLMP .

- **Model Operations** (Optional): The *Model Operations* category, where *components* modify the positions of particles in the models, is optional. For instance, if a protein and a DNA strand are added, *components* in this category can adjust their positions to avoid overlap at the start of the simulation.
- **Model Extensions** (Optional): This category includes *components* that modify models without adding new particles. Examples include adding potentials for protein-DNA interactions or fixing the center of mass of a group of particles.
- **Integrators** (Mandatory): Integrators are responsible for the temporal evolution of the simulation. VLMP offers various integrators, from Verlet for NVE to NVT integrators like Langevin or Brownian.
- **Simulation Steps** (Optional): Using the above *components*, we specify the simulation we wish to conduct. However, none of the mentioned *components* perform any function to extract information from the simulation. This is achieved through *Simulation Step components*, which perform operations at certain intervals during the simulation. These operations can include writing particle positions to a file or measuring quantities like temperature or stress.

7.1.3 Simulation Pool

Just as *components* are combined to form a **simulation**, multiple simulations are merged to form a **simulation pool**. The *simulation pool* encompasses all the simulations to be conducted. Once the *simulation pool* is defined, VLMP distributes the simulations into *different sets*, named **simulation sets**, each of which can be run in parallel on a single GPU. This distribution process is highly customizable, allowing users to specify splitting criteria based on various factors such as the size of the simulations (determined by the number of particles), the specific *components* involved, or any other relevant parameters. For example, if we distribute the *simulation pool* according to some size, N , some particle number, we ensure that every *simulation set* has N particles at most. VLMP provides several built-in options for distributing simulations, but users can also incorporate their own.

Figure 7.2 illustrates the *simulation pool* and its distribution into *simulation sets*. The *simulation pool* contains all the individual simulations. These simulations are then partitioned into distinct *simulation sets*, each of which can be executed in parallel. Within each *simulation set*, the underlying simulations are run simultaneously on a single GPU.

Figure 7.1: The different *components* are merged to create a simulation

Figure 7.2: *Simulation pool* and its distribution into *simulation sets* for parallel execution. The *simulation pool* contains all the individual simulations, which are partitioned into *simulation sets*. Each *simulation set* can be executed in parallel. In this image in particular N simulations are distributed across M simulations sets.

In VLMP , the concept of a *simulation pool* is implemented using a simple Python list, where each element of the list represents an individual simulation. This list is then processed by VLMP , and the simulations are distributed into different groups based on the specified criteria.

7.2 Workflow

In this section, we list all the different steps we have to follow to run a set of simulations in VLMP . As previously mentioned, the process consists of four stages, which we will now describe in greater depth. These stages, from the building of simulations to their execution (Code 7.5), are:

1. **Simulation Pool Creation:** Initially, we create the *simulation pool*. This involves constructing various simulations using chosen *components*. Upon completion, we have a list of dictionaries, where each dictionary represents a simulation. Each dictionary contains entries for categories and a list of *components* used for each category.
2. **Simulation Pool Distribution:** After filling the *simulation pool*, we proceed to distribute it. The distribution process transforms the *simulation pool* from a list into a list of lists, with each sublist being a set of simulations (similar to a *simulation pool*). This distribution process can be repeated multiple times, and the result is always a list of lists of simulations. Each sublist is known as a *simulation set* and is the **unit executed on each GPU**.
3. **Files Generation:** With the different *simulation sets* prepared, we generate all necessary files and directories for the simulation. A folder with the session name (provided by the user) is created, containing the "VLMPsession.json" file. This file encapsulates all session information, necessary for executing the simulations and reconstructing all simulation files. Additionally, two subfolders are created within the main simulation folder: "simulationSets" for execution and "results" for examining the simulation post-completion. The "results" folder contains a separate folder for each simulation with all the output of the simulation upon completion.
4. **Execution:** VLMP can execute simulations locally (on the current computer) or in an HPC environment with various compute nodes. For execution, VLMP is used as an executable. This executable takes "VLMPsession.json" and parameters selecting and configuring the execution environment (local or HPC) as arguments.

Code 7.5: VLMP Workflow

```
import VLMP
...

simulationPool = []
# Populate simulation pool
for ...
    simulationPool.append(
        {"system": [...],
         "units": [...],
         "types": [...],
         "ensemble": [...],
         "integrators": [...],
         "models": [...],
         "modelExtensions": [...],
         "simulationSteps": [...]}
    )
...

vlmp = VLMP.VLMP()

vlmp.loadSimulationPool(simulationPool)
vlmp.distributeSimulationPool(...)
vlmp.setUpSimulation("SESSION_NAME")
```

In the following sections we will discuss in more detail the different aspects of each of these processes. First, we will discuss the *components* available to form a simulation. Subsequently we will see how to distribute the *simulation pool* and how the different folders and files are created. Finally we will discuss the different methods for running the simulations.

7.3 Components and Simulation in Detail

In this section, we will explore the different *components* of VLMP in detail, examining how to construct simulations and the properties and parameters of each component category.

Component Order: Both categories and *components* within VLMP are processed in order. *Components* of each category are indicated in a list. Lists are ordered data sets, and VLMP assumes this order, so the user can always assume that if one component appears after another in the list of a category, the previous *components* have been processed when the last one is being evaluated. This can be used in the construction of the simulation. For instance, if we first add a protein model, we can later add an interaction model and examine the previously added model to evaluate if the interaction model is compatible.

Figure 7.3: The order in which different categories are processed. A small box has been added to each category. This box indicates the information available when the current category is processed.

When constructing a simulation, the different categories are processed in order (Fig 7.3). Let us now examine each category in detail, following the order in which VLMP processes them.

1. **System:** As previously mentioned, *System components* handle more technical aspects of the simulation. The mandatory *System component* in VLMP is "simulationName," which must always be present as it names the simulation. An optional component is "backup," which, if added, performs a simulation backup at specified intervals. Here is an example of the System category with two components, the mandatory "simulationName" and "backup" (Code 7.6).

Code 7.6: System example

```
"system": [
  {"type": "simulationName", "parameters": {
    "simulationName": "exampleName"}},
  {"type": "backup", "parameters": {
    "backupIntervalStep": 1000, "backupFilePath": "backup"}}
]
```

This example shows how, besides the simulation name, a backup component is added. This component will perform a backup every 1000 steps and save it in the file named "backup". When this component is added, it not only enables backup at certain intervals but also allows for rebooting the simulation if an error occurs.

2. **Units:** In the *Units* category, we set the unit system for the simulation. Only one unit system can be set. Currently, VLMP has two available unit systems: "none" and "(Kcal/mol)/A" (section 6.6.2, code 7.7).

Code 7.7: Units Example

```
"units": [{"type": "KcalMol_A"}]
```

3. **Types:** In the "Types" category, we set the format for particle types. This means we fix the information available for each type. *We do not add the types themselves*; this is handled by the models. Currently, there are two options: "none", where no information is set, and "basic" (Code 7.8).

Code 7.8: Types Example

```
"types": [{"type": "basic", "parameters": {"mass": 1.0}}]
```

In this example, the "basic" component is added, allowing particle types to define three properties: mass, radius, and charge. By specifying `mass = 1.0`, it means that if not indicated when creating the type, the default mass will be 1.0. The types are created by the models. For example, if we use a coarse-grained protein model where each amino acid is represented by a bead, it is expected that the type "ARG" (corresponding to Arginine) will be defined, specifying parameters such as mass, radius, and charge. Model can expect some unit system (in this case, "(Kcal/mol)/A"), if the selected unit system is not compatible with the selected model, an error will be raised when processing the model. In summary, when selecting a type, we do not fix the types present in the simulation but their format. The model(s) we choose to use will add the types.

4. **Ensembles:** Only one component is allowed in this category, as having more than one ensemble does not make sense. Currently, VLMP has two available ensembles: "NVT" (Code 7.9) and "NVTlambda" (which is needed to perform Thermodynamic Integration, see Section 6.10).

Code 7.9: Ensemble Example

```
"ensemble": [{  
  "type": "NVT",  
  "parameters": {  
    "box": [100.0, 100.0, 100.0],  
    "temperature": 300.0}  
}]
```

The units of the box and temperature are those given by the selected units. For example, if we have chosen "(Kcal/mol)/A" units, then the box size will be interpreted in angstroms and the temperature in Kelvin. Once the ensemble is set, the parameters defined are accessible to all subsequent *components*. For example, if we set the NVT ensemble, the rest of the *components* will be able to access both the box size and the temperature.

5. **Models:** Models are one of the central elements in VLMP. These *components* add particles to the simulation and can also include potentials and new particle types.

VLMP offers a wide range of models, from simple polymer models like WLC to coarse-grained models for large protein complexes like viruses (see online documentation [286] for a complete list).

Let us take the MADna model (section 1.1.2) for coarse-grained DNA as an example (Code 7.10).

Code 7.10: Model Example 1

```
"models": [{
  "name": "dna",
  "type": "MADna",
  "parameters": {
    "sequence": "GATACA",
    "debyeLength": debyeLength}
}]
```

As observed, this component takes the data necessary to generate the particles and the required potentials of the MADna model, such as the sequence or Debye length. Let us check what is going on underneath. The model defines the types. In this case, it adds the types of the beads in the model. If the "basic" type is selected, the model will add the corresponding information for each bead, such as mass, radius, and charge. Subsequently, it will add the particles, setting their position and defining the topology. Each particle is assigned a type and structural information such as the base pair to which it belongs or the strand. Once this is done, the model will add the potentials. In this case, bonds for pairs, angular and dihedral potentials, and non-bonded interactions like the WCA or Debye-Huckel interaction. All this information is necessary to conduct the simulation with the model.

An important feature of models is that they can **define selections**. Selections can be used by other categories of *components* (`modelOperations`, `modelExtensions`, or `simulationStep`) to *apply transformations or measure properties of certain particle groups*. The MADna model defines several selections. For example, one of them is the "basePairIndex" selection that allows selecting base pairs according to their pair indices. For instance, the "basePairIndex 2" will be the particles belonging to the second base pair.

The different models can be combined. We can even place the same model several times (Code 7.11).

In this case, we simulate two DNA sequences. By adding a potential for their interaction, we could study DNA-DNA interaction phenomena.

VLMP incorporates a large number of models. In particular, it incorporates the models described in the first part of this thesis. In addition to models such as the SBCG (section 2), patchy particles models (section 3) and vesicle models

Code 7.11: Model Example 2

```

"models": [
  { "name": "dna1",
    "type": "MADna",
    "parameters": {
      "sequence": "GATACA",
      "debyeLength": debyeLength}
  },
  { "name": "dna2",
    "type": "MADna",
    "parameters": {
      "sequence": "ACATAG",
      "debyeLength": debyeLength}
  }
]

```

(section 4), VLMP incorporates a set of alpha carbon (C_α) resolution models for proteins, DNA and lipids. This makes VLMP a very useful tool for simulating these types of biological systems. These models have a similar scale and can be combined with each other to build complex biological structures. Currently VLMP has the following C_α resolution models available:

- **Proteins:**
 - *Clementi*: [22, 87]
 - *Karanicolas-Brooks*: [61, 90]
 - *SOP*: [65]
- **DNA:**
 - *MADna*: [32]
- **Lipids:**
 - *La Torre*: [31]

The different interaction models described in the first part of the thesis are also available in VLMP. The interaction models are not added in this category. They belong to the `modelExtensions` category, this is done to allow for greater freedom in the building of simulations. We can set one model for the internal representation of proteins, DNA and lipids and then use another one for the interaction between these entities.

6. **Model Operations:** Model operations are processed after the models are added. These *components* apply transformations to the coordinates of the particles. VLMP has both simple transformations, like rotation or fixing the position

of the particle, and more complex ones, such as distributing models within a volume (Code 7.12)

Code 7.12: Model Operations

```
"modelOperations": [{
  "type": "rotation",
  "parameters": {
    "axis": [1.0, 0.0, 0.0],
    "angle": 3.14,
    "selection": "all"}}, {
  "type": "distributeRandomly",
  "parameters": {
    "mode": {
      "sphere": {
        "radius": 40.0,
        "center": [0.0, 0.0, 0.0]
      }
    },
    "avoidClashes": True,
    "selection": "all"}}
]
```

As seen, in most cases, model operations require specifying a selection of particles to apply them. In the above example, the keyword "all" is used, which selects all particles added to the simulation. As mentioned, models can also define selections (Code 7.13).

Code 7.13: Model Operations Selection

```
"modelOperations": [{
  "type": "setCenterOfMassPosition",
  "parameters": {
    "position": [0.0, 0.0, 0.0],
    "selection": "dna basePairIndex 2"}}
]
```

In this case, we would fix the position of the center of mass formed by the particles of the model named "dna" that belong to the second base pair. Model operations can be combined, and like the rest of the *components*, their processing order is ensured.

7. Model Extensions:

Model extensions modify models, but unlike model operations, they do not alter the position of the particles; rather, they add interactions. An example of this type of interactions could be external potentials. Imagine that we have added a set of models as for example the models needed to simulate a protein virus. As we add it this virus will be in a vacuum but it is likely that we want to add a surface. This can be done by means of a model extension (Code 7.14).

Code 7.14: Surface Example

```
"modelExtensions": [{  
  "type": "surface",  
  "parameters": {  
    "epsilon": 1.0,  
    "sigma": 1.0,  
    "surfacePosition": 0.0,  
    "selection": "all"}  
}]
```

Other external potentials that can be added are the many body bonds described in section 6.15. By adding these types of interactions we can perform pulling experiments. By combining this extension with a protein model or a DNA model we can simulate what would be an optical tweezers experiment (Code 7.15).

Code 7.15: Force Torque Example

```
"modelExtensions": [{  
  "type": "constantForceBetweenCentersOfMass",  
  "parameters": {  
    "force": 150.0,  
    "selection1": "dna basePairIndex 2",  
    "selection2": "dna basePairIndex -2"  
  }  
}]
```

Similar to how it happens with model operations, when we add model extensions, we can also (sometimes it is mandatory, depending on the extension) add a selection so that the extension only applies to a subset of the particles. In the previous example, we applied a constant force between the centers of mass of two sets of particles. Therefore, the model extension requires declaring two sets. This is done by indicating two selections, in both of which we select the model named "dna" and the selection type called "basePairIndex". In one case, we indicate the

base pair 2, and in the other, the -2. This means that the sets will be composed of the particles that make up the second-to-last base pair of the model called "dna" and another set with the penultimate base pair. It is important to mention that for this to not produce an error, it is necessary to effectively add a model called "dna" which allows a selection called "basePairIndex". In other words, we need the model to define this selection and take the appropriate parameters. *If this is not done, the VLMP will emit an error and terminate the execution.*

Another type of extension would be those that add interaction models among the entities in the simulation. In particular, VLMP offers models for interactions: protein-protein, DNA-protein, and protein-lipids for protein, DNA, and lipid models with C_α resolution. VLMP implements the following models:

- **Protein-Protein:**
 - *Kim-Hummer*: [35]
 - *Ravikumar*: [146]
- **Protein-DNA:**
 - *Zhang*: [36]
- **Protein-Lipids:**
 - *La Torre*: [37, 132]

These models are designed to be used with C_α resolution models. They can be combined with various models for proteins, DNA, and lipids with C_α resolution available in VLMP. By combining models for structures with those for interactions, we can simulate a wide variety of biological aggregates.

8. **Integrators** are crucial components in VLMP, responsible for the temporal evolution of the system. VLMP offers a large number of integrators. Particularly for simulating coarse-grained systems with C_α resolution models, it is common to use Langevin integrators, specifically, VLMP incorporates the BBK integrator. The Brownian integrator for rigid bodies [276] can also be used, which is necessary for employing the potentials for lipids described in Chapter 4 or the coarse-grained models presented in Chapter 1. Along with these potentials, VLMP also has many potentials that add hydrodynamic interactions, such as BDHI, fluctuating hydrodynamics, etc. (for a complete list of all available integrators, the online documentation in can be consulted). The following example shows how we can add a BBK-type Langevin integrator (Code 7.16).

Code 7.16: Integrator Example

```
"integrators": [{
  "type": "BBK",
  "parameters": {
    "timeStep": 0.02,
    "frictionConstant": 1.0,
    "integrationSteps": 1000000}
  }
],
```

Multiple integrators can be added to a single simulation. They will activate sequentially, following their order in the category list. This feature is particularly useful for processes like thermalization or avoiding steric clashes at the beginning of a simulation.

9. **Simulation Steps** are a diverse class of *components*. By adding simulation steps, we introduce specific operations or calculations to be performed at intervals during the simulation. Through this type of operation, we can perform a wide variety of calculations, such as measuring temperature or pressure. We can also calculate properties of the particles like stress or the forces acting on them. One of the most important uses is to save the state of the simulation at certain intervals. This can be done using the "saveState" component, where we can choose from several formats for the data output (Code 7.17).

Code 7.17: Simulation Step Example

```
"simulationSteps": [{
  "type": "saveState",
  "parameters": {
    "intervalStep": 10000,
    "outputFilePath": "output",
    "outputFormat": "sp"}
  }
]
```

The complete list of available simulation steps, as well as their parameters, can be consulted in the online documentation [286].

Each mentioned category has a set of available *components*. VLMP allows adding new *components* easily; when adding a component, what we need to do is indicate how it contributes to the construction of the input. VLMP manages and combines the different *components*. A detailed description of the process, as well as a collection of examples, can be found in the online documentation [286].

Selections

Selections are a highly useful feature of VLMP. As mentioned, a *model* can declare a *series of selections*, meaning each model understands certain keywords that return a list of IDs, pairs of IDs, etc. These selections can be employed in other *components* to target specific particles. The syntax for defining selections is as follows: Firstly, we specify the name of the model to which we are referring as "`modelName`", secondly the name of the selection we wish to use "`selectionName`", and finally the parameters for that selection "`p1 p2 p3...`". Thus, the format would be "`modelName selectionName p1 p2 ...`". If the model does not exist or the specified selection or parameters are incorrect, an error will be issued. All selections can be negated using the "`not`" operator, meaning we can write "`modelName not selectionName p1 p2 ...`" in such a way that the selection will be all those particles of the model "`modelName`" that do not belong to the selection "`modelName selectionName p1 p2 ...`". Finally, it is also possible to combine simple selections using the logical operators "`and`" and "`or`", and the use of parentheses. For example, we could write "`modelName1 selectionName1 p1_1 p1_2 ... or modelName2 selectionName2 p2_1 p2_2 ...`" thus obtaining a selection that contains particles from two different models.

Selections are declared by the models and can be employed by `modelOperations`, `modelExtensions`, `simulationSteps`. To know which selections each model incorporates, we must consult the documentation of that model.

7.4 Simulation Pool and Pool Distribution in Detail

Once we have set up the **simulation pool**, meaning we have added all the simulations we wish to carry out, the next step is to distribute the *simulation pool*. By distributing the simulation, we mean dividing this *simulation pool* into smaller pieces in order to maximize performance, which is generally achieved by running each of the different pieces of the *simulation pool* in parallel. Each piece into which the *simulation pool* is divided must contain at least one simulation and has no maximum limit. Each of these pieces is called a **simulation set**.

There are different criteria for distributing the *simulation pool*, and which one to use depends on the type of simulation and what the user needs. These are the different criteria currently implemented:

- *none*: All simulations from the *simulation pool* are allocated to a single *simulation set*.
- *one*: Each *simulation set* contains one simulation.
- *upperLimit*: The simulations are distributed in such a way that in all *simulation sets* a certain quantity is not exceeded. Currently, only a quantity can be specified as a limit, which is the number of particles. Therefore, through this criterion, we can ensure that no *simulation set* exceeds the indicated number of particles.

```

...
vlmp.loadSimulationPool(simulationPool)
vlmp.distributeSimulationPool(
    "upperLimit", "numberOfParticles", 20000
)
...

```

In the example the simulations are grouped in the *simulationSets* ensuring that no *simulation set* has more than $2 \cdot 10^4$ particles.

- *size*: Using *size*, we indicate the number of simulations for each *simulation set* directly. For example:

```

...
vlmp.loadSimulationPool(simulationPool)
vlmp.distributeSimulationPool("size", 100)
...

```

In this case, the simulations from the *simulation pool* are distributed sequentially until each *simulation set* contains 100 simulations. When a simulation set is full, another one is created, and simulations are added until this limit is reached.

- *property*: A certain property of the simulation is indicated by its path in the input. Then the simulations are grouped in such a way that each *simulation set* has the same value of that property which is different in the rest of *simulation sets*.

```
...
vtmp.loadSimulationPool(simulationPool)
vtmp.distributeSimulationPool(
    "property",["topology","forceField","bond","parameter","K"]
)
...
```

In the example the simulations are grouped into *simulation sets* ensuring that all simulations belonging to the same *simulation set* have the same value for "K", a parameter for the interaction "bonds".

The distribution of the *simulation pool* can be carried out several times. In other words, we can first separate the *simulation pool* according to one criterion into different *simulation sets* and subsequently apply another criterion so that each *simulation set* is subdivided according to this new criterion. This process can be applied an arbitrary number of times (Code 7.18).

Code 7.18: Distribute Simulation Pool

```
...
vtmp.loadSimulationPool(simulationPool)
vtmp.distributeSimulationPool(
    "upperLimit","numberOfParticles",20000
)
vtmp.distributeSimulationPool("size",10)
...
```

Once the *simulation pool* is distributed, we can perform the last step, **set up** the simulation. When we execute this last step, all the files required to carry out the simulation will be generated (Code 7.19).

Code 7.19: Set Up Simulation Pool

```
import VLMP
...

vtmp = VLMP.VLMP()
...
vtmp.setUpSimulation("SESSION_NAME")
```

The generated files are organized in the following way (Fig. 7.4). A folder with the name specified in the `setUpSimulation` method call ("`SESSION_NAME`" in the example) will be created. Inside, we can find three elements:

- `VLMPsession.json`: This file contains all the necessary information to carry out the simulations, how the files are distributed, and also keeps a record of the *simulation pool*, i.e., the existing simulations and the selected *components*.
- `simulationSets`: This folder contains all the *simulation sets* organised into folders named `simulationSet_0`, `simulationSet_1`, ... Each contains a `simulationSet_N.json` file (where N is the particular index of the *simulation set*) in the format described in Section 6.3, i.e., it is a **UAMMD-structured** input. It contains all the simulations in the set, and determines how to carry them out in parallel. The set folder contains a folder for each simulation in the set to store the corresponding results.
- `results`: This folder contains the simulation results, and it was added to facilitate access to the data. It is made up of *symbolic links* to the simulation folders in each set. Each *symbolic link* is named as the simulation that contains (as specified in the "`system`" component) for easy identification.

7.5 VLMP Execution

Once we have generated all the files required to carry out the simulations, the last step is to actually **execute the simulation**. For this, VLMP has two options: a **local** one, intended to be executed on personal computers, and another for **HPC clusters**, particularly those using **Slurm** as manager (which is probably the most popular option). The process in both is similar, but the parameters vary. In both cases, we must execute the VLMP module through Python, i.e., `python -m VLMP`, and pass the "`VLMPsession.json`" file as an argument using the `--session` parameter. In other words, we must execute `python -m VLMP --session VLMPsession.json` (Note that the file can be named differently and can be indicated using its path). The rest of the options will specify what type of simulation to execute and how it will be carried out. Once the execution is finished, the results can be inspected in their respective folders (see the previous section).

Figure 7.4: Example of the files and folders structure created by VLMP. In this example, we consider a VLMP session containing N simulations. These simulations are distributed across M simulation sets (Sec. 7.4). When we execute the `setUpSimulation` method, a folder is created with the given session name ("Session Name" in the figure) containing everything necessary to carry out the simulations. Within this folder, the "VLMPsession.json" file is created. This file contains all the information VLMP needs to initiate the simulations, as well as the selected options for creating the *simulation pool*. At the same time, the "results" and "simulationSets" folders are created. The "simulationSets" folder contains a folder for each of the M simulation sets. In each of these folders, we find a "simSet_...json" file, written in UAMMD-structured input format, containing the necessary information to execute the simulations belonging to the corresponding *simulation set*. Additionally, within each *simulation set* folder, a folder is created for each simulation present in that *simulation set*. The configuration of "simSet_...json" ensures that the results of each simulation, the output of the different *simulation steps*, are stored in their corresponding folder. For example, "simName_0" belongs to "simSet_0", so when we execute the simulation given by "simSet_0.json", the *simulation steps* associated with this simulation will generate the output files in the "simName_0" folder. Finally, to facilitate access to the simulation results, the "results" folder is created. This folder contains a set of *symbolic links* for quick access to the results of a particular simulation (represented by blue arrows in the figure).

7.5.1 Local Execution

When executing in local mode, the simulations can employ the **visible GPUs**. To carry out this type of execution, we must add the `--local` parameter and the `--gpu` parameter, through which we indicate the GPUs (using their ID) that we want to employ. For example:

```
python -m VLMP --session VLMPsession.json --local --gpu 0,1
```

When VLMP is executed in this mode, the different *simulation sets* (these elements, as we recall, can be executed in parallel) are distributed among the different GPUs. **VLMP has its own job queue manager** that is responsible for executing all the *simulation sets*. The *simulation sets* are executed sequentially on each GPU (i.e., two are never sent to the same GPU at the same time). The queue manager is responsible for initiating the remainder simulations when a GPU becomes available.

7.5.2 HPC Cluster

VLMP has an option to execute the simulation in an **HPC environment**. In particular, it includes the option to execute the simulations using the *popular Slurm queue manager*:

```
python -m VLMP --session VLMPsession.json --slurm [...]
```

This option adds the simulations to the queue manager. To do this, we must add the `--slurm` option. When executed in this mode, we can add a wide variety of options to select the nodes where to send the calculations, the modules which must be loaded, etc. (the complete list can be consulted in [286]).

7.6 VLMP Experiments

VLMP has a higher layer of abstraction, the **experiments**. Sometimes, certain types of simulations have elements in common. To understand this, let us present an example, the *simulation of an AFM indentation*. To construct an AFM simulation with VLMP, we must add several **common elements** such as a surface, the AFM tip, and the interaction between the AFM tip and the sample, but these types of elements are common in all simulations of this kind. Among simulations, what changes is the sample. With this idea in mind, we can construct certain procedures in such a way that when we

want to simulate an AFM, we only need to indicate the specific parameters of the sample. These types of generalizations are what motivate the experiments. Currently, there are two experiments available in VLMP , but these can be easily increased.

- **High throughput AFM:** We can indicate the parameters of the sample, and the rest of the AFM elements (as well as the simulation steps used for the measurements) are added automatically. Many of the parameters can be indicated not with a single value but as a list. Each element of the list creates an additional simulation that can be executed in parallel, thus allowing us to easily construct AFM simulations with different samples in parallel.
- **Surface Umbrella Sampling:** To determine the free energy of interaction between a sample and a surface, we can perform a technique known as umbrella sampling [291–293]. The procedure requires applying a series of harmonic potentials that restrict the position of the sample at different heights. Subsequently, by applying the WHAM algorithm, we can calculate the effective free energy potential [291]. This procedure is a key element in a project based on the simulation of the interaction between viruses and surfaces, and it is described in more detail in section 10.2.5. In VLMP , there is an experiment where we can indicate the sample, and it automatically makes copies of the sample, places them in the appropriate initial position, and adds the harmonic potential.

As we also know the structure of the resulting files when we perform an experiment, we can use this to encapsulate their analyses as well. Each experiment, in addition to the functions to carry out the simulation, also has a series of functions to analyze the results. For example, in the case of AFM, it processes the indentation curves, and in the case of umbrella sampling, it applies WHAM to the simulation results, allowing the calculation of the effective potential. A detailed description of the experiments, as well as the available parameters, can be found in the online documentation [286].

7.7 Backend

Currently, all the execution of VLMP code is performed using `UAMMD-structured`. In other words, VLMP constructs the input, and `UAMMD-structured` executes it. However, this does not necessarily have to be the case. VLMP is, in principle, **agnostic with respect to the execution**. VLMP essentially provides a series of tools to combine the *components*, which are relatively simple elements, to create complex simulations. The generated input is managed using `pyUAMMD` (section 6.20), but although it may seem counterintuitive due to its name, `pyUAMMD`, in terms of input management, is also agnostic with respect to `UAMMD-structured`.

In this way, we can understand VLMP as a tool for constructing input for simulations. Once the input is constructed, `pyUAMMD` stores it in the `UAMMD-structured` format (section 6.3). This format is easily translatable to other formats such as the one used by Gromacs [226] or Charmm [125]. Currently, `pyUAMMD` does not have this capability, but implementing it is feasible. Doing so, *VLMP would become a much more far-reaching tool since it could be used for creating input for multiple simulation software applications.*

Chapter 8

Virtual-Experiments Web Interface

While UAMMD , UAMMD-structured , and VLMP have each simplified the process of conducting simulations within their respective domains, there remain certain challenges for **less experienced users**. For instance, using VLMP to build simulations still requires a basic knowledge of Python. If working locally, the user must be capable of compiling UAMMD-structured and properly configuring CUDA. On the other hand, if working in an HPC (High-Performance Computing) cluster environment, familiarity with such systems is essential for submitting jobs and understanding configurations, including the number of GPUs, MPS (Multi-Process Service), and other related aspects.

Beyond these technical considerations, there are also theoretical limitations. Often, researchers who might be interested in the outcomes of certain simulations are not well-versed in the fundamental elements of these processes. This lack of familiarity raises numerous questions, such as understanding the integration time step, configuring the simulation box, or applying potentials for umbrella sampling. This limitation restricts not only the usage of these tools by such researchers but also their overall impact on the wider community. It is not uncommon for the development of physical models or specialized software to involve significant effort. All too often, these efforts are dedicated to a specific problem, after which the resulting tools are set aside and potentially forgotten. *This practice is not only tremendously inefficient but also counterproductive.*

To address these issues, we have developed **Vexperiments** , a web platform designed to bridge the gap between the work of theoretical/computational researchers and the broader community. **Vexperiments** features a straightforward interface, minimizing technical details as much as possible.

This concept has been previously implemented, particularly in the field of quantum mechanics, with applications in material development and pharmaceuticals. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no equivalent platform for reproducing experiments like AFM, Optical Tweezers (OT) or Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM).

8.1 Design

Vexperiments can be initially conceptualized as a “**marketplace**” where the commodities on offer are specific scientific simulations or calculations tailored for particular problems.

To illustrate, let us consider an experiment involving QCM. This experiment simulates a protein attached through an Intrinsically Disordered Protein (IDP) linker to a substrate. This model has been developed by a group of researchers, which we will refer to as the theoretical group, G_{theo} . Concurrently, there is another group of experimental researchers who are interested in conducting such simulations, named the experimental group, G_{exp} . The aim of **Vexperiments** is not only to connect these two groups but also to manage the computational tasks involved.

Let us first look at the problem from the perspective of G_{theo} . Generally, to carry out calculations, G_{theo} would have developed software that, through specific input, customizes and conducts the calculations for a particular system. **Vexperiments** allows for the construction of this input through the programming of a simple JavaScript code. This code comprises the input that G_{theo} wishes to expose to the users. **Vexperiments** manages this input and sends it off. The JavaScript code creates a user-friendly graphical interface for input entry. In this interface, all advanced parameters can be omitted, exposing only those that are relevant for the users conducting the calculations. In our QCM example, this could include the PDB of the protein, the linker sequence, and QCM parameters like its frequency or selected harmonic.

Figure 8.1: A schematic representation of the **Vexperiments** interface showcasing user input fields for a QCM simulation.

This interface generates an input file that is transmitted over the network to the computation server. On this server, the calculations or simulations are carried out and the results processed.

In addition, the theoretical group G_{theo} is also responsible for writing an HTML file that contains a description of the experiment or calculation to be performed.

From the perspective of the experimental group G_{exp} , upon entering the **Vexperiments** website, a series of icons representing various available experiments will be displayed (Fig. 8.1). Among these, the Protein QCM experiment can be found. Selecting this icon will open a panel displaying the HTML description provided by G_{theo} . This panel also shows a list of similar past submissions, indicating their current status such as 'completed', 'in progress', etc. To initiate a new submission, G_{exp} interacts with a corresponding element, such as a 'start task' button (Fig. 8.1). This action opens a web page utilizing the JavaScript interface created by G_{theo} , where G_{exp} fills in the required fields and starts the task. This process results in the input being processed in the interface and encapsulated into a file, which is then sent to computation service of G_{theo} .

The execution time for the task can vary. Once completed, the data is analyzed and a decision is made on what information should be displayed. In the case of the QCM, this could involve showing frequency and dissipation over time. This information is stored on the server. G_{theo} must also add JavaScript code that will take these data as input and visually represent them.

Figure 8.2: An illustration of the data visualization interface in **Vexperiments**, showing the analyzed results of a QCM experiment.

Once a calculation/simulation is complete, G_{exp} can visit the presentation window of the experiment, where all conducted experiments are listed. The completed experiment can be selected to display the analyzed results (Fig. 8.2). At this stage, the data is retrieved from the server and visualized using the code provided by G_{theo} .

This setup creates a user-friendly environment that enables G_{exp} to easily access and interpret the results of their computational experiments.

This section describes the general functionality of **Vexperiments** from the perspective of the users. In summary, users can interact with **Vexperiments** in two main ways: by adding experiments or by using them.

When an experiment is added, it is by default visible to all users. However, this can be configured to restrict access to specific users only. This feature opens up the possibility for **Vexperiments** to become a meeting point for researchers.

Consider a scenario where the groups G_{exp} and G_{theo} wish to collaborate. G_{exp} requires the collaboration of G_{theo} for conducting certain simulations or developing a model for data interpretation. G_{theo} can develop these tools and make them available to G_{exp} through **Vexperiments**. Initially, both groups might not want their ongoing research to be public. In this case, G_{theo} can add various calculations so that they are available only to the members currently involved in the research.

This turns **Vexperiments** into a tool not just for sharing finished simulations or models, but it can also transform the platform into a highly useful tool for conducting collaborative research projects.

Each job carried out on **Vexperiments** runs on a computation server. These servers can be easily deployed. Once set up, they can be registered on **Vexperiments** and associated with an experiment and a user, creating a trio (user, experiment, computation server). This means that launching a calculation does not require large infrastructure; a user can set up a computation server, register it, and assign it to another user for their exclusive use. This facilitates personal interaction between users, enhancing the collaborative and dynamic nature of the platform.

8.2 Web Architecture

The **Vexperiments** web application is structured around multiple interconnected components, each playing a specific role in the overall ecosystem of the application. The efficiency and effectiveness of **Vexperiments** hinge on the coordination and synergistic operation of these components, as illustrated in Figure 8.3. This segmented architecture offers several advantages, such as greater scalability, flexibility in resource management, and effective component isolation. In the figure, each element within a dotted box runs in the same instance, while elements in solid black-bordered boxes represent independent servers.

Figure 8.3: This diagram shows the key components of `Vexperiments`. Each independent entity is represented by a rectangle with continuous borders; these entities can exchange information through different communication protocols. The dotted lines represent different computers where these entities are deployed. The "Backend" server, "Job server", and "Database" currently share the same computer, but they could be distributed across different computers by updating the communication protocols.

- **Database:** Centralizes the storage of essential data such as user records, experiments, associations between users and experiments, and the status of jobs. It logs the results of calculations and simulations, focusing on processed data like graphs and numerical values. Massive simulation data are stored on dedicated compute servers. Currently, the database uses SQLite and shares an instance with the Backend and Job Server, but it could be migrated to a separate instance in the future to improve scalability and performance.
- **Frontend:** Responsible for delivering HTML code to the user, who accesses the graphical interface of `Vexperiments` through their browser. Developed in JavaScript, the frontend employs the React library and Node.js tools.
- **Backend:** This server acts as a bridge between the frontend and the database, processing frontend requests through a REST API built with Django in Python.
- **Job Server:** Manages and distributes computing jobs, handling the routing of jobs to the appropriate compute servers. This server also oversees job creation and deletion, as well as updating their status, interacting directly with the database and other servers through sockets and the TCP/IP protocol. It is programmed entirely in Python, using the socket library.

- **Compute Servers:** These are the pillars of task and calculation execution. They can be deployed on different machines and configurations, each with a unique identifier. They communicate with the Job Server to receive instructions and send updates on job progress and status.

In terms of security, all socket connections between the various system components are encrypted end-to-end using the Diffie-Hellman key exchange method [294]. This ensures secure data transmission and protects against unauthorized interception or manipulation attempts.

To demonstrate the functionality of *Vexperiments*, use cases will be presented that include accessing and manipulating data in the database, the lifecycle of jobs from creation to deletion, and the updating and monitoring of job statuses in real time.

8.2.1 Job Result Analysis

Once a simulation or calculation is completed, the results are processed, analyzed, and stored in the database (this process is described in section 8.2.3). The user can then request these results from the web interface. The process by which this data is displayed to the user is illustrated in Figure 8.4.

Figure 8.4: Sequence diagram illustrating the process of retrieving and displaying job results to the user in *Vexperiments*.

The process is as follows:

- (1): First, the user requests the results by interacting with the frontend (the web interface).
- (2): The frontend generates a request that is sent to the backend server. The backend server analyzes the requested information and verifies that the job has

indeed finished and that the requesting user has the correct permissions. If the checks are satisfactory, it makes a request to the database; otherwise, it returns an error message to the frontend via channel (5), which is displayed to the user.

(3),(4): If the request is validated, the data is retrieved from the database and returned to the backend server. If for some reason the information cannot be found in the database or is corrupted, an error message is generated and sent back to the backend, which in turn forwards it to the frontend to be displayed to the user.

(5),(6): The information is returned to the frontend. The frontend processes the received data and prepares its representation based on the type of experiment, i.e., it prepares the graphs, tables, etc., for display.

8.2.2 Job Creation and Deletion

Creating and deleting jobs are central processes in *Vexperiments*. These procedures allow users to initiate and manage the calculations they wish to perform. The processes for creating and deleting a job are similar and involve communication between various elements of *Vexperiments*, as illustrated in Figure 8.5.

Figure 8.5: Sequence diagram illustrating the process of creating and deleting jobs in *Vexperiments*, involving communication between the frontend, backend, job server, database, and compute servers.

The job creation and deletion processes can be described as follows:

(1),(2) The user initiates a job creation or deletion request through the frontend, which sends the request to the backend server.

(3),(4) The backend server performs a check with the database. For job creation, it verifies that the job has not been previously created and that the requesting user has the necessary permissions. For job deletion, it checks that the job exists and that the user has the appropriate permissions to delete it. If any of these checks fail, an error message is generated and displayed to the user.

(5) If the database check is successful, the backend server sends the request to the job server.

(6) The job server is responsible for routing the connection. It analyzes the job and user information to determine which compute server should handle the job creation or deletion. If the designated compute server is unavailable, an error is emitted. Otherwise, the job server sends the necessary information to the compute server to start the job or delete it.

(7),(8) The compute server carries out the requested operation. For job creation, the sent files are used to generate the input for the simulation or job. This approach is used to avoid transferring large amounts of data across the network, which can be slower. Once the input is generated, the calculation begins. For job deletion, if the job is currently running, the calculation is stopped, and all generated files are deleted. In both cases, the compute server sends a response back to the job server. If a job has been successfully created, it is registered in the database. If a job has been deleted, it is removed from the database.

8.2.3 Job State Update

In addition to user-initiated processes, **Vexperiments** also performs internal processes that involve various elements of the infrastructure. These processes are carried out automatically, without requiring user action. One such process is the updating of the state of a job, which is illustrated in Figure 8.6. The job state update process occurs at a configurable time interval and consists of the following steps:

(1) At the specified interval, the compute server examines the states of the various jobs that are either running or queued. If any of these jobs have changed state, such as transitioning from queued to running or from running to finished, the compute server sends the updated state information to the job server.

(2) The job server receives the new state information and updates the corresponding value in the database. This ensures that when a user checks the status of a job, the most up-to-date state is displayed.

Figure 8.6: Sequence diagram illustrating the automatic process of updating job states in `Vexperiments`, involving communication between the compute server and the job server, which updates the database.

8.3 Current Implementation

As mentioned, it is not necessary to use `UAMMD-structured` and `VLMP` through the `Vexperiments` web interface, but both tools provide a simple interface for it. To demonstrate a real application that showcases the entire process, from selecting the experiment to conducting the simulation and processing the data, we will present the following example. This example involves the simulation of a Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM) experiment. In this experiment, we study how a sample modifies the vibration of the balance. Simulating this process requires various tools ranging from molecular dynamics to hydrodynamics [295]. In particular, this example carries out a simulation of the type of experiments conducted by the group headed by Marisela Velez, where the QCM is used to study the polymerization process of the FtsZ protein (this protein is described in more detail in section 13.2). The protein consists of two sections: a globular one and another, the linker, without structure.

To carry out the simulation, we proceed as follows. The QCM measurements involve calculating the pressure exerted by the fluid on the surface. This pressure modifies the natural frequency of the QCM, and it is this difference that we measure [295]. That is, we need to simulate the fluid in the entire box and calculate its properties on the surface. This type of simulation, where the fluid is simulated, is computationally expensive, and directly doing this would not allow us to observe sufficiently long time scales. Therefore, we opt for a different strategy. We perform simulations with an implicit fluid (using a Langevin integrator), which we use to generate a set of states

Figure 8.7: Coarse-grained model for the FtsZ protein. A C_α resolution is used, where each amino acid is represented by a bead located at the position of the alpha carbon. The protein has two parts: a globular region and an unstructured region. A different model is used for each region. Additionally, the interaction with the surface is added.

for the system. At certain time intervals, we take a QCM measurement, adding information about the fluid dynamics. This measurement is what we would obtain in laboratory experiments.

Simulating the system using an all-atom model is not feasible. We employ coarse-grained models, specifically the C_α resolution models described in Chapter 1. For the globular part, we use the Karanicolas-Brooks model described in Sec. 1.1.1, and for the unstructured region, we employ the model described in Sec. 1.1.3.

This experiment is available on the web. First, we access the web page, and after entering the user credentials, the welcome page is displayed (Fig. 8.8). This page shows the different types of experiments or calculations that the user can perform. In particular, to perform the FtsZ calculation, we select the one called "VQCM-Protein".

Figure 8.8: Welcome page of the web. It lists the experiments available to the user (the displayed image is cropped). In this example, three experiments are shown, each with an image, a name, and a brief descriptive text. The FtsZ experiment is circled in red. This is the one we will select.

When we select this experiment, a presentation panel of the experiment opens. The experiment presentation has two sections: the first displays a brief description of the experiment, and the second part shows the jobs that have been carried out previously and their status (the status is updated through the process described in 8.2.3). The next step to launch a new simulation is to click on the button containing the "+" sign, circled in Figure 8.9.

Pressing this button opens a new dialog to configure the new simulation (Fig. 8.10). We must indicate the name of the simulation (this name must be unique and cannot match that of other jobs), and we can also add a short descriptive text to the job. We have different parameters for the simulation, such as the size of the box and parameters specific to the fluid. The experiment allows simulating any protein bound by a linker to a substrate. To specify our case, we must select the FtsZ protein and the

Figure 8.9: Presentation panel of the Virtual Quartz Crystal Microbalance (VQCM) experiment. It is divided into two sections: a description of the experiment and a list of previously run jobs with their current status. The button to create a new job is circled in red.

correct linker sequence. Once all the parameters are configured, we add the simulation to the queue using the corresponding button. When we want the calculation to start, we do so from the Queue tab, where all the queued jobs are shown and can be sent for execution. This is done through the process described in 8.2.2.

When the job finishes, it will be listed similarly to the other jobs, as shown in Fig. 8.10. Then, when the job is completed, the "Analyze" button will be enabled. Clicking this button triggers the process described in 8.2.1. The results are then displayed; in the FtsZ example, we would obtain something similar to what is shown in Figure 8.11.

In this case, the signals that we would measure in a laboratory QCM would be shown, allowing us to compare them with the laboratory experiments. What is shown in the experiments, as well as the presentation of the experiment and its dialog for creation, are fully configurable. This is what a user of the page would see. As observed, it is not necessary for the user to have any knowledge of programming, executing GPU programs on a cluster, etc.

Next, we will describe what happens behind the scenes. When a simulation is created by selecting parameters (Fig. 8.10), the result is a configuration file, usually in JSON format. When the job is sent to the associated compute server (Fig. 8.5), the generated JSON is analyzed. Each experiment is associated with a program that processes the JSON. In this particular case, the JSON is processed by a Python script that generates a `simulationPool` for VLMP (see section 7.1.3).

Figure 8.10: New job creation dialog for the Virtual Quartz Crystal Microbalance (VQCM) experiment. It allows specifying the job name, a descriptive text, and various simulation parameters such as box size, fluid properties, protein PDB file, and linker sequence. The button to add the job to the queue is located at the bottom (not shown in the cropped image).

Figure 8.11: Results visualization for a completed Virtual Quartz Crystal Microbalance (VQCM) experiment. It displays the frequency and dissipation signals over time, which can be compared with laboratory experiments.

To carry out this type of simulation, we employ different components of VLMP . In particular, for the building of the FtsZ model, we use a model called `Protein_IDP`. It takes parameters such as the PDB of the protein (a specific PDB is selected when choosing FtsZ) and the linker sequence, both provided by the generated input (Fig. 8.10). This model allows selecting the models used for the protein and the IDP. In this case, the Karanicolas-Brooks model 1.1.1 is used for the globular region, and the model described in section 1.1.3 is used for the unstructured region. When adding the model, we must position it correctly. For this, we use `modelOperations` (section 7.3, particularly `"setParticlePosition"`, which sets the position of a particle. In our case, we set the position of the last particle of the linker. Now, using `modelExtensions` (section 7.3), we add the missing interactions, including the surface and fixing the position of the last bead of the linker using a harmonic spring to keep it attached to the surface during the simulation. Additionally, the interaction between the beads of the globular part and the linker is added, specifically a simple steric interaction using a WCA-type potential.

At this point, we have the basic elements of the simulation: the model and the integrator, which, as mentioned, is a BBK Langevin integrator. Finally, we add the `simulationSteps`. In this case, we add the one that allows performing the QCM measurement, `"virtualQCM"`.

In summary, using the JSON, we generate a simulation that we add to the `simulationPool` of VLMP . For now, the `simulationPool` only has one simulation. Certain parameters of the job creation (Fig. 8.10), instead of a single value, accept a list of values, such as the density, linker sequence, etc. If any parameter is a list, then each element is added as an additional simulation to the `simulationPool`. Once the JSON has been processed and the `simulationPool` created, it is processed and distributed (in this example, `simulationSets` with a single simulation are created for simplicity). Then, we follow the process described in 7.2 and load the simulations into the job queue of the compute server. The simulations are carried out using `UAMMD-structured` . Each simulation in the `simulationPool` generates an input file in the `UAMMD-structured` format. The `simulationStep` selected in VLMP adds a `simulationStep` (with the same name in this case) that uses functions specific to UAMMD for fluid simulation to calculate the effect of the fluid on the surface and determine the VQCM signal [295]. This process is performed at certain step intervals (set in the input, Fig. 8.10). This `simulationStep` (mostly implemented by Pablo Palacios Alonso) calculates the effect of the fluid and transforms it into the quantity measured by the QCM. The result is stored in a file. When the simulation ends, this file is sent to the database (through the process 8.2.3), and then it can be represented as mentioned previously. This example shows the capabilities of the different frame-

works when working together. All the components used `UAMMD` , `UAMMD-structured` , `VLMP` and `Vexperiments` are modular and customizable, allowing them to be tailored to carry out a large number of diverse tasks and providing a series of interfaces to exchange information with each other.

Part III

Projects

This part presents four projects that showcase the application of the techniques discussed in the first part of the thesis and the computational tools described in the second part. Each project aims to understand and interpret specific experimental results by employing theoretical physics tools or simulations.

The first two projects are described in detail, as the application of theoretical tools or simulations is a central element. The latter two are presented more concisely, focusing on how the different computational tools are employed. The first three projects have been carried out in collaboration with experimental group lead by Pedro J. de Pablo.

The first project, "**Adenovirus cooperative disassembly**", uses Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) to force the disassembly of certain parts of the Adenovirus. Rather than using simulations, we build a model based on the theory of Kramers (see Chapter 5) to obtain information about the Adenovirus disassembly process. Although "Virtual Experiments" is not used directly in this project, the developed model can be applied in other similar experiments and has been added to the "Virtual Experiments" website for researchers in the group to use in similar projects (see Chapter 8). The method allows for the calculation of the energy of certain sample parts during the fatigue experiment, as described in the project.

The second project, "**Coronavirus surface adhesion**", investigates the adhesion of coronaviruses on different surfaces. Here, we extensively use `UAMMD-structured` (Chapter 6) and `VLMP` (Chapter 7) to simulate the process. In parallel, we develop a theoretical model based on the Helfrich model for vesicles. The combination of simulations and the theoretical model reveals that coronaviruses possess a mechanism that provides them with great adaptability when adhering to surfaces.

The third project, "**Electromechanical photophysics of packed GFP**", studies protein behavior at high concentrations. A nanocontainer is filled with the fluorescent protein GFP, and its fluorescence variation is studied under certain stresses and medium modifications. `UAMMD-structured` is used to simulate the experiment, combining the simulation of protein structure, interaction between proteins, and the effect of their compression.

Lastly, we present a project in collaboration with the group of Salvatore Assenza. This work, "**Mechanical response of phased Atracts**", examines how certain DNA sequence patterns (called A-tracts) exhibit special properties and proposes different biological processes that could be affected by these mechanical properties. Although there is no direct collaboration with an experimental group, the presented results are always compared with those obtained by experiments, specifically AFM and optical tweezers. The computational tools are a central element of this work, as it is essentially computational.

Chapter 9

Adenovirus cooperative disassembly

Adapted from: "Long-Range Cooperative Disassembly and Aging During Adenovirus Uncoating", Pablo Ibáñez-Freire et al. Phys. Rev. X 11, 021025

Icosahedral virus capsids are closed shells built up with a hexagonal lattice of proteins, which incorporate pentamers at their fivefold vertices. Human adenovirus particles lose pentamers (pentons) during infection under a variety of physicochemical cues, including mechanical pulling of molecular motors and the viscous drag of the cytoplasm. By combining Atomic Force Microscopy experiments with survival analysis and Markovian transition state theory (Chapter 5), we investigate the sequence of adenovirus penton disassembly that reveals the aging of the virus structure. We show evidence that the lifetime of pentons gradually decreases, accompanied by capsid softening as neighboring pentons are lost. This cooperative dismantling process, which involves first neighbor penton-penton distances of at least 45 nm, leads to a 50% increase in the virus disassembling rate of the virus particle. Theory and experiments fit remarkably well, allowing us to obtain the spontaneous escape rate and the energy barrier of penton disassembly ($\approx 30 k_B T$). The observed increase in the penton's loss rate reveals long-ranged structural correlations within the capsid. Our estimations suggest that the mechanical cues arising from the strokes of protein-motors carrying the virus to the nucleus, could help penton disassembly and warrant the timely delivery of weak enough capsids for adenovirus infection.

9.1 Introduction

Upon entry into the host cell, eukaryotic viruses undergo a controlled genome uncoating process [74] which usually requires capsid disassembly following a timely precise process. In icosahedral viruses, protein subunits (capsomers) arrange in 20 triangular facets delimited by 12 fivefold vertices forming a structure of hexamers and pentamers [296]. Pentamers are located at each one of the twelve vertices surrounded by five hexamers. Therefore, pentons can be understood as the disclinations needed for achieving the curvature of a closed cavity using a planar hexagonal lattice [297]. Due to the geometrical constraints of the pentons within the icosahedral capsid, they are subjected to built-in mechanical stress [298–300]. In fact, some experimental findings report pentons as the weakest capsomers of icosahedral viruses under thermal or chemical stress [301, 302]. In adenovirus, penton release is a necessary step for uncoating and infectivity [302, 303]. Adenoviruses are responsible for acute infections in immunocompromised individuals, but they are also widely used as potential therapeutic tools [304–308]. Human adenovirus type 5 (Ad5) has a pseudo $T = 25$ icosahedral shell composed of 12 pentons and 240 hexon trimers occupying the hexamer positions [309]. A protruding fiber is attached to the penton base to mediate binding to the cell membrane protein CAR [310, 311] (Fig. 9.1a). For a successful infection, the adenovirus particle releases protein VI to escape into the cytosol. This process requires capsid opening by penton loss [312, 313]. Ad5 uncoating has been mimicked *in vitro* by physicochemical cues such as heat, inducing partial disruption and disassembly of the capsid shell [312]. The cyclic mechanical loading induced by an Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) stylus also supplies energy to the system, allowing it to simultaneously trigger and monitor the disassembly of individual Ad5 particles in real time [313]. Pentons of the facet oriented upwards in mica-adsorbed particles escape sequentially, and afterwards the shell cracks open allowing genome release [314]. In this work, we explore the dynamics of Ad5 penton release by combining single particle AFM imaging experiments with theoretical modelling based on survival analysis.

9.2 Material and methods

9.2.1 AFM experiments

AFM was used to consecutively image individual Ad5 particles and monitor the evolution of penton loss [313] and to perform benchmark indentation experiments to obtain the spring constants of the viral particles (k_i). In brief, we pipetted a droplet of virus solution on mica in the presence of NiCl_2 , resulting in a random population

Figure 9.1: Adenovirus in biological context, experimental and theoretical setups. (a) Ad5 infection. (b) AFM jumping mode. The tip approaches the sample (1), then withdraws (2), and moves laterally to the next pixel (3). Two missing pentons are shown (white circles). (c) Energetic profile of penton release process when two states are considered.

of single particles with an intact condition, i.e., with a negligible substrate-induced deformation (Fig. A.1). We used rectangular silicon nitride cantilevers RC800PSA (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) with a nominal spring constant of 0.05 N/m. This parameter was calculated before each experiment by using Saders method [315]. The AFM (Nanotec Electrónica S.L., Spain) was operated in Jumping Mode Plus in liquid (Fig. 9.1(b)) [316, 317]. To determine the stiffness of the viral particles, a first image was taken; then, the tip was located at the top of the particle, and a force-versus-distance curve was recorded. During the first stage of indentation, the particles showed a linear deformation from which their spring constant can be derived [318].

9.2.2 Establishing the force range for controlled ad5 penton release under mechanical perturbations

AFM imaging at low forces (about 70 pN) allows us to select individual virus particles adsorbed on the mica surface in a threefold orientation, presenting three intact pentons [319]. For each selected capsid, we acquire a series of AFM images inducing cyclic mechanical stress [313] with forces between 100 and 250 pN (Fig. 9.2(a), top left). We note that the applied force should be large enough to remove pentons during one experimental session (about 5 hours) and small enough to avoid sudden uncontrollable large cracks on the viral particles. We find that the lower threshold is 100 pN, close to the limit force value, allowing us to obtain AFM images of viruses [316].

The experimental procedure consists of performing a sequence of AFM images of the virus particle using a prefixed imaging force F . Pentons are gradually lost, as more images are taken, neatly showing that pentons are the most fragile structures of the capsid. This result is in agreement with previous experiments where capsids were subjected to heat stress [312, 320] and with the existence of built-in stress at the vertices [319]. In each experiment, we recorded the image number N_i at which we observed the escape of the first N_1 , second N_2 , and third N_3 pentons (Fig. 9.2(a)). Further imaging beyond the dissociation of the third penton revealed how penton-less capsids undergo further disassembly through cracking and crumbling [313] (Fig. 9.3). In the experiments, we opted to use the applied force F as the relevant parameter, instead of increasing the imaging rate, which is also known to accelerate capsid disassembly [321]. The imaging rate was fixed to about 10 ms per pixel (128×128 pixels), which is long enough to guarantee the mechanical relaxation of the capsid after obtaining the topographical data of each pixel [40]. This rate includes other relevant experimental parameters, such as the vertical distance traveled by the cantilever at each pixel (jump off) and the sampling rate (jump sample) (Fig. 9.1(b)) [316]. This rate ensures that each indentation is independent from the previous one or, equiva-

Figure 9.2: a) Individual frames of one Ad5 particle at 150 pN (scale bar 37 nm, white circles mark the penton vacancies). b) Penton release distribution at five forces. Dots represent the experimental data. For example, for 100 pN data (red) about 40% of the pentons remain on the capsid after 20 frames. Data fitting for a discrete Weibull distribution is shown with solid lines.

lently, that the capsid does not accumulate any stress over successive AFM strokes. In mathematical terms, this lack of memory of the previous stroke is called the Markovian hypothesis and will be later used (and validated) within the theoretical framework for the escape process.

Figure 9.3: Ad5-wt disruption by mechanical fatigue at 150 pN of applied force. Selected individual frames along the disassembly process of a single adenovirus. Scale bar 50 nm. Green circles indicate the loss of a penton.

9.3 Results and analysis

9.3.1 Evidence of aging in the probability of penton release: weibull analysis

To investigate the statistics of penton escapes, we first collect all the penton failure timepoints (measured in frame number) in the same set of data $\{N\} = \{N_1, N_2, N_3\}$ irrespective of the chronological order of escape (Fig. 9.2(b)). We then construct the histograms for the number of escape events observed at each image N and integrate (Fig. 9.4) to obtain the cumulative probability $P(N)$ for penton rupture (Fig. 9.2(b)). $P(N)$ is thus the probability that some penton is lost after taking N images at a given force F or, equivalently, the fraction of released pentons from the total sample at a given frame.

As shown in Fig. 9.2(b), $P(N)$ significantly deviates from a Poissonian distribution, meaning that the penton failure rate is not constant but instead varies over time (i.e., over the frame number N). To get more insight, we fit $P(N)$ with a Weibull distribution [322, 323], which, in survival analysis, is a standard way to model processes with a time-dependent failure rate. As the variable N is an integer, we use the discrete

Figure 9.4: Histograms of penton loss events for the five forces studied. Experimental histograms of penton loss events for each frame and their cumulative probability (black lines) for 100, 125, 150, 200 and 250 pN. These cumulative probabilities are represented in dots in (Fig 9.2b)

version of the Weibull distribution whose cumulative probability is

$$P(N) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{N+1}{\langle N_p \rangle} \right)^\beta \right]. \quad (9.1)$$

Here, $\langle N_p \rangle$ represents the average lifetime of a penton in terms of the number of images. Note that the failure rate varies with N as $\left[\frac{d(\log(1-P(N)))}{dN} \right] = \left(\frac{\beta}{\langle N_p \rangle} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{N}{\langle N_p \rangle} \right)^{\beta-1}$, being determined by $\langle N_p \rangle$ and the so-called shape parameter β . Importantly, $\beta = 1$ corresponds to a constant failure rate, and in this case, the Weibull distribution becomes equivalent to a Poissonian distribution. By contrast, $\beta > 1$ is indicative of aging: The failure rate increases over time (i.e., with N). Experimental penton-escape probabilities (Fig. 9.2(b)) are found to be in excellent agreement with aging, i.e., with Weibull distributions having $\beta > 1$. In particular, we find $\beta \approx 1.5$ for the range $100 pN < F < 200 pN$, while for $F = 250 pN$, it increases up to $\beta \approx 2.5$, which indicates fast aging. In fact, the increase in failure rate with time is even faster than predicted by the Weibull test, as we did not consider that the probability of finding a survival penton decreases after another penton(s) disappears. For instance, after one of the three accessible pentons is lost, the probability of hitting one of the remaining pentons decreases by a factor $\frac{2}{3}$, and this contributes to a spurious decrease in the Weibull analysis of the failure rate. As an aside, during the AFM experiments, we observe that when applying forces higher than 150 pN, the experimental probability curves start to overlap (Fig. 9.2(b)), preventing the use of higher forces. As we will show later, this experimental resolution limit in force agrees with our theoretical prediction for having a probability higher than 95% of penton release during the acquisition of the first image.

The increase of the penton release rate along the experiment is a landmark of aging, which might arise either from an accumulation of capsid stress during each pixel acquisition or from the fact that we did not take into account the chronological order of penton escape in the analysis. It is important to elucidate between both causes because the first one (stress accumulation) would be against the Markovian hypothesis. To analyze this point, we remove the memory stored in the chronological chain of escape events by resetting the time counter each time an escape event takes place. This approach allows us to study each penton-escape event independently. To this end, for each applied force, we gather three types of time-interval data: $\{n_1\} = \{N_1\}$, $\{n_2\} = \{N_2 - N_1\}$, and $\{n_3\} = \{N_3 - N_2\}$, which correspond to the survival times for the first, second, and third pentons, respectively. Notably, Weibull tests based on n_i , with $i = \{1, 2, 3\}$, revealed that the resulting probabilities $P_i(n)$ correspond to exponentials (i.e., $\beta \approx 1.0$, see Table 9.1). The escape of a single penton is thus a Poissonian

(memoryless) process and confirms the validity of the Markovian hypothesis; i.e., the tapping process does not introduce stress accumulation in the capsid, as the particle has enough time to relax between successive pixels (taken every 10 ms). This result is to be expected, as the mechanical relaxation time of virus capsids measured from vibrational modes [324] is about 100 ps.

Table 9.1: Weibull Shape Parameters, β , for the Different Forces and Separated by Pentons Order. $\beta = 1$ Corresponds to an Exponential Distribution.

Force (pN)	100	125	150	200	250
One Penton Lost	0.91±0.06	0.92±0.14	1.04±0.34	0.94±0.17	1.64±0.58
Two Pentons Lost	0.96±0.08	0.88±0.15	1.12±0.22	0.46±0.24	0.69±0.22
Three Pentons Lost	0.84±0.08	0.62±0.16	1.00±0.24	1.05±0.23	0.55±0.41

We then estimate the average escape rates for the first, second, and third pentons, which correspond to well-defined, relaxed states of the capsid. Interestingly, we find that after the first penton is released, the average lifetime of the following pentons is reduced. For instance, at $F = 100 \text{ pN}$, the average lifetime of the first penton is about 37.5 minutes (12.5 images), while for the second and third pentons, it is about 27 minutes (9 and 8 images, respectively) (Table 9.2). This fact explains the increase in failure rate over image time observed in the Weibull analysis. The result indicates that pentamer disassembly events constitute a cooperative stepwise process, where the first step facilitates the following ones. Cooperativity has a sense of purpose, which could be attributed to the need of the capsid to gradually dismantle to achieve successful infection.

9.3.2 Estimation of the spontaneous penton-escape rate

We now focus on an analytical determination of the probability of releasing the i th penton after taking n images $P_i(n)$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$), which is amenable for comparison with experiments.

From a theoretical point of view, the transition kinetics of penton release can be simplified as a two-state process (bound and unbound) (Fig. 9.1(c)). In the absence of external mechanical perturbations (i.e., zero external work, $W = 0$), the transition rate α_0 for a penton to change from bound to unbound in a thermal bath is related to the free energy well ΔG by a simple Arrhenius-type law, (Chapter 5),

$$\alpha_0 = \omega_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G}{k_B T}\right). \quad (9.2)$$

Note that α_0 is the spontaneous or natural escape rate, and ω_0 is the natural frequency

Table 9.2: Average Lifetime and Standard Deviation (in Units of Image) for the Escape of the Three Pentons in Experiments Performed with Increasing of Indentation Force F . The Similar Values of the Average and Deviations Indicate an Exponential Distribution with a Well Defined Escape Rate.

	Penton 1				
Force (pN)	100	125	150	200	250
Avg. Lifetime (s)	12.5	5.4	3.8	3.6	4.0
Std. Deviation	11.6	4.6	3.2	3.0	2.2
N	18	13	12	16	11
	Penton 2				
Force (pN)	100	125	150	200	250
Avg. Lifetime (s)	9.0	4.0	3.0	3.1	3.2
Std. Deviation	10.2	3.6	2.3	3.3	2.8
N	18	13	12	16	11
	Penton 3				
Force (pN)	100	125	150	200	250
Avg. Lifetime (s)	8.0	5.7	3.7	4.5	1.6
Std. Deviation	9.3	7.0	2.9	3.5	1.5
N	18	13	12	16	11

of fluctuations of the penton in the energy well. To extract α_0 and then estimate ΔG , we use a well-known strategy in transition theory [46], which consists in applying mechanical work W into the system to lower the free energy well ($\Delta G - W$) and accelerate the penton-escaping events to gather statistics in reasonable experimental times (this is similar to the pulling experiments mentioned in Chapter 5). In the jumping mode imaging of the AFM, the tip induces mechanical work to the capsid through an intermittent force $f_{\text{AFM}}(t)$ whose time dependence is known. From the virus perspective, each stroke of this long series of indentations is extremely slow, and during each single jump, the applied work $W(t) > 0$ increases the transition rate to the unbonded state according to [46]

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha_0 \cdot e^{\frac{W(t)}{k_B T}}, \quad (9.3)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature. To further advance, we first propose a linear relation between the work applied by the AFM tip and the set point force (maximum F), $W = -F x_{\text{ef}}$, where x_{ef} is a constant effective indentation length. A second route consists of using the harmonic-well approximation, $F = -kx$, with an effective spring constant of the capsid, k . The indentation is then $x = (-F/k)$, and the applied work becomes quadratic in the applied force, $W =$

$\frac{1}{2}(F^2/k)$, allowing us to compare theoretically estimated values of spring constants k with the experiments. The free parameters of the two-state model are α_0 and either x_{ef} or the effective spring constant k , which will be calculated by fitting the theoretical $P_i(n)$ with the experimental results.

The derivation of the single-penton escape probability $P_i(n)$ is detailed in the Appendix B. Starting from the expression for $\alpha(t)$ in Eq. 9.3, we first calculate the probability $P_f(t)$ of penton failure after a given time, during a pixel. We are dealing with a Markov unidirectional process (from bound to unbound state) representing a first-order kinetic reaction. In an ensemble average, the increase in the number of unbound (or free) pentons, $dP_f(t)$, would be simply proportional to the population of bonded pentons, and the master equation reads

$$dP_f(t) = \alpha(t) \cdot [1 - P_f(t)] dt. \quad (9.4)$$

The applied force $f_{AFM}(t)$ used in Eq. 9.3 is experimentally known [313], which permits us to perform a change of variable, mapping the image number n with real time in seconds. This mapping is essential as Eq. 9.2 requires one to have the natural α_0 escape rate in proper inverse-of-time units, to estimate the energy barrier ΔG . Briefly, by integrating Eq. 9.4, we first determine the escape probability after a single pixel and then integrate over one complete image and finally over an arbitrary number n_i of images. The resulting expression for the probability of releasing the i th penton is

$$P_i(n_i) = 1 - (1 - C_i)^{n_i}, \quad (9.5)$$

where C_i , given in the Appendix B, depends on the applied force F and the free parameters we seek to find out (x_{ef} , k_i and the natural escape rate of the i th penton, $\alpha_{0,i}$).

By fitting the theoretical probability $P_i(n)$ [Eq. (9.5)] with the experimental results, we estimate x_{ef} and $\alpha_{0,i}$. The value of x_{ef} was found to be independent of the penton index, and the best fit ($x_{ef} = 0.18 \pm 0.03$ nm) was used for all the penton sequences. As shown in Fig. 9.5, the theoretical model is in excellent agreement with experimental data. Additionally, we estimate an increase in the spontaneous escape rate as the penton-release order i increases: $\alpha_{0,1} = (2.7 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\alpha_{0,2} = (4.7 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\alpha_{0,3} = (6.4 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (first, second, and third penton, respectively). Interestingly, the spontaneous escape rate of the third penton results to be about twice faster than the first one. As a curiosity, these values of the spontaneous rates are of the same order of those reported in mechanical unfolding of proteins [46, 325, 326]

Figure 9.5: Penton release distribution under Markov process model. Top: AFM images taken after the first, second, and third penton-escape events (in the left panel, the scale bar corresponds to 44 nm). White circles mark the penton vacancies. Bottom: cumulative probability of penton failure $P_i(n)$ for successive penton escapes when the capsid is exposed to strokes of forces of 100 pN, 125 pN, and 150 pN (right panel). Dots represent the experimental data, and dashed lines represent the model results [Eq. 9.5].

9.3.3 Weakening of the capsid stiffness

It has been reported that penton vacancies may be accompanied by a change in the global capsid stiffness [327, 328]. Although this might seem logical, it is not a common feature in nanomaterials [329]. The increase of the failure rate that we observe after the release of the first penton indicates a global effect, which could be ascribed to the capsid structure softening. In addition, this capsid softening is not obvious, as pentons are the weakest capsomers of the virus structure [301, 302]. We can estimate the decrease in stiffness by using the ansatz $W = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{F^2}{k} \right)$ based on the energy of a harmonic well with effective local stiffness k . The form of the theoretical failure probabilities was found to be in good agreement with the experimental trends (Fig. 9.6) and allowed us to fit the theoretical $P_i(n)$ with the experimental outcome to obtain estimations for the capsid stiffness. For intact capsids, we found $k_0 = 0.50 \pm 0.02$ N/m, while for capsids without one or two pentons, we obtained $k_1 = 0.42 \pm 0.01$ N/m and $k_2 = 0.41 \pm 0.01$ N/m, respectively. These values were compared with independent experimental data for intact capsids (k_0) and a group of 18 pentonless capsids (k_i). In these benchmark experiments, Ad5 pentonless particles were obtained by applying a temperature stress ($T = 40^\circ\text{C}$ during 5 minutes in solution), which caused viral particles to lose at least one penton [312]. The benchmark experiments yielded $k_0 = 0.58 \pm 0.01$ N/m (for a capsid population of $N = 50$) [314] for intact particles and 0.42 ± 0.06 N/m ($N = 18$) [327] for heated capsids. These values are consistent with those obtained from escape probability distributions, where the penton number and release order were considered. The similarity between the estimated values of k_i is remarkable if one considers that both experiments are radically different. The benchmark experiments measured k from the linear regime of the force-indentation curves, using single indentation with a force of a few nN, which ultimately causes large capsid deformations of tens of nm, as well as cracks and capsid breaking. Here, we typically apply about 10^5 gentle AFM strokes of about 100 pN, at low frequency (10 ms).

9.3.4 Estimation of the free energy barrier for penton release

We have seen that losing pentons affects the Ad5 particle in two ways: (i) a gradual increase in the penton-escape rate and (ii) a decrease in the capsid stiffness. From the ratio $\alpha_{0,3}/\alpha_{0,1}$, Eq. 9.2 allows us to assess the difference between the energy barriers of the third and first pentons, which is about $\Delta G_3 - \Delta G_1 = -1 k_B T$. This value might indicate a small but noticeable modification in the molecular configuration of the residues sustaining the penton (after two partners are lost), which leads to the particle softening.

Figure 9.6: Penton release distribution based on the ansatz $W = \frac{1}{2} \frac{F^2}{k}$. The left panel illustrates AFM images taken after the first, second, and third escape events (the scale bar corresponds to 40 nm). The right panels show the cumulative probability of penton failure for successive penton escape when the capsid is exposed to strokes of forces of 100 pN, 125 pN, and 150 pN. Dots represent the experimental data and dashed lines represent the model results. Curves correspond to the ansatz $W = \frac{1}{2} \frac{F^2}{k}$ for the applied work, with elastic constants k equal to $k_0 = (0.5 \pm 0.02)$ N/m, $k_1 = (0.42 \pm 0.02)$ N/m, and $k_2 = (0.41 \pm 0.3)$ N/m, respectively for the intact capsid and capsids without one and two pentons respectively; the average escape rate is the same value in all cases $\alpha_0 = (0.63 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Our analysis also allows us to estimate the average energy barrier for the penton release, ΔG . For the process, we need to estimate ω_0 , the rate of exploration of the local well of the pentamer. A reasonable estimate is based on the balance of cohesion forces and environmental friction, and it yields $\omega_0 = (k/\xi) \approx 10^{10}$ Hz (the pentons friction coefficient ξ is taken as the Stokes value in water, where the dynamic viscosity is $\eta \sim 10^{-3}$ Pa s). Alternative estimations of ω_0 require the cutoff radius of the well λ (a subnanometric length of the order of the junction between the penton and the neighboring hexamers). We infer that λ must be similar to the displacement produced by the limit force at which the loss of the penton can be seen as extremely fast (i.e., approximately within a single image), i.e., $\lambda = (F_{\text{limit}}/k) \approx 0.5$ nm. Thermal fluctuations lead to an average kinetic energy $Mv^2 = k_B T$, and using $\omega_0 = (v/\lambda)$, this leads to $\omega_0 = 6.4 \times 10^9$ Hz. Vibrations around the quadratic potential lead to $\omega_0 = \left(\frac{k}{M}\right)^{1/2}/(2\pi) = 10^{10}$ Hz. These three estimations are quite close, and we conclude that $\omega_0 \approx 7.0 \times 10^9$ Hz, which is in good agreement with the relaxation rates of capsid units evaluated from NMR spectra [330] and from the vibrational modes via light scattering [324]. Taking logarithms in Eq. 9.2 and averaging over $\{\alpha_{0,i}\}$, we predict an energy barrier of $\Delta G \approx (30 \pm 1)k_B T$. This value is consistent with those reported in the literature for capsid assembly, either from coarse-grained simulations [319] or calorimetry studies [331]. The pairwise interaction between capsid units is known to be between 5 and 6 $k_B T$. For the five contacts of the pentamer, this interaction leads to a total binding free energy of about 30 $k_B T$, which agrees with our result.

9.4 Discussion

Theoretical simulations of virus assembly consider capsomer interactions to first neighborhoods [298, 332]. In principle, this type of building method might suggest that penton disruption is a local event depending solely on the neighboring capsomers, i.e., hexons. However, we measure a significant increase of the penton-escape rate after the first penton is lost. In the Ad5 capsid, neighboring pentons are about 45 nm away, so the loss of one penton is not expected to induce a strong local modification of the protein environment surrounding the other pentons. Since every penton is surrounded by similar hexons, the penton loss rate will not depend on the chronological order as long as their local structural environment remains unchanged. However, our analysis clearly shows that, far from being a local event, penton disassembly depends on the global state of the capsid. Additionally, our analysis confirms a measurable softening of Ad5 capsids after one penton is lost. Both results suggest that the cooperativity in the penton-release process (aging) is related to a gradual modification in the global mechanical structure of the capsid. Notably, 45 nm would be the largest correlation distance identified between structural elements in a virus capsid [333] and other protein assemblies [334–337]. Further support of this conclusion is given in theoretical studies, which reveal that the tangential stress distribution along the capsid presents long-range correlations connecting pentons, being particularly strong in $T = 25$ capsids [319]. Aside from a global change in the particle stiffness, some enhancement in fluctuations and particle breathing, perhaps also influenced by loss of internal components such as protein VI or core protein V [312], might also facilitate the next penton escape.

We now explore the implications of our findings in the timeline of adenovirus uncoating [303]. In the initial stage, integrins bind to the penton base and induce the release of the associated penton. Penton loss facilitates externalization of protein VI, whose lytic activity disrupts the endosome membrane to allow virus escape at 15 min post infection (p.i.). Afterwards, the semidisrupted particle is pulled along the microtubules, against the drag of the viscous cytoplasm, by both dynein (minus-end) and kinesin (plus-end) motor proteins, which bind to the capsid hexons [338, 339]. During this randomized travel (active diffusion) along the microtubule network, the Ad5 capsid keeps losing capsomers [338, 340]. Each stroke of the molecular motor introduces mechanical work ($\sim 10 k_B T$ [58]) into the capsid at a rate of about 10 Hz and corresponds to a step of about 5 nm. During the travel to the nucleus that covers between 5 and 10 μm [339], the partially disassembled capsids are subjected to thousands of these strokes. This energy is partly dissipated to the motor-protein linker and to the surrounding area, but part of this mechanical energy (W) will reach

the capsid, thus increasing the penton-escape rate by the Boltzmann factor $e^{W/k_B T}$. We find that the penton lifetimes exponentially decay with the applied force, at least for $100 pN \leq 200 pN$. As an educated guess, if $W \sim 2.5 k_B T$ (a quarter of the protein-motor power stroke), the lifetime of a penton would be reduced by a factor of 10. Once at the nuclear membrane (4560 min p.i.), the virus particle is broken by the coupled action of the attached kinesin motor pushing in opposite directions [339]. At this stage, most virus particles appear to be weak enough to release the viral genome into the nuclear pore. The work introduced by each tap over the long series ($\sim 10^5$) of gentle AFM strokes mimics the mechanical queues that the virion receives during its travel to the nucleus.

Our *in vitro* experiments reveal that genome ejection takes place after at least three pentons have been removed (Fig. 9.7(a)). Figure 9.7(b) shows that the dsDNA escapes from the virus cage through big cracks that require the additional disassembly of hexons [313]. *In vivo*, semidisrupted particles must be strong enough to preserve genome integrity when traveling from the endosome to the nucleus [341]. Most likely, the uncoating process is adapted to achieve these two apparently contradictory goals: (i) to keep the capsid stable enough during the transport to the nucleus and (ii) for the capsid to become weak enough once it arrives at the nuclear pore. Retaining a large number of pentons would guarantee a safe trip to the nucleus, but it might delay or even preclude the final uncoating at the nuclear pore (Fig. 9.7(c)). The survival analysis presented here estimates the average natural lifetime of the first penton in about $\frac{1}{\alpha_{0,1}} \sim 1$ hour. The lifetime is gradually reduced to $\frac{1}{\alpha_{0,2}} \sim 30$ minutes (second penton) and $\frac{1}{\alpha_{0,3}} \sim 20$ minutes (third penton). The whole process is over 50% faster than a noncooperative penton-escaping sequence. We conclude that the cooperative penton disassembly helps in achieving the required capsid aging on time for the genome to be successfully delivered at the nuclear pore (i.e., between 60 and 90 min p.i.). In view of the relatively adjusted times in the infectious cycle, a 50% delay might already prevent the virus from releasing its dsDNA on time (e.g., by allowing detection by cell defense mechanisms or ending up stuck on the nuclear pore) (Fig. 9.7(c)). Therefore, we suggest that the increased disruption rate of the pentons helps fine-tune the uncoating process of human adenovirus.

Figure 9.7: Genome exposure and cooperative penton release. (a) Top-left panel: intact virus particle (scale bar corresponds to 40 nm). Top-right panel: the same particle with three penton vacancies at frame No. 12. Bottom-left panel: the same particle at frame No. 30, showing some DNA released. Bottom-right panel: the final state of the collapsed particle. (b) Chart presenting the number of frames required for releasing the pentons and inducing DNA exposure. (c) Model of viral-uncoating at the nuclear pore assuming aging (left) and nonaging (right) penton release.

Chapter 10

Coronavirus surface adhesion

Adapted from: "Broad adaptability of coronavirus adhesion revealed from the complementary surface affinity of membrane and spikes", Pablo Ibáñez-Freire et al. Accepted at Advanced Science

Coronavirus stands for a large family of virus characterized by protruding spikes surrounding a lipidic membrane adorned with proteins. We explore the adhesion of transmissible gastroenteritis coronavirus (TGEV) particles on a variety of reference solid surfaces that emulate typical virus-surface interactions. Atomic force microscopy informs about trapping effectivity and the shape of the virus envelope on each surface, revealing that the deformation of TGEV particles spans from 20% to 50% in diameter. Given this large deformation range, experimental Langmuir isotherms convey an unexpectedly moderate variation in the adsorption free energy, indicating a viral adhesion adaptability which goes beyond the membrane. The combination of an extended Helfrich theory and coarse-grained simulations reveals that, in fact, the envelope and the spikes present complementary adsorption affinities. While strong membrane-surface interaction lead to highly deformed TGEV particles, surfaces with strong spike attraction yield smaller deformations with similar or even larger adsorption free energies.

10.1 Introduction

The study of viruses is intimately connected to their interactions with surfaces. From the biological standpoint, the cell membrane is the first barrier a virus needs to cross for infection. From the prophylactic view, inanimate surfaces might act as fomites for disease dissemination [342], but also, new materials are actively being searched to maximize virus-trapping and deactivation [343]. Indeed, understanding virus-surface interaction is extremely relevant both for biological and health concerns [344]. The adhesion free energy ΔG , determining the virus affinity for a surface, is a thermodynamic quantity measurable via the dissociation constant K_d , which depends on the

interfacial free energy per area W and on mechanical properties of the viral particle [319]. These features, such a surface tension Σ and bending rigidity κ are essential to regulate the adhesion of enveloped virus [345]. The virus particles of coronavirus (CoV) family takes its lipid envelope from the host cell, becoming essentially spherical particles containing single-stranded positive-sense RNA packed with nucleoprotein (N) to form the ribonucleoprotein [346]. Major common features of CoV include several key membrane-bound proteins: small envelope proteins (E), membrane proteins (M) and the spike glycoproteins (S) protruding out of the membrane. The standard picture of the initial step of infection consists of the receptor-binding domain (RBD) at the end of the spike protein binding to the cell receptor. In this picture, the virus lipid envelope is far away and has a minor role. Yet, the CoV structure has a radius of about 40 nm [347], and the spikes of 17 nm, are known to be translationally mobile and flexible [348, 349]. This leaves room for interaction between the cell membrane and the virus lipid envelope. Coronavirus adsorption to host cell membranes revealed the role of the membrane protein M in the initial infection steps [350]. Membrane attraction might arise even between hydrophilic surfaces (driven by hydrogen bond formation) [351] or slightly negative charged surfaces [352], which might also lead to spontaneous fusion. Notably, membrane-membrane fusion is one of the critical aspects of infection [353] which just requires the virus membrane surface tension to be larger than that of the host cell [353]. On the other hand, a recent contribution shows that COVID infection is possible (yet slower) even without ACE2 receptors, due to cleavage to a cell membrane protusion and activation of S2 unit via extracellular protease, leading to fusion [354]. All these facts highlight the relevance of the adhesive and mechanical properties of the coronavirus envelope in the infectious process. The transmissible gastroenteritis virus (TGEV) is a human-safe swine coronavirus which shares with SARS-CoV-2 most of the structural features [106, 355, 356]. TGEV and SARS-CoV-2 present a similar compression rigidity or effective "spring constant" under atomic force microscopy (AFM), $k_{sp} \simeq 0.01 \text{ N/m}$ [106, 357]. There is a strong correlation between the effects of different antiviral metal nanoparticles across TGEV and SARS-CoV-2 [358]. In fact, due to the strong similarities, TGEV is one of the most frequently used surrogates for SARS-CoV [106, 359, 360], and we use it as a model system to study the adhesion of CoV structures on surfaces.

The adhesion of CoV to material surfaces has been studied for virus inactivation purposes [342, 344], but little attention has been paid to the physical foundations, including adhesion free energy ΔG , envelope surface tension Σ and bending rigidity κ . The standard route to ΔG is the construction of Langmuir isotherms [361], which leads to the equilibrium constant or its inverse, the dissociation constant $K_d/[1M] \approx \exp(\Delta G/k_B T)$. In this vein, during the past century some experimental

studies on viral adsorption provided ΔG based on Langmuir isotherms [361–364]. Only very recently some experiments appear based on quartz-microbalance [365, 366], providing qualitative information which is difficult to quantify [295]. In addition, AFM and electron microscopy have been also used to study CoV adsorption on surfaces [367]. Measurements of the very thermodynamic affinity or dissociation constant K_d of CoV on surfaces has not been yet accomplished. Interestingly, the physicochemical mechanisms regarding colloidal adsorption onto surfaces are mainly known [145]: electrostatic interactions [362, 368], Van der Waals forces [363, 364], hydrophobic effects [369], formation of hydrogen-bonds [351], or dipolar interactions [145]. However, when dealing with highly inhomogeneous biological analytes such as virus particles, the estimation of their relative importance remains difficult to achieve. Capsid amino acids can be positively ionized to enhance adsorption [370] but this ionization can also be influenced by the inner genome negative charge [371]. While virus adsorption is highly influenced by both electrostatic interactions and hydrophobic effects, [342] Van der Waals interactions are relevant in neutral surfaces [344]. The topic of adsorption mechanisms reaches even higher levels of complexity if we consider the variability between non-enveloped and enveloped viruses (with lipids and glycoproteins involved [372]) the latter being the case for CoVs.

In this work, we deploy AFM to study the adhesion of TGEV coronavirus on different reference surfaces by measuring the topographies of absorbed viruses [373], contact angles and virus surface coverage (trapping). The combination of these data with the virus concentration in solution, estimated via spectrophotometric evaluation of the genome, leads to Langmuir isotherms and the dissociation constants K_d for each surface. Joining experimental results with elastic theory and a realistic coronavirus coarse-grained model (CG), we estimate the surface tension Σ , bending rigidity of the virus envelope κ , and the interfacial energy per area W associated to the virus membrane and the spikes. We conclude that the large affinity of the coronavirus to quite different surfaces is due to the seemingly complementary physicochemical nature of the lipid envelope and the spikes. We now present the computational model of the coronavirus, combining different models presented in Chapter 2 and Chapter 4. Then we present experimental results for the virus deformation profiles on several surfaces, and Langmuir isotherms to calculate the dissociation constant and adsorption free energy. Then in Section 10.3 we introduce an analysis based on Helfrich theory which is used to rationalize simulations and experimental results. Conclusions are given in Section 10.4. Details of experimental procedures are given in Appendix C.

10.2 Coarse grained model

In this study, we employ a coarse-grained model to conduct in-depth computational simulations of virus-surface interactions. Our model combines a modified virus spike protein model [201], the spike model is build using the shape-based-coarse-grained model described in Chapter 2, with a single-bead coarse-grained membrane model (Chapter 4), adapted to meet the specific questions raised hereby, which required taking into account the spike and membrane adhesion, mobility, and flexibility.

The virus lipid envelope is modeled as a single layer of "polar" beads, allowing for the fine-tuning of critical membrane properties such as 2D diffusion, mean radius, and bending rigidity. Our chosen parameters create a fluid membrane composed of beads approximately 1.8 nm in radius, resulting in a bending rigidity of $\kappa = (39 \pm 1)k_B T$, as ascertained from thermal fluctuations. This approach is based on a single-bead membrane layer formed with beads with polar interaction described in detail in Chapter 4.

The spike proteins are represented by a network of 17 elastic blobs, with the initial blob also forming part of the membrane. This integration guarantees a smooth membrane-spike coupling and sets the spike's diffusion mobility in line with values reported in Ref. [349]. The model further includes angular bonds within the spike structure to maintain the orientation of its various sections and to fit with experimentally estimated spike fluctuations [201].

A critical element of our model is the differentiated surface interaction potentials for the membrane and spike proteins. While each bead, whether part of the membrane or a spike, interacts with the surface through a Lennard-Jones-like potential, the parameters of this potential can be independently adjusted for the membrane and spike beads. This versatility allows for the simulation of a range of adhesion behaviors, from purely repulsive to attractively adhering scenarios, depending on the nature of the virus-surface interaction.

Our model, with approximately 2000 beads, strikes a balance between detail and computational efficiency. We employ an NVT overdamped Langevin integrator [246] to effectively manage polar interactions and particle orientation updates. The objective of merging these two existing models was to maintain key physical properties while reducing unnecessary computational complexity. We then discuss in detail the spike and membrane models and finally discuss how these models have been introduced into both UAMMD-structured and VLMP and how the simulations have been carried out.

Figure 10.1: Schematic representation of the coarse-grained spike protein model. The model consists of 17 beads, symbolized by red spheres, which maintain their positions to preserve the overall shape and size of the spike protein. The beads are connected by blue lines representing an elastic network. The numerical labels 1 to 4 illustrate specific beads that play a crucial role in the protein's 'hip' and 'knee' regions, where angular harmonic bonds are applied to simulate realistic flexibility informed by cryo-electron microscopy data. Bead 4, in particular, serves a dual function: it is part of the protein and the membrane, it represents the segment of the spike embedded within the lipid membrane.

10.2.1 Virus spikes

Our work simplifies a previously developed spike protein model [201]. This original model, based on the SBCG (Chapter 2), provides a representation of the spike protein structure. We have streamlined the detailed molecular interactions of the model, replacing them with a more generalized elastic network. This refinement aims to balance the fidelity of the original detailed structure with the practicalities of computational efficiency, ensuring that our adapted model remains both accurate and more manageable for simulation tasks.

This alteration is enough to maintain the general shape and size of the spike protein, a key factor in its adhesion capabilities, while easing the computational demand. We keep the number of beads, 17, and its position unchanged.

In constructing the elastic network, we established a cutoff distance of $R_{\text{cut}} = 7\text{nm}$ and uniformly applied a spring constant of $K = 10\text{ kcal/mol} \cdot \text{nm}^{-2}$, a typical value at this level of coarse graining [201]. Therefore, for every pair of beads within 8 nm of each other in the reference configuration [42], an interaction is introduced as follows:

$$U = \frac{1}{2}K(R - R_0)^2 \quad (10.1)$$

where R_0 denotes the inter-bead distance in the reference structure.

Furthermore, in order to accurately represent the dynamic properties of the spike protein, we integrated two angular bonds within the model. These bonds are substantiated by data derived from cryo-electron microscopy studies [347], thus imparting a realistic degree of flexibility to the protein's structure. The model employs a harmonic angular potential, represented by the equation:

$$U = \frac{1}{2}K(\Theta - \Theta_0)^2 \quad (10.2)$$

In this context, the parameters K and Θ_0 were determined through fitting to the experimental data. Our analysis yielded a value of $K = 11.92\text{ kcal/mol} \cdot \text{rad}^{-2}$ and $\Theta_0 = 23.76\text{ rad}$ for the 'hip' (comprising the first three particles of the spike, beads 4,3,2 in 10.1). Additionally, for the 'knee' (encompassing the second and third beads of the spike, along with another bead at the spike's head center, beads 3,2,1 in 10.1), the values identified were $K = 8.38\text{ kcal/mol} \cdot \text{rad}^{-2}$ and $\Theta_0 = 1.62\text{ rad}$.

As a result, our model is constructed with 17 coarse-grained beads interconnected by both harmonic and angular harmonic bonds. This configuration provides a practical and effective framework for exploring the behavior of virus spikes during adhesion, striking a balance between capturing essential structural characteristics and ensuring computational tractability.

Figure 10.2: $\langle a_l^2 \rangle$ as a function of $l(l+2)(l^2-1)$ obtained averaging over 6 independent simulations [200]. The fitting for high values of l is not accurate because beads are too big to solve accurately the shape fluctuations for values of $l \geq 7$

10.2.2 Virus membrane

The membrane is formed by a single layer of beads or blobs equipped with a polarity vector, which self-assemble in a roughly hexagonal, yet mobile, lattice. A detailed description of the model is given in Chapter 4.

The adjustment of the model parameters has been performed by searching for a combination that results in a membrane with similar size, 2D diffusion coefficient, and bending rigidity to typical values reported for SARS-CoV-2. The parameters found to match these typical values are: $\varepsilon = 5k_B T$, $\mu = 3$, $\zeta = 7$, $\theta_0 = 0$, $\sigma = 1.8$ nm, and $N = 1501$ particles. The equilibrium angle used is 0, which would result in a planar surface. However, if the initial bead positions form a sphere, the simulation will result in a quasi-spherical membrane with some surface tension. The surface corresponding to each bead is approximately $A_{bead} \approx 1250 \text{ \AA}^2$, and the typical surface of a phospholipid of $A_{lipid} \approx 35.5 \text{ \AA}^2$ [374], this leads to each bead in the model corresponding to approximately 35 phospholipids. We can compute the model bending rigidity fitting the fluctuations of each spherical harmonic mode to those predicted by the Helfrich model [200]:

From the fit of figure 10.2 we have obtained that the bending rigidity in the simulations is $k_c \approx 39k_B T$. It is a typical value for lipidic membranes, and it leads to a membrane with relatively strong deformations. In cryo-TEM images it has also been observed that the membrane can have big deformations [348, 375].

Finally, the 2D diffusion coefficient of the beads in the membrane has been characterized computing the 2D mean square displacement of the beads in a planar membrane

with small fluctuations in the z direction. The value of the diffusion coefficient of the beads in the membrane is $D_{2D} \approx 0.94 \text{ \AA}$. This value is in the range of values observed in [349].

10.2.3 Spikes and membrane coupling

In this section, we describe the methodology employed to couple the membrane model with the spike model, a key aspect of our simulation framework. This coupling was achieved by integrating the last bead of the spike model into the membrane, representing the region of the spike that is embedded in the membrane. Consequently, this bead assumes a dual character: it is part of both the spike and the membrane.

The integration process involves the strategic placement of all spikes (a total of 30) [376] onto the membrane, ensuring that there are no collisions during the initialization phase.

For the interactions between different spikes, as well as between the spikes and the membrane, we employ a Weeks-Chandler-Andersen (WCA) potential. This choice is based on the current understanding that there are no significant interactions between the spikes or between the spikes and the membrane beyond the region of the spike embedded within the membrane [347]. The WCA potential effectively models these interactions by preventing overlap between the spikes and between the spikes and the membrane, reflecting the physical exclusion without specifying detailed interaction forces.

This approach to coupling provides a realistic and computationally efficient representation of the virus structure. It allows us to simulate the behavior of the spikes in relation to the membrane accurately, which is crucial for understanding the overall adhesion process of the virus to surfaces. The dual nature of the last bead of each spike plays a central role in this model, capturing the essential interface between the spike and the membrane.

In conclusion, our model, comprising approximately 2000 beads, strikes an optimal balance between detail and computational efficiency. This allows us to conduct the extensive umbrella sampling necessary for our study, effectively handling the large number of simulations required to explore the virus adhesion process in depth.

10.2.4 Surface interaction

In our model's concluding section, we elaborate on the interactions between the viral membrane, the spike proteins, and the surface. A feature of our model is that the shape

of the interaction potential is the same for both the membrane and spike protein beads, though the specific parameters may vary.

The interaction between each bead and the surface is governed by a Lennard-Jones-like potential. The potential $U(\Delta z)$, as a function of the distance $\Delta z = z - z_0$ (with z being the z -coordinate of the bead and z_0 the position of the surface), is expressed as follows:

For beads where the interaction energy parameter ε is negative, indicating repulsion, the potential is:

$$U(\Delta z) = \begin{cases} -4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{\Delta z} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{\Delta z} \right)^6 \right] - \varepsilon, & \text{if } \Delta z \leq 2^{1/6}\sigma, \\ 0, & \text{if } \Delta z > 2^{1/6}\sigma \end{cases} \quad (10.3)$$

In this scenario, the potential mimics a purely repulsive force akin to the WCA potential, operational up to a cutoff distance $z_{cut} = 2^{1/6}\sigma$, beyond which the potential is set to zero.

Conversely, for beads where ε is positive, indicative of attraction, the potential has an attractive component similar to the standard Lennard-Jones potential:

$$U(\Delta z) = -4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{\Delta z} \right)^{12} - 2 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\Delta z} \right)^6 \right] \quad (10.4)$$

Here, σ is the parameter associated with the size of the bead, which can differ for membrane and spike protein beads. This dual application of the potential allows for both attractive and repulsive interactions, tailored by the specific values of ε and σ for each type of bead.

10.2.5 Umbrella sampling surface

Umbrella sampling [291] was used to obtain the free energy profile for the interaction between the CG virus model and the surface. Umbrella potentials at each window centered at z_i , consist of harmonic potentials applied to the vertical coordinate of the center of mass of the virus envelope z_{cm} (i.e. excluding the spikes), i.e., $(k/2)(z_i - z_{cm})^2$. We swept over values of z_i separated by about 5 nm to generate a series of overlapping biased probability 'windows' or 'umbrellas' from which we obtained the less-biased free energy profile $\Delta\mathcal{F}(z_{cm})$, using the weighted histogram analysis method (WHAM) [292]. As a result of this procedure we obtain the free energy as a function of the height of the virus. We transform the free energy to express it as a function of the virus height, which is the quantity we measure at laboratory. An example for a particular membrane-surface and spike-surface interaction energy is show in Fig. 10.9 E.

10.2.6 Implementation in UAMMD-structured and VLMP

Carrying out these simulations is an excellent example of how the UAMMD-structured and VLMP work and their interoperability. The first step in simulating the model described in the previous sections is to identify the different components that we will need in UAMMD-structured .

Initially, there is no need to add any new component to UAMMD-structured . For the simulation, we employ the "KcalMol_A" units to facilitate comparison with experiments. The simulations are carried out in the NVT ensemble, and we can describe the particles by type: those belonging to the membrane and those belonging to the spike, indicating their mass, radius and charge.

Regarding the interactions, the bonds are common: a harmonic bond for distance and a harmonic bond for angular potentials. The WCA interaction potential between the beads of the spikes and those of the membrane is also a common potential and is implemented in UAMMD-structured . The only potential that needed to be implemented is the one described in Chapter 4. This potential, used for modeling the membrane beads interaction, is a pairwise potential that depends on the distance, but it also has an interaction that depends on the relative orientation of the particles. The potential has been implemented, taking into account that it computes not only forces but also torques. In particular, we can employ it by selecting the type "[ShortRange,Zhang]". The particles of our model possessed both a position and an orientation, as mentioned in section 6.8, UAMMD-structured implements a specialized integrator for this type of particle [246], which is the Brownian integrator that can be selected using the type "[Brownian,EulerMaruyamaRigidBody]". Once we have all the needed components, we can examine how the input would look like (Code 10.1).

Note that since we are using a Brownian integrator, which lacks inertia, the mass of each particle is irrelevant, and therefore they are all set equal to 1.0. The charges are 0.0 since we do not consider electrostatic interactions directly. The radius of the spike particles is calculated as described in section 2. The types "LV" and "LP" are used to model the lipids, with "LP" being the bead that has a dual character (Fig 10.1). The types "S0", "S1", ... are the different types for each bead that composes the spike. Next, we can select the integrator (Code 10.2).

In this example, we consider 10^8 integration steps, but these can vary depending on the type of simulation we are carrying out. For the "timeStep" variable, we take 0.1 ps, and for "viscosity", we use 1.0 ps^{-1} . However, the example does not show these values but rather those in the "KcalMol_A" unit system, where time employs its own units (Section 6.6.2). Once the beads are defined and the integrator is set, we can define the structure (Code 10.3).

Code 10.1: Coronavirus model types

```
global:
  units:
    type: ["Units", "KcalMol_A"]
  ensemble:
    # ...
  types:
    type: ["Types", "Basic"]
    labels: ["name", "mass", "radius", "charge"]
    data:
      - ["LV", 1.0, 18.0, 0.0]
      - ["LP", 1.0, 18.0, 0.0]
      - ["S0", 1.0, 18.64, 0.0]
      - ["S1", 1.0, 19.67, 0.0]
    # ...
# ...
```

Code 10.2: Coronavirus model integrator

```
# ...
integrator:
  EulerMaruyamaRigidBody:
    type: ["Brownian", "EulerMaruyamaRigidBody"]
    parameters:
      timeStep: 2.045
      viscosity: 0.049
    schedule:
      type: ["Schedule", "Integrator"]
      labels: ["order", "integrator", "steps"]
      data:
        - [1, "EulerMaruyamaRigidBody", 100000000]
# ...
```

Code 10.3: Coronavirus model structure

```

topology:
  structure:
    labels: ["id", "type", "modelId"]
    data:
      - [0, "LV", 0]
      - [1, "LV", 0]
      - [2, "LV", 0]
      # ...
      - [387, "LP", 0]
      # ...
      - [1501, "S0", 1]
      - [1502, "S1", 1]
      # ...
      - [1517, "S0", 2]
      - [1518, "S1", 2]
      # ...
    forceField:
      # ...
# ...

```

As observed, particles with IDs between 0 and 1500 are part of the membrane, some of them associated with the "LP" type since these are those with a dual character and connect with the spikes. The particles of the vesicles are associated with model 0, while each spike is associated with a different model starting from 1. This will be useful when adding the interactions (Code 10.4).

Firstly, we have added the bonds, both those depending on the distance and the angular ones (as mentioned, the parameters of the latter are given by the adjustment to the experimental results obtained in [347]). Next, we begin with the short-range interactions. To do this, we first define a set of conditioned Verlet lists (Section 6.12.1) where the condition we set is "nonExclIntra_nonExclInter". This condition will create two neighbor lists for each particle: one whose neighbors are ensured to belong to the same model and another in which the opposite is ensured. In both cases, it is ensured that there will be no excluded particles, meaning that if particle j is in the exclusion list of i , then particle j will not be in either of i 's neighbor lists, intra or inter. Next, we declare a group that contains only the particles of type "LV" or "LP", that is, those belonging to the membrane. We then add the potential described in section 4. As observed, this potential acts only on those particles of the previous group (the lipids) that have the same model, i.e., the beads representing the membrane. The interaction parameters are those discussed in section 10.2.2. Next, we add the repulsive interaction between spikes and other spikes, and between spikes and the membrane. This is done by indicating that this interaction is of type WCA and that it acts between those

Code 10.4: Coronavirus model force field

```

topology:
  structure:
    # ...
  forceField:
    angBond:
      type: ["Bond3", "HarmonicAngular"]
      labels: ["id_i", "id_j", "id_k", "theta0", "K"]
      data:
        - [387, 1516, 1508, 2.72, 11.92]
        - [1516, 1508, 1511, 3.11, 8.38]
        # ...
    dstBonds:
      type: ["Bond2", "Harmonic"]
      labels: ["id_i", "id_j", "r0", "K"]
      data:
        - [387, 1516, 45.20, 0.1]
        - [1516, 1508, 45.12, 0.1]
        # ...

```

particles that belong to different models, intra (taking into account the exclusions, in particular, particle 4 and particle 3 of 10.1 are excluded). Finally, we add a Lennard-Jones-type surface as described in 10.2.4. The parameter ϵ for the particle surface interaction can be set for each type of particle, allowing us to explore different values for the beads of the membrane and the beads of the spike.

Once we have specified all the interactions and defined the types, we need to indicate the initial position and orientation of each particle and introduce them in the "state" section. The result can be seen in Fig. 10.3.

Once we are able to generate an input file for the simulation, we can add it as a model to VLMP. That is what we do in this case. After adding the model to VLMP, we can use the `SurfaceUmbrellaSampling` experiment (Section 7.6) to carry out the umbrella sampling simulations. This experiment takes an array of different models as input and performs umbrella sampling with the surface for each of them (Code 10.6).

In the parameters dictionary, we configure the parameters used to carry out the umbrella sampling simulation. In particular, we set the number of windows, the position where they start, and where they end. We also select the K value used for the umbrella potential (Section 10.2.5). The VLMP experiment allows adding several K values and associating each one with a number of steps for thermalization. In this case, the first K value is relatively small, and this is done to situate the sample in the correct position. The measurements are made only for the last value. All these parameters are described in the online documentation [286]. Next, we set the simulation values, and for now, we leave the models as an empty list. This experiment does

Code 10.4: Coronavirus model force field (Cont.)

```

verletList:
  data:
    - [387, [1508, 1516]]
    - [1516, [387, 1508, 1511]]
    # ...
  labels: ["id", "id_list"]
  parameters:
    cutOffVerletFactor: 1.2
  type: ["VerletConditionalListSet", "nonExclIntra_nonExclInter"]
groups:
  type: ["Groups", "GroupsList"]
  labels: ["name", "type", "selection"]
  data:
    - ["pgLipids", "Types", ["LV", "LP"]]
lipidsLipids:
  type: ["ShortRange", "Zhang"]
  parameters:
    condition: "intra"
    group: "pgLipids"
  labels: ["name_i", "name_j", "radius", "epsilon", "mu", "chi",
    "theta"]
  data:
    - ["LV", "LV", 18.0, 2.9807865, 3.0, 7.0, 0.0]
    # ...
nonPolar:
  type: ["ShortRange", "WCAType2"]
  parameters:
    condition: "inter"
    cutOffFactor: 2.5
  labels: ["name_i", "name_j", "epsilon", "sigma"]
  data:
    - ["LV", "S0", 0.596, 36.645]
    - ["S0", "S1", 0.596, 38.316]
    # ...
surface:
  type: ["Surface", "SurfaceGeneralLennardJonesType2"]
  parameters:
    surfacePosition: 0.0
  labels: ["name", "epsilon", "sigma"]
  data:
    - ["LV", -0.35769438, 18.0]
    - ["S0", -0.5961573, 18.645525]
    # ...
# ...

```

Code 10.6: Surface umbrella sampling

```

import VLMP
from VLMP.experiments import SurfaceUmbrellaSampling
from VLMP.utils.units import picosecond2KcalMol_A_time

# Other imports ...

ps2AKMA = picosecond2KcalMol_A_time()

parameters = {
    "umbrella": {"nWindows": 70,
                "windowsStartPosition": 230.0,
                "windowsEndPosition": 700.0,
                "K": [0.001, 0.05],
                "Ksteps": [1500000, 150000000],
                "measurementsIntervalStep": 10000},
    "simulation": {...
                "units": "KcalMol_A",
                "types": "basic",
                "temperature": 300.0,
                "box": [2000.0, 2000.0, 4000.0],
                "models": [],
                "selection": {"type": "lipids"},
                "integrator": {"type": "EulerMaruyamaRigidBody",
                               "parameters": {"timeStep": 0.1*ps2AKMA,
                                              "viscosity": 1.0/ps2AKMA}},
    "output": {...}
}

lipidsSurface = [-0.6, -0.8, -1.0, -1.2]
proteinsSurface = [1.0, -1.0, -2.0, -2.5, -3.0, -3.5]

for lpd, prt in itertools.product(lipidsSurface, proteinsSurface):
    model = {"name": f"CORONAVIRUS_lipids_{lpd}_proteins_{prt}",
            "type": "CORONAVIRUS",
            "parameters": {"nSpikes": 30,
                           "surface": True,
                           "lipidSurfaceEpsilon_kT": lpd,
                           "proteinSurfaceEpsilon_kT": prt}}
    parameters["simulation"]["models"].append(copy.deepcopy(model)
)

surfUmbrella = SurfaceUmbrellaSampling(parameters)

surfUmbrella.generateSimulationPool()
surfUmbrella.distributeSimulationPool("size", 10)
surfUmbrella.setUpSimulation("CORONAVIRUS_SURFACE_UMBRELLA")

```


Figure 10.3: As initial conditions, we place the membrane beads in a spherical arrangement following a Fibonacci grid [377]. We set the orientation of each bead parallel to the radial direction of the bead to ensure a stable configuration at the beginning of the simulation. Next, we randomly select a bead from the membrane and add the corresponding spike to that bead. We repeat the process until all N_{spikes} are added. Each time we add a spike, we check if it collides with any of the already present spikes. If so, we discard the current spike position and attempt to add it again.

the following: for each model in the parameters["simulation"]["models"] list, it copies the model "nWindows" times, and each window is assigned an umbrella potential that fixes the position of the center of mass (of the particles indicated in the selection). It then performs the simulation in each window, and the results are later analyzed by another program that implements the WHAM algorithm, particularly [293], and finally, we calculate the PMF.

After setting the experiment parameters, we will fill the list with the models. We create a model for each combination of lipid and protein interaction energies that we are interested in.

Finally, we generate the simulation pool, distribute it, create all the necessary files, and execute the simulations (for a description of this process, see section 7).

The use of `UAMMD-structured` and `VLMP` is essential for this project. In particular, we look at $4 \times 6 = 24$ possible combinations, and for each one, we have to perform 70 simulations, which is the number of windows, making a total of 1680 simulations. Each of these simulations takes around 3 hours on an NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU. If we were to perform each simulation individually, it would require 210 days, making the project nearly infeasible. These simulations are grouped into batches of 10, for which the time to perform the 10 simulations is similar to performing just one. In this case, we have distributed the project across 6 GPUs, reducing the time required to carry

out the simulations to 3.5 days, which is a reasonable timeframe and allows for the exploration of other model parameters.

10.2.7 Virtual AFM image

In the process of generating virtual Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) images from our coarse-grained simulations, the first step involves positioning a virus on a surface using the surface interaction set by ε_{spk} and ε_{mem} and run a long Brownian dynamics simulation to let the system reach the equilibrium (total energy, height). To accurately replicate Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) we fix the bead positions during the data acquisition phase. To imitate real-life conditions, we discard the spike proteins that do not make direct contact with the surface, a scenario that mimics their displacement by the AFM tip in an actual AFM scan. The resulting AFM images represents the locus of the beads associated with the lipids and those spike proteins that are in immediate contact with the surface. We then define the radius of the AFM tip, typically (set to approximately 15-30 nm). The resolution of the image is then determined, frequently being either 64x64 or 128x128 pixels. This resolution allows us to individually inspect each pixel in the x-y plane. For each pixel, we ascertain the height as the point of collision between the AFM tip and some virus blob, or the surface. By mimicking the functionality of real-world AFM, we are able to generate a detailed topographical image of our sample. This virtual AFM image can be utilized for subsequent analysis (Fig. 10.4(c) and Fig. 10.6), providing us with valuable microscopic insight, upon comparison with experimental data.

10.3 Results and analysis

We studied the adhesion of TGEV particles in reference surfaces including monocomponent substrates: mica, mica pretreated with poly-L-lysine (mica + PLL), highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG), isopropanol-cleaned silicon oxide (SiO₂-isopropanol), and plasma-cleaned silicon oxide (SiO₂-plasma), and a bicomponent surface composed by SiO₂ and Molybdenum disulfide, MoS₂. Although TGEV is polymorphic it is possible to ascribe a radius of $R = (41 \pm 2)$ nm [106, 376]. TGEV is decorated with ≈ 40 spikes of 15-20 nm in length [347, 376] which are remarkably mobile and flexible [348] [349, 357]. To compare TGEV AFM topographies with a reference system, we also study the adhesion of the Haloarcula Californiae icosahedral virus 1 (HCIV-1) internal vesicle [378] to mica and HOPG, endorsed with a radius of $R = 33$ nm [378].

10.3.1 Analysis of AFM topographies

AFM offers relevant information about the surface viral capture, as well as the size and shape of adsorbed viruses. Figure 10.4A-C presents high resolution images of individual virus adsorbed at several surfaces (pixel size ≈ 5 nm). Larger AFM images ($8 \times 8 \mu\text{m}^2$) using low spatial resolution (pixel size ≈ 30 nm) as those in Fig. 10.4D-F, were used to quantify viral capture. In the process of virus counting, we consider the particles which heights between 30 nm and 100 nm to avoid small portions of damaged viruses and large aggregates.

Figure 10.4: Examples of AFM topographical images of TGEV on various substrates. Panels A (HOPG) and B (SiO₂-isopropanol) illustrate single virus particles highlighting their nearly spherical shape due to lipid envelopes. The image size is $\sim 500 \times 500 \text{ nm}^2$. Viruses still may differ in size due to pleomorphism and present different degrees of attachment to the surfaces, which will be the main focus of our analysis later. Panels A and B correspond to real virus with radii 53 nm and 50 nm, respectively. Panel C shows the virtual AFM image of a coarse-grained virus model (with average radius $R_v \approx 43$ nm). In panel C the structural details in yellow are the adsorbed viral spikes. Panels D (mica), E (mica + PLL) and F (MoS₂) exhibit images with a 1/30 viral dilution on each surface. Panel F includes a dotted white line to highlight MoS₂ - SiO₂ boundaries, which can be easily seen by optical microscopy, and the inset caption shows a cross-section of the solid white line, displaying the approximately 2.5 nm thickness of the MoS₂ flake.

Virus size, shape and deformation

The average geometry of virus particles are necessarily convoluted with the relatively broad virus size polydispersity [376] and tip dilation. About 20 high-resolution images of individual particles per surface (Fig. 10.4) were used to draw one-dimensional projection of the topography profiles $y_{AFM}(x)$ against the surface coordinate x (Fig. 10.5A). Topography profiles need to be corrected to consider the dilation induced by the AFM tip radius R_{AFM} and the compression due to the applied force. An obstacle located at some given position x is sensed by the AFM at $x_{AFM} = x \pm R_{AFM}$ (Fig. 10.5A). Therefore, for an object of width $2L$ the expansion factor in any plane direction (x) is $\lambda_x = 1 + R_{AFM}/L$. Experimental values are around $\lambda_x \approx 1.4$, which agree with Ref. [379]. The compression in the vertical direction is related to the particle stiffness ($k_{sp} \approx 0.01$ N/m [106]). For 100 pN force, this implies a deformation $\delta_y = F/k_s \in [5 - 10]$ nm. Thus, the compression factor is $\lambda_y \approx (H - \delta_y)/H$, where H is the virus height directly measured from the AFM profile (Fig 10.5A), resulting in $\lambda_y \approx 1.1$. Using this information, we correct the shape of the AFM profiles by the re-scaling $y(x) = \lambda_y y_{AFM}(x/\lambda_x)$. Figure 10.5A illustrates the measured $y_{AFM}(x)$ (orange) and the corrected $y(x)$ (blue) for the AFM topography of one TGEV particle over mica.

To evaluate the true radius of the spherical shaped virus, we use a volume-based estimation which minimizes the assumptions on the shape other than the circular symmetry in the plane. The adsorbed particle volume is taken as half the volume of revolution associated to the profile $y(x)$. The radius R_v associated to the *volume-based* estimation is,

$$\frac{4\pi}{3}R_v^3 = \mathcal{V} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{x_0}^{x_1} \pi y(x)^2 dx \quad (10.5)$$

where the integration limits x_0 and x_1 are determined by the selected cutoff height $y(x_0) = y(x_1) = y_{cut}$ (we used a reasonably small value $y_{cut} \in (5 - 10)$ nm leading to small variations in R_v). This approach is validated by using two virtual spherical AFM tip of 15 nm and 30 nm on a CG virus simulation (Section 10.2). This analysis resulted in $R_v \approx (45 \pm 2)$ nm which is consistent with the real radius of the CG model 41 nm. Afterwards, we applied Eq. (10.5) to the experimental HCIV-1 profiles to obtain, $R_v = (29 \pm 2)$ nm which is consistent with the size measured from chromatography (33 ± 2) nm [380].

Once the size estimation methods have been validated, we analyzed the experimental topographical profiles of TGEV. Taking data from all surfaces and considering $\delta_y \approx 5$ nm for compression correction, we obtain $R_v = (46 \pm 3)$ nm for the TGEV particle. This value is consistent with the envelope radius measured from cryo-EM $R_0 \approx 41$ nm [106]. The histogram of the coronavirus radius, presented in Fig. 10.5B,

show a maximum range between 30 and 70 nm and standard deviation of 7 nm. The average and the radius range are consistent to those reported in Ref. [376] via cryo-EM. As an aside, we also tested the more frequently used *surface-based* estimation for the radius, $R_s = (1/2)(H^2 + 2L^2)^{1/2}$, based on equating the bare surface $4\pi R_s^2$ to that of an adsorbed drop (spherical cap) with height H and width $2L$ extracted from the AFM profiles. This method consistently estimates the radius $R_s \simeq R_v$ when it is applied to a CG vesicle model and to the HCIV-1 vesicle ($R_s = (31 \pm 2)$ nm). Interestingly, R_s surpasses the TGEV particle size in about 10 nm, due to the overestimation of the basal width $2L$. This overestimation-value ΔL is correlated to the presence of spikes adsorbed to each type of substrate. Thus, we use R_v in Eq. 10.5 to estimate the individual radii of virus particles. Data for R_v permits to obtain the scaled virus height, H/R_v which will be a central quantity in the adhesion analysis. The averages $\langle H/R_v \rangle$ were found to be 1.08 on mica-PLL, 1.09 on SiO₂-plasma, 1.17 on SiO₂-isop, 1.20 on HOPG, 1.24 on MoS₂ and 1.25 on mica, with error bars smaller than 0.03. The polydispersity in H/R_v (standard deviation over average) is small (about 0.05 on SiO₂-plasma) except for mica and MoS₂ (~ 1.4). Figure 10.6A illustrates the relatively broad profile distribution observed in mica: from flattened $H/R_v < 1.2$ to slightly deformed particles, with H/R_v reaching up to 1.6.

Adsorption energy and mechanical properties from AFM profiles

For an statistical analysis of the absorbed virus shapes, each AFM profile was normalized with its own radius (evaluated by Eq. 10.5) defining $\hat{y} = y/R_v$ and $\hat{x} = x/R_v$. Each profile was carefully centered at its maximum so as to evaluate the average, $\bar{\hat{y}}(\hat{x})$, and the local standard deviation, $\text{Std}[\hat{y}](\hat{x})$, for the collection of profiles on each surface.

Examples of AFM scaled averaged profiles for mica and HOPG are illustrated with red lines in Fig. 10.6A. Despite being seldom reported, the local standard deviation (over AFM profiles), shown in Fig. 10.6A, provides relevant information, as we explain below. Black lines in Fig. 10.6 indicate the best fit to the averaged profiles using the spherical-cap shape [381, 382]; i.e. the arc $x = R_c \cos(\phi)$ and $y - y_0 = R_c \sin(\phi)$, with $y_0 = H - R_c$ and R_c being the fitted curvature radius. The spherical cap fitting provides a first order estimation to the contact angle $\theta_0 = \arccos(1 - H/R_c)$ [383], which corresponds to the drop-like adsorption limit. The complete set of profiles is presented in Fig. S3. To get insight on how a realistic virus shape $h(x)$ translates into the average AFM profile $y(x)$ and its standard deviation (Std), we have processed the virtual-AFM profiles $y(x)$ from the profiles $h(x)$ obtained from CG simulations (Section 10.2), using the same protocol as in the experiments. As shown in Fig. 10.6B, $h(x)$ runs over the contour of the virus. The projection of the virus CG-beads in the xz plane

Figure 10.5: (A) Measured AFM profile (orange line) and corrected profile taking into account AFM tip dilation and compression. The AFM tip is illustrated as a sphere of about 25 nm. Results correspond to one TGEV particle on mica. The contour of the corrected profile $y(x)$ is used in Eq. (10.5) to provide the bare radius of the individual virus particle ($R_v = 41$ nm in this case, indicated with a red line). The black dashed line fits the corrected profile to a spherical cap, from which the contact angle θ_0 is obtained. (B) Probability density function of virus radii obtained from all the analyzed samples (colored symbols below indicate the lack of bias with different surfaces). The orange line indicates a Gaussian fit with average 47 nm and standard deviation 7 nm.

are indicated by filled circles. For the sake of clarity we have removed the spikes in this image. Moving from $x = 0$ to positive x , one notices that $\text{Std}[y(x)]$ suddenly increases once the tangent of $h(x)$ drops vertically (due to the vesicle-like shape). In these border domains, the paths followed by the AFM tip present larger variations precisely because $|dh(x)/dx|$ becomes very large (and eventually infinite at the maximal width of the path, Fig. 10.6B). Quite interestingly, from Fig. 10.6B the location where $\text{Std}[y(x)]$ is larger, closely matches the non-adsorbed portion of the virus, and as suggested from CG simulations (Fig. 10.6 B) it even indicates the shape of the profile $h(x)$ near the surface. Moreover, the central region where $\text{Std}[y(x)]$ is smaller (often close to zero) reveals the adsorbed surface of the virus. This information will be later used to estimate the ratio between the bending and the adsorption energy. In the case of the TGEV, the domains with large $\text{Std}[y]$ are much more pronounced than those found for the HCIV-1 vesicle (Fig. 10.6A). This feature is quite probably due to the effect of the TGEV spikes. A general feature in the shape of adsorbed vesicles, compared with that of liquid drops, is the formation of a domain with larger curvature close to the surface (Fig. 10.6B). At a distance $\lambda \sim \sqrt{\kappa/W}$ from the detachment point, the elastic energy due to the vesicle curvature (zero in the adsorbed region) balances the adsorption energy. Figure 10.6B indicates λ in the CG virus model. Using the spherical cap shape as first order estimation, an analytical relation for the so-called extrapolation length λ was derived in Ref. [383], $\lambda_0 = \sqrt{2\kappa/W} \cot(\theta_0/2)$. Here λ_0 is the distance from the point where the vesicle detaches from the surface to the intersection between the spherical cap and the substrate (Fig. 10.6B, right). We use the location where $\text{Std}[y(x)]$ increases to estimate the detachment point. The distance to the intersection of the fitted spherical-cap with the surface ($z = 0$) provides λ_0 (the distance to the maximum of $\text{Std}[y(x)]$ could be another option, leading to very similar estimations). As an example, for HOPG in Fig. 10.6(B), we get $\theta_0 \approx 83^\circ$ and $\lambda_0 \approx 0.55R_v$ or 24 nm therefore, $\kappa/W \sim 270 \text{ nm}^2$. Note that vesicles with radius smaller than $(2\kappa/W)^{1/2} \approx 23 \text{ nm}$ prefer to be free than to be bound to the surface [345, 384]: consistently, this lower cutoff radius (half the size of the average virus) is outside the range of the histogram of Fig. 10.5.

Having the ratio κ/W , we need a sound estimation for either κ or W . To the best of our knowledge, the bending rigidity of the coronavirus envelope has not been so far estimated, so we start by arguing by analogy with similar vesicles. We can estimate κ using a theoretical relation between W and the flattening ratio L/H for strong adhesion (pancake regime), developed by Tordeux *et al.* [383] and experimentally tested by Boxer *et al.* [385] with $R = 50 \text{ nm}$ phosphatidicholine liposomes. For large flattening ratios $L/H \sim 3$, Boxer *et al.* [385] report $W \sim 1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ J/m}^2$ on a glass substrate, i.e. essentially SiO_2 , and also predict $W \sim 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ J/m}^2$ for mica (upon Reviakine

Figure 10.6: (A) Average profiles and standard deviation $\text{Std}[y]$ for TGEV (left) and HCIV-1 vesicles (right) obtained from a collection of about 20 AFM images. We illustrate the heterogeneity of TGEV profiles in mica, showing conditional averages for deflated particles with $y_{\max} < 1.2R_v$ and less deformed particles with $y_{\max} > 1.2R_v$. The spherical cap approximation is shown with black lines. (B) The right panel shows a virtual-AFM profile from the virus CG-model (Section 10.2). The circles indicate the location of the CG beads. The relation between the $\text{Std}[y](x)$ profile and the extrapolation length $\lambda = \sqrt{\kappa/(2W)}$ is indicated. The right panel shows an experimental AFM profile, illustrating the determination of λ_0 and contact angle θ_0 from the spherical cap approximation (black line).

Surface	θ_0	$W/\Sigma = 1 + \cos(\theta)$	WR_v^2/κ
Mica	96°	0.90	4.7
MoS ₂	88°	1.04	5.5
HOPG	83°	1.12	6.0
SiO ₂ -isop	78°	1.18	6.4
MicaPLL	57°	1.55	8.2
SiO ₂ -plasma	55°	1.56	8.3

Table 10.1: Effective contact angle, and ratio between the surface adhesion energy W and the virus envelope surface tension Σ and estimated adhesion parameter WR_v^2/κ (see text).

and Brisson results [386]). Combining our previous estimation $\kappa/W \sim 270 \text{ nm}^2$ with $W \sim 1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ J/m}^2$ we get $\kappa \sim 10 k_B T$. The effective contact angles θ_0 provide, via the Young-Dupré expression $W = (1 + \cos \theta_0)\Sigma$, a relation between the surface adhesion W and the surface tension Σ of the virus envelope (Table 10.1). For HOPG we get, $\Sigma \simeq W/1.12 \sim 1.33 \times 10^{-4} \text{ J/m}^2$. Taking this value as reference and using $W = (1 + \cos \theta_0)\Sigma$, we forecast the values of the adhesion parameter WR_v^2/κ shown in Table 10.1. The estimated ranges $W \sim \Sigma \sim 10^{-4} \text{ J/m}^2$ are consistent with the expected limits: first, Σ is smaller than the upper limit of lysis tension for the rupture of a bound vesicle (around $[10 - 50] \times 10^{-4} \text{ J/m}^2$ [384]). And second, Table 10.1 shows that the values of the adhesion parameter are larger than the free vesicle threshold [345], below which vesicles prefer to be unbounded, i.e. $WR_v^2/\kappa > 2$. It will be later shown these estimations for WR_v^2/κ are in good agreement with a continuum elastic theoretical model derived from CG-virus simulations. To conclude, note that the ordering of W/Σ values in Table 10.1 shows that the strongest adhesion energies correspond to SiO₂-plasma and mica-PLL, being about twice larger than the weakest surface energies, MoS₂ and mica.

10.3.2 Viral adhesion and dissociation constants

In this section, we present Langmuir adsorption isotherms to study the affinity of the TGEV particles to the substrates. One might expect that the dissociation constant K_d will correlate with the surface energy W , as it happens in vesicles [345]. We advance that, surprisingly, this is not the case, this is not the case for TGEV.

Monocomponent surfaces

Adsorption isotherms of TGEV on different monocomponent surfaces were obtained by studying virus trapping on every substrate under increasing bulk concentration. The adsorption isotherm requires counting the virus particles trapped on the sur-

face per square micron (virus capture, VC) from the free viruses in bulk, at different concentrations (Appendix C). Measurements were accomplished at a very low concentration, which avoids systematic errors such as the underestimation of VC due to virus aggregates.

Determining the molar virus concentration in solution is a non-trivial task which has been solved by measuring the mass of genome in solution (Appendix C). Each virus includes a single copy of the viral genome of mass $2.37 \cdot 10^{-17}$ g, which permits us to calculate the number of viral particles in our sample. Viral concentrations ranged 3.56×10^{11} virus/mL (i.e. 1/10 dilution of original stock) to 1.48×10^{10} virus/mL (1/240 dilution). At these small concentrations, we found that the adsorption isotherms correspond to the Henry regime, where the number of captured particles is proportional to bulk concentration (Fig. 10.7). To estimate the dissociation constant K_d from the Langmuir model in the Henry regime we use $\Theta/\Theta_{max} \approx c_v/K_d$, where Θ is the fraction of surface occupied by virus particles and Θ_{max} the maximum virus coverage. The fraction of virus-occupied surface is defined as $\Theta = VC A_v$ where A_v is the area covered per virus, $A_v = \pi L^2$ (with L obtained from the spherical-cap envelope, Fig. 10.6). We consider $\Theta_{max} \approx 0.54$ which corresponds to the 2D random packing fraction. Hence, $K_d = \Theta_{max}/(a\pi L^2)$, being a the slope of the curves in Fig. 10.7. These slopes provide the virus capture ability for each surface, ordered as: SiO₂-plasma 6.3 Virus/($\mu\text{m}^2\text{nM}$); mica (6.6), HOPG (11.9), mica-PLL (13.7) and SiO₂-isop (20.6). These numbers result in $K_d \sim 5\text{nM}$ which is about 10 times the virus concentration in solution and within the Henry regime

Figure 10.7: Hill-Langmuir adsorption isotherm showing the adsorbed viral particles per μm^2 (VC) against the concentration of virus in bulk c_v . Dashed lines are fits to the linear (Henry) regime.

Bicomponent surfaces MoS₂ and SiO₂

For the estimation of K_d on MoS₂ surfaces we used a different approach based on differential adsorption. To that end we captured virus particles on bicomponent surfaces composed by MoS₂ flakes (typically of $10\mu\text{m}^2$) on a SiO₂ background, as illustrates Fig. 10.8. MoS₂ flakes are identifiable in AFM topographies as boundaries with an increase in height (Fig. 10.4F, inset). Drops with controlled virus dilution were incubated on these bicomponent surfaces to study the differential virus adsorption. As shown in Fig. 10.4F, we found ~ 4 viruses attached to the MoS₂ flakes for one virus deposited onto the SiO₂ background. This ratio 4 : 1 was found to be similar for all the viral dilutions considered, which confirms that adsorption events in both patches are fully independent, without second-order kinetics or competition effects. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. S5 and Fig. S6, both the viral capture and the distribution of virus heights in the SiO₂ background, are compatible with those measured in monocomponent SiO₂-isopropanol surfaces. This permits us to use the K_d obtained for pure SiO₂-isopropanol to estimate that of MoS₂. As the virus concentration in bulk is the same above each patch of the bicomponent surface, the result for differential adsorption leads to $K_d(\text{MoS}_2) \approx (1/4)K_d(\text{SiO}_2\text{isop})$.

Figure 10.8: Optical microscopy image of MoS₂ flakes on SiO₂ background. The image confirms that monolayer MoS₂ flake boundaries are defined by irregular sharp angles.

Dissociation constant K_d and adhesion free energy ΔG

With this last result at hand, we provide in Table 10.2 the estimated values of K_d for the different surfaces. Larger values of K_d correspond to smaller adsorption affinities. The free energy of adsorption ΔG at the standard concentration [1M], is usually presented as $K_d/[1M] = \exp[\beta\Delta G]$, where $\beta = 1/k_B T$. We find $\Delta G \sim -19 k_B T$ with variations of about $4 k_B T$ between surfaces; a range which is consistent with medium-size vesicles [145]. To put some examples based on Langmuir isotherms, Ref. [387] reported $\Delta G = -23.7 k_B T$ for unilamellar vesicles of average diameter of 100 nm on functionalized surfaces and Murray and Park [361] report $\Delta G \approx -22 k_B T$ for the adhesion of poliovirus (50 nm in diameter) on SiO₂.

Surface	VC = Virus/ $(\mu\text{m}^2 \text{ nM})$	% of capture	K_d [nM]	$\Delta G/k_B T$
MoS ₂	81.0	(25%)	1.2 nM	-20.5
SiO ₂ -isopropanol	20.6	6.30%	4.9 nM	-19.1
Mica + PLL	13.7	3.97%	4.0 nM	-19.3
HOPG	11.9	2.87%	9.8 nM	-18.4
Mica	6.6	1.75%	20.9 nM	-17.7
SiO ₂ -plasma	6.3	1.72%	8.2 nM	-18.6

Table 10.2: Virus captured per micron square surface and nano-molar virus concentration, percentage of total viruses captured onto the surface, the virus dissociation constants K_d and net adsorption free energy ΔG on different surfaces. MoS₂ K_d values were obtained in bicomponent surfaces, from differential adsorption with respect the SiO₂ background (which is similar in properties to isopropanol-cleaned SiO₂). In this case we extrapolate from VC the effective percentage of capture (in brackets). To estimate K_d we used an area per virus πL^2 given by the basal radius L of the spherical cap and $\Theta_{\text{max}} = 0.54$ (random packing limit).

Yet, a surprise arises when comparing the results for K_d or ΔG in Table 10.2 with those obtained for the effective adsorption energy W in Table 10.1. There is no clear correlation between W and K_d . In fact, the opposite trend tends to be the case, as the substrate with the smallest affinity for TGEV is the one presenting the largest effective adsorption energy (SiO₂-plasma, $\Delta G = -18.6 k_B T$ and $W = 8.3 \kappa/R_v^2$). And, vice versa, the MoS₂ surface ($\Delta G = -20.5 k_B T$ and $W = 5.5 \kappa/R_v^2$) presents a large affinity for the TGEV, but a relatively large virus height upon adhesion, which is compatible with a small adhesion energy W .

10.3.3 Theory and Coarse-Grained Simulations

We now present results from a fairly realistic particle-based coarse-grained (CG) model of the coronavirus and an analytical approach based on a continuum model based on a Helfrich-type free energy, generalized to include spikes. Analysis of CG simulations permit us to extract essential insights on the viral adhesion. We insert such information in the continuum model so that it provides quantitative agreement with particle simulations (Fig. 10.9C,F). By combining both approaches, we are able to match experimental results for the CoV and extract the adhesion energies of the membrane and spikes on different surfaces.

Coarse-graining simulations of adsorbed TGEV coronavirus

Coarse graining models have been extremely useful to understand the spike structure and fluctuations [201] and also the virus diffusive dynamics and its role in infection [388]. We performed an analysis of the TGEV adsorption using a CG model illus-

trated in Fig. 10.9A (Section 10.2). The model is composed of beads with effective radius $b \approx 2$ nm, used to build the lipid envelope and the spikes. The lipid envelope is modelled using a single layer of beads interacting with nearest neighbor dipolar potentials and lateral interactions based on central forces. A relevant novelty of this model, essential for this work, is to include the fluidity and flexibility of the lipid membrane [200] which allows the spike to diffuse over the envelope. To this end, each spike is bonded to one CG-lipid of the membrane (bead #4 in Fig. 10.1), which can therefore freely diffuse. The spike structure is adapted from a previous model [201] and interactions are tuned to reproduce the flexibility observed in cryo-electron tomograms [348] (Appendix C). A critical aspect of our model is the interaction of membrane and spike beads with the substrate, modelled by a potential well of depth ε per CG-bead. Specifically, the interaction energy values for the lipid membrane beads were chosen to be $\varepsilon_{\text{mem}}/k_B T = \{0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2\}$ and those for the spike beads were $\varepsilon_{\text{spk}}/k_B T = \{-1.0, 1.0, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5\}$. Positive values of ε correspond to attractive bead-substrate interactions, which are obviously required for adsorption. The negative value of ε_{spk} indicate a purely repulsive interaction of the spike with the surface (Section 10.2). Our model allows tuning the bending rigidity κ of the virus envelope, whose value is connected with the number of beads used for the CG vesicle, i.e. with the membrane area-per-bead, A_{bead} . An effective bead radius $b \approx 2$ nm (SI) leads to $A_{\text{bead}} = \pi b^2 \approx 12.50$ nm² which limits the lowest value of the membrane bending rigidity to $\kappa \simeq 40 k_B T$ (Fig. S9). Reaching smaller values ($\kappa \sim 10 k_B T$) require smaller beads, which prohibitively increases the cost in simulation time. As the model does not consider molecular details below ≈ 4 nm, it does not resolve lipid protrusion fluctuations (one CG bead corresponds to ~ 30 membrane lipids). Heterogeneity in hydrophobicity, partial charge along the spike or lipid envelope and solvent (water) degrees of freedom are neither resolved. Thus, a great deal of solvent, spike and lipid-related entropy are encoded inside the effective interaction energies ε . Despite these limitations, the CG model offers essential features to understand the different roles of the envelope and the spikes in the adhesion of CoV on surfaces.

We start by analyzing the relation between the adhesion energy and the shape of a virus with nominal radius R , determined by its height H and radius of contact on the surface L (Fig 10.6B). A reasonable ansatz for the membrane adhesion energy is $E_{\text{mem}} = \pi L^2 [\alpha \varepsilon_{\text{mem}} / (\pi b^2)]$, where we use the spherical cap approximation for the contact area $A_c \approx \pi L^2$. Note that ε_{mem} is the minima of the bead-surface potential (SI), which corresponds to the adhesion energy density at *contact* $W_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} = \varepsilon_{\text{mem}} / (\pi b^2)$. As pointed out by Lipowski [389], due to thermal fluctuations, the average energy in microscopic particle-based CG descriptions of the surface-membrane interaction (Section 10.2) is a factor $\alpha < 1$ smaller than the contact value used in continuum

descriptions. Our ansatz is verified in Fig. 10.9B, by plotting the equilibrium average of E_{mem} scaled with $\varepsilon_{\text{mem}}(L/b)^2$ against L/R for different spike and membrane interaction energies. We find that $\alpha \approx 0.35$, which it is indeed roughly constant, with a small increasing trend with L . Thus, the relation between the non-dimensional average adhesion energy and the energy per CG blob is $w_a = \alpha w^{(c)} = \alpha \varepsilon_a R^2 / (\pi b^2 \kappa) \approx 1.11 \varepsilon_a$, where $a = \text{spk}$ (spike) or mem (membrane). Values at contact, $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)}$ are shown in Fig. 10.9C against the net free energy ΔG , presented below.

The net spike adhesion energy is considered to scale as $E_{\text{spk}} = 2\pi L L_{\text{spk}} \varepsilon_{\text{spk}} / (\pi b^2)$. This relation assumes that the spike-surface contact area is proportional to the adsorbed perimeter $2\pi L$ times an effective length, L_{spk} which may depend on ε_{spk} . This dependence is clearly observed in Fig. 10.9D where $\ell_{\text{spk}} \equiv L_{\text{spk}}/R = [E_{\text{spk}}/\varepsilon_{\text{spk}}][b^2/(2LR)]$ is plotted against $\varepsilon_{\text{spk}}/k_B T$. The solid line is a fit based on a Hill adsorption isotherm model: $\ell_{\text{spk}} = \ell_{\text{spk}}^{\text{max}} p / (1 + p)$, with $p = \exp[-n \Delta\varepsilon / k_B T]$, where $\Delta\varepsilon = (-\varepsilon_{\text{spk}}) - \mu_0$ is the energy difference between the bounded and the unbounded spike, with chemical potential μ_0 [390]. The fit in Fig. 10.9D yields $n = 1.2$. Since the spike-spike interaction is not attractive the small degree of cooperativity is probably due to a small increase in the contact perimeter as ε_{spk} increases. We also find $\ell_{\text{spk}}^{\text{max}} \approx 0.25 R$ and $\mu_0 \approx -3.3 k_B T$, which are consistent with the spike length and excluded area (i.e., $\mu_0 \sim -k_B T \ln[A_{\text{cap}}/A_{\text{spike}}]$ with $A_{\text{cap}} = 2\pi R_c H$ and $A_{\text{spike}} \sim \pi(10\text{nm})^2$).

We next use umbrella sampling (Section 10.2), [292] to measure the profile of free energy difference between the bounded and unbounded state $\Delta\mathcal{G}(z)$ of CoV CG model (Fig. 10.9E) as a function of the maximum height z of the lipid envelope (Fig. 10.9A). Solid lines correspond to adhesion free energy profile $\Delta\mathcal{G}(z)$ for the CG virus model, and the dashed line correspond to the CG vesicle (i.e. the membrane envelope without spikes). The spikes introduce several relevant effects. The free energy well becomes more negative (attractive) as the spike adhesion energy is increased $\varepsilon_{\text{spk}} > 0$. However, the spikes also introduce a substantial effective repulsion of purely entropic origin. This steric interaction with the surface increases in about $10 k_B T$ the binding free energy with respect to a vesicle (this value probably increases with the number of spikes). Notably, as shown in Fig. 10.9E, even virus with mildly attractive spikes ($\varepsilon_{\text{spk}} = k_B T$, blue) present $\sim 10 k_B T$ less adhesion free energy than a naked vesicle (dashed line). The free energy of a naked envelope is in fact similar to that of a virus with rather sticky spikes $\varepsilon_{\text{spk}} = 2.0 k_B T$. For $\varepsilon_{\text{spk}} < 2 k_B T$, we find a potential barrier around $z \sim 2R_v \sim 85\text{nm}$, whose value reaches $E_b \sim 5 k_B T$. Such a barrier should lead to a significant delay in the adhesion process, similar to a reaction-limited process, with a prefactor e^{E_b} multiplying the diffusion-limit characteristic time.

To connect the free energy profiles of Fig. 10.9E with the dissociation constant K_d ,

we evaluate the average adhesion free energy $\Delta G \propto \int \Delta \mathcal{G}(z) \exp[-\beta \Delta \mathcal{G}(z)] dz$, where the integral runs over the simulation box. The result is quite close to the minimum of the profile, $\Delta G \approx \Delta \mathcal{G}_{\min}$. Results for ΔG from CG simulations are presented (filled circles, Fig. 10.9C, F) along with the results of the continuum elastic model (solid lines) presented below (Eq. 10.6). A first important message of Fig. 10.9F is that the particle height H strongly varies with the membrane adhesion energy (indicated by gray numbers in Fig. 10.9F), but it does not greatly vary with the spike adhesion energy (colored coded circles, Fig. 10.9F). Another relevant information concerns the critical adhesion energy density w_{cr} needed for a stable capture ($\Delta G > 0$). For the CG vesicle, we find unbinding for $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} < w_{cr}$ where $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} \equiv R^2 W_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} / \kappa$. For the CG model, the critical adhesion parameter is $w_{cr} \approx 2$, which is in excellent agreement with theoretical predictions based on continuum elasticity [384, 389]. This unbinding transition at finite adhesion energy have energetic and entropic origins. For $w^{(c)} < w_{cr}$, the elastic energy penalty created the vesicle-surface contact line, with curvature $\lambda^{-1} = [2W/\kappa]^{1/2}$, overpowers the adhesion energy. Close to the transition ($w^{(c)} \geq w_{cr}$) the contact area roughly scales as $A_c/R^2 \sim \Delta w$ with $\Delta w = w - w_{cr}$. Similar to the Casimir effect [145], a positive free energy density associated to membrane fluctuations $w_{fluc} \sim (k_B T R / \kappa d)^2$ [205] is created due to the reduction of the membrane undulations entropy, when confined in a layer of width d [389]. Energetic unbinding yields $w_{cr} = 2$ and dominates for small particles (below 100 nm size [389]). Yet, for the CG vesicle we get $w_{fluc} \sim 1$ for an adsorbed layer of $d \sim 1$ nm, which is not negligible. Interestingly, we observe that the presence of adsorbed spikes slightly increases w_{cr} (see below), which could be consistent with an increase of the local curvature at contact, or an increase in the steric undulation repulsion by reducing d .

Continuum elastic theory for CoV adsorption

We developed a simple continuum model for coronavirus adsorption which permit us to connect with the experimental results and the CG virus model. The virus envelope is approximated as an elastic spherical cap with base radius L , height H and curvature radius $R_c = H/2 + L^2/2H$. The envelope area is taken to be constant over the adsorption process (an approximation commonly used for lipid vesicles [382, 384]): hence $4\pi R^2 = \pi L^2 + A_{cap}$ with $A_{cap} = 2\pi R_c H$ the spherical cap area. This yields, $L = (2 - H^2/2)^{1/2}$ which determines the envelope adhesion energy $-W_{\text{mem}}\pi L^2$. The spike-surface interaction energy $-W_{\text{spk}}\pi L L_{\text{spk}}$ is proportional to the perimeter of the contact line $2\pi L$ and the surface-projected effective spike length, L_{spk} discussed in Fig. 10.9D. The elastic energy is proportional to the bending rigidity κ , and it follows from the Helfrich-Canham description [205, 389]. In describing the elastic energy, the spherical cap approximation becomes valid in the pancake regime (highly deformed

Figure 10.9: (A) Illustration of the CG virus model. The membrane is composed by self-aggregating mobile polar beads of radius $b \approx 2$ nm and the spike is an elastic-network with realistic values of flexibility and diffusivity (Section 10.2). The adhesion energy per bead is noted as ϵ_{mem} (blue) for the envelope and ϵ_{spk} for the spikes (red) (the figure corresponds to $\epsilon_{\text{spk}} = 3.0 k_B T$ and $\epsilon_{\text{mem}} = 0.8 k_B T$). (B) Average membrane adhesion energy scaled with $\pi L^2 \epsilon_{\text{mem}} / (\pi b^2)$; the dashed line corresponds to the mean value $\alpha = 0.35$. The color-coded filled circles indicate the energy of the spike CG beads ϵ_{spk} (in $k_B T$ units). (C) Envelope non-dimensional adhesion energy at contact $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} = \epsilon_{\text{mem}} R^2 / (\pi b^2 \kappa)$ against the total adsorption free energy. (D) Effective spike adsorption length $\ell_{\text{spk}} \equiv L_{\text{spk}} / R = E_{\text{spk}} / [2 \epsilon_{\text{spk}} L R / b^2]$; where E_{spk} is the total spike adhesion energy. The solid line is a fit to the adsorbed population of a Hill model $\ell_{\text{spk}} = \ell_{\text{max}} p / (1 + p)$ with $\ell_{\text{max}} = 0.25$ and $p = e^{-n([-\epsilon_{\text{spk}}] - \mu_0) / k_B T}$ with Hill index $n = 1.2$ and chemical potential for unbounded spikes $\mu_0 = -3.3 k_B T$. (E) Free energy profiles $\Delta G(z)$ associated to the envelope maximum height z (see A), obtained from umbrella sampling ($\epsilon_{\text{mem}} = 0.8 k_B T$). (F) The CG virus height H/R against the unbounded-net free energy difference $-\Delta G/\kappa$ scaled with the CG-model bending rigidity $\kappa \approx 40 k_B T$ (Section 10.2). The inset corresponds to the CG-vesicle (no spikes). Lines in (B) and (E) corresponds to the theoretical model in Eq. (10.6). In (F) the gray figures (and dotted lines) indicate the isolines of $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} = R^2 W_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} / \kappa$.

particle) observed for the virus particles. Therefore we opt for a simplification of the theoretical model, which does not explicitly describe the elastic energy excess close to the contact line with curvature $(2W/\kappa)^{1/2}$ [389]. Instead, we take into account elastic and entropic repulsive effects (due to the reduction of the membrane undulation entropy) by introducing an effective "unbinding" free energy density w_{cr} which induces a shift in the membrane adhesion energy as $\Delta w = w_{mem} - w_{cr}$. As shown in Fig. 10.9F, this approximation (colored lines) quantitatively matches the results from CG simulations (filled circles), even close to the unbinding transition ($\Delta G > 0$ in Fig. 10.9C). The work of compression is $-\Delta P [4\pi R^3/3 - V_{cap}]$, with deformed envelope volume $V_{cap} = (\pi H^2/3)(3R_c - H)$ and internal excess pressure ΔP . We use κ and $R = R_v$ as reference units to obtain non-dimensional quantities: $g = G/\kappa$, $h = H/R$, $\ell = L/R$, $r_c = R_c/R$, $a_{cap} = A_{cap}/R^2$ and the volume change $\delta v = (V_{cap}/R^3) - 4\pi/3$ with $\kappa_p = \Delta P R^3/\kappa$. Finally, $w_a = W_a R^2/\kappa$, with a either membrane or spike, and W_a the average adhesion energy density. The analysis of the CG virus model leads to the following the continuum version of the adsorption free energy,

$$g = -\Delta w_{mem} \pi \ell^2 + \frac{1}{2} a_{cap} (2r_c^{-1} - c_0)^2 - \kappa_p \delta v + g_{spk} \quad (10.6)$$

where the spikes' contribution contain an adhesive and a repulsive depletion term: $g_{spk} = -w_{spk} 2\pi \ell_{spk} + g_{steric}$. From Fig. 10.9E we take the spikes steric interaction with the surface as $g_{steric} = 10k_B T/\kappa$ and $\ell_{spk} = L_{spk}/R$ is taken from Fig. 10.9D. Also, the best fit to CG-model results in Fig. 10.9C yields $w_{cr} = 2 + 0.1w_{spk}$.

In order to compare the theoretical model with the CG-virus model, we use $\kappa = 40k_B T$ and a small spontaneous curvature, $c_0 = 0.2$, consistent with the vesicle model (Section 10.2). In the CG model, the excess in internal pressure is solely due to surface tension: from the Laplace relation $\Delta P = 2\Sigma/R$ and thus $\kappa_p = 2\Sigma R^2/\kappa$. The lateral bead-bead interaction energy is about $k_B T$, so $\Sigma \simeq k_B T/(\pi b^2) \approx 3.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{J/m}^2$. This yields $\kappa_p = 6.3$ which leads to an excellent agreement with the CG-results. Figures 10.9C and F show quantitative agreement between the model in Eq. 10.6 (solid lines) and the free energy ΔG from umbrella sampling simulations on the CG virus model. This gives us confidence to deploy the theoretical model for the analysis of the experimental results for the TGEV. The thick virus envelope, containing multiple types of membrane proteins (E and M) presents a large spontaneous curvature [391]. Thus we choose $c_0 = 1$ and the previously estimated $\kappa = 10k_B T$ which leads to $\kappa_p = 3$ as the best fit to experimental results using Eq. 10.6. It is important to remark that using these parameters in Eq. 10.6, we reproduce the envelope adhesion energies estimated from AFM profiles in Table 10.1 (Figs. 10.10 and 10.11). The estimation for κ_p is consistent with the Laplace pressure induced by the above reported

surface tensions, $\Sigma \sim 10^{-4} \text{J/m}^2$. Note that TGEV particles are fully filled with a protein-condensed RNA chain, which barely creates osmotic pressure. The compression response of the TGEV particle under AFM indentation is thus far from the "soft" ($\kappa \approx 14k_B T$) but pressurized lipid vesicles studied by Wuite's *et al.*[382], which reached MPa internal pressures due to a large concentration of impermeable osmolites (free lipids). In fact, under compression, the TGEV acts more like a soft polymer nanodroplet. AFM indentation curves reveal that the effective spring constant for TGEV compression is $k_{sp} \approx 0.01 \text{N/m}$ [106], similar to SARS-CoV-2 (0.013 N/m [357]). This value is consistent with a soft polymeric material [392] with Young modulus around $E \sim k_{sp}/R \sim 200 \text{kPa}$. In fact, we verified that for this Young modulus range, the elastic theory for soft nanodroplets [392] reproduces the experimental values of H , ΔG shown with circles in Fig. 10.10. An exploration of this dual characterization (vesicle-like versus nanopolymer-like) is left for future work.

The analysis of the adhesion energy densities is particularly interesting. Results of the continuum model of Eq. 10.6 are presented in Fig. 10.10 (solid lines). Figure 10.11 collects results for ΔG and the non-dimensional adhesion energies $w_a^{(c)} = W_a^{(c)} R^2 / \kappa$ for each surface and highlights the excellent agreement between Eq. 10.6 and the values for $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)}$ in Table 10.1, obtained from the analysis of AFM-profiles (Fig.10.11B). In the case of the spikes, our estimations are in the range $W_{\text{spk}} \sim [1 - 3] \times 10^{-4} \text{J/m}^2$; which is consistent with the Derjaguin approximation on the pulling force experiments of isolated spikes using AFM [393]: $W = F/(2\pi R_{\text{tip}}) \in [8 - 20] \times 10^{-4} \text{J/m}^2$ for silicon-oxide tips and $W < 3 \times 10^{-4} \text{J/m}^2$ for other metal oxides.

Figure 10.10 shows the interplay between the membrane and spike adhesion energies of TGEV in different surfaces. Membrane-substrate energies (indicated by small black figures over the lines) range between $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} \approx 5$ for MoS₂ and mica to $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} \approx 8$ for SiO₂-plasma and mica-PLL where the virus is more deformed (lowest H). As shown in the inset of Fig. 10.10 under such a range of adhesion energies, a standard vesicle would undergo a large modification in shape, from a small distortion $h = H/R \approx 1.8$ to a pancake shape $h \approx 1.0$ at $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} \approx 8$. In the TGEV, the spikes make the difference: the spike adhesion energy is stronger $w_{\text{spk}}^{(c)} \approx 9.4$ in those surfaces with the smallest membrane adhesion (MoS₂ and mica) while w_{spk} is smaller for surfaces with strong membrane-substrate attraction (SiO₂-plasma and mica-PLL). In the discussion section we argue that this adhesion "adaptability" of the TGEV to quite different surfaces is due to the different electrostatic nature of the spike and the membrane envelope.

Figure 10.10: Scaled particle height against the scaled adsorption free energy ($\Delta G/\kappa < 0$). Lines corresponds to the theoretical model in Eq. 10.6 using $c_0 = 1$ and $\kappa_p = 3$. Experimental results for ΔG for TGEV (circles) are scaled with $\kappa = 10 k_B T$. Values of $W_{\text{mem}}^{(c)} R^2/\kappa$ are indicated with small black figures and $W_{\text{spike}}^{(c)} R^2/\kappa$ indicated with large colored figures. (Inset) Theoretical prediction for a vesicle (no spikes) over the range of adhesion energy density predicted for the virus.

10.4 Discussion

Using AFM, coarse-grained simulations and a theoretical approach, this work evaluates the adhesion free energy and affinity of coronavirus (TGEV) to different substrates, as well as virus mechanical properties, such as bending rigidity, deformation and surface energy per area W (Table 10.1). Additionally, using AFM images for virus counting and a precise mapping of the virus bulk concentration via its genome mass, we draw Langmuir isotherms and measure dissociation constants K_d and adhesion free energies $\Delta G \sim -20k_B T$ for different surfaces (Table 10.2). Our findings can be discussed in several lines. In the applied side, our results confirm that surface cleaning and functionalization can be an efficient way to modulate viral attachment, either towards a higher degree of viral capture or towards the prevention of viral adsorption. Although seemingly small, the differences in adhesion free energy between surfaces $\Delta G \in [-17, -21]$ lead to substantially different virus desorption times. Kramer's escape-time relation (Chapter 5), $\tau_{esc} \approx (6\pi\eta R_v \delta^2 / k_B T) e^{-\Delta G / k_B T}$, for a width of the free-energy potential well of $\delta \sim 10$ nm and η as the water viscosity, leads to estimates for desorption waiting times of $\tau_{esc} \sim 7$ hours for MoS₂, while just about 6 minutes for SiO₂-plasma. Similar exponential effects lead to a substantial difference in the number of virus captured, with a factor 15 difference between surfaces. In particular, we find MoS₂ to be the best surface for virus capture, followed by SiO₂. In this line, we find that plasma cleaning of surfaces appears as a possible way to significantly prevent coronavirus adsorption, which may be relevant, for instance, as a pre-treatment for hospital material. Our results indicate that O₂ plasma-cleaning of SiO₂ reduces the capacity of SiO₂ to capture TGEV, when compared to isopropanol-cleaned SiO₂ and the rest of surfaces under study. We also explored the use of bicomponent surfaces to sense, in a single experiment, the capacity of viral particles to attach to different surfaces. Using this approach, we find that MoS₂ captures four more times virus than SiO₂ cleaned with isopropanol, making this material a good candidate for applications such as air filters, mopping material or biosensors. Given the capacity of MoS₂ to affect lipid membranes under blue light irradiation [394], it could be used as a double-purpose material which not only captures viruses but also inactivates them. Precisely, a recent study in this direction used TiO₂ substrates and ultraviolet light to deactivate the SARS-CoV-2 virus [367]. Additionally, experiments with mica and mica functionalized with poly-L-lysine (PLL) have shown that surface functionalization can improve virus adhesion, however up to a more moderate factor of two (Table 10.2).

The study of the virus profiles using AFM surprisingly showed that differences in viral capture (Table 10.2) are not correlated to the virus height or deformation measured from the contact angle θ_0 (10.1). For instance, adsorption on the MoS₂ surface leads to less deformed virus $\theta_0 \approx 88^\circ$ than on SiO₂ cleaned with O₂ plasma

Figure 10.11: Illustration of the different conformations of the coronavirus according to the spike and membrane adhesion at each surface. (A) Experimentally measured adhesion free energy $-\Delta G/k_B T$. (B) Circles indicate the values of $w_{\text{spk}}^{(c)}$ and $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)}$ derived from Eq. 10.6 which match the experimental values of H and ΔG , as shown in Fig. 10.10. Squares correspond to $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)}$ derived from the analysis of AFM profiles (Table 10.1). Dashed lines, drawn to guide the eye, highlight the opposite trends for $w_{\text{spk}}^{(c)}$ and $w_{\text{mem}}^{(c)}$. (C) CG simulations for a case with large membrane adhesion (left), large spike adhesion (right) and similar adhesion (middle).

$\theta_0 \approx 55^\circ$. Yet, MoS_2 captures about 14 times more virus (Table 10.2). This behavior is certainly at odds with that found in the case of simple vesicles, whose deformation obviously increases with the adhesion energy W . Coarse-grained simulations of the coronavirus and a Helfrich-type model generalized to include spike contributions, were used to explain this surprising result. The key connection between experiments and theory was the calculation of the surface affinity via the dissociation constant K_d for each surface (highly correlated with the viral capture, Table 10.2). The relatively small differences in $K_d \in [1 - 20]$ nM amongst surfaces could only be explained by the complementary physicochemical nature or surface-interaction observed in the spikes and the CoV lipid envelope. For instance, MoS_2 should present a high attraction to the CoV spikes, but a mild interaction with the virus membrane while, the opposite takes place in the case of SiO_2 -plasma surface. As shown in Fig. 10.11B, the counter-correlation between the surface-energy density of the membrane W_{mem} and the spike W_{spk} (blue and orange lines respectively) is pretty consistent when taking into account all the studied cases.

Moreover, it is interesting to highlight that ΔG and K_d for our surfaces (1 to 20 nM) are similar to the binding affinity of SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV spikes to ACE2 receptors whose kinetics were studied by surface plasmon resonance [395] and biolayer interferometry binding analysis [396]. This later work reports values of $K_d = 1.2$ nM for SARS-CoV-2 and 5 nM for SARS-CoV, close to several works on umbrella sampling MD simulations [397, 398], precisely finding $\Delta G \approx -20k_B T$ for the RBD-ACE binding free energy. Larger values (i.e. smaller affinity) were reported for the spike-ACE2 in other experiments [395] (up to 100 nM). Taking into account that membrane-membrane interfacial energies can be of the same order or even larger [145] than surface-membrane energies ($W \sim [0.1 - 10]$ mJ/m²), our results suggest some nuances to the standard entry pathway picture. The CoV might adsorb to the host, diffuse over the host cell membrane and eventually use several entry pathways, aside from the RBD-ACE2 receptor route. This is confirmed by recent results [354] showing, however, that ACE2 receptor *enhances* the entry rate.

Although this work is not focused on surface chemistry details, we attempt some discussion on the putative molecular origins underlying the alleged membrane and spike complementarity in terms of surface interaction. We start by assuming that the virus membrane (similar to the membrane it steals) is slightly negatively charged and of polar nature, hydrophilic and prompt to form hydrogen bonds. By contrast, at biological pH 7 (used in our experiments), the spike S1 has been reported to be positively charged in virtually all variants of CoV [399], which is quite probably related to natural evolution towards the negatively charged ACE2 receptor. The spike also presents a relatively high dipole pointing outwards the S1 unit [400]. This brief description already points out some degree of complementarity for the spikes and the virus mem-

brane interactions. At the electrostatic level, mica is negatively charged, which might attract the spikes. Consistently, in mica we find one of the highest spike adhesion energies, which is similar to what has been found in quartz-microbalance studies in mica [366]. By contrast, mica-PLL ($C_5H_{12}N_2O$)-n leads to a high positive charge, which would in principle enhance the interaction with negatively-charged phosphate groups from lipids and repel the spikes. This interpretation is consistent with our results (Fig. 10.10).

Our findings suggest a strong attraction of the virus membrane to SiO_2 -plasma, which is hydrophilic (due to the so formed SiOH groups) and probably presents a small negative charge. However, supported lipid bilayer formation upon rupture of negatively charged vesicles is readily observed in silica under small amount of positive charge [352] (not in mica, unless calcium added to screen electrostatic repulsion). The possibility of hydrophilic attraction is strongly enhanced by the formation of hydrogen bonds [351]. In SiO_2 -plasma, we find a mild interaction with the spikes (Fig. 10.11B), but the reason why is not clear, and it might be due to the negatively charged glycoproteins (apparently designed to avoid detection by negatively charged antibodies [401]). SiO_2 -isopropanol is mainly hydrophobic and neutral, so there should not be a strong attraction or repulsion to the membrane or the spike. HOPG is also very hydrophobic and neutral. Moderate attraction from *both* W_{mem} and W_{spk} (Fig. 10.11) probably due to dispersion forces and hydrophobic patches in the virus envelope [344], seems to optimize virus capture. Finally, MoS_2 is neutral and hydrophobic, which should explain the moderate membrane attraction, large contact angle and small virus deformation (Table 10.1). However, MoS_2 is well known for having a strong affinity to the coronavirus spike [402], partly due to the formation of disulfide bonds with the relatively abundant cysteines in the spike [403]. This explains the large spike- MoS_2 energy leading to the highest viral capture (Table 10.1). As an aside, although the RBD - MoS_2 affinity is high and similar to the RBD-ACE affinity (about 11 nM [343]) a recently developed nanomaterial reaches the pM range [343].

The TGEV ability to adhere to disparate surfaces, added to its exceptional self-healing properties [357] surely help its adaptation to a wide range of environmental circumstances. Our study unveils that the TGEV adaptability to adhere on different surfaces is due to a seemingly complementary physicochemical nature of the lipid envelope and the spikes. This adaptability and versatility of the coronavirus family might be the reason why three coronaviruses have already crossed the species barrier to cause deadly pneumonia in humans since the beginning of the 21st century: SARS, Middle-East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), and SARS-CoV-2. The multidisciplinary single-particle methodology proposed here might help in finding potential therapies or prophylactic alternatives.

Chapter 11

Electromechanical photophysics of packed GFP

Adapted from: "Electromechanical Photophysics of GFP Packed Inside Viral Protein Cages Probed by Force-Fluorescence Hybrid Single-Molecule Microscopy", Klara Strobl, Ekaterina Selivanovitch, Pablo Ibáñez-Freire et al. Small 2022, 18, 2200059.

Proteins in living systems often function in highly crowded and confined environments, such as inside cellular compartments. These conditions can significantly influence protein behavior, including their conformational dynamics, aggregation propensity, and overall function [404–408]. To study proteins under confinement, we can use nanoscale molecular containers that mimic the crowded conditions found in nature [409–411]. These synthetic compartments not only provide insights into protein behavior in cellular environments but also have potential technological applications [412–414].

In this work, we employ virus-like particles (VLPs) derived from the P22 bacteriophage as a model system to study the effect of confinement on proteins [163, 301, 415]. In particular, we employ green fluorescent protein (GFP) [416]. This protein exhibits green fluorescence when exposed to light in the ultraviolet range. Since the fluorescent behavior of GFP is related to both its environment and its structure [417], we can obtain information about the effect of confinement by analyzing the fluorescence signal. For producing VLPs filled with some protein, the target protein is fused with another protein the virus uses to assemble itself (called scaffolding protein) [415, 418–420]. As a result, when the capsid of phage P22 self-assembles, it also assembles the target protein, GFP in our case, with it. These GFPs remain linked to the scaffolding protein, which interacts in a specific way with certain regions of the capsid [105]. The resulting structure of the VLP filled with GFP is the virus capsid with the proteins distributed throughout the lumen and attached to the capsid via the scaffolding protein, as shown in Fig. 11.1A

By packaging GFP within the P22 VLP capsid, we created a well-defined, crowded environment that allowed us to measure the fluorescence of individual GFP-filled VLPs using a combination of atomic force microscopy (AFM) and total internal reflection fluorescence microscopy (TIRFM) [327, 421–424] (Fig. 11.1B). The custom-built AFM-TIRFM setup allow us for the simultaneous visualization of individual VLPs using fluorescence microscopy while we are able to manipulate them using the AFM tip [327].

Figure 11.1: A) To produce GFP-filled VLPs, the scaffolding protein (the protein employed by the VLP for its assembly) is fused with GFP. This protein is distributed on the inner surface of the capsid [105], resulting in a final distribution of the attached GFP as shown in the figure. B) Schematic of the experimental setup, where the VLPs are represented as green spheres. C and D) Correspondence between the AFM image of a VLP distribution and its corresponding signal in the TIRFM. As shown in this example, sometimes the diffraction spot of the TIRFM does not allow distinguishing the VLPs, while this is possible using AFM.

To study individual P22 VLPs, an AFM tip is approached to the apex of the particles (Fig. 11.1B). TIRFM setup is then used to selectively excite GFP-loaded P22 VLPs adsorbed on a glass surface, enabling correlative identification of VLP patterns from both AFM and TIRFM (Fig. 11.1C-D). Force-distance (FZ) measurements (indentations) are performed at the apex of individual P22 VLPs to investigate their

mechanical properties [425] (Fig. 11.2A). As the AFM tip deforms the VLP, the FZ curve shows a non-linear stepwise regime (Fig. 11.2B-C, black) corresponding to unzipping events between capsomers [425–427], leading to fractures between VLP subunits [23]. At the same time as we perform the indentation on VLP with the AFM tip we record the fluorescence signal, in this way we are able to measure the effect that the change in confinement has on the encapsulated GFPs. To perform the indentation we use two types of AFM tips: an insulator (Si_3N_4) and a conductor (Au-covered).

To investigate the effect of mechanical deformations (changes in confinement) on the encapsulated GFPs, we perform a series of indentations using the two types of tips. In both cases, we observe fluorescence **quenching** during the indentation process (quenching, in this context, refers to a decrease in the fluorescence intensity of the GFPs). However, the way this quenching process evolves differs significantly between the two types of tips.

When using the Si_3N_4 tip (insulator), the fluorescence remains constant during the initial stages of indentation, even during linear deformation of the VLP structure (Fig. 11.2B). Quenching begins coinciding with force steps indicating yielding and breaking of the protein shell, reaching a minimum once the particle collapsed. After the tip is released, the fluorescence recovers to its initial value, demonstrating the reversibility of the deformation process.

In contrast, when using Au-covered tips (conductive), fluorescence quenching starts before the tip touches the VLP and reaches a plateau upon contact (Fig. 11.2C). Quenching resumes during the mechanical rupture of the VLP. As with the Si_3N_4 tips (insulator), the fluorescence recovers to its original magnitude after tip release.

To explore the interplay between VLP structural state and fluorescence emission, we perform consecutive AFM tip indentations measurements on the same particle (using both tip types) to induce progressive and permanent damage until the VLP collapsed [428] (Fig. 11.3A). With Au tips the maximum quenching (for which fluorescence is reduced about 20 percent), occurs when the VLP is intact (the first indentation). With consecutive indentations, as the particle dismantles and the material is expelled, the quenching gradually decreases (Fig. 11.3B-C). In the case of insulator tips (Si_3N_4), quenching is lower (Fig. 11.3D-E). The response to successive indentations is similar to that observed with Au tips. The maximum quenching occurs during the first indentation (in this case, fluorescence is reduced by about 10 percent), and the emission continues to decrease with subsequent indentations. However, there is an important difference in the response of the sample between the two types of tips. The Au tip is able to produce quenching even when the VLP has collapsed, quenching the GFP debris. In contrast, the Si_3N_4 tips do not produce any effect on the fluorescence of these debris (Fig. 11.3G). The quenching behavior is summarized by plotting the

Figure 11.2: Diagram of the AFM indentation experiment showing the three stages of the process, from non-contact (left) to virus collapse (right). B, C) Combined data charts of the synchronously measured force (black) and light (green) for Si_3N_4 and Au-covered tips, respectively. The blue vertical dashed lines indicate the moment at which the fluorescence decrease begin (quenching).

maximum quenching (q_{\max}) as a function of VLP height for multiple particles probed with Au and Si_3N_4 tips (Fig. 11.3F).

The different behaviors observed with conductive and insulating tips suggests the possibility of *multiple quenching mechanisms*. In particular, the results obtained could be explained by the presence of two quenching mechanisms, one **mechanical** and the other **electronic**. The mechanical quenching would be produced by the deformations of the VLP while the electronic quenching would be due to the conductive nature of the Au tips.

First we examine the origin of electronic quenching. In both cases (when we use the Au tip or the Si_3N_4 tip) the fluorescence recovers after the indentations. However, the initial behavior differs in the two cases. In the case of Si_3N_4 tips quenching starts when the tip has indented the VLP, by contrast, in the case of Au tips the quenching starts before the indentation, i.e. Au tips are able to induce quenching at a distance (Fig 11.1B-C). This type of phenomenology can be explained by the coupling of the surface plasmon resonance [428] with the emissive states of GFP. In a nutshell, the oscillatory field of light induces a collective movement of free electrons present on the surface of the Au tip (the Si_3N_4 tip lacks these electrons, as it is an insulator). The amplitude of these oscillations reaches a maximum at certain frequencies; this phenomenon is known as surface plasmon resonance (SPR). This SPR couples with the emissive states of GFPs, resulting in quenching (a detailed description of the process can be found in [220]).

To study the origin of mechanical quenching, we will only use the Si_3N_4 tip, thus ensuring that there is no electronic quenching. From the results obtained so far, we can deduce that mechanical quenching arises as a consequence of the modification of GFP confinement. However, we do not know how the internal structure of GFPs encapsulated in the VLP conditions this behavior. To investigate this, we carried out indentations varying the concentration of GFP encapsulated in the VLPs [419]. Using these VLPs, we observed mechanical quenching only in those with a relatively high concentration of GFPs. VLPs with 47% GFP loading exhibit mechanical quenching, those with 21% loading do not (Fig. 11.4), indicating that mechanical quenching depends on structure and the crowding conditions of GFPs inside the P22 VLP.

Determining this structure and how it relates to mechanical quenching is not feasible experimentally. Therefore, we carried out a coarse grained simulation of the process. To simulate this process, we use alpha carbon resolution models (Chapter 1). These models have been previously applied to study capsid compression using AFM [66, 109]. To construct the model, we take the crystal structure of the P22 phage capsid [429], from which the VLP is derived, and GFP [430] and we connect them using a unstructured protein linker, which sequence is known [415]. This structure reproduces

Figure 11.3: A) AFM topographies of the same VLP throughout the disruption process induced by ten consecutive indentations B) Sequential topographical profiles after performing the corresponding indentations with Au tip. C) Normalized fluorescence evolution along each indentation on the corresponding topographic profile of (B) with the same color code. D) Sequential topographical profiles after executing the corresponding indentations with an Si₃N₄ tip on an intact particle. E) The normalized fluorescence evolution along each indentation on the corresponding topographic profile of (D) with the same color code. F) Fluorescence evolution charts of five and eight VLPs during the gradual disruption induced by Au (red) and Si₃N₄ (blue) tips, respectively. Quenching q is defined as $q = 1 - f$, where f is the normalized fluorescence. The dotted lines correspond to panels (B, C) and (D, E). The thick lines depict the average for Au (red) and Si₃N₄ tips (blue). Only the Au tip was able to quench the fluorescence of collapsed particles (10 nm in height). G) Normalized fluorescence evolution during an indentation (black chart, left axis) performed on unpacked GFP debris with Si₃N₄ (blue) and Au (red) tips.

Figure 11.4: Probing mechanical quenching of VLPs with low GFP packing fraction. Simultaneous indentation and fluorescence data of A) 47% and B) 21% GFP-loaded VLPs, including the light of the control particles. While quenching still occurred with 100 GFPs inside the cage, it was suppressed when the cargo was reduced to 40 GFPs.

the structure of the VLP with GFPs.

By studying the simulations, we can deduce the origin of mechanical quenching. Before starting the indentation. When the system has reached equilibrium, we observe that the GFPs have aggregated. When we begin the indentation, we see how certain GFPs undergo an unfolding process, which can be considered the cause of quenching. Some protein residues near the linker separate from the structure. It has been experimentally determined that GFP must be completely intact to emit [417], so it is expected that these GFPs undergoing an unfolding process will stop emitting.

This interpretation explains the previous phenomenology. The recovery of emission occurs because once mechanical stress is no longer exerted on those proteins that are partially unfolded, they refold. The aggregation of GFPs is also necessary for unfolding to occur, as the simulations show that it is due to the compression of these aggregates that certain GFPs unfold. Therefore, we stop observing mechanical quenching when the concentration of GFPs inside the VLPs is reduced, because in this situation, the GFPs are not capable of forming aggregates.

In conclusion, through single-molecule experiments and simulations, we have demonstrated that the fluorescence of GFP within the VLPs could be reversibly quenched by two distinct mechanisms: mechanical and electronic. Mechanical quenching, induced by the physical disruption of the VLP structure with an insulating AFM tip, was found to be dependent on the integrity of the capsid and the tight packing of GFPs. In contrast, electronic quenching, caused by the interaction between GFP and a conductive AFM tip, occurred regardless of the structural state of the VLP.

Figure 11.5: Coarse-grained molecular dynamics simulation of the GFP aggregates (green) inside a P22 procapsid (blue) before deformation. In this 3D image, one half of the capsid has been removed to show the internal configuration of the GFPs located below the virus lumen. B) A deformed virus where the partially unfolded GFPs are highlighted in red.

While crowding has minimal impact on GFP emission, it favors aggregation that affects their response to mechanical stimuli. Therefore, our experiments mainly probe the effect of crowding on the GFPs sensitivity to changes in the mechanical microenvironment due to their aggregation.

11.1 How were the computational tools used in this work?

The system consists of a virus-like particle (VLP), specifically the capsid of a P22 virus, as well as a series of proteins (GFP) attached to the capsid through a linker, which is an unstructured amino acid sequence.

To simulate this system, we combine different models, all of them at carbon-alpha resolution. These models were presented in Chapter 1. For the capsid, we employ the self-organized polymer (SOP) model described in section 1.1. This model has been widely used for simulating virus deformations [277, 278]. The model requires parameterization by determining the average interaction energy between amino acids [110], i.e., the average interaction energy between native contacts, ϵ (Section 1.1). Since we are not interested in the response of the VLP itself but rather its contents, we determine this parameter by inspection. We select a series of parameters in the valid range $\epsilon \in (0.8, 1.2)\text{kcal/mol}$ [65] and then simulations of VLP indentation are performed until they match the experiments. We obtain a value of $\epsilon = 1.0\text{kcal/mol}$, which is similar to that reported in other studies for virus indentations [110].

Once we have a model for the capsid, we proceed to model the rest of the system. Each GFP is also modeled using the SOP model, which has been previously used to study this protein [65] so we use the parameters employed in that work. The GFP is

connected to the virus capsid through an unstructured region. For this part, we employ pairwise bonds and angular bonds parameterized as described in [35]. As discussed in section 1.1.3, for the interaction between different beads that do not interact through bonds, we use a protein interaction model. In this case, we employ the Kim-Hummer model, described in section 1.2, for both GFP-GFP and GFP-VLP interactions.

Regarding the coupling between the linker and the VLP, a simple harmonic bond is considered between the last amino acid of the VLP protein and the linker.

For the evolution of the system, we employ a BBK-type Langevin integrator with a friction coefficient of 0.2 ps^{-1} . This friction coefficient is significantly lower than that of water, but by selecting this coefficient, we accelerate the system dynamics while ensuring thermalization. This is known as Kramer's turnover and is a widely used technique in the simulation of coarse-grained models [240].

All the models used have been introduced in `UAMMD-structured`. In particular, the Kim-Hummer model employs the solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) of each residue to weight the interaction. In `UAMMD-structured`, adding this type of information is straightforward. In this case, since it is different for each amino acid (depending on the structure), it is not possible to indicate it through types, so we specify it in the "state" section (described in 6.7). Adding this new type of information to `UAMMD-structured` is a simple process using USCM [235].

Finally, we need to place all the copies of GFP while ensuring there are no collisions with other components. When this work was done, `VLMP` had not yet been developed, so it was not used for this project. However, `VLMP` has all the mentioned models (SOP, Kim-Hummer, IDPs, etc.), so this simulation could be easily performed using `VLMP` tools.

For the AFM simulation, we use two parallel plates that compress the system. This model reduces the complexity of the simulation, as otherwise, modifications to the model would be required to ensure correct interaction with the substrate and that the sample does not move during indentation [110, 278]. This model has been widely used for simulating AFM indentations of viruses [66].

Using MDAnalysis [431, 432], we confirm that native contacts of the GFPs break following the definition given in [58]. Through this method, we are able to identify the GFPs that undergo an unfolding process.

Chapter 12

Mechanical response of phased A-tracts

Adapted from: "Mechanical response of phased A-tracts through coarsegrained MD simulations", Nerea Alcazar-Cano, Pablo Ibáñez-Freire et al. To be submitted

DNA is the biological molecule responsible for storing genetic information in living organisms. Its structure and mechanical properties play a crucial role in various cellular processes, such as gene regulation, DNA repair, and DNA packaging [55–57, 433–437]. The conformation and flexibility of a DNA fragment are strongly dependent on its sequence, and this relationship has been the focus of numerous experimental and computational studies [438–445].

DNA packaging is a critical process that enables the efficient storage and protection of genetic information within the cell. The mechanical properties of DNA, which are largely determined by its sequence, play a crucial role in this process [55, 435–437]. One of the key structures involved in DNA packaging is the nucleosome, which consists of DNA wrapped around positively charged proteins called histones (Fig. 12.1) [433, 447]. The ability of DNA to bend and wrap around histones is strongly influenced by its local sequence-dependent structure and flexibility [448, 449]. Consequently, understanding the relationship between DNA sequence and its mechanical properties is essential for elucidating the mechanisms underlying DNA packaging and its regulation [56, 57].

A particularly interesting example of how DNA structure and flexibility depend on its sequence is provided by A-tract sequences [56, 450]. A-tracts are DNA fragments containing four or more consecutive A:T base pairs, with no interruptions by other base pair combinations. When these A-tracts are periodically located along the DNA molecule and in sync with the helical twist of the DNA, the molecule exhibits a pronounced spontaneous curvature. This curvature can accumulate over longer distances, leading to the formation of large-scale superhelical structures [451, 452].

Figure 12.1: Image of a nucleosome generated from the structure obtained in [446] (PDB:2CV5). A) Top view of the structure, the DNA is represented in red and the histones in blue. Note that although a single color is used, histones are a set of proteins [433]. B) Side view of the nucleosome, the color code is similar to the previous case. As can be seen, the DNA makes more than one turn around each histone.

In addition to causing overall curvature, the periodic placement of A-tracts also leads to a narrowing of certain regions along the DNA molecule. This narrowing plays a crucial role in the formation of nucleosomes. The narrowed regions of the DNA, caused by the A-tracts, have a higher negative charge density, which allows them to interact more strongly with the positively charged histones, facilitating the formation of nucleosomes [55]. As a result, A-tracts may play a central role in DNA packaging.

The mechanical properties of A-tracts have been a topic of debate in the literature [52]. While some studies suggest that A-tracts are rigid at short length scales [453–456], others indicate that there is no significant effect on bending deformations when compared to random sequences [457–459]. A recent single-molecule study by Marin-Gonzalez et al. [444] has shed light on this controversy by analysing the mechanical response of A-tracts over a wide range of external forces using magnetic tweezers and the different conformations of A-tracts over a surface by using AFM imaging. The study concluded that these molecules show increased stretching stiffness while maintaining standard bending rigidity, and exhibit a non-trivial mechanical response to pulling forces that cannot be described by conventional polymer theories.

In this work, we investigate the conformational and mechanical properties of long DNA molecules containing phased A-tracts using coarse-grained simulations and how they can be related with packaging.

By employing the MADna (mechanically accurate DNA) model introduced in section 1.1.2, we are able to simulate DNA molecules with several hundreds of base pairs while maintaining a sequence-dependent description at the sub-nucleotide level [32].

First, we evaluate the ability of MADna to reproduce the experimental results. For this purpose, we use two A-tract sequences, both consisting of 11 base pair repeats occurring 60 times. Specifically, we employ A-tracts with one sequence containing longer A-tracts of 8 base pairs, (CAAAAAAAAAACG)₆₀, and the other containing shorter A-tracts of 5 base pairs, (TTCAAAATGGA)₆₀. Additionally, we use a control sequence with random nucleotides. The results obtained from both pulling experiments (magnetic tweezers) and surface configurations (AFM imaging) successfully reproduce the findings described in the Marin-Gonzalez et al. article [444]. This demonstrates the capacity of MADna to faithfully replicate the special behavior of A-tracts.

Secondly, we explore how the properties of A-tracts relate to DNA packaging. For each sequence, we impose a constraint that forced the DNA to adopt the geometry it would have in a nucleosome. We do not add any additional interactions beyond this constraint; therefore, the differences in energy we measured are solely due to mechanical properties. After applying the constraint, we calculate the free energy difference between the nucleosome configuration and the free configuration. We use the Thermodynamic Integration (TI) technique for this purpose. By multiplying the potential by the TI parameter λ , we can "turn off" the constraint. By varying this parameter and calculating the value of the derivative of the potential with respect to this parameter, we are able to compute the free energy. The obtained results are as follows:

Table 12.1: Free energy packaging of the different sequences.

Sequence	$\Delta G_{free \rightarrow nucleosome}$ (kT)	Free energy error (kT)
Control	76.70	5.60
(TTCAAAATGGA) ₆₀	64.05	2.60
(CAAAAAAAAAACG) ₆₀	56.25	2.56

The results obtained indicate that the presence of A-tracts facilitates DNA packaging in nucleosomes. As observed in the Table 12.1, the difference between the control sequence and the A-tracts is significant, being 10kT for the sequence with 5-base pair A-tracts and 20kT for the sequence with 8-base pair A-tracts.

These results suggest that the presence of A-tracts may be a strategy for DNA packaging, as it significantly favors it energetically.

12.1 How were the computational tools used in this work?

The potentials involved in the MADna model are commonly used potentials (Section 1.1.2) implemented in `UAMMD-structured`, such as harmonic bonds, angular and dihedral potentials, as well as a Debye-Huckel interaction and a repulsive volume potential. In MADna, a model constructor is also introduced [32] that places the particles in their minimum energy position. In the case of A-tracts, this allows us to observe how they give rise to superhelices:

Figure 12.2: These are the initial configurations of the two A-tracts used in this project. Both are 11 base pair sequences that are repeated 60 times. Specifically, we employ the A-tracts with one sequence containing longer A-tracts, 8 base pairs, $(CAAAAAAAAAACG)_{60}$ and the other containing shorter A-tracts, 5 base pairs, $(TTCAAATGGA)_{60}$. As observed, the minimum energy configuration corresponds to a superhelix. In the project, this circumstance is explored since it places these A-tracts closer to the configuration they adopt in the nucleosome, which translates into requiring less energy to package.

The MADna model has been implemented in `VLMP`, which allows generating this system by simply specifying the sequence. We can prepare a single simulation using MADna model (Code 12.1).

In the simulation, we establish various components. This simulation is relatively straightforward when employing `VLMP`. To simulate the DNA chain using MADna, we merely need to incorporate the corresponding model and specify the sequence using the appropriate parameter. For the proper functioning of the model, it is necessary to utilize the "KcalMol_A" unit system, as the MADna model is parameterized accord-

Code 12.1: VLMF MADna

```

{
  "system": [{"type": "simulationName",
    "parameters": {
      "simulationName": SIM_NAME}},
    {"type": "backup",
      "parameters": {
        "backupIntervalStep": 500000}}],
  "units": [{"type": "KcalMol_A"}],
  "types": [{"type": "basic"}],
  "ensemble": [{"type": "NVT",
    "parameters": {
      "box": [10000.0, 10000.0, 10000.0],
      "temperature": 300.0}}],
  "integrators": [{"type": "GFJ",
    "parameters": {
      "timeStep": 0.4,
      "frictionConstant": 0.01,
      "integrationSteps": 25000}}],
  "models": [{"type": "MADna",
    "parameters": {
      "sequence": "GTAC...CTAG",
      "debyeLength": 10.8}}],
  "simulationSteps": [{"type": "saveState",
    "parameters": {
      "intervalStep": 25000,
      "outputFilePath": "output",
      "outputFormat": "lammprj"}},
    {"type": "thermodynamicMeasurement",
      "parameters": {
        "intervalStep": infoSteps,
        "outputFilePath": "thermo.dat"}},
    {"type": "info",
      "parameters": {
        "intervalStep": infoSteps}}]
}

```

ingly. Furthermore, we employed the BBK-type Langevin integrator and selected a relatively low friction coefficient to adhere to the Kramers turnover strategy [240]. In the current work, as mentioned, to verify that the model satisfactorily reproduces the experimental results, the AFM imaging and magnetic tweezers experiments carried out in [444] are reproduced. For the optical tweezers case, the simulation we define in VLMP is shown in code 12.2.

Code 12.2: VLMP MADna Pulling

```
import VLMP
...

SEQUENCES = {
"Atrac8": "CAAAAAAAAAACG"*60, # A-tract 8 base pairs
"Atrac5": "TTCAAAATGGA"*60, # A-tract 5 base pairs
"control": "TAG...AAG" # Control sequence
}

forces = [0.5,1.0,5.0,10.0,20.0,50.0,100.0,150.0]
nSimPerSeq = 100

simulationPool = []
for seqName in ["Atrac8","Atrac5","control"]:
    for f in forces:
        for i in range(nSimPerSeq):
            SIM_NAME = seqName + str(f) + str(i)
            SEQ = SEQUENCES[seqName]

            simulationPool.append({
                ...
                "modelExtensions": [{
                    "type": "constantForceBetweenCentersOfMass",
                    "parameters": {
                        "force": force,
                        "selection1": "MADna basePairIndex 2",
                        "selection2": "MADna basePairIndex -2"
                    }
                }],
            })

vlmp = VLMP.VLMP()

vlmp.loadSimulationPool(simulationPool)
vlmp.distributeSimulationPool("size", nSimPerSeq)
vlmp.setUpSimulation("MADNA_PULLING")
```

In the example, we first define the sequences that we will use in the simulation and store them in a list. Subsequently, we create another list with the forces that we will employ when performing pulling, as well as the number of simulations that we will carry out for each combination of sequence and force, denoted as `nSimPerSeq`.

Afterwards, we declare the `simulationPool` and iterate first over the sequences, then over the forces, and finally over the number of realizations. Once these three parameters are fixed—the sequence, the force, and the realization number—we define a name for the simulation (recalling that this name must be unique for each simulation) and add the simulation to the `simulationPool`. We utilize the simulation from the previous example and additionally include the corresponding `modelExtension`, `constantForceBetweenCentersOfMass`, which introduces the pulling force, simulating the effect of optical tweezers. Finally, we process the `simulationPool` and generate the necessary files for the simulation (section 7.2). Once the files are generated, we can proceed with the simulation (the details can be found in the section 7.5). That is, to perform the pulling experiments, we must apply a constant force between two sets of beads, those at the beginning and those at the end. This type of potential is implemented using the many-body bond 6.15 of `UAMMD-structured`. Thus, through these types of components, we can simulate a wide variety of experiments involving optical tweezers and DNA.

For the AFM imaging simulations, the strategy is similar. We compress the different sequences between two plates. Through this setup, we intend to simulate what happens in experiments where, due to the attraction between DNA and the surface, the DNA goes from being a 3D structure to a 2D one. In the case of A-tracts that have a significant torsional component, in this work, we demonstrate that this torsion is converted into bending energy when dimensions are restricted. To simulate the effect of the interaction with the substrate and the restriction of the sequence to a 2D environment, instead of adding an interaction potential with the substrate, we opted for an alternative strategy. We are solely interested in understanding how the DNA sequence behaves when dimensionality is reduced, rather than focusing on particular aspects of the interaction with the surface. Therefore, to simulate this effect, we compressed the sequence between two planes. Initially, the planes are separated by a certain distance compatible with the initial positions of the DNA. As the simulation starts, these two planes approach each other until reaching a specific distance (2.5 nm), which corresponds to the average diameter of a DNA strand. Once this distance is attained, the compression is halted, and the measurement process begins. This procedure is carried out in `VLMP` by adding the `modelExtension` plates (Code 12.3).

This potential introduces two planes that interact with the sample through a purely repulsive potential,

$$U(z) = \epsilon \left(\frac{\sigma}{z} \right)^{12} \quad (12.1)$$

Code 12.3: VLMP MADna AFM

```

simulationPool.append({
  ...
  "modelExtensions": [{
    "type": "plates",
    "parameters": {
      "platesSeparation": "auto",
      "epsilon": 1.0, "sigma": 1.0,
      "compressionVelocity": 0.0001,
      "minPlatesSeparation": 25.0,
      "selection": "all"
    }
  }],
  ...
})

```

This potential takes two parameters, ϵ and σ , which must be specified in the component, in addition to the compression velocity (which is selected to be sufficiently slow to avoid errors in the integration). We must also indicate the final separation of the plates (2.5 nm in this case). Through selection, we specify the particles upon which this interaction acts (in this case, all added particles), and the initial position of the plates is determined automatically to ensure that no incompatible initial conditions are generated.

Regarding the constraint, it is applied by adding the "helixBoundaries" modelExtension, which adds the potential of the helical boundaries. The implementation of this potential in UAMMD-structured involves certain tools originally developed in UAMMD and used in the simulation of systems with hydrodynamic interactions. Specifically, it employs the interpolation functions of the **Immersed Boundary Method** (IBM) [231]. The efficient implementation of these kinds of functions on the GPU is one of the most significant features of UAMMD. The construction of this potential is as follows. We wish to use a potential of the following form:

$$u(\vec{r}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } r_h(\mathbf{r}) < R \\ \lambda \frac{K}{2} (r_h(\mathbf{r}) - R)^2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12.2)$$

where $r_h(\mathbf{r})$ is the distance from a point, \mathbf{r} to a helix (which in our case is the shape that DNA takes when it is in the nucleosome, Fig 12.1), K is a constant that measures the strength of the constraint, λ is the parameter of the TI and R is the radius of the "tube" which center follows the helix.

To implement the above potential, we first have to compute $r_h(\mathbf{r})$, but is not easy to find out an analytical expression for this distance. Therefore, we implement this function numerically.

First, we uniformly distribute points along the helix, in our case around 10^4 points, and then we divide the simulation box to create a grid. In our case, the cells of our grid have a size of $\approx 1 \text{ \AA}$, and the grid is made of $500 \times 500 \times 500$ cells. Next, for each of the cells, we calculate the distance from each point of the helix to that cell and consider the *smallest of all of them* as the distance from the helix to that grid point. We then calculate the potential value (using equation 12.2) and the force that will act on a particle in that position (deriving 12.2). Note that given the volume of necessary calculations, it has been necessary to implement these calculations on the GPU.

At this point, we have a grid where at each point we have a value of energy and force. We then use the IBM algorithms present in UAMMD that allow us to calculate the energy/force for a particle at any point in space by interpolating the value of nearby grid cells.

To carry out these simulations, we first conduct a previous simulation that place the DNA strand in positions compatible with the helical restriction. For this, we use harmonic springs whose K value increases throughout the simulation, positioning the DNA strand in the correct position starting from a random configuration.

TI at this point is easy to evaluate. We vary the value of λ and calculate the derivative of 12.2 with respect to λ , which is a value proportional to the energy (calculated by interpolation of the grid values). Using the value of these derivatives, we can calculate the free energy of the transformation, obtaining the results given in Table 12.1.

VLMP opens the door to carrying out these types of projects that require a large number of simulations of relatively small systems. These types of experiments could be useful for other researchers, for example, in this case, for those who perform experiments with optical tweezers and DNA. We could also do the same with other types of models, such as the protein models mentioned in Chapter 1. These experiments could be easily made available through the web, that is, by selecting the DNA sequence or the protein through its PDB and carrying out the simulations, which could be useful for quickly testing hypotheses in the laboratory.

Part IV

Ongoing projects and conclusions

Chapter 13

Ongoing projects

In this chapter, we will briefly describe some currently ongoing projects that employ UAMMD-structured , VLMP or Vexperiments . All projects are in collaboration with experimental groups, and we aim to use coarse-grained model simulations to study how the different physical properties of certain biological structures condition their behavior.

13.1 Mechanical signature

Proteins can assemble to form nanocontainers, which can be employed in various ways, such as fulfilling a catalytic function, as in the case of encapsulins [110], or storing certain substances, as is the case with ferritin [460]. Many types of viruses also have a capsid composed of proteins, which they use to store their genome and other proteins or compounds necessary for carrying out the infection process [461]. This is the case for Adenovirus (studied in Chapter 9) and bacteriophages [462]. Through bioengineering techniques, we can modify certain viruses to eliminate their infective capacity and package the proteins of our choice inside them. This is the case for the bacteriophage P22, studied in Chapter 11.

In these types of structures, it is not easy to determine the **content** and its **structure**. Through imaging techniques such as transmission electron tomography (TEM), we do not have sufficient resolution, and through other techniques such as cryo-electron tomography (CryoTEM), it is not possible to determine the internal structure because, in many cases, the content of the nanocontainer does not possess a determined structure and therefore cannot be averaged over a set of images.

Given the limitations of imaging techniques, we can consider an alternative: the use of AFM. The response of a nanocontainer to indentation *varies depending on its content*, not only in terms of its quantity but also in terms of its structure.

For example, in the case of the VLP derived from P22, the indentation profiles change when it is empty compared to when it is full, and they even change depending on the proteins we encapsulate [105] (Fig 13.1). Different stages of VLP maturation can also be distinguished [463]. In the case of adenovirus, it has been observed that, depending on its content, there are changes in the indentation signal that can be related to an increase in the internal pressure of the virus [327], as well as the effect of certain proteins on the structural integrity of the capsid [51]. The cases of VLP and Adenovirus are just examples among many others [464–466].

Figure 13.1: Experimental indentation curves of empty and GFP-filled P22 VLPs [105]. The fact that the particles are filled with GFP modifies the indentation curve. When comparing the curves for the empty particles (blue) with those containing GFP (green), we observe that the latter possess a higher spring constant (they are more rigid), and additionally, the tip is unable to penetrate as deeply as in the empty ones [105].

These relationships between the mechanical signal obtained through indentation and the internal structure are inferred indirectly, i.e., there is no direct measurement of the internal state of the structure; we measure how this state affects the structure itself. To attempt to fill this gap, we have opted for direct simulation of the process.

As an example, we show the strategy followed for the case of the P22 VLP. By employing the Shape-Based Coarse-Grained model described in Chapter 2, we construct a model of the capsid. The different parameters of the model are adjusted so that the indentation curve is similar to that of the empty capsid [105], and then we add the proteins using a similar model and considering a DLVO-type potential between them [120]. Certain parameters of the DLVO are not easy to determine, so we perform an exploration of them by assigning reasonable values for this type of interaction. In the case of P22, we have data for when it is filled with the GFP protein and the β -glucosidase protein, although the internal structure of these is not clear [163, 467]. Then, by inspecting the parameters, we can observe how the mechanical response of the virus changes (Fig. 13.2).

Figure 13.2: A) Snapshot of an indentation simulation, where the tip (white bead) is observed to deform the capsid of the VLP (blue) and its contents (green), in this case, GFP. The simulation is carried out using the model described in Chapter 2, where the interaction between the cargo (GFP) and the capsid is modeled using a DLVO-type potential. We explore the parameters of the DLVO potential to obtain different configurations of the cargo. In this case, the fixed values correspond to the formation of an aggregate. B) Simulated indentation curves. The blue curve represents the empty capsid; these results are compared with the experimental ones (Fig. 13.1) to adequately parameterize the empty capsid. The green curve shows the simulation results for a capsid filled with GFP, specifically, the interaction parameters that lead to the aggregation of GFP as shown in A. As can be seen, the effect of GFP is similar to that observed in the experiments (Fig. 13.1), where the particle becomes more rigid, and the tip is unable to indent as deeply as in the empty case. This contrasts with the hypothesis proposed in [105], where these differences are attributed to the effect of pressurization. Through these types of simulations, we can suggest and test new hypotheses.

This approach can also be applied to Adenovirus using a simple Worm-like-chain model for the DNA [468]. Through this type of simulation, we can add the condensing proteins present in adenovirus [468, 469] and see what effect they have on the internal pressure and determine if this change translates into a change in indentation as outlined in [314] (Fig. 13.3)

Figure 13.3: Image of the preparation for the AFM indentation of a virus filled with DNA and condensing proteins. A) This image shows the adenovirus model, particularly the SBCG model described in Chapter 2. Each of the different types of beads is represented with different colors. Those in shades of blue correspond to the pentons. B) Section of the adenovirus filled with DNA and condensing proteins. The DNA is modeled using a WLC model, and the condensing proteins are modeled as spheres composed of beads (red dots inside the virus). This model is similar to the one proposed in previous works [468]. Through these types of simulations, we can obtain indentation curves and compare them with experimental ones [314]. Properties of the system can be modified to see how they affect the indentation curves and compare them with different experiments. We can remove the condensing proteins and study their effect [314, 469], modify the properties and quantity of the DNA [314], or remove certain capsid proteins [51], among other options.

In conclusion, by employing these simulation techniques, we aim to expand the capabilities of AFM, facilitation easier interpretation of the experimental signals obtained. All simulations have been carried out using both `UAMMD-structured` and `VLMP`. The different interactions are implemented in `UAMMD-structured`, and through `VLMP`, we can select a capsid and fill it with the cargo we desire. Finally, it is expected that the entire process can be presented through `Vexperiments`. In this way, researchers can quickly test their hypotheses about the structure of viruses and how the cargo affects the AFM indentation signal.

13.2 FtsZ treadmilling origin

Bacterial cell division is a fundamental process for the propagation and survival of bacterial species. The process of bacterial separation begins with DNA duplication [470]. Once duplicated, each copy of the DNA moves to opposite ends of the bacterium. At this point, the **FtsZ protein** comes into play. This protein polymerizes in the form of a ring in the center of the bacterium, the so-called Z ring, and acts as a template for other components necessary for division [471]. The Z ring begins to exert pressure, pulling the plasma membrane inward while the rest of the components begin to build a new membrane in the division site [472]. Finally, the bacterium divides into two, each with a copy of the original DNA (they are genetically identical) and with all the proteins and other components necessary for its proper functioning.

Given the importance of the cellular separation process and the role that FtsZ plays in it, the mechanism behind its assembly (the formation of Z rings) and how the force that exerts pressure is generated have been the subject of study for years [470]. In recent years, the advancement of microscopy has allowed obtaining a lot of information about these processes *in vitro* and *in vivo* [470, 471]. It has been observed that one of the most important characteristics of FtsZ for its proper functioning, such as accumulating in the center of the bacterium, is its ability to undergo **treadmilling** [473].

By treadmilling, we refer to a special polymerization process that certain types of cytoskeletal proteins, such as actin filaments [474], microtubules [475], and FtsZ polymers [470], can carry out. This phenomenon occurs when a filament has the ability to polymerize in one direction and depolymerize in the other direction at an equivalent rate. This causes the size of the polymer to remain constant and gives the appearance that it is moving in one direction. This phenomenon, clearly out of equilibrium, requires a continuous supply of energy. In the case of FtsZ, this is produced by the hydrolysis of GTP. Certain details of how this process works are known, but the physical principles and the particular type of molecular interactions that give rise to treadmilling are still unclear.

To improve the understanding of the polymerization and treadmilling process of FtsZ, computational models have proven to be very useful. These theoretical models have focused on various aspects of FtsZ assembly, such as cooperative polymerization, filament bending, lateral interactions, and attachment to the membrane [476–478]. These models focus on the surface phenomena observed (using AFM imaging [479–481]) when FtsZ polymers are attached to a membrane. The FtsZ protein has a set of unstructured amino acids (IDPs, see Sec. 1.1.3) that form a linker by which the protein can bind to a membrane (Fig. 8.7 shows a schematic representation of

the FtsZ attached to a surface). So far, FtsZ polymers have been modeled in a 2D scenario, where polymers are represented as a set of beads that can interact with each other. To recover the observed patterns in AFM experiments, three interactions have been shown to be crucial; the need for an excluded volume interaction, an interaction that results in a polymer with curvature, and a certain lateral attraction between monomers [470]. This type of interaction does not break the symmetry between the different directions of the polymer, meaning it does not define a "front" and a "back". Therefore, a phenomenon like treadmilling, where this symmetry has been broken, cannot arise. However, any model that attempts to reproduce FtsZ treadmilling must have these elements present to recover the full FtsZ behavior.

In this work, we explore the hypothesis presented in [470]. This hypothesis proposes that both the interaction with the surface and the twist of the filaments are key elements to differentiate one end from the other. It is known that FtsZ filaments in addition to having curvature also possess a twist, this combination of elements results in the filaments tend to have a helical shape [482]. When these helices interact with the surface they can be expected to take the shape represented in Fig. 13.4. This configuration is a result of the helical shape of the filaments and the position of the monomer anchor points (represented as white patches in Fig. 13.4). It is this type of configuration that gives rise to the differentiation between the different ends. Indeed, for the case in which the polymer is in bulk both ends have the same properties, but when the polymer is in the configuration of Fig. 13.4 the dynamics of the ends becomes different. This is due to the difference in dimensionality. The yellow end lives in a 2D world, while the red end inhabits a 3D one. Importantly, because helices are structures that possess a direction, the yellow end is always the one attached to the surface. Although now the polymerization rates between both ends differ, they are at equilibrium at each end, i.e., the effective rate, polymerization + depolymerization, is zero at both ends, although they are different from each other. Then an additional element, which necessarily involves the addition of energy (i.e. requires the participation of GTP), is necessary to reproduce the treadmilling.

We are currently studying how to achieve configurations similar to those in Fig. 13.4. To this end, we have modeled the FtsZ monomers as patchy particles (Chapter 3). Each FtsZ monomer is represented by a bead to which two patches are attached, one at each polymerization site (Fig. 13.5). These two patches have a different nature, and then are associated with different types. Only points of different types can interact. To implement this logic, we use the conditional Verlet lists from section 6.12.1. We can also set the different parameters of the interaction, such as the binding energy and its rigidity.

Figure 13.4: FtsZ polymer. Each protein is represented by a blue bead (Fig. 13.5). The binding point to the surface is represented by a white patch. In the figure, the two ends of the protein are represented differently: red for the free end and yellow for the end bound to the surface.

Figure 13.5: Model used for the representation of FtsZ. The model shows two proteins (red and blue structures) of the polymer formed by FtsZ (PDB 1W59 [483]). Each protein is represented by a bead (blue circle) with two patches of different types (small red and yellow circles). The patches can interact with each other only if they are of different types.

The model we use permits to fix the relative orientation of the monomers, which allow us to reproduce the helical structures in bulk (Fig. 13.6). We add an additional patch at a specific position on the monomer so that this patch interacts exclusively with the surface in an attractive way (the white patch in Fig. 13.4). In this way, we can study the effect of torsion and the constraint imposed by the surface, and how their interaction conditions the polymerization process (Fig. 13.7).

Figure 13.6: A) Example of a bulk simulation of the model. Initially, monomers (FtsZ) are placed in suspension at a fixed concentration (the monomers are represented by a blue bead, and the two polymerization zones are represented by yellow and red patches (Fig. 13.5)). B) As the simulation progresses, for certain interaction parameters, the monomers polymerize, giving rise to helical structures (highlighted in green in the figure). The parameters of this helix coincide with those obtained through all-atom simulations [482].

Once we have understood the polymerization process on the surface we plan to add the effect of GTP. To model this phenomenon we consider that the bonds between patches can be found in different states. These states differ from each other in the bond parameters, such as their interaction energy, equilibrium angles or elastic constants. Bonds can change state with some probability (which depends on the GTP concentration). To implement this process we have modified the simulation integrator (we employ an integrator capable of taking into account the orientation of the particles [246]) by adding an additional step. In this step, a random number for each bond is generated, and depending on the transition probability, we either perform the state change or not. Through this procedure, we are able to explore how changes in the bond properties can give rise to the treadmilling as is suggested in [470].

The model is fully implemented in `VLMP` and `UAMMD-structured`, which facilitates the exploration of parameters and we employ GPU algorithm described in Sec. 6.16) that enable the efficient simulation of these types of systems.

A

Figure 13.7: A) Example of a simulation with surface interaction. At the beginning, the simulation is similar to the bulk case, with different monomers suspended in solution. B) When the monomers polymerize, they interact with the surface, forming patterns observed in experiments [470], as well as the situation presented in Fig. 13.4, which is suggested as a condition for treadmilling.

Chapter 14

Overview and conclusions

In this thesis, we focused on studying certain mesoscale biological processes by applying knowledge from the theoretical physics of soft matter. To do this, we developed and used models capable of working with these types of multiscale processes, which require tools that transmit relevant information across scales, known as coarse-grained models.

Collaboration between researchers from different fields, such as experimental physicists, chemists, and biologists, was essential for understanding these complex phenomena. Experiments served as the meeting point and unifying element between disciplines. From our field, we developed coarse-grained models to carry out simulations of the systems under study, seeking to reproduce experimental results both qualitatively and quantitatively. These simulations required substantial computational power, which was solved by using specific hardware like GPUs that allow exploiting their parallel computing capabilities.

To popularize the use of these sophisticated tools, we developed a set of computational tools of varying difficulty levels, from those requiring more specialization to others enabling complex calculations through a simple interface.

The thesis is structured in three main parts. The different coarse-grained models used for simulations of biological systems like proteins, DNA, and lipids. The development computational tools: `UAMMD-structured`, `VLMP`, and `Vexperiments web`. `UAMMD-structured` extends the capabilities of the The software previously developed by the group, `UAMMD`, implementing many integrators and interactions present in coarse-grained models, and excelling in its GPU implementation and ability to perform parallel simulations. `VLMP` allows easily combining different parts of a simulation and executing complex simulations in HPC environments. Finally, `Vexperiments web` which is a platform for exposing these complex simulations through a simple web interface. The projects carried out using the developed models and tools. Two central projects are discussed in depth: the disassembly of a virus, where we developed a model based on Kramers theory to deduce the presence of a process that facilitates

disassembly due to loss of structural integrity; and the adhesion of coronaviruses on surfaces, where simulations allow us to deduce how the coronavirus effectively adheres to surfaces of different natures. In addition, we present two other projects that exemplify how the computational tools are able to tackle diverse problems, such as studying the influence of environment on protein function and the relationship between DNA's mechanical properties and its sequence.

The tools and techniques developed in this thesis are being used by different groups to improve understanding of various physical processes. Some current projects are listed:

- Pablo Palacios Alonso, supervised by Rafael Delgado Buscalioni, is developing a model to simulate the quartz microbalance response based on the sample, implementing it in `UAMMD-structured`, `VLMP`, and `Vexperiments` web.
- Noel F. Bonet, together with Marisela Vélez, Pedro Tarazona and Rafael Delgado Buscalioni studies the properties and functioning of the FtsZ protein, using the tool developed by Pablo Palacios and coarse-grained models to interpret the signal from QCM experiments. They also expect to use the “patchy particles” model we developed to understand the FtsZ polymerization process.
- Juan Luengo, a student in Salvatore Assenza's group, uses `VLMP` to perform DNA simulations using coarse-grained models like `MADna`, aiming to understand how differences in sequence modify DNA's mechanical properties and affect various processes.
- Students from the group led by Pedro J. de Pablo, who conduct experiments with AFM and viruses, use `UAMMD-structured` /`VLMP` simulations to understand the observed phenomena. Alejandro Diez's work stands out, studying the interaction between RNA and the tobacco virus capsid. The methods developed for data interpretation and AFM simulation are expected to be exposed through the `Vexperiments` web.
- New students from Rafael Delgado Buscalioni's group use different tools in their projects. Lucas Fernández Alonso employs `UAMMD-structured` to simulate the frequency response of AFM and how it changes based on the sample. Pablo Silva is implementing models of interaction between charged particles in a solvent in `UAMMD-structured`, studying how external fields can be used for detailed control of these particles.

In conclusion, the tools developed in this thesis have proven to be very useful for studying mesoscale phenomena. Their successful application to different problems and continuous development by other researchers will contribute to advancing the understanding of these complex phenomena. These tools are expected to be accessible and used by as many people as possible, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and scientific progress in this field.

Conclusiones

En esta tesis, nos hemos enfocado en el estudio de ciertos procesos biológicos que toman lugar en la mesoescala, empleando el conocimiento de la física teórica de la materia blanda. Para ello, hemos desarrollado y utilizado modelos capaces de trabajar con este tipo de procesos multiescala, que requieren herramientas que transmitan la información relevante a través de dichas escalas, conocidos como modelos de grano grueso o coarse grained.

La colaboración entre investigadores de diferentes campos, como físicos experimentales, químicos y biólogos, ha sido fundamental para comprender estos fenómenos complejos. Los experimentos han sido el punto de encuentro y el elemento unificador entre las diferentes disciplinas. Desde nuestro ámbito, hemos desarrollado modelos de coarse grained para llevar a cabo simulaciones de los sistemas bajo estudio, buscando reproducir los resultados experimentales tanto de forma cualitativa como cuantitativa. Estas simulaciones requieren una gran potencia computacional, que se ha solventado gracias al uso de hardware específico, como las GPU, que permiten explotar su naturaleza de cálculo en paralelo.

Para popularizar el uso de estas sofisticadas herramientas, hemos desarrollado una serie de herramientas computacionales que difieren en su nivel de dificultad, desde aquellas que requieren mayor especialización hasta otras que permiten llevar a cabo complejos cálculos mediante un sencillo interfaz.

La tesis se estructura en tres partes principales. En la primera parte, presentamos los diferentes modelos de coarse grained empleados para las simulaciones de sistemas biológicos, como proteínas, DNA y lípidos. La segunda parte se centra en la presentación de las herramientas computacionales, a saber: `UAMMD-structured`, `VLMP` y `Vexperiments web`. `UAMMD-structured` extiende las capacidades del software previamente desarrollado en el grupo, `UAMMD`, implementando un gran número de integradores e interacciones presentes en los modelos de coarse grained, destacando por su implementación en GPU y su capacidad para realizar simulaciones paralelas. `VLMP` permite combinar diferentes partes de una simulación de forma sencilla y ejecutar simulaciones complejas en entornos HPC. Por último, `Vexperiments web` es una plataforma que permite exponer estas simulaciones complejas mediante un sencillo

interfaz web.

En la tercera parte, presentamos los proyectos llevados a cabo utilizando los modelos y herramientas desarrollados. Dos proyectos centrales se discuten en profundidad: el desensamblaje de un virus, donde desarrollamos un modelo basado en la teoría de Kramers para deducir la presencia de un proceso que facilita el desensamblaje debido a la pérdida de integridad estructural; y la adhesión de virus de la familia de los coronavirus en superficies, donde las simulaciones nos permiten deducir cómo el coronavirus se adhiere eficazmente a superficies de diferente naturaleza. Además, presentamos otros dos proyectos que ejemplifican la capacidad de las herramientas computacionales para afrontar problemas diversos, como el estudio de la influencia del entorno en el funcionamiento de las proteínas y la relación entre las propiedades mecánicas del DNA y su secuencia.

Las herramientas y técnicas desarrolladas en esta tesis están siendo empleadas por diferentes grupos para mejorar la comprensión de diversos procesos físicos. A continuación, se listan algunos de los proyectos actuales:

- **Pablo Palacios Alonso**, supervisado por Rafael Delgado Buscalioni, está desarrollando un modelo para simular la respuesta de la microbalanza de cuarzo en función de la muestra, implementándolo en `UAMMD-structured`, `VLMP` y `Vexperiments` web.
- **Noel F. Bonet**, junto con Marisela Vélez, Pedro Tarazona y Rafael Delgado Buscalioni estudia las propiedades y el funcionamiento de la proteína FtsZ, empleando la herramienta desarrollada por Pablo Palacios y los modelos de coarse grained para interpretar la señal de los experimentos con la QCM. Además, se espera que empleen el modelo de "patchy particles" que hemos desarrollado para entender el proceso de polimerización de FtsZ.
- **Juan Luengo**, estudiante del grupo de Salvatore Assenza, emplea `VLMP` para realizar simulaciones de DNA utilizando modelos de coarse grained, como `MADna`, con el objetivo de entender cómo las diferencias en la secuencia modifican las propiedades mecánicas del DNA y afectan a diferentes procesos.
- Estudiantes del grupo dirigido por Pedro J. de Pablo, que realizan experimentos con AFM y virus, emplean las simulaciones mediante `UAMMD-structured` /`VLMP` para comprender los fenómenos observados. Destaca el trabajo de Alejandro Diez, que estudia la interacción entre el RNA y la cápside del virus del tabaco. Se espera exponer los métodos desarrollados para la interpretación de datos y la simulación de AFM a través de la `Vexperiments` web.

- Nuevos estudiantes del grupo de Rafael Delgado Buscalioni utilizan diferentes herramientas en sus proyectos. Lucas Fernández Alonso emplea `UAMMD-structured` para simular la respuesta en frecuencia del AFM y cómo esta se modifica en función de la muestra. Pablo Silva está implementando en `UAMMD-structured` modelos de interacción entre partículas cargadas en un solvente, estudiando cómo los campos externos pueden utilizarse para el control detallado de estas partículas.

En conclusión, las herramientas desarrolladas en esta tesis han demostrado ser de gran utilidad para el estudio de fenómenos en la mesoescala. Su aplicación exitosa a diferentes problemas y su continuo desarrollo por parte de otros investigadores contribuirán al avance en el entendimiento de estos complejos fenómenos. Se espera que estas herramientas sean accesibles y empleadas por el mayor número de personas posible, fomentando la colaboración interdisciplinaria y el progreso científico en este campo.

Appendices

Appendix A

Adenovirus cooperative disassembly: Experimental methods

Production of human Adenovirus 5 virus particles

For this study, we used the E1-deleted Ad5 variant Ad5GL, which lacks fundamental genes for replication but produces structurally wild-type particles in complementing cell lines [484]. Ad5GL was propagated at 37 °C in HEK 293 cells (MOI of 5) and harvested at 40 h postinfection. Virus particles were purified by equilibrium centrifugation at 18 °C in two consecutive CsCl gradients. Bands extracted from the gradients were desalted on a Bio-Rad 10 DC column and stored in HBS (20 mM HEPES, pH 7.8, 150 mM NaCl) supplemented with 10% glycerol at −80 °C for long-term storage. The virus stock concentration was 5.1×10^{11} viral particles (vp)/ml. For the AFM experiments, samples were thoroughly dialyzed against HBS to remove the storage glycerol and stored in 5 μ l aliquots at −20 °C. Samples were diluted four times in HBS supplemented with 5 mM NiCl₂, for a final concentration of approximately 1.25×10^{10} (vp)/ml, and incubated during 20 min on cleaved mica. Then, a drop of 500 μ l of HBS + 5 mM NiCl₂ was placed on the AFM liquid chamber to render a random population of virus particles (Fig. A.1).

Figure A.1: (Left) AFM topography of HAdV on mica. (Right) Height distribution data presented in histograms for HAdV. Mean data and standard deviation (SD) are obtained by fitting a Gaussian distribution to the histogram (blue line).

Appendix B

Adenovirus cooperative disassembly: Penton release theoretical model

We derive a theoretical model for the statistics of the lag time between successive penton-escape events, treated as a Markovian process (see Chapter 9). The experimental results (Fig. 9.5 and Table 9.1) indicate that these events correspond to Poissonian processes with a well-defined, time-independent escape rate. We separately consider the survival times for the first, second, and third pentons, taking the survival time (in image units) as the difference between successive escape events. In order to reproduce the experimental data, the theoretical model should reconstruct each step of the experimental procedure, which is composed of three parts: first, an individual pixel (or indentation); second, a single image with $M = 128 \times 128$ pixels (this corresponds to the experimental resolution); and third, a number n of images for the escape event to occur. We derive the probability of losing a penton over each of these steps, to finally obtain $P(n)$ in Eq. 9.5

To begin, one needs to consider the spatial details of a single indentation, which has two possible outcomes: (i) the indentation touches an area that stimulates a penton, or (ii) it touches a region that disturbs the penton. In the first case, we consider that a certain work W is applied to the penton, while in the latter case, $W = 0$. The small indentation area, about $(5 \text{ nm})^2$, permits us to assume that indentation has a local effect; i.e., we consider $W = 0$ if the tip touches a region of the capsid where the penton has already been lost. Therefore, the case $W = 0$ includes two subgroups: indentations outside the capsid (on the substrate) and indentations in a region of the capsid that has already lost its penton. By inspecting many experimental images, we calculate the average fraction of the image covered by the capsid, which is noted as the

parameter ν . Within the capsid domain, the fraction of the image that corresponds to the region of influence of an exposed penton is noted as $\rho_i\nu$, where ρ_i is the fraction of the remaining exposed pentons. Since there are three pentons exposed to the AFM tip [Fig. 9.2(a)], this parameter will take the values $\rho_1 = 1$ when no penton has been lost, $\rho_2 = \frac{2}{3}$ when one penton has left the virus, and finally, $\rho_3 = \frac{1}{3}$ when only one penton remains. Let P_{out} be the probability of losing a penton if the indentation does not touch the penton ($W = 0$), and P_{in} the probability of losing a penton after touching it with the AFM tip ($W > 0$). The total probability of losing the i th penton after resolving one pixel is then

$$B_i = (1 - \nu)P_{\text{out}} + \nu(\rho_i P_{\text{in}} + (1 - \rho_i)P_{\text{out}}). \quad (\text{B.1})$$

We now deduce the form of P_{out} and P_{in} and integrate over pixels and images to derive Eq. 9.5, i.e., the probability of losing the i th penton after a number n of images, $P(n)$. This value is precisely the quantity amenable for comparison with experiments.

We start by considering a single indentation. Equation (4) is the master equation for the probability $P_f(t)$ of pentons being in the free (unbonded) state at time t . This equation is equivalent to a first-order kinetic reaction and requires evaluating the transition rate $\alpha(t)$. To this end, we need to consider the location of the indentation. The case indentation out corresponds to the AFM tip not perturbing the penton (either because the AFM tip touches the substrate or avoids it in the capsid without pentons). In such a case ($W = 0$), we set $\alpha(t) = \alpha_0$, which is the spontaneous escape rate, related to the free energy barrier ΔG by the Kramer relation given in Eq. 9.2,

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha_0 = \omega_0 \exp\left[-\frac{\Delta G}{k_B T}\right] \quad (\text{indentation out}). \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Integrating the master equation, Eq. 9.4, leads to the probability of escaping after a single indentation that is outside the penton domain,

$$P_{\text{out}} = 1 - \exp(-\alpha_0 T), \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where T denotes the time required for one indentation (10 ms).

Second, if the indentation stimulates the penton domain (we denote this case as in), the tip introduces some mechanical work $W(t)$, which increases the escape rate as described in Eq. 9.3,

$$\alpha(t) = \omega_0 \exp[-(\Delta G - W(t))/k_B T] = \alpha_0 \exp[W(t)/k_B T] \quad (\text{indentation in}). \quad (\text{B.4})$$

The in scenario requires a more detailed analysis. Integration of the master equa-

tion Eq. 9.4 using Eq. B.4 leads to

$$P_{\text{in}}(t) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_0^t \alpha(t') dt'\right) = 1 - \exp\left(\alpha_0 \int_0^t \exp(W(t')/k_B T) dt'\right). \quad (\text{B.5})$$

To proceed with the integration of the exponent, we first examine the profile of the indentation force as a function of time, $f_{\text{AFM}}(t)$. This profile, measured experimentally, has the form of a top-hat function with five different steps. In the initial step ($t_0 < t < t_1$, where $t_0 = 0$), the tip approaches the sample and the applied force is zero; this free-force step has a duration $t_1 = t_F$. Upon contact ($t_1 < t < t_2$), the force increases linearly in time until it reaches the maximum (set point) force F . The elapsed time during this ramp step is t_R . For $t_2 < t < t_3$, the force F is held fixed over a contact time t_C , and the rest of the process follows similarly in inverse order: force ramp back to zero ($t_3 < t < t_4$) and tip moving away from the sample ($t_4 < t < t_5$). The total time needed for a single indentation is thus $T = t_5 = 2t_F + 2t_R + t_C$, with $t_1 = t_F$, $t_2 = t_1 + t_R$, $t_3 = t_2 + t_C$, $t_4 = t_3 + t_R$. As a function of time, the applied force $f_{\text{AFM}}(t)$ is a piecewise function: $f_{\text{AFM}}(t) = 0$ for $t_0 < t < t_1$; $f_{\text{AFM}}(t) = \frac{F(t-t_F)}{t_R}$ for $t_1 < t < t_2$; $f_{\text{AFM}}(t) = F$ for $t_2 < t < t_3$; $f_{\text{AFM}}(t) = -\frac{F(t-t_F-2t_R-t_C)}{t_R}$ for $t_3 < t < t_4$; and $f_{\text{AFM}}(t) = 0$ for $t_4 < t < t_5$. The duration of each step depends, in turn, on the maximum force F and can be determined experimentally,

$$t_F = 0.00588 - 0.00000078F,$$

$$t_R = 0.00000088 - 0.00000041F,$$

$$t_C = 0.00076 - 0.000000077F.$$

The next piece of information requires some relation between the applied work and the force. The first model is based on $W = -Fr$ where $r = x_{\text{ef}}$ in Chapter 9 is a constant effective indentation length. We first perform the integrals I_k appearing in the exponents of Eq. (B.5) for each one of the five time intervals $t_{k-1} < t < t_k$ of the indentation process (we define $\beta = \frac{1}{k_B T}$),

$$I_1(t_0, t_1) = I_5(t_0, t_1) = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \exp(0) dt = (t_1 - t_0) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$I_2(t_0, t_1) = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \exp\left(\frac{t - t_F}{t_R} \beta F r\right) dt \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$= t_R \beta F r \left(\exp\left[\beta F r \left(\frac{t_1 - t_F}{t_R}\right)\right] - \exp\left[\beta F r \left(\frac{t_0 - t_F}{t_R}\right)\right] \right) \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$I_3(t_0, t_1) = (t_1 - t_0) \exp(\beta F r) \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$I_4(t_0, t_1) = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \exp\left(-\frac{t - 2t_F - 2t_R - t_C}{t_R} \beta F r\right) dt \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$= -t_R \beta F r \left(\exp\left[-\beta F r \left(\frac{t_1 - 2t_F - 2t_R - t_C}{t_R}\right)\right] \right) + \quad (\text{B.11})$$

$$t_R \beta F r \left(\exp\left[-\beta F r \left(\frac{t_0 - 2t_F - 2t_R - t_C}{t_R}\right)\right] \right) \quad (\text{B.12})$$

Using these integrals, the probability of encountering a free penton over time results in another piecewise function, such that $P_{\text{in}}(T) = 1 - \exp[-\alpha_0 (I_1(t_0, t_1) + I_2(t_1, t_2) + I_3(t_2, t_3) + I_3(t_4, t_3) + I_5(t_4, T))]$, where we recall that $T = 2t_F + 2t_R + t_C$ corresponds to the total time lapse of a single indentation cycle ($T = 10$ ms). After some algebra, this yields the probability of losing a penton in a single indentation performed in a pentamer domain,

$$P_{\text{in}} \equiv P_{\text{in}}(T) = 1 - \exp\left[-\alpha_0 \left(\exp(\beta F r) t_C + \left(\frac{1}{\beta F r}\right) (\exp(\beta F r) - 1) 2t_R + 2t_F \right)\right]. \quad (\text{B.13})$$

In the second model, the work is expressed as $W(t) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{F^2}{k}$, and a similar procedure leads to

$$P_{\text{in}} \equiv P_{\text{in}}(T) = 1 - \exp\left[-\alpha_0 \left(\exp\left(\beta \frac{F^2}{2k}\right) t_C + \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi k \beta F^2}} \operatorname{erfi}\left(\beta \frac{F^2}{2k}\right) t_R + 2t_F \right)\right]. \quad (\text{B.14})$$

Following Eq. (B.1), collecting the spatial details of the indentation (AFM tip either in or out) leads to the total probability for penton unbinding during a single indentation,

$$B_i = (1 - \nu) P_{\text{out}} + \nu (\rho_i P_{\text{in}} + (1 - \rho_i) P_{\text{out}}), \quad (\text{B.15})$$

where $\rho_i = \frac{4-i}{3}$ is the fraction of remaining pentons in the capsid area facing the AFM, with $i = 1$ (intact capsid), $i = 2$ (one penton is lost), and $i = 3$ (two pentons are lost).

We can follow a similar procedure to model the image acquisition process. In this

case, we face a discrete case since we are interested in the escape probability as a function of the number of pixels we are indenting (unlike the previous case, in which we were interested in the evolution of the probability as a function of time along a single indentation). In this case, we introduce the stochastic transition matrix of the process,

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - B & B \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.16})$$

The evolution of the discrete process can be written in terms of the transition matrix as

$$\begin{pmatrix} P_{p+1}^{\text{bonded}} \\ P_{p+1}^{\text{free}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P_p^{\text{bonded}} \\ P_p^{\text{free}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 - B & B \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{B.17})$$

i.e., according to a Markovian process, the state after the $p + 1$ indentation only depends on the state at the previous pixelation p . If the initial state is

$$\left(P_0^{\text{bonded}}, P_0^{\text{free}} \right) = (1, 0), \quad (\text{B.18})$$

the probability after performing m indentations is thus obtained by the recursive application of the transition matrix, resulting in

$$\left(P_m^{\text{b}}, P_m^{\text{f}} \right) = \left(P_0^{\text{b}}, P_0^{\text{f}} \right) T^m. \quad (\text{B.19})$$

One can compute the m power of the stochastic matrix, T^m , as

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 - B & B \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}^m = \begin{pmatrix} (1 - B)^m & 1 - (1 - B)^m \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{B.20})$$

so the probability of losing a penton after m indentations is

$$p(m) = P_m^{\text{f}} = 1 - (1 - B)^m. \quad (\text{B.21})$$

In deriving this expression, we assume that the pixels are taken at random locations, which is not strictly true because during a single image, the pixelation follows a well-defined order. However, this point is not crucial because we are interested in the probability of losing a penton after passing all the M pixels of the image. The large number of pixels per image ($M = 128 \times 128$) indicates that the above expression is appropriate. Taking everything into account, we obtain the probability of losing a penton after taking one image (i.e., M pixels),

$$C := p(M) = 1 - (1 - B)^M. \quad (\text{B.22})$$

Moreover, M is a large number, so this expression can be approximated by

$$C := 1 - (1 - B)^M \approx 1 - \exp(-BM), \quad (\text{B.23})$$

which is easier to work with. In conclusion, the probability of releasing the i th pentamer after a single image is

$$C_i := 1 - \exp(-B_i M) \quad (\text{B.24})$$

where B_i is given in Eq. (B.1) and involves Eq. (B.5), (B.13), or (B.14).

The last step is to compute $P_i(n_i)$, the release probability after a number n_i of images (where we recall n_i starts to be counted since the previous penton $i-1$ is lost). We can compare this information with experiments. The situation is formally analogous to the previous case, and following a similar approach, we arrive at Eq. (9.5). Note that C_i is given in Eq. (B.24), and $P_i(n_i)$ is compared with experimental results in Fig. 9.5.

Appendix C

Coronavirus surface adhesion: Experimental methods

Virus purification, cell culture, buffers

TGEV virions were purified using a slightly modified version of a previously reported method [106] Initially, supernatants from TGEV-infected cells were clarified by centrifugation at 4500E g for 20 min at 4 °C. Virions were then sedimented by ultracentrifugation at 112,000E g for 120 min through a 31% (w/w) sucrose cushion in TEN buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl [pH 7.4], 1 mM EDTA, 1 M NaCl) with 0.2% Tween 20 (Sigma, Saint Louis, MI, USA). The viruses were subsequently centrifuged through a continuous 15% to 42% (w/w) sucrose gradient in order to separate wild-type virions and defective virions with lower density. Finally, virions were pelleted by ultracentrifugation at 112,000E g for 60 min and resuspended in TNE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl [pH 7.4], 1 mM EDTA, 100 mM NaCl) using 0.05% Tween 20. Purified virions were disaggregated by sonication (six pulses at medium intensity in a Branson sonifier 450). SDS-PAGE protein analysis of the purified TGEV virions using Coomassie staining showed the presence of the major viral proteins S, N and M. This result confirmed the presence of TGEV virions in the samples used for AFM and cryogenic electron microscopy.

Virus genome mass and bulk concentration

Taking into account that the average molecular weight of ribonucleotide triphosphates is 500 g/mol or 500 Da and that the average weight of a Dalton is 1.66054×10^{-24} g, we calculate the weight of the TGEV strain PUR46-MAD consisting of 28580 nucleotides [485] obtaining a final result of 2.37×10^{-17} g per copy, used to calculate

the virus concentration from the total genome mass. The sample was analyzed after a 1-hour treatment at 37 °C with 1% SDS and 0.5 mg/ml of proteinase K in TNE buffer and subsequently measured on a NanoDrop 1000 (ThermoFisher) to obtain the concentration of RNA in our sample. Thus, the achieved viral titer of the stock was $(3.56 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{12}$ virus/ml.

AFM imaging

Measurements were performed with an AFM (Nanotec Electrónica S.L., Madrid, Spain) in Jumping Plus Mode[316] In this mode, lateral interactions are minimized as the lateral displacement is done with the tip far from the sample. The tip moves in the Z axis (perpendicular to the surface) until a certain present interaction force. Topography data is obtained and the tip releases the surface and is moved laterally one pixel to repeat the procedure again. Parameters for the Jumping Plus Mode were: jump off = 100 nm, jump sample = 200 nm and control cycles = 20. Image size was typically 8x8 microns, but some images of smaller size were taken for each sample, in order to check viral integrity.

AFM tips used were NANOWORLD PNP-DB-20, with a tip radius below 10 nm. Cantilevers used presented a nominal force constant of 0.06 N/m (200x40 nm rectangular cantilevers). The applied perpendicular force for Jumping Plus imaging was calculated precisely with the method of Sader[315] for rectangular cantilevers, and it was in the 50–100 pN range, in order to nullify the impact of the loading force on viral height, as the deformability of lipid-enveloped viruses is reportedly higher than protein-capsid ones[106, 486]

Viral Capture on surfaces and dissociation constant calculation

We define Viral Capture (VC) as:

$$VC = \frac{\text{Number of viruses scanned}}{\text{Total scanned area}} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Where the total scanned area is given in μm^2 . Thus, VC represents the number of virus detected by AFM in 1 μm^2 . VC is defined for a given virus concentration and surface, by analysis of different images and presenting VC as the arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation of the VC values for each image. For bicomponent samples with two different regions, VC is defined for each region by dividing the number of viruses

in the region by the area (in μm^2) of the region. Note that VC can be further divided by the concentration of viruses (in nM) for each case, therefore grouping all dilutions and concentrations in a single combined value that defines the capture capacity for each substrate globally.

Binding affinity was quantitatively evaluated via the dissociation constant K_d following the Hill-Langmuir equation for non-cooperative binding [390]

$$\Theta = \frac{\Theta_{max}[V]_F}{K_d + [V]_F} \quad (C.2)$$

Where Θ stands for the area fraction covered by viruses which is set to $\Theta = VC\pi L^2$, with L the surface projected radius (Fig. 10.6); $[V]_F$ is the concentration of free viruses. K_d represents the virus concentration required for a half-coverage of the surface. We assume that we are in the Henry regime (far from saturating conditions) $K_d \gg [V]_F$, which is later confirmed by our results. The maximum virus coverage Θ_{max} is set to 0.64 which roughly equals the 2D random packing limit. Equation C.2 simplifies to

$$\Theta = \Theta_{max} \frac{[V]_F}{K_d} \quad (C.3)$$

Note that $[V]_F = [V]_0 - [V]_C$ where $[V]_0$ is the initial virus concentration in the sample and $[V]_C$ the correction due to the virus captured onto the substrate, estimated as

$$[V]_C = \frac{VC \pi R_s^2}{N_A \mathcal{V}} \quad (C.4)$$

Where VC is the virus surface density, $R_s \approx 4 \times 10^3 \mu m$ the 30 μL droplet projected radius (average over surfaces) and \mathcal{V} is the sample's droplet volume 3×10^{-5} L (equal for every case). $N_A = 6.022 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ the Avogadro number. Note that $[V]_C \ll [V]_0$ and this correction can be neglected.

Image processing, virus counting and viral height measurements

Images were processed using WSxM program (www.wsxm.es).[487] First, the function flatten plus was used to help with the flattening process for images and drift correction. Second, images the function equalize was used to adequately fix the zero level of the sample. Then, the function flooding was applied for image quantification. To quantify the number of viruses, flooding was set to find hills with a 35 nm limit. The number of detected hills equals the number of virus detected, the value is then used for VC

calculation in Eq C.1 . Then, for viral height analysis, the same hills information was copied to a spreadsheet, where the maximum heights were plotted, using SigmaPlot 11.0 (Systat Software Inc.), as height histograms, later normalized and linearized using the same software for a direct comparison among samples.

Sample preparation and virus addition

Muscovite mica and highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) were prepared by stack-exfoliation (freshly cleaving). Poly-L-lysine functionalization of mica was achieved as previously described[106] Briefly, a 30 μl droplet of 0.1% poly-L-lysine was deposited onto freshly cleaved mica for 15 min and rinsed with 1 ml ultra-pure water. Then, a highly pure stream of N_2 was applied to the surface to dry it. This method results in a thin layer of poly-L-lysine deposited onto the mica.

For SiO_2 surfaces, the method can be described as follows. Starting from a 4" Si/ SiO_2 wafer (300 nm) from MicroChemicals GmbH (Ulm, Germany), square substrates of 10 mm lateral size were cut with a diamond tip. They were then cleaned in an ultrasonic bath of isopropanol for 15 min and subsequently blown with nitrogen. This resulted in the surfaces dubbed as SiO_2 -isopropanol. For the preparation of some of the samples (dubbed as SiO_2 -plasma) we performed an oxygen plasma surface treatment at 50% power for 15 minutes using a Femto Low Pressure plasma system from Diener Electronic GmbH (Ebhausen, Germany).

Regarding virus addition, the same procedure was applied for every substrate: a 30 μl droplet with a viral titer of $(3.56 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{12}$ virus/ml in TNE buffer (or accordingly diluted by the desired dilution factor) was incubated for 60 min and rinsed with a clean buffer 5 times, adding 1x incubation volume and removing it. A final volume of 90 μl was then used for measuring the virus under the AFM.

MoS_2 flakes preparation

A single-zone tube furnace is used for the growth of MoS_2 . 2.5 mg MoO_3 powder is evenly distributed in an alumina boat and located at the centre of the furnace. A layer of molecular sieve (Alfa Aesar 5A 1-2 mm diameter pellets) covers the MoO_3 boat to control the growth rate. SiO_2/Si substrates, spin-coated with 0.5 mg/mL NaOH promoter, are placed on the MoO_3 boat. 60 mg sulphur powder in another alumina boat is located 17 cm upper stream at the edge of the furnace. Before starting growth, the tube is purged with 460 sccm N_2 for 20 minutes. The N_2 flow rate is then decreased to 60 sccm. The temperature of MoO_3 is set and kept at 720 $^\circ\text{C}$ for around 10 minutes, while the temperature of sulphur could reach 230 $^\circ\text{C}$. At the finishing step, the furnace

is switched off, the sulphur source is pulled out of the heating zone, and the MoO_3 boat is let to cool down in 460 sccm N_2 gas.

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